

SUSTRACK

D3.3 CASE STUDY ASSESSMENT RESULTS

Work package	WP3 Definition and analysis of relevant case studies for the circular bioeconomy
Task	T3.3 Case Study Analysis
Due date	28 February 2025
Submission date	28 February 2025
Deliverable lead	Wageningen Research
Version	1.0
Authors	Iris Vural Gursel, Berien Elbersen and Heleen Ballemans (WR)
Contributors	Sanabel Abdulbawab (WR), Gülşah Yılan, Alireza Khosravi, Majid Zaeemi (UNIT), Luana Ladu, Mariam Rasheed (BAM), Joris Van Acker, Tobi Hallez (UGENT), Marco Bianchi, Janire Clavell (TECNALIA), Laura García Laverde (DBFZ), Carlota Garcia Diaz (CIRCE)
Reviewers	All partners

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	10.11.2024	Draft structure of the deliverable	WR
0.2	10.01.2025	First draft of the deliverable	WR
0.3	04.02.2025	Complete draft ready for review	WR, UNIT, BAM, UGENT, TECNALIA, DBFZ, CIRCE
0.4	19.02.2025	Reviewer’s comments and edits	All partners
0.5	25.02.2025	Final draft after implementing edits/comments	WR
1.0	28.02.2025	Final check and submission	UNIT

Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and biobased systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular biobased systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular biobased systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union under project number 101081823. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright notice: © 2022 - 2025 SUSTRACK Consortium

Deliverable information		
Nature of the deliverable:		R*
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web	x
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

SUSTRACK Consortium:

#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA UNITELMA SAPIENZA	UNIT	IT
2	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
3	KNOWLEDGE SRL	KE	IT
4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC	SK
5	DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	DBFZ	DE
6	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGENT	BE
7	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	ES
8	FVA SAS DI LOUIS FERRINI & C	FVA	IT
9	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	UNIFE	IT
10	BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG	BAM	DE
11	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS	CIRCE	ES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of achieving net-zero emissions by the European economy by 2050 demands a shift from linear, fossil-based systems to circular, biobased systems. This transition is vital for meeting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and reconciling environmental protection with sustainable growth. However, the complexity of the transition relies on societal transformations, cutting-edge technologies, and multi-actor processes, requiring a new economic framework and policy priorities that align with the European Green Deal.

This report presents the SUSTRACK T3.3 results on case study assessments. In T3.1, 10 case studies were selected, later an additional case study was included. In T2.1 the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System was developed. In T3.2, validation of this monitoring system was carried out and guidelines for the implementation of the case study assessment were prepared. For this, the monitoring system was tested, and the most relevant indicators were identified for each case study. Additionally, guidelines were made for mapping stakeholders and policy instruments, and for collection of information and data for the case study analysis. T3.3 builds on the work carried out in T3.2. The guidance and methodology for case study analysis as set out in D3.2 is followed for the assessment of the 11 selected case studies. Also, the analysis of indicators that was carried out as part of consistency check forms the foundation for this work. Additionally, in T3.3 stakeholder engagements were used in gathering input for the case studies. This includes besides dedicated interviews with targeted stakeholders input gathered at the INSPIRE and DESIGN co-creation workshops. The findings from these engagements were categorised into three dimensions: market, policy, and sustainability. The outcomes from these case study assessments serve as input for other WPs, especially for WP4 for the analysis of each sector by means of the Green Economy Model and for WP5 for the identification of policy priorities, the definition of policy actions based on discussions on challenges and opportunities.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	23
2	Approach and Methodology	25
3	Results From The Construction Sector Case Studies.....	27
3.1	Sector-specific insights from stakeholder consultations	27
3.2	Construction - Cross laminated timber	29
3.2.1	Introduction to the cross laminated timber case study	29
3.2.1.1	General description	29
3.2.1.2	Value chain and the process.....	30
3.2.1.3	Baseline and market	32
3.2.2	Stakeholders in the CLT value chain.....	34
3.2.2.1	Identification of relevant stakeholders	34
3.2.2.2	Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders.....	38
3.2.3	Policies of relevance to the CLT value chain	39
3.2.4	Analysis of indicators of the CLT case study.....	41
3.2.4.1	Environmental/circular indicators	47
3.2.4.2	Economic indicators	52
3.2.4.3	Social indicators.....	54
3.2.5	Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations	56
3.2.6	Key learnings CLT case study	58
3.3	Construction - Biochar as an additive in concrete	59
3.3.1	Introduction to the biochar in concrete case study	59
3.3.1.1	General description.....	59
3.3.1.2	Value chain and the process.....	60
3.3.1.3	Baseline and market	61
3.3.2	Stakeholders in the biochar in concrete value chain	62

3.3.2.1	Identification of relevant stakeholders	62
3.3.2.2	Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders.....	64
3.3.3	Policies of relevance to the biochar in concrete value chain	66
3.3.4	Analysis of indicators of the biochar in concrete case study.....	70
3.3.4.1	Environmental/circular indicators	70
3.3.4.2	Economic indicators	75
3.3.4.3	Social indicators.....	76
3.3.5	Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations	77
3.3.6	Key learnings of Biochar in concrete case study	78
3.4	Construction - Hemp insulation	79
3.4.1	Introduction to the hemp insulation case study.....	79
3.4.1.1	General description.....	79
3.4.1.2	Value chain and the process.....	80
3.4.1.3	Baseline and market	82
3.4.2	Stakeholders in the hemp insulation value chain	85
3.4.2.1	Identification of relevant stakeholders	85
3.4.2.2	Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders.....	87
3.4.3	Policies of relevance to the hemp insulation value chain	89
3.4.4	Analysis of indicators of the hemp insulation case study.....	98
3.4.4.1	Environmental/circular indicators	98
3.4.4.2	Economic indicators	102
3.4.4.3	Social indicators.....	104
3.4.5	Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations	105
3.4.6	Key learnings of hemp insulation case study	108
4	Results From The Textile Sector Case Studies	110
4.1	Sector-specific insights from stakeholder consultations	110
4.2	Textile - Recycled carded wool from Prato, Italy	112
4.2.1	Introduction to Recycled carded wool from Prato Textile District	112

- 4.2.1.1 General description 112
- 4.2.1.2 Value chain and the process 114
- 4.2.1.3 Baseline and market 116
- 4.2.2 Stakeholders in the Prato Textile District case study 117
 - 4.2.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders 117
 - 4.2.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders..... 120
- 4.2.3 Policies of relevance to the Prato Textile District case study 123
- 4.2.4 Analysis of Indicators in the Prato Textile District case study 127
 - 4.2.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators 128
 - 4.2.4.2 Economic indicators 131
 - 4.2.4.3 Social indicators 134
- 4.2.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations 138
- 4.2.6 Key learnings of the Prato Textile District case study 140
- 4.3 Textile - Man-made cellulosic fibres, like Lyocell..... 142
 - 4.3.1. Introduction to man-made cellulosic fibres case study 142
 - 4.3.1.1 General description 142
 - 4.3.1.2 Value chain and the process 144
 - 4.3.1.3 Baseline and market 146
 - 4.3.2 Stakeholders in the Lyocell and other MMCF's man-made cellulosic fibres value chain
148
 - 4.3.2.1. Identification of relevant stakeholders: 148
 - 4.3.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders..... 151
 - 4.3.3 Policies of relevance to man-made cellulosic fibres value chain..... 153
 - 4.3.4 Analysis of indicators on -the man-made cellulosic fibres case study 156
 - 4.3.4.1 Environmental /circular indicators 156
 - 4.3.4.2 Economic indicators 160
 - 4.3.4.3 Social indicators 162
 - 4.3.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations 164
 - 4.3.6 Key learnings of man-made cellulosic fibres case study 165

4.4	Textile - Latxa sheep wool from the Basque Country	166
4.4.1	Introduction to the Latxa sheep wool from the Basque Country	166
4.4.1.1	General description	166
4.4.1.2	Value chain and the process	167
4.4.1.3	Baseline and market	168
4.4.2	Stakeholders in the Latxa sheep wool case study.....	169
4.4.1.4	Identification of relevant stakeholders	169
4.4.1.5	Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders.....	173
4.4.3	Policies of relevance to Latxa sheep wool case study.....	174
4.4.4	Analysis of indicators on Latxa sheep wool case study.....	177
4.4.1.6	Environmental/circular indicators	177
4.4.1.7	Economic indicators	183
4.4.1.8	Social indicators.....	187
4.4.5	Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations.....	191
4.4.6	Key learnings of Latxa sheep wool case study.....	193
5	Results From The Chemicals Sector Case Studies.....	195
5.1	Sector-specific insights from stakeholder consultations	195
5.2	Chemical - Waste-to-methanol	197
5.2.1	Introduction to waste-to-methanol case study.....	198
5.2.1.1	General description	198
5.2.1.2	Value chain and the process.....	198
5.2.1.3	Baseline and market	201
5.2.2	Stakeholders in the waste-to-methanol value chain	203
5.2.2.1	Identification of relevant stakeholders	203
5.2.2.2	Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders.....	206
5.2.3	Policies of relevance to waste-to-methanol value chain	207
5.2.4	Analysis of indicators of the waste-to-methanol case study	213
5.2.4.1	Environmental/circular indicators	213

- 5.2.4.2 Economic indicators 217
- 5.2.4.3 Social indicators 219
- 5.2.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations 220
- 5.2.6 Key learnings of waste-to-methanol case study 223
- 5.3 Chemical - Bio-MEG, bio-MPG, and renewable functional fillers from wood 225
 - 5.3.1 Introduction to bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study 225
 - 5.3.1.1 General description 225
 - 5.3.1.2 Value chain and the process 226
 - 5.3.1.3 Baseline and market 229
 - 5.3.2 Stakeholders in the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study 231
 - 5.3.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders 231
 - 5.3.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders: 236
 - 5.3.3 Policies of relevance to bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass 238
 - 5.3.4 Analysis of indicators on bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study
242
 - 5.3.4.1 Environmental /circular indicators 242
 - 5.3.4.2 Economic indicators 249
 - 5.3.4.3 Social indicators 250
 - 5.3.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations 252
 - 5.3.6 Key learnings of bio-MEG case study 255
- 6 Results From The Plastics Sector Case Studies 256
 - 6.1 Sector-specific insights from stakeholder consultations 256
 - 6.2 Plastics - Polylactic acid 258
 - 6.2.1 Introduction to polylactic acid case study 258
 - 6.2.1.1 General description 258
 - 6.2.1.2 Value chain and the process 259
 - 6.2.1.3 Baseline and market 260
 - 6.2.2 Stakeholders in the PLA value chain 263
 - 6.2.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders 263

- 6.2.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders..... 265
- 6.2.3 Policies of relevance to PLA value chain 266
- 6.2.4 Analysis of indicators of the PLA case study..... 265
 - 6.2.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators 265
 - 6.2.4.2 Economic indicators 269
 - 6.2.4.3 Social indicators..... 270
- 6.2.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations 271
- 6.2.6 Key learnings of PLA case study 271
- 6.3 Plastics - Polypropylene from used cooking oil 272
 - 6.3.1 Introduction to PP from UCO case study 272
 - 6.3.1.1 General description 272
 - 6.3.1.2 Value chain and the process..... 273
 - 6.3.1.3 Value chain and the process..... 273
 - 6.3.2 Stakeholders in the PP from UCO value chain..... 274
 - 6.3.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders 274
 - 6.3.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders..... 277
 - 6.3.3 Policies of relevance to PP from UCO value chain..... 279
 - 6.3.4 Analysis of indicators of the PP from UCO value chain..... 283
 - 6.3.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators 283
 - 6.3.4.2 Economic indicators 287
 - 6.3.4.3 Social indicators..... 289
 - 6.3.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations 290
 - 6.3.6 Key learnings PP from used UCO value chain..... 292
- 6.4 Plastics - Cellulose acetate 293
 - 6.4.1 Introduction to cellulose acetate case study 293
 - 6.4.1.1 General description 293
 - 6.4.1.2 Value chain and the process..... 293
 - 6.4.1.3 Baseline and market 295

6.4.2	Stakeholders in the cellulose acetate value chain.....	298
6.4.2.1	Identification of relevant stakeholders	298
6.4.2.2	Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders.....	301
6.4.3	Policies of relevance to cellulose acetate value chain.....	303
6.4.4	Analysis of indicators of the cellulose acetate case study	311
6.4.4.1	Environmental/circular indicators	311
6.4.4.2	Economic indicators	316
6.4.4.3	Social indicators.....	319
6.4.5	Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations	322
6.4.6	Key learnings of cellulose acetate case study.....	324
7	Conclusions and further steps in WP3	328
8	References	330

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Example of CLT panel (Source: Van Acker et al., 2023)..... 30

Figure 2. Value chain of cross laminated timber 31

Figure 3. Full cycle forest management (Source: Debitum Investments, 2023)..... 33

Figure 4. Identified stakeholders in cross laminated timber value chain..... 37

Figure 5. Stakeholders of biochar-concrete composites mapped in a power-interest matrix ... 39

Figure 6. Value chain of biochar-concrete composites 60

Figure 7. Yearly biochar production capacity in Europe [in tonnes] (Source: EBI, 2024) 61

Figure 8. Identified stakeholders for biochar-concrete composites 63

Figure 9. Stakeholders of biochar-concrete composites mapped in a power-interest matrix ... 66

Figure 10. Hemp insulation (Source: Hempitecture) 80

Figure 11. Value chain of the hemp insulation case study 81

Figure 12. Biobased building materials valorisation scenarios at end-of-life (Source: Rabbat et al., 2021)..... 82

Figure 13. Hemp products (Source: Ingrao et al., 2015)..... 82

Figure 14. Thermal insulation overview (Source: Pavel & Blagoeva, 2018) 83

Figure 15. Identified stakeholders in the hemp insulation value chain 86

Figure 16. Stakeholders of the hemp insulation value chain mapped in a power-interest matrix 88

Figure 17. Mechanical recycling of wool textile garments based on open and closed loop recycling (Source: Russel et al., 2016) 114

Figure 18. Value chain of the Prato Textile District 115

Figure 19. Identified stakeholders in the Prato Textile District 118

Figure 20. Stakeholders mapped in a power-interest matrix 122

Figure 21. Types of cellulosic based fibres based on their origin. MMCF is represented by generated fibres and cellulosic derivatives. (Edited from Harmsen et al, 2022.)..... 143

Figure 22. Global MMCF production in 2023 (Source: Textile Exchange, 2024)..... 144

Figure 23. Value chain of MMCFs 145

Figure 24. Processing lyocell (Source: Felgueiras, 2021) 146

Figure 25. Global fibre production in 2023 (Source: Textile Exchange, 2024)..... 147

Figure 26. Global MMCF production by type in 2023 (Textile Exchange, 2024)..... 148

Figure 27. Identified stakeholders in the lyocell value chain 150

Figure 28. Stakeholders of lyocell mapped in a power-interest matrix..... 151

Figure 29. Value chain of the TERNUA case study 168

Figure 30. Identified stakeholders in the Latxa sheep wool value chain 171

Figure 31 Stakeholders of the Latxa sheep wool case study mapped in a power-interest matrix 174

Figure 32. Value chain of the waste-to-methanol system..... 199

Figure 33. Schematic representation of waste-based methanol production by Enerkem (2023) 200

Figure 34. Global methanol demand per feedstock, divided in fuels and chemicals, in 2019 (Source: IRENA & METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2021)..... 202

Figure 35. Identified stakeholders in the waste-to-methanol value chain 205

Figure 36. Stakeholders of the waste-to-methanol value chain mapped in a power-interest matrix 206

Figure 37. Value chain of the bio-MEG from agriculture and forest biomass 226

Figure 38. Potential production pathways for bio-MEG from lignocellulosic feedstock (agriculture, forest) (Source: Ren et al. 2015)..... 229

Figure 39. Growing plastic production since 1950 as a driver for MEG market growth (Source: nova-Institute, 2024)..... 230

Figure 40. Identified stakeholders in bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study 234

Figure 41. Stakeholders of the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study mapped in a power-interest matrix..... 237

Figure 42. Value chain of PLA 259

Figure 43. Graphical representation of the PLA-based packaging film value chain (Source: STAR-ProBio, 2018) 260

Figure 44. Global capacities, production and trends 2022-2027 of biobased building blocks and polymers (Source: nova-Institute, 2023) 261

Figure 45. Identified stakeholders in the PLA case study 264

Figure 46. Stakeholders of the PLA case study mapped in a power-interest matrix 266

Figure 47. Value chain of PP from UCO 273

Figure 48. Global biobased PP market (Source: Wang et al., 2023) 274

Figure 49. Identified stakeholders in PP from UCO value chain.....275

Figure 50. Stakeholders of the PP from UCO value chain mapped in a power-interest matrix.278

Figure 51. Value chain of the cellulose acetate system294

Figure 52. Production process cellulose acetate flakes (Source: Cerdia, 2022).....295

Figure 53. Biobased polymer capacities and production 2023 (Source: Skoczinski, et al., 2024)296

Figure 54. Cellulose acetate market share by major application (Source: GVR, 2024).....297

Figure 55. Biobased building blocks and polymers - global capacities, production and trends 2022-2027 (Source: Skoczinski, et al., 2024)298

Figure 56. Identified stakeholders in the cellulose acetate value chain.....299

Figure 57. Stakeholders of the cellulose acetate value chain mapped in a power-interest matrix302

Figure 58. Overview of main policies affecting the cellulose acetate sector303

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Selected case studies and corresponding sectors	23
<i>Table 2. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the CLT case study</i>	<i>42</i>
Table 3. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the CLT case study	48
Table 4. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the CLT case study.....	53
Table 5. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the CLT case study	55
Table 6. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the biochar in concrete case study.....	68
Table 7. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the biochar in concrete case study	70
Table 8. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the biochar in concrete case study	75
Table 9. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the biochar in concrete case study	76
Table 10. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the hemp insulation case study	92
<i>Table 11. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the hemp insulation case study.....</i>	<i>99</i>
Table 12. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the hemp insulation case study .	102
Table 13. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the hemp insulation case study	104
<i>Table 14. In-progress map of local key relevant stakeholders of Prato Textile District, Italy .</i>	<i>119</i>
Table 15. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the Prato Textile District case study.....	124
<i>Table 16. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the Prato Textile District case study.....</i>	<i>128</i>
<i>Table 17. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the Prato Textile District case study</i>	<i>132</i>
<i>Table 18. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the Prato Textile District case study</i>	<i>135</i>
Table 19. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the man-made cellulosic fibres case study.....	154
Table 20. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the man-made cellulosic fibres (MMCFs)case study.....	157

Table 21. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the man-made cellulosic fibres case study..... 160

Table 22. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the man-made cellulosic fibres case study 162

Table 23. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the Laxta sheep wool case study..... 175

Table 24. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the Latxa sheep wool case study 178

Table 25. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the Latxa sheep wool case study 184

Table 26. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the Latxa sheep wool case study 188

Table 27. Impression of recent waste-based methanol production initiatives across Europe .. 202

Table 28. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the waste-to-methanol case study..... 210

Table 29. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the waste-to-methanol case study 214

Table 30. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the waste-to-methanol case study 217

Table 31. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the waste-to-methanol case study . 219

Table 32. Impression of recent bio-MEG production initiatives across Europe 230

Table 33. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study 240

Table 34. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study..... 243

Table 35. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study 249

Table 36. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study 251

Table 37. PLA main pros and cons (Source: NA.A.B. Taib, M.R. Rahman, D. Huda et al, 2023) 261

Table 38. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the PLA value chain..... 268

Table 39. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the PLA case study 266

Table 40. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the PLA case study 269

Table 41. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the PLA case study 270

Table 42. Information regarding the policy instrument to the PP from UCO value chain..... 281

Table 43. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the PP from UCO value chain283

Table 44. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the PP from UCO value chain...287

Table 45. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the PP from UCO value chain289

Table 46. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to cellulose acetate 307

Table 47. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the cellulose acetate case study.....312

Table 48. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the cellulose acetate case study316

Table 49. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the cellulose acetate case study ...319

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
BBCP	Biobased, Biodegradable and Compostable Plastics
BFB	Bubbling fluidised bed
BP	Bioplastics
BPD	Biodiversity Damage Potential
BTX	Benzene, toluene, xylene
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Methodology
CAGR	Compound annual growth rate
CBBE	Circular Biobased Economy
CEAP	Circular Economy Action Plan
CA	Cellulose Acetate
CNC	Computer numerically controlled
CLT	Cross laminated timber
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DEG	Diethylene glycol
DACH	Germany, Austria, and Switzerland
EBIT	Earnings Before Interest and Taxes
EC	European Commission
ECOS	Environmental Coalition on Standards
EEB	European Environmental Bureau
EO	Ethylene oxide
EoL	End-of-Life
EPBP	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPD	Environmental product declaration
ESG	Environmental, social and governance

ETS	Emission Trading System
EU	European Union
EUDR	EU Deforestation Regulation
EUTR	EU Timber Regulation
EWP	European Waste Catalogue
EWP	Engineered wood product
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GCD	Green Claims Directive
GEM	General equilibrium modelling
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global warming potential
HTW	High-Temperature Winkler
HVO	Hydrotreated vegetable oil
IEA	International Energy Agency
ISCC	International Sustainability & Carbon Certification
ISTAT	National Statistics Institute of Italy
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute for Technology
LCA	Life cycle analysis
LCC	Life cycle costing
LEED	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design
LNG	Liquid natural gas
LUC	Land use change
MESG	Methanol Sector Group
MEG	Monoethylene glycol
MMCFs	Man-made cellulosic fibres
MPG	Monopropylene glycol

MPW	Municipal plastic waste
MSW	Municipal solid waste
MTBE	Methyl tert-butyl ether
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NRDC	Natural Resources Defense Council
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PBS	Polybutylene Succinate
PEFC	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PLA	Polylactic acid
PP	Polypropylene
PPM	Parts per million
PPRW	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation
PPWD	Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive
PRF	Phenol resorcinol formaldehyde
PUR	Polyurethane
R&D	Research and Development
RDF	Refuse-derived fuel
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restrictions of Chemicals
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RES	Renewable Energies Share
rPP	Recycled polypropylene
RVO	Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland (in English: Dutch Enterprise Agency)
SAF	Sustainable aviation fuel

SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SMR	Steam methane reforming
SO	Societal objective
SOC	Soil organic carbon
SUPD	Single-Use Plastics Directive
T	Task
TEG	Triethylene glycol
TRL	Technology readiness level
TU	Technical university
UCO	Used cooked oil
UN	United Nations
UoF	University of Freiburg
VerpackG	Verpackungsgesetz
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WGS	Water-gas shift
WMA	Waste Management Act
WP	Work package

1 INTRODUCTION

The SUSTRACK project adopts a bottom-up approach to the development and validation of key project outputs (including the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System developed in WP2) by testing them against real case studies. In T3.1, 10 case studies were selected. Later on another case study was added on cellulose acetate (see Table 1). They belong to four sectors that face critical challenges within the current linear system: (a) the construction sector (requiring, e.g., a shift from concrete to sustainable renewable alternatives); (b) the textile sector (requiring, e.g., a shift from fossil-based to biobased fibres); (c) the (fine) chemical sector (requiring, e.g., a transition to renewable carbon sources and biorefineries); and (d) the plastics sector (requiring, e.g., a shift from fossil-based to biobased polymers).

Table 1. Selected case studies and corresponding sectors

Sector	Case study
Construction	Cross-laminated timber
Construction	Biochar as an additive in concrete
Construction	Hemp insulation
Textile	Recycled carded wool from Prato, Italy
Textile	Man-made cellulosic fibres, like Lyocell
Textile	Latxa sheep wool from the Basque Country of Spain
Chemical	Waste to methanol
Chemical	Bio-MEG, bio-MPG, and renewable functional fillers from wood
Plastics	Polylactic acid (PLA)
Plastics	Polypropylene from used cooking oil
Plastics	Cellulose acetate

The objective of T3.2 was to validate the applicability and comprehensiveness of the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System developed in WP2. This framework includes a database of indicators structured under societal objectives (SOs) and its sub-topics in line with the approach used in Kardung et al. (2021). For this, the 5 societal objectives of the EU Bioeconomy strategy (EC, 2018) were taken as a basis i.e., 1. Food and nutrition security; 2. Sustainable natural resource management; 3. Dependence on non-renewable resources; 4. Mitigating and adapting to climate change; 5. Employment and economic competitiveness.

In T3.2, the 10 case studies and their needs were matched to relevant indicators following a stepwise approach, and any gaps identified were provided as feedback for WP2. This concerns comments for the further development of the monitoring system in terms of clarity, completeness and other relevant aspects and to complement it with additional indicators. T3.2 also provided guidance for the case study analysis to be carried out in T3.3. This includes the mapping of stakeholders and policies of relevance for these case studies. Moreover, guidance was provided in terms of information and data collection. This refers to identifying and reviewing relevant (publicly) available information (i.e., publications, reports) and the results of previous environmental, social, and economic assessments. This also considers engagement with

stakeholders through emails, interviews or workshops organised to generate additional knowledge on the case studies.

The objective of this T3.3 is to report on the assessment of the SUSTRACK case studies belonging to the four sectors: construction, textile, chemical and plastics. For each case study it is aimed to provide information on the value chain, the process description, and its market. Moreover, to provide identification of the most relevant stakeholders involved in the value chain and their mapping in terms of their power and interest to drive change and influence the further development and implementation of that value chain. Furthermore, policies that are relevant for the value chain are identified and information is provided whether it is stimulating or acts as a barrier to the development of that value chain. As explained above, in T3.2 a preliminary identification of the most relevant indicators was conducted for each case study. This list of indicators that fall under three categories as environmental/circular, economic and social are used as a starting point in this task and refined by removing or adding indicators based on the further information and data collection carried out on the case study. Based on this analysis of indicators it is aimed to provide information on the sustainability performance of the value chain as well as research gaps existing in performing assessments. The stakeholder workshops carried out generated both case study specific and sector-wide insights. These are aimed to be complemented with insights from interviews and reported.

The report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 presents the methodological approach used for the assessments; Chapters 3 to 6 present the results from the case study assessments with one chapter per sector (construction, textile, chemical and plastics, respectively). Each chapter starts with overall outcomes for that sector from the stakeholder engagements carried out structured into three dimensions: market, policy, and sustainability. This is followed by the reporting of the assessments of the two or three case studies belonging to that sector. In each case study assessment, a brief description of the examined value and its (market) context is provided, followed by stakeholder and policy mapping, analysis of indicators, outcomes from stakeholder consultations and the assessment ends with key learning from this case study. Finally, Chapter 7 reports the main conclusions from this task and provides information on the next steps in WP3.

2 APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY

The following stepwise case study assessment methodology was followed in this report:

1. Introductory section

This section provides brief description of the examined case study and its (market) context, including the description of the value chain (i.e., from feedstock delivery to end-of-life processing, showing the main processing steps) and the current and potential market applications of the end-product with market volumes, also providing information on the dominant (fossil) system currently in place that the analysed system seeks to replace.

2. Stakeholder mapping

This section firstly includes the identification of the relevant stakeholders and then a mapping the identified relevant stakeholders in a power-interest matrix. The identified stakeholders are distinguishing between those directly in the Bioeconomy supply chain or present in the Enabling environment. Description is provided on the link of these stakeholders to the examined case study. In the power-interest matrix the identified relevant stakeholder types were classified in accordance with their power and interest to drive change and influence the further development and implementation of that value chain. Brief analysis is provided of how these stakeholders are expected to either negatively or positively impact the implementation of the examined system.

3. Policy mapping

In this section, policies are identified that could either stimulate or impede the implementation of the value chain. An overview is provided of the relevant policies in a table which provides a short description of the main goal of the policy instrument and its type (i.e., direct regulation, economic instrument, voluntary approach, and market-based signalling approaches). Further information is provided in text on how these policies are of relevance to the case study and how they are stimulating or impeding the development of the value chain.

4. Analysis of relevant sustainability indicators

The identification of the indicators that are relevant for the case studies was taken as an iterative process. As part of this T3.2, a first review was conducted and the indicators in the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System deemed highly relevant for each case study were identified and presented in deliverable D3.2. This list of indicators is further elaborated and refined as part of T3.3 case study assessment where the case study owners collected further data and information on their case studies through literature review and stakeholder engagement. This deeper analysis can lead to removing or adding indicators based on the review conducted. In this next stage also the data availability to make an assessment on these indicators are analysed. In the case that no information or data could be found to support the analysis of the indicator that was selected as highly relevant for that case study, this is reported as a research gap. The analysis is performed, similarly to D3.2, under three sub-sections as: environmental/circular indicators, economic indicators, and social indicators. Under each sub-section, the overall findings in terms

of sustainability performance of the examined value chain are reported alongside the research gaps identified (e.g., related to data availability, or assessment methodology).

5. Reporting on outcomes from stakeholder engagements

The sectorial stakeholder workshops carried out as part of DESIGN conference generated both case study specific and sector-wide insights. These are categorised in three dimensions: Market, Policy, and Sustainability. For each, the challenges brought up by stakeholders are reported as well as recommendations and examples of good practices proposed. In reporting of case-study specific insights these findings are also complemented with the findings through interviews with targeted stakeholders.

6. Reporting on key learnings

This section is for reporting on the summary of the key lessons learnt from the analysis of the case study. Examples of questions that could be answered include:

- What policies and stakeholders have the highest potential to stimulate or hinder the development of the examined system further in relation to the envisioned sustainability transition?
- What urgent actions are recommended to further strengthen, inhibit, or reverse this dynamic (e.g., a different approach to powerful stakeholders, more effective implementation of the policies, improved monitoring on certain sustainability indicators)?
- What research and data gaps exist and how can they be addressed?

A template was prepared based on this stepwise case study assessment methodology with guidance and shared with the case study owners to facilitate reporting of their analysis. Additionally, templates were provided in developing the visuals for the stakeholder mapping and power-interest matrix with instructions. Each case study owner performed the assessment and filled the templates for their case study. For this purpose, each case study owner performed a literature review on the available information on the value chain, relevant stakeholders, and sustainability performance for the case study at hand. The literature search covers identifying, screening, and extracting information from relevant scientific publications, previous studies, reports, etc. from grey literature. In addition, engagement is done with the relevant stakeholders through interviews and workshops, to collect additional information and close data gaps.

3 RESULTS FROM THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR CASE STUDIES

As part of SUSTRACK, three case studies were examined to explore sustainable and bio-based materials in the construction sector. The insights gained from these case studies were crucial in shaping sector-specific discussions during stakeholder consultations. The first construction case study focuses on cross-laminated timber (CLT), a highly engineered wood product that provides structural strength and sustainability benefits, offering an alternative to traditional concrete and steel construction. The second case study investigates biochar as an additive in concrete, an innovative approach that enhances durability and carbon sequestration, improving the environmental performance of concrete structures. The third case study explores hemp insulation, a bio-based material with excellent thermal and acoustic insulation properties, contributing to energy-efficient and circular building practices.

The following section provides an overview of the construction sector-specific insights derived from the SUSTRACK DESIGN workshop discussions, including perspectives from stakeholders engaged in these case studies and the broader sustainable construction industry.

3.1 Sector-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Policy dimension

Challenges

- Insufficient regulatory support tailored for biobased construction products hinders their widespread adoption and market integration. Current regulations often fail to account for the unique properties and benefits of biobased materials, creating barriers to certification, standardisation, and large-scale use. Developing policies that specifically address the needs of biobased construction products would encourage innovation and enhance market confidence.
- Biobased materials have distinct characteristics compared to geo- and fossil-based materials, yet regulations are primarily designed for the latter, creating an inequity in standards and treatment. This misalignment fails to acknowledge the environmental and performance benefits of biobased materials, making certification and market entry more challenging.

Recommendations/good practices

- Facilitating knowledge exchange and mutual learning within projects like SUSTRACK is essential for fostering innovation and best practices. Collaborative initiatives enable stakeholders to share insights, address challenges, and develop effective strategies for advancing sustainable solutions. Strengthening these networks accelerates the adoption of biobased materials and drives progress toward a more sustainable and resilient built environment.
- Adapting regulations to better reflect the unique properties of biobased materials would ensure fairer treatment, foster innovation, and accelerate the shift toward more sustainable construction practices. By recognising the environmental and performance benefits of these materials, policymakers can create a more supportive framework that encourages their widespread adoption and integration into the built environment.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- Insufficient knowledge hinders the adoption and development of sustainable and innovative practices because education and traditional methods are primarily oriented toward the use of fossil-based materials. This reliance on conventional approaches limits awareness of alternative solutions and slows the transition to sustainable construction.
- The shortage of skilled workers and formal training programs along the value chain presents an obstacle to the growth of the biobased materials industry.

Recommendations/good practices

- Achieving social and professional community acceptance is crucial for the widespread adoption of new materials and sustainable construction practices. Overcoming scepticism, addressing misconceptions, and demonstrating the long-term benefits of biobased solutions are essential steps in fostering trust and encouraging industry-wide adoption. Engaging stakeholders through education, advocacy, and real-world applications will help integrate sustainable materials into mainstream construction.
- Expanding biobased construction education and training is essential for accelerating the adoption of sustainable building practices. Comprehensive programs that equip architects, builders, and other industry professionals with the knowledge and skills to work with biobased materials will help bridge the current expertise gap. Investing in specialised training initiatives, apprenticeships, and certification programs will ensure a skilled workforce capable of driving innovation and promoting environmentally friendly construction solutions.

Market dimension

Challenges

- The insufficient focus on designing long-lasting buildings with circularity and recyclability in mind leads to excessive material waste, inefficient resource use, and a higher environmental footprint. Without prioritising durable construction, material reuse, and end-of-life planning, buildings contribute to resource depletion and increased landfill accumulation. The lack of integration of these sustainable principles hinders the transition to a more resilient and environmentally responsible construction industry, slowing the adoption of innovative building practices.
- Optimising the availability and use of local material streams in construction is a challenge due to the fragmented supply chains, lack of standardised quality control, and limited infrastructure to process these materials on a large scale. As a result, the use of local materials is often less efficient and more expensive compared to traditional, widely available options.

- Difficult access to capital for developing and marketing new biobased products stems from the high perceived risk associated with these innovations. Investors and financial institutions often view biobased materials as unproven, with uncertain market demand and regulatory challenges, making them hesitant to provide funding. This lack of financial support slows down the growth of biobased industries, limiting opportunities for research, development, and scaling.
- The absence of a strong lobbying presence for biobased products, compared to the well-established lobbying efforts for fossil-based products, creates an imbalance in policy and market support. Fossil-based industries have long benefited from powerful advocacy that influences regulations, subsidies, and incentives, while biobased alternatives struggle to gain the same level of attention and support. This disparity limits the growth of biobased industries, hindering innovation and adoption.
- The limited size of the biobased market and industries makes it challenging to benefit from economies of scale and technological learning effects, which are crucial for reducing costs and improving efficiency. Without larger production volumes and widespread adoption, biobased products remain more expensive and less competitive compared to conventional alternatives.

Recommendations/good practices

- Integrating various biobased materials, such as bamboo, wood, natural fibres, and mycelium, into construction and design presents challenges related to material compatibility, performance consistency, and a lack of standardised guidelines. These materials, while highly sustainable, have distinct properties that require specialised knowledge to ensure they function well together in structural applications. Additionally, the absence of clear regulations and certification processes for biobased materials makes it difficult for builders and designers to confidently adopt them.
- Applying systems thinking in building design is challenging due to the complexity of evaluating the entire life cycle of a building, from material sourcing to demolition. It requires integrating diverse factors such as environmental impact, energy use, resource efficiency, and social factors, which often involves trade-offs between competing priorities. Furthermore, the lack of standardised tools and frameworks for assessing life cycle impacts across all stages of a building's life complicates this approach. Overcoming these challenges demands a shift in design practices, with a focus on collaboration, education, and the development of comprehensive life cycle analysis tools to ensure buildings are truly safe, sustainable, and optimised throughout their entire lifespan.

3.2 Construction - Cross laminated timber

3.2.1 Introduction to the cross laminated timber case study

3.2.1.1 General description

Cross Laminated Timber, or CLT, is an engineered wood product, or EWP, constructed from multiple layers of lumber boards that are stacked, glued, and pressed into a solid panel (see Figure 1). Each layer is oriented perpendicular to each other, resulting in a panel with structural rigidity in both directions giving it great tensile and compressive strength. CLT can be used for floors, walls, roofs, and stairs and allows developers to create wood construction multi-floor buildings.

Figure 1. Example of CLT panel (Source: Van Acker et al., 2023)

CLT is a large-scale solid engineered wood panel that is lightweight yet exceptionally strong, offering excellent fire, seismic, and thermal performance. A significant advantage of CLT is its high level of prefabrication. Custom-made panels, featuring all necessary openings for doors, windows, connections, and utility locations, are created using computer numerically controlled (CNC) machinery. This results in rapid construction times, minimal on-site waste, and considerable design flexibility, all contributing to a low environmental impact. Consequently, cross laminated timber is emerging as a highly advantageous alternative to conventional materials like concrete, masonry, or steel, particularly in multi-family and commercial constructions.

3.2.1.2 Value chain and the process

The value chain of CLT (see Figure 2) starts off with the management of forests and the harvesting of round timber. The current manufacturing of cross laminated timber is done almost exclusively using softwood species such as pine, spruce, larch. In 2022, the demand for softwood to produce CLT reached 1,5 million m³ in the DACH (i.e., Germany (D), Austria (A), and Switzerland (CH)) region plus Italy and Czechia out of the total 115,2 million m³ sawn softwood being produced in Europe (Sustained CLT Boom, n.d.) (UNECE/FAO, 2023). The raw material in the form of logs is then processed at sawmills into sawn timber. Most of the larger CLT producers in Europe have their own sawmills to process the timber they need for their CLT production. By-products such as bark, chips, shavings and sawdust are further recycled into other EWPs or used for pellets or biomass for energy.

After the timber is sawn, it is strength-graded according to standard EN 14081-1. The next step in the production process is visual grading and drying of the timber, as the moisture content of timber for the production of CLT needs to be between 8% and 15% when the timber boards or planks are glued together. The exact moisture content is also dependent on the type of adhesive used in the CLT manufacturing process as well as the end use of the CLT product (Borgström et al., 2019).

The actual manufacturing process of CLT generally starts with the trimming or re-cutting, finger-jointing, and planing of individual boards to create boards with a desired length and thickness for the eventual CLT panel. This step allows for the removal of defects of boards. The following step in the CLT manufacturing process is somewhat dependent on the manufacture and the scale of the manufacturing line. Stora Enso, producer of biomaterials, first produces single-layer panels by glueing boards edge to edge, the single layers are then stacked in cross sections and pressed together with adhesive to form a 3, 5, 7 or more layer panel with a maximum thickness of approximately 500 mm. CLT can also be produced without the single-layer manufacturing step. Here boards are laid out, adhesive is applied and the boards for the next layer of the panel are laid out on top before being pressed together for curing.

After the pressing stage, the panel is planed again and sanded to remove any excess adhesive from the surface and make sure the panel is the right thickness. For blank CLT, only the edges are trimmed to dimensions before the panel is ready for transport. One of the major advantages of CLT is the level of prefabrication and design freedom that the material offers as each individual panel can be shaped to desire through computer numerically controlled (CNC) machining meaning that all the needed cuts, openings and slots are machined in the factory, ready to be installed when they arrive at the construction site.

Figure 2. Value chain of cross laminated timber

3.2.1.3 Baseline and market

CLT is a versatile construction material suitable for a wide range of building applications. It can be utilised in single and multi-family houses, public and commercial buildings, agricultural structures, industrial facilities, and office buildings. Additionally, CLT is well-suited for modular and temporary constructions, as well as for expanding existing buildings such as adding additional floors (Borgström et al., 2019).

The advantages of CLT have contributed significantly to its use in mass timber construction and the development of tall timber buildings worldwide. In addition to its excellent material properties, such as strength, stiffness, and lightweight, CLT offers architectural design flexibility, enabling innovative designs that may not be achievable with other building materials. An example of this is Mjøstårnet, the Tower of Lake Mjøsa, which is an 18 storey tall timber building that was built in Norway and completed in March 2019. At the time of completion it was officially the world's tallest wooden building at 85.4 meters (Voulpiotis et al., 2020). It is projects like this that showcase that wood can be a valid alternative to steel and concrete while also helping and playing a potentially important role in reducing the environmental impact of construction sector.

In its current state, the built environment sector is responsible for at least 37% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Division et al., 2023) and around half of all extracted materials in the EU (Fetting, 2020). Most of the progress of reducing environmental impacts has been focused on improving energy efficiency of buildings through the EU's Renovation Wave (Renovation Wave, n.d.) to reduce the operational carbon emissions of buildings. However, efforts to mitigate the embodied carbon emissions stemming from the design, manufacturing, and utilisation of building materials like cement, steel, and aluminium have fallen short. This is where a shift to biobased building materials, such as CLT, can have a big impact on reducing the use and extraction of non-regenerative materials and reducing atmospheric carbon (Division et al., 2023). When looking at the production of cement alone, worldwide production has grown from 1.39 billion tons in 1995 to an estimated 4.1 billion tons in 2022, which gives an indication of the extent to which the construction industry has grown. Cement is also overwhelmingly made by burning fossil fuels like coal and pet coke in cement kilns, akin to large furnaces to heat limestone (Key Facts & Figures, n.d.).

While biobased materials offer promising prospects for reducing environmental impact, the management of these materials, from sourcing to end-of-life, can significantly influence their overall carbon footprint (Division et al., 2023). Despite their ability to store and sequester carbon, there remain considerable uncertainties in current life cycle analyses (LCAs) concerning the complete biogenic carbon emissions and sequestration of wood building products, as the effects on carbon storage in forest soils during and after harvesting (see Figure 3, depicting the full cycle of forest management) are not consistently factored in (Stiebert et al., 2019).

FULL CYCLE FOREST MANAGEMENT

Figure 3. Full cycle forest management (Source: Debitum Investments, 2023)

The production of CLT started in the 1990s in Europe and has since then spread to various regions worldwide. As of 2020, the global production capacity of CLT was approximately 2.8 million cubic meters (m³), with Europe accounting for the majority at 48%, notably led by the DACH region plus the Czech Republic and Italy. Following closely, North America constituted 43%, trailed by Oceania at 6% and Asia at 3%. Projections indicate a continued expansion in production capacity, expected to reach around 4 million m³ by 2025 (Rakhmanin et al., 2021). In Europe, the current CLT production output has reached a volume of 1.7 million m³ in 2023. While most European CLT is still being produced in the DACH region, numerous other European countries have also gained one or more CLT production plants over the last decade. Production capacities also keep increasing as new plants are built or the production capacity of existing plants grows. With five new plants becoming operational in 2023 and a few more to come in 2024, Europe's overall production capacity will reach around 2.3 million m³ a year (The Temporary End to Major Investments, n.d.).

Given below is a list of the top five CLT manufacturers that are anticipated to dominate the European market:

- **Stora Enso**

Stora Enso was formed in 1998 when the Swedish mining and forestry products organisation, Stora AB, merged with the Finnish forestry products firm, Enso Oyj. It is currently one of the leading global forest products groups which has around 26,000 employees in more than 35 countries. Its sales in 2015 were EUR 10.0 billion with an operational EBIT (Earnings Before Interest and Taxes) of EUR 915 million. Stora Enso derives nearly 75% of its revenues from countries in the European region and 15% of its revenues from the countries situated in Asia.

- **KLH Massivholz GmbH**

KLH Massivholz GmbH was founded in 1999 and is based in Murau, Austria, with a subsidiary in Sollentuna, Sweden. It is one of the biggest producers of large-sized CLT products worldwide with more than 15,000 reference projects as well as an annual production capacity of 125,000 m³. It provides ceiling, structural wall, and roofing elements, floors, timber boards, crosswise laminates, and CLT panels. The company has an extensive distribution network across Europe and sells its products in the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Sweden, Switzerland, Spain, Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Finland, France, Great Britain, Italy, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, and the Czech Republic.

- **Binderholz**

Binderholz is the leading European organisation that produces solid wood panels and innovative construction solutions. It primarily deals with the industrial use and distribution of wood products. Some of the wood products provided by the company include glulam, timber, profiled timber, laminated timber, and single and multi-laminated solid wood panels. The company employs about 1,400 people with operations at five sites in Austria, two sites in Bavaria, and two sites in Finland. Apart from Austria and Italy, the company is also actively operating in Germany, Switzerland, France, and Spain.

- **Mayr-Melnhof Holz Group**

Initiated in 1850, the Mayr-Melnhof Holz Group is owned by the F. Mayr-Melnhof-Saurau Industrie Holding GmbH. The company has two major divisions which include processing and sawn timber. Moreover, it owns three sawmill plants in Leoben (Austria), Paskov (Czech Republic), and Efimovski (Russia), and timber processing plants in Gaishorn (Austria), Reuthe (Austria), and Richen (Germany). Additionally, the company's production program includes laminated ceiling elements, glued-laminated timber, special components, concrete formwork technology, and CLT. The product portfolio of the company also comprises briquettes and pellets produced at different locations.

- **Haslacher**

Haslacher is a family enterprise, based in Sachsenburg (Austria), which was founded in 1901. The company owns eight manufacturing sites in Germany, Slovenia, Austria, and Russia and is one of Europe's largest and most prominent timber industry companies with a workforce of more than 1,200. It offers sawn, pellets, shuttering boards, cross, and glue-laminated, finger jointed structural, solid timber ceiling systems, laminated beams DUO/TRIO, and surfaced timber products. The firm also converts biomass into energy for drying wood and generating electricity, supplies energy to the local district heating network of Möllbrücke and Sachsenburg and operates a small hydropower plant.

3.2.2 Stakeholders in the CLT value chain

3.2.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

The identification of stakeholders and actors relevant to the cross laminated timber value chain were determined through exploratory desk and literature research (e.g., websites of

governmental organisations and initiatives, research and advisory organisations supporting the wood and biobased construction material industry, and CLT manufacturers). An overview of the schematic representation of the identified stakeholders and actors can be found in Figure 4. The bioeconomy supply chain is represented in the light green section and its Enabling environment in the light grey section.

Bioeconomy supply chain:

The bioeconomy supply chain for CLT involves a diverse array of stakeholders, beginning with the production and harvesting of wood in forests. The sustainable management of forests plays a pivotal role in ensuring a steady supply of wood, with ownership structures varying across Europe. While approximately 60% of forests are privately owned and 40% are publicly owned, the distribution can differ significantly due to historical and social factors.

Forest owners, logging companies, and forestry advisors are key stakeholders engaged in the management and production of roundwood or logs, the primary raw material for CLT. Logging companies or contractors, along with sawmills, are responsible for transporting and processing logs into timber planks, one of the fundamental components for CLT production. The second essential component is an adhesive that effectively binds the timber planks together. Commonly used synthetic adhesives include polyurethane (PUR), phenol resorcinol formaldehyde (PRF), melamine urea formaldehyde (MUF), and emulsion polymer isocyanate (EPI).

Following the production of timber planks, the next stage in the value chain involves manufacturing CLT panels and potentially post-processing them as needed, including trimming, cut-outs, milling, and drilling. Once manufactured, the CLT panels are transported to designated construction sites for installation. An additional stage in the manufacturing process may occur when blank CLT panels undergo post-processing and are sold separately from the initial CLT production.

The end-of-life stage of CLT is still relatively uncharted territory, as most CLT constructions have not yet reached their end of life. In theory, CLT panels could be reused, as many of the connections used, such as screws, brackets, and hold-downs, are reversible. However, further research and exploration are needed to fully understand and optimise the end-of-life possibilities for CLT.

Enabling environment:

In discussing the enabling environment, it is crucial to delineate between governmental bodies, commercial entities, academia, and civil society. When examining relevant stakeholders within the EU or at an international scale, their direct involvement pertains to either the CLT value chain or the broader construction sector.

Firstly, governmental organisations encompass policymakers and regulatory authorities operating at various tiers, including the EU, national, or regional levels. Beyond formulating policies, these entities are tasked with establishing and enforcing building codes and regulations. Regional collaborations like Vlaanderen Circulair and Kamp C play instrumental roles in facilitating the

shift towards more sustainable living and construction practices. Additionally, supra-national bodies such as the United Nations (UN) contribute to this regulatory landscape.

Secondly, academia and research institutions, exemplified by institutions like UMONS (Université de Mons), EPFL (Swiss Federal Technology Institute of Lausanne) and UGent (University of Ghent) play a pivotal role. These entities contribute to advancing our understanding of CLT's characteristics, performance, potential enhancements, and implementation strategies. Organisations like wood.be are instrumental in driving this research forward.

The third category encompasses industry-related stakeholders and actors. This includes professionals engaged in CLT construction, such as architects, construction engineers, and construction companies. Financial entities like banks, investment firms, and insurance companies also play significant roles by providing funding for CLT projects and conducting risk assessments.

Lastly, civil society represents a vital category, including end-users like residents, businesses, and public services. Environmental organisations focus on evaluating the ecological footprint of construction materials, while non-governmental organisations like CEI-Bois (European Woodworking Industry Confederation) advocate for sustainable practices within the industry.

In summary, by recognising and engaging with stakeholders across these distinct categories, we foster an enabling environment conducive to the sustainable development and widespread adoption of CLT within the construction sector.

Figure 4. Identified stakeholders in cross laminated timber value chain

3.2.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

The different stakeholders identified as relevant to the case study were mapped in a power-interest matrix depending on their ability and interest to drive change. Figure 5 shows the different stakeholders mapped by their relative interest and power through the lens of being able to positively or negatively influence the further implementation of CLT.

Policymakers at regional, national, and international levels play a crucial role in shaping the CLT and construction sector. Their influence extends to both the adoption of CLT and the broader use of wood as a construction material, guiding regulatory frameworks, market incentives, and sustainability standards. NGOs, supranational organisations, regional partnerships, knowledge institutes and forest industry stakeholders, who have a high interest and power in shaping the transition to a more biobased construction sector with a growing focus on sustainable building practices, also play important roles in providing input to the decision-making processes that takes place at the (inter)national level.

The stakeholder group of end-users, or the general public, are a group with a very high potential and power to drive the further implementation of CLT in the construction sector through boosting the demand for CLT, timber and sustainable buildings. However, due to the high costs of building materials and construction in general, as well as misconceptions and mindset, the general interest in timber-based construction, such as CLT, is not equally high. Likewise, construction companies, and the architects and engineers responsible for construction also can have a large impact on the implementation of CLT, but a lack of understanding and knowledge about timber-based solutions depending on the region results in a relatively low interest. Moreover, financial institutes have the ability to play an important role into the further adoption and use of CLT, however factors like insurance and financing challenges of CLT projects indicate that interest is still not as high as for more traditional construction methods.

Stakeholders with high interest, but relatively little power, are education providers, commercial businesses, adhesive manufacturers, trade, and business associations as well as alliances and coalitions. This group of stakeholders all have an interest in one way or another in the increasing implementation and growth of CLT as this can support their business opportunities.

Stakeholders involved in the end-of-life processing of CLT products are rather limited and underdeveloped. While reuse is a potential end-of-life option, in practice it is difficult to achieve. The relative newness of CLT also means that the amount of end-of-life CLT currently available for processing is very limited. For sawmills, construction timber for the use of CLT manufacturing can be a potential market, however, larger CLT manufactures have their own sawmills, and the required investments for sawmills to be able to produce the needed graded timber can be a challenge and limits interest.

Figure 5. Stakeholders of biochar-concrete composites mapped in a power-interest matrix

3.2.3 Policies of relevance to the CLT value chain

In this section, policies were identified that could either propel or impede the implementation of CLT. These policies were detected through desk research and interviews with stakeholders. In Table 2, an overview is provided of the relevant policies, including the type of policy it concerns, further general information, as well as its relevance to the CLT case study.

To begin with, the European Green Deal (European Union, 2019), serves as the overarching framework for achieving climate neutrality by 2050. This initiative emphasises emission reduction, resource efficiency, and the transition to a circular economy, all of which are strongly

supported by the properties of CLT. With its ability to sequester carbon, reduce embodied emissions compared to traditional materials like steel and concrete, and its potential for reuse and recycling, CLT represents a vital component of the Green Deal's vision for a sustainable built environment.

The Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) further underscores CLT's importance. The CEAP promotes a shift away from the linear "take-make-dispose" model toward a circular economy that minimises waste and maximises resource efficiency. CLT supports this transition through its prefabricated design, which facilitates deconstruction and reuse, as well as the repurposing of its manufacturing by-products, such as sawdust and wood chips, for applications like biochar, biobased polymers, and other sustainable products.

Furthermore, the EU Climate Law and the 2030 Climate Target Plan establish ambitious goals for reducing GHG emissions, including a 55% reduction by 2030 and achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. CLT contributes significantly to these targets by offering a low-carbon alternative to conventional construction materials and benefiting from carbon pricing mechanisms, such as cap-and-trade systems, which penalise emissions-intensive materials like concrete and steel. Additionally, carbon credits could enhance the economic feasibility of CLT by accounting for its dual carbon benefits: long-term carbon storage and avoided emissions. However, carbon credits remain a complex and multifaceted topic, with uncertainties surrounding issues such as additionality, permanence, leakage, and the accurate calculation of savings.

CLT also aligns closely with the New European Bauhaus initiative, which seeks to create beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive living spaces. CLT's natural aesthetic, adaptability for modular designs, and strong environmental performance make it an ideal material for projects that reflect these goals. Similarly, the Renovation Wave Initiative, which aims to double renovation rates by 2030, benefits from CLT's prefabricated nature. This enables faster, more energy-efficient renovations that improve building performance while reducing emissions.

Beyond these applications, CLT can play a role in climate adaptation and biodiversity protection. The Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change supports regions and communities in building resilience to climate impacts, where CLT contributes through its ability to enable sustainable, low-carbon construction adaptable to local needs. At the same time, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the New EU Forestry Strategy for 2030 promote sustainable forestry practices and ecosystem restoration. CLT production complements these initiatives by sourcing timber responsibly, supporting sustainable forest management, and enhancing biodiversity while combating deforestation. However, additional support and adaptive strategies are required throughout the entire wood processing chain to ensure a sustainable supply and availability of wood while addressing the strategic innovation challenges faced by the forest-based sector. Regulations must remain credible, impactful, and practical for the forest sector. Forest-based value chains should be regarded as essential strategic materials. Recognising domestic wood as a vital raw material can enhance sustainability initiatives and support a more resilient bioeconomy.

Ensuring sustainable timber sourcing is further reinforced by the EU Timber Regulation (EUTR) and the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) (European Union, 2023a), which require that timber used in CLT manufacturing is legally harvested and deforestation-free. Compliance with these

regulations enhances the environmental credentials and market competitiveness of CLT, aligning with global efforts to protect forests and reduce illegal logging. However, the strict due diligence requirements impose additional administrative costs. While large CLT manufacturers with established compliance systems benefit from regulatory enforcement, smaller or uncertified suppliers may face challenges in meeting these standards. Additionally, some inconsistencies in enforcement across EU member states still remain.

Finally, initiatives such as the Carbon Farming Initiative and the Sustainable Built Environment Strategy emphasise the importance of using buildings as carbon stores and integrating circular economy principles into construction practices. These policies highlight CLT's long-term carbon storage capabilities, its role in waste reduction, and its contribution to energy efficiency throughout a building's lifecycle. While the EU-wide EN 15804+A2 standard provides clear guidelines for environmental product declarations (EPDs), inconsistencies in national adaptations of this standard create barriers to the cross-border adoption of CLT products. Addressing this challenge through the implementation of universally recognised European EPDs could streamline CLT's integration across EU nations.

Complementary directives such as the Energy Efficiency Directive (European Union, 2023b) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive further support the adoption of CLT by prioritising energy-efficient building solutions, renewable energy integration, and the use of smart technologies. Together, these policies solidify CLT's role as a cornerstone of the EU's green transition and its efforts to create a more sustainable, resilient, and climate-neutral future.

3.2.4 Analysis of indicators of the CLT case study

In T3.2, a consistency check was conducted to identify the indicators within the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System that are most relevant to the CLT case study. As a result of this process, a subset of indicators was classified as highly relevant. This initial analysis was based on a thorough literature review, with a specific focus on the environmental, economic, and social sustainability dimensions of the CLT value chain. The literature review employed various search queries using keywords such as: "social," "economic," "environmental," "life cycle assessment," "impacts," "cross-laminated timber," "timber construction," "value chain," and "sustainable construction."

The subsequent section builds upon the results of this preliminary analysis, further refining and elaborating on the findings. Each identified indicator will be utilised to assess the performance of the CLT value chain in comparison to conventional, non-biobased construction materials. The analysis integrates insights from T3.2, the literature review, and stakeholder consultations. In cases where no data or information was available to support the evaluation of a specific indicator, this was documented as a research gap.

Table 2. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the CLT case study

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
European Green Deal	The European Green Deal aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 through a broad framework of policies, including emission reduction, resource efficiency, and circular economy initiatives	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument by promoting the use of energy-efficient and sustainable building materials, such as cross-laminated timber, to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. By encouraging the use of sustainable materials in construction and renovation, the Green Deal fosters innovation and growth in the industrial hemp industry as well.	EU	Current	Policy framework and financial incentives	EC COM (2019)640
Circular Economy Action Plan	The Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) is a comprehensive initiative by the European Union aimed at promoting sustainable growth by transitioning from a linear "take-make-dispose" model to a circular economy. It focuses on reducing waste, maximising resource efficiency, and keeping materials in use for as long as possible. Key elements of the plan include fostering sustainable product design, promoting circular business models, encouraging recycling, and addressing sectors with high resource use, such as electronics, textiles, construction, and plastics.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates reduction of waste and keeping resources as long as possible in the economy.	EU	Current	Strategic framework and regulatory directives	EC COM (2020)98

EU Climate Law	The EU Climate Law makes the EU's commitment to climate neutrality by 2050 legally binding, with a target to cut emissions by 55% by 2030. It ensures all EU policies support the green transition, aligning with the European Green Deal and the Paris Agreement.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument for CLT and other sustainable materials by mandating legally binding climate targets for low carbon construction solutions.	EU	Current	Strategic framework and regulatory directives	Strategic framework and regulatory directives
2030 Climate Target Plan	The 2030 Climate Target Plan is the EU's strategy to reduce GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. It outlines measures to accelerate the transition to a sustainable economy, including boosting renewable energy, improving energy efficiency, and promoting green technologies. This plan is key to achieving climate neutrality by 2050 under the European Green Deal.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument for CLT and other sustainable materials by setting binding goals.	EU	Current	Regulatory directives	EC COM 2020/562
New European Bauhaus	New European Bauhaus is a policy and funding initiative that makes green transition in built environments enjoyable, attractive, and convenient for all. Even the smallest communities on the ground deserve living spaces that improve their well-being and sense of belonging. The initiative promotes solutions that are not only sustainable, but also inclusive and beautiful, while respecting the diversity of places, traditions, and cultures in Europe and beyond.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument for CLT by promoting sustainable, aesthetic, and inclusive design in the built environment. This initiative emphasises the use of innovative, low-carbon materials like CLT to create sustainable and visually appealing buildings.	EU	Current	Policy framework and financial incentives	New European Bauhaus
The Renovation Wave Initiative	The Renovation Wave Initiative is the EU's plan to improve the energy efficiency of buildings across Europe. It aims to double renovation rates by 2030, reducing energy consumption, cutting GHG emissions, and improving living conditions. The initiative focuses on making buildings greener, more affordable, and resilient, while creating jobs and advancing the EU's climate neutrality goals under the European Green Deal.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument for CLT by promoting the large-scale renovation of buildings to improve energy efficiency and reduce emissions. The initiative encourages the use of sustainable and low-carbon materials like CLT in retrofitting and construction projects.	EU	Current	Policy framework and financial incentives	EC COM 2020/662

Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change	The Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change is an EU initiative to support regions, cities, and communities in building resilience to climate impacts. It promotes innovative solutions, knowledge sharing, and funding to help adapt to challenges like heatwaves, floods, and droughts. The mission aims to engage at least 150 regions and communities by 2030.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument for CLT by encouraging sustainable and resilient construction practices to adapt to climate impacts.	EU	Current	Policy framework and financial incentives	EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change
Biodiversity Strategy for 2030	The Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 is the EU's plan to protect and restore nature, ensuring ecosystems' resilience and sustainability. It aims to expand protected areas to 30% of EU land and seas, restore degraded ecosystems, and tackle biodiversity loss. The strategy supports climate goals, food security, and a sustainable economy.	Potential stimulation or barrier	Potential stimulator by promoting forest management that conserves ecosystems. However, focus on protecting biodiversity could raise concerns about balancing timber production with forest conservation goals.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EC COM 2020/380
New EU Forestry Strategy for 2030	The New EU Forestry Strategy for 2030 is a key initiative to ensure the sustainable management of forests while enhancing their role in combating climate change and biodiversity loss. It aims to increase forest area, improve resilience, and promote sustainable forestry practices. The strategy supports rural livelihoods, bioeconomy development, and the EU's climate neutrality and biodiversity targets.	Potential stimulation or barrier	Potential stimulator by promoting forest management that conserves ecosystems. However, focus on protecting biodiversity could raise concerns about balancing timber production with forest conservation goals.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	New EU forest strategy for 2030
EU Deforestation Regulation	The EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) aims to prevent the import and sale of products linked to deforestation and forest degradation within the EU. It requires companies to ensure their supply chains are deforestation-free, covering commodities like food and timber. This regulation supports global efforts to combat deforestation, protect biodiversity, and address climate change.	Potential barrier	Potential barrier for CLT if it leads to overly strict sourcing requirements and effecting imports and exports.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EU 2023/1115
EU Timber Regulation	The EU Timber Regulation (EUTR) prohibits the placing of illegally harvested timber and timber products on the EU market. It requires businesses to ensure due diligence by	Potential barrier	Potential barrier for CLT if it leads to overly strict sourcing requirements and	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EU 2023/1115

	sourcing timber from legal and sustainable origins, promoting forest conservation and reducing illegal logging.		effecting imports and exports.				
Carbon farming initiative	Using buildings as a carbon store (coupled with substitution benefits) will contribute to a reduction of GHGs, as required under the EU climate targets (European Union, 2024).	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument for CLT by promoting sustainable land management practices that enhance carbon sequestration and support the carbon storage potential of CLT.	EU	Current	Voluntary approach	EU 2024/3012
Sustainable Built Environment Strategy	The Sustainable Built Environment Strategy is the EU's plan to promote sustainability throughout the lifecycle of buildings. It aims to improve resource efficiency, reduce emissions, and integrate circular economy principles into construction and renovation. The strategy is expected to ensure coherence across policy areas related, for example, to climate, energy, management of construction and demolition waste, digitalisation, or skills (European Parliament, n.d.).	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument for CLT by promoting the use of sustainable materials in construction and renovation.	EU	Planned	Strategy	Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment
Energy Efficiency Directive	The Energy Efficiency Directive is an EU policy aimed at reducing energy consumption and improving efficiency across sectors. It sets binding targets for energy savings, promotes technologies to cut energy use, and ensures better energy performance in buildings, industry, and transport. The directive is crucial for achieving the EU's climate goals and supporting the transition to a sustainable energy system.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates the use of CLT by promoting energy-efficient building practices. Reducing energy consumption for heating and cooling, as the directive encourages the renovation of buildings to improve energy efficiency.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EU 2023/1791
Energy Performance of Buildings Directive	The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) is an EU policy aimed at improving energy efficiency and reducing emissions from buildings. It sets standards for energy performance, requires energy certifications, and promotes measures like renovations, smart technologies, and renewable energy integration.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates the use of CLT by promoting energy-efficient building practices. Reducing energy consumption for heating and cooling, as the directive encourages the	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EU 2024/1275

			renovation of buildings to improve energy efficiency.				
Carbon removal certification proposal	The Carbon Removal Certification Proposal is an EU initiative to establish a reliable framework for certifying carbon removal activities. It aims to ensure transparency, quality, and accountability in methods like carbon storage in soil, forests, and technology-based solutions. The proposal supports scaling up carbon removal to meet the EU's climate neutrality goals and promotes innovation in sustainable carbon management.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument for CLT by recognising and certifying the carbon sequestration potential of sustainably sourced wood. By providing a clear framework for carbon removal, it encourages the use of CLT in construction.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EU 2024/3012
Waste Framework Directive	The Waste Framework Directive is the European Union's key legislation on waste management. It establishes principles for waste prevention, recycling, and disposal, emphasising the waste hierarchy: prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery, and disposal.	Stimulating instrument	A stimulating instrument for CLT, as it reduces construction and demolition waste (CDW) while also promoting reuse. CLT's design facilitates easier deconstruction rather than demolition, enhancing the understanding of its reusability and supporting a more sustainable circular economy in construction.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	2008/98/EC

3.2.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators

A total of 66 environmental and circular indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. However, after further review, refinement, and stakeholder input, several indicators were found to be too general and not closely related enough to the CLT case study. These indicators were eventually eliminated, resulting in the following list of indicators shown in Table 3 below.

CLT has emerged as a sustainable and innovative solution for modern construction, particularly in mid- and high-rise buildings. Its environmental performance is shaped by several key indicators, including forest sustainability, material efficiency, GHG emissions, carbon capture, and lifecycle impacts. When compared to traditional fossil-based materials like concrete and steel, CLT offers compelling environmental benefits, but challenges remain in optimising its sustainability and scalability.

CLT production relies heavily on softwood species such as spruce, pine, and fir, making sustainable forest management a cornerstone of its environmental credentials. Certification schemes such as the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) ensure that the wood is sourced responsibly, minimising deforestation, promoting reforestation, and protecting ecosystem services like biodiversity and water quality (Haisma et al., 2023; Sheppard et al., 2020). As demand for CLT grows, sustainable forest practices must evolve to ensure resilient forests capable of meeting future needs. Diversifying timber supply by incorporating fast-growing and less-utilised tree species can strengthen forest health and industry resilience, reducing pressure on softwood monocultures (Benneter et al., 2018). Sustainable management also addresses the forest footprint of CLT by ensuring that increased timber harvesting does not degrade ecosystems or lead to deforestation (Arto et al., 2022).

Material efficiency and circularity play a critical role in enhancing the sustainability of CLT. Currently, CLT is predominantly produced from virgin timber, but the incorporation of secondary wood from deconstructed buildings could reduce the demand for virgin resources. This approach aligns with the principles of cascading wood use, where materials are reused or repurposed in high-value applications before being converted to energy or disposed of (Haisma et al., 2023). For example, reusing wooden beams as window frames can significantly reduce the need for fresh timber. Design for disassembly also offers potential for increasing the reuse and recycling of CLT components. However, challenges remain, such as the presence of adhesives and potential damage during deconstruction, which complicate recovery processes (Harris et al., 2022). As of 2010, only 22.3% of post-consumer wood in the market was recovered, highlighting the need for improved recycling systems and infrastructure to enhance material circularity in CLT (Mantau & INFRO e.K., 2012).

Table 3. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the CLT case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Material and waste recycling and recovery rates	At the end of a building's life, the potential for reusing or recycling CLT components can further enhance its environmental benefits. Through design for disassembly, the level of components that could be reused or recycled could increase. However, certain challenges exist in recycling CLT, such as the presence of adhesives and potential damage during deconstruction, which can complicate material recovery processes (Harris et al., 2022). In 2010, 36.1 million m ³ of the 52.0 million m ³ potential post-consumer wood was recovered. This represents a recovery rate of 22.3% of the total wood market volume, with 9.2% used for materials and 12.1% for energy (Mantau & INFRO e.K., 2012).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Land use change (LUC)	Change in wood/wood fibre demand for forest products	An increased demand for mass timber could create competition for lumber between traditional applications, such as furniture production, and mass timber construction. However, this demand may also generate additional by-products, such as chips and mill residues, due to the increased production of softwood lumber, potentially reshaping the current forest product market (Nepal et al., 2021).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Primary Biomass production	Wood consumption	Most harvested timber is currently used for paper products (e.g., cardboard) and energy generation, which are short cycle uses and less sustainable. Redirecting timber to long-term applications, where carbon remains stored, is crucial for reducing carbon impact and conserving forests. Cascading wood use is also vital—for example, repurposing a wooden beam into a window frame instead of burning it can significantly reduce the need for virgin wood (Haisma et al., 2023).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Primary energy savings (kWh or % of total primary energy consumed)	The use of CLT can significantly reduce energy consumption during a building's operational phase. Although the extent of energy savings varies depending on the climate zone, buildings constructed with CLT generally demonstrate substantially lower energy demands compared to reinforced concrete structures. This is due to CLT's excellent thermal insulation properties, which help regulate indoor temperatures more efficiently and reduce the need for heating and cooling (Guo et al., 2017).	No.

3	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	% of deforestation or afforestation /product unit	To ensure resilient forests that support ecosystem services and sustainable construction, new forestry practices are essential. These practices must enhance forest resilience to climate change while meeting future demand across sectors (Haisma et al., 2023).	No.
	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	Share of forests certified for sustainable management	CLT production is intrinsically linked to the availability of sustainably managed forests, as it primarily relies on softwood species such as spruce, pine, and fir. Utilising certified wood in CLT production ensures that the raw materials are sourced from responsibly managed forests, where logging practices are sustainable, environmental impacts are minimised, and reforestation is promoted. Forest certification programs (e.g., FSC and PEFC) play a critical role in verifying sustainable forest management. Additionally, adherence to green building standards such as LEED or BREEAM enhances the environmental credentials of CLT.	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Procedures for recovering materials for other uses, such as incineration for raising process steam or heating, or agricultural use (yes/no)	To enhance the sustainability of the CLT production process, it is essential to optimise the utilisation of wood production residues, including sawdust, shavings, and cuttings. One viable option is to repurpose these residues for energy or heat generation, which can, in turn, be utilised to power the production processes of lumber or CLT panels (Vamza et al., 2021).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of the total amount of wood used is waste wood according to waste wood categories	CLT is currently exclusively produced from virgin timber, however the use of secondary timber from demolished buildings could help reduce virgin materials needs and increase the circularity of CLT and other timber materials.	Yes, pathways that incentivise and standardise the expansion of use of waste wood are required.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Carbon intensity	In 2022, the buildings sector accounted for about one-third of energy system emissions, with 26% from operations and 7% from embodied emissions in construction materials (UN Climate Change High-Level Champions et al., 2023). Mass timber has emerged as a low embodied carbon alternative for mid- and high-rise buildings, but its embodied energy and carbon vary based on factors like timber properties, sourcing, and transportation (Atnoorkar et al., 2024).	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle GHG emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	CLT offers a substantial reduction in GHG emissions over the full life cycle of a building compared to concrete. Its combination of low embodied carbon, carbon sequestration, energy efficiency, and recyclability make it a key material for reducing the construction industry's carbon footprint (Shin et al., 2023).	No.

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Rate of GHG emissions reduction or savings	Using CLT in construction offers significant GHG emissions savings across the building lifecycle. Depending on design and material substitution, total emissions can be reduced by up to 44.6% compared to conventional methods, with the added benefit of carbon sequestration making it a key strategy in reducing the construction industry's carbon footprint (Shin et al., 2023).	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Carbon stock (kg/unit of biomass)	Uncertainties remain in assessing the life cycle carbon footprint of CLT buildings, including biogenic carbon accounting, service-life predictions, maintenance assumptions, GHG flow dynamics over time, and end-of-life treatment of wood materials (Younis & Dadoo, 2022).	Yes, further research is needed to address these challenges and optimise the carbon footprint of CLT building systems from a full lifecycle perspective.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP100; gr eq. CO ₂)	Results show that an average of 26.5% reduction in the global warming potential is achieved in the hybrid CLT building compared to the concrete building, excluding biogenic carbon emissions (Pierobon et al., 2019).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Forest footprint	The forest footprint of CLT depends heavily on adherence to sustainable forest management practices to ensure that the growing demand for timber does not lead to deforestation or ecosystem degradation (Arto et al., 2022).	Yes, more detailed analysis and data collection are needed to fully assess the relationship between CLT production and forest ecosystems.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Sustainable forestry	The integration of sustainable forest management and timber-oriented forest practices is a key driver in advancing the development of CLT and supporting the transition to a more biobased construction sector. Ensuring future-resilient forests through sustainable management practices will be crucial for maintaining ecological balance, securing a reliable supply of raw materials, and fostering long-term environmental and economic benefits. (Haisma et al., 2023) (Sheppard et al., 2020)	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Biomaterial replacing non-renewable resources	Wood-based constructions	CLT is an innovative construction solution that is rapidly gaining traction in the industry. It is revolutionising the use of timber in mid- and high-rise construction, offering a sustainable alternative to traditional materials like steel and concrete. Additionally, its high degree of prefabrication is transforming how we approach building processes, enhancing efficiency, and reducing construction times.	No.

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Climate change adaptation	Diversity of tree species	CLT manufacturing currently exclusively uses softwood species. To create a more resilient CLT industry and forest industry, the utilisation and demand for other fast growing tree species can help push for more diverse timber production and more resilient and healthy forests (Benneter et al., 2018).	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Forest carbon emissions and removals	CLT can play a significant role in forest carbon dynamics by influencing both carbon emissions and removals throughout its lifecycle. CLT's impact on carbon storage and emissions depends on factors such as sustainable forestry practices, wood processing, transportation, and end-of-life disposal.	Yes, research gaps remain in evaluating the full net carbon impact of CLT throughout its lifecycle.

One of CLT's most significant advantages over concrete and steel is its potential to act as a carbon sink. During their growth, trees absorb CO₂, which remains stored in the wood throughout the building's lifecycle. When used in long-lasting structures, CLT effectively delays carbon release, contributing to climate change mitigation (Shin et al., 2023). Buildings using CLT can reduce total lifecycle emissions by up to 44.6% compared to traditional methods (Pierobon et al., 2019). Concrete and steel, on the other hand, are among the most carbon-intensive materials in construction. Cement production alone accounts for approximately 8% of global CO₂ emitted due to the high energy demands of processing limestone. Steel production similarly emits significant amounts of CO₂, with an average of 1.85 tons of CO₂/per ton of steel produced (UN Climate Change High-Level Champions et al., 2023). In addition to its low embodied carbon, CLT reduces operational emissions due to its excellent thermal insulation properties. This reduces energy consumption for heating and cooling, with buildings demonstrating substantially lower energy demands compared to reinforced concrete structures, particularly in cold and temperate climates (Guo et al., 2017).

Despite its advantages, uncertainties remain in assessing the full lifecycle carbon footprint of CLT. Factors such as biogenic carbon accounting, maintenance assumptions, and end-of-life treatment of wood materials introduce variability in lifecycle analyses. Further research is needed to address these gaps and refine carbon accounting methods for CLT buildings, ensuring their role as a climate-efficient construction material (Younis & Doodoo, 2022). Recycling at the end of a building's life is another area for improvement. While CLT components can potentially be reused, challenges like adhesive removal and damage during disassembly limit the efficiency of current recycling practices. Scaling up research and innovation in this area could enhance the circularity of CLT and extend its lifecycle benefits (Harris et al., 2022)

An increased demand for mass timber, including CLT, could reshape forest product markets by creating competition for lumber traditionally used in furniture, paper, and energy generation. However, this demand also generates by-products such as chips and mill residues, which can be repurposed for energy or other applications (Nepal et al., 2021). Shifting timber use from short-cycle products, like paper and energy, to long-term applications like CLT supports carbon storage and reduces overall carbon impact. Additionally, adherence to green building standards such as LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) or BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Methodology) enhances the environmental performance of CLT buildings, ensuring they meet high sustainability benchmarks. Optimising CLT production processes by using wood residues for energy generation also contributes to a lower carbon footprint (Vamza et al., 2021).

3.2.4.2 Economic indicators

A total of 11 economic indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. However, after further review, refinement, and stakeholder input, several indicators were found to be too general and not closely enough related to the CLT case study. These indicators were eliminated, resulting in the list of indicators shown in Table 4 below. One indicator newly identified as relevant was included in red.

Table 4. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the CLT case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Residual biomass potential	Residual biomass from forestry and sawmill operations presents potential for contributing to the CLT value chain. Studies show that CLT and modular buildings achieve lower primary energy consumption during production while generating higher biomass residues compared to concrete alternatives (Tetty et al., 2019).	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Potential market share of the product	CLT has significant growth potential as a sustainable, cost-competitive alternative in construction. Its ability to increase market share will depend on industry innovation, supportive policies, and public perception. With wood construction positioned as a key pillar of the EU's Green Deal and circular economy goals, CLT is well-aligned to contribute to these ambitions.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Primary Biomass production	Forests	The economic viability and growth of CLT are closely tied to the health and management of forests.	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Biomass self-sufficiency rate	Biomass from waste	The strategic utilisation of biomass from CLT waste can help with cost savings and job creation in the manufacturing process. Utilising biomass for on-site energy can lower operational costs by decreasing reliance on external energy sources (Cesprini et al., 2021).	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Recycling rate of biobased products	Due to the construction method of CLT and its prefabricated nature, the recycling rate of entire CLT components can be maximised by reversing the connections between individual panels. Additionally, design-for-deconstruction strategies and modular designs, both well-suited for CLT, can play a crucial role in supporting the EU's Construction and Demolition Waste recycling goals (Ahn et al., 2022).	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Post-consumer product used in industrial processes as material	CLT offers a wide range of post-consumer applications depending on how it is handled at the end of its life. When buildings that utilise CLT are deconstructed (rather than demolished), much of the material can be reclaimed, repurposed, or recycled.	Yes, lack of understanding, regulation, and utilisation of post-consumer wood.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Industrial residues used in industrial processes as material	Residual materials generated as by-products of the CLT manufacturing process, such as sawdust, offcuts, wood chips, and shavings, can be repurposed for a variety of applications. These include the production of other EWPs, feedstock for the pulp and paper industry, composite materials, biobased polymers, biochar, and chemical extraction of lignin and cellulose. Additionally, they can	No.

				support innovative uses like the production of mycelium-based materials and other sustainable solutions (Dupas et al., 2024; Duran et al., 2024; Vamza et al., 2021).	
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Cost of decarbonisation	CLT plays a vital role in the decarbonisation of our built environment. It contributes to this goal through carbon sequestration, reduced embodied carbon, and improved energy efficiency during construction. Additionally, carbon pricing schemes, such as cap-and-trade systems, enhance the competitiveness of CLT by penalising carbon-intensive materials like steel and concrete. Furthermore, the use of carbon credits could help offset the costs of CLT (Debnath et al., 2021).	Yes, lack of framework and understanding of full carbon cycle.

Residual biomass from forestry and sawmill operations offers significant opportunities for enhancing the sustainability and economic viability of the CLT value chain. Studies show that CLT and modular buildings have lower primary energy consumption during production compared to concrete alternatives, despite generating higher biomass residues (Tetty et al., 2019). These residuals, such as sawdust, offcuts, wood chips, and shavings, can be repurposed for various applications, improving the efficiency of resource use, and reducing environmental impact. The potential for using these by-products extends beyond CLT production and includes their use as feedstock for biobased materials, composite products, and even biochar, offering multiple avenues for waste valorisation (Dupas et al., 2024; Duran et al., 2024; Vamza et al., 2021).

CLT holds considerable promise as a sustainable and cost-competitive alternative in the construction sector, driven by its ability to reduce environmental impacts and contribute to circular economy goals. As a material with significant potential for decarbonising the built environment, CLT aligns well with the European Union's Green Deal and its focus on promoting sustainable construction. The expansion of CLT's market share in the construction sector will depend on several factors, including industry innovation, supportive policies, and growing public perception of its benefits. The economic viability and growth of CLT are intrinsically tied to the health and management of forests. Sustainably managed forests that provide the raw materials for CLT production are critical to the long-term sustainability of the industry. At the same time, the strategic use of residual biomass from the CLT manufacturing process, such as the generation of heat or energy on-site, can significantly reduce operational costs and enhance the economic feasibility of CLT production (Cesprini et al., 2021).

3.2.4.3 Social indicators

A total of 2 social indicators, shown in Table 5, were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. Newly identified relevant indicators were included in the table in red.

Table 5. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the CLT case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Existence of (legal) obligation on public sustainability report (yes/no)	There is an inconsistency in the legal obligations for public sustainability reporting between biobased materials like CLT and traditional materials such as concrete and steel, with biobased materials often facing less standardised and regulated reporting frameworks.	Yes, standardised testing and evaluation procedures specific for biobased products and technologies are needed.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Number of certifications/ labels the organisation obtained for the product/site	The certification processes for the acceptance of CLT systems in the construction industry remains not fully harmonised. Currently, significant differences in standards across the world exist: EN-16351 (Europe), ANSI/APA PRG-320 (North America), JAS-3079 (Japan). These differences make cross-certification difficult.	Yes, the development of a global harmonised standard would ensure global use and product certainties.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Regulatory measures	There are different policies, strategies, and regulations available at national, EU and global level that both stimulate but also hinder the further development and implementation of CLT.	Yes, regulatory gaps remain in construction for biobased materials like CLT, hindered by limited knowledge and skills. A shift in frameworks and implementation is needed.

The social impact of CLT is shaped by regulatory policies, job creation, public health, and community acceptance. However, its integration into the construction industry is challenged by inconsistencies in legal obligations, certification processes, and policy frameworks. Unlike traditional materials like concrete and steel, CLT is subject to sustainability reporting and standards that are not optimised for biobased materials, highlighting the need for a shift in framework, mindset, and implementation. The absence of a unified global standard for CLT complicates cross-border trade and certification, limiting its potential for international market expansion. Establishing a harmonised standard could streamline production, facilitate adoption, and enhance the global competitiveness of CLT. While national and EU policies, such as the Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan, promote biobased materials, outdated regulations and insufficient local incentives create barriers to wider adoption. Addressing these inconsistencies through standardised reporting, certification, and supportive policies would strengthen CLT’s role in sustainable construction and accelerate its market growth.

3.2.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Policy dimension

Challenges

- A lack of sufficient knowledge and expertise in utilising timber as a construction material persists at both the EU and national levels, hindering its widespread adoption and the development of effective policies and practices to fully realise its potential in the building industry.
- Existing building norms and standards, both at the EU and national levels, are often unfavourable to timber construction, creating barriers that limit its adoption by prioritising traditional materials and failing to fully accommodate the unique properties and benefits of timber as a sustainable building material.
- The restrictions imposed by current fire safety regulations on timber-based constructions present significant challenges, as they often rely on outdated assumptions and fail to reflect advancements in timber technology, such as fire-resistant treatments and engineered wood products, limiting the broader adoption of sustainable timber solutions.

Recommendations and examples of good practice

- Revamping building norms and regulations to promote the use of biobased materials is essential for fostering a sustainable construction industry. By updating standards to recognise the performance, safety, and environmental benefits of materials like timber and other biobased solutions, policymakers can encourage innovation, reduce reliance on carbon-intensive materials, and support the transition to a circular and low-carbon economy.
- Providing clearer, more comprehensive, and directly actionable governmental guidelines for assessing embodied carbon emissions in construction materials is crucial for ensuring transparency and consistency across the industry.
- Incorporating the assessment of biogenic carbon in biobased materials is crucial for accurately capturing their climate impact. Recognising the carbon sequestration potential of materials like timber and hemp, alongside their embodied carbon emissions, provides a more complete picture of their role in reducing GHG emissions in construction.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- Common misconceptions about building with wood and biobased materials often centre around concerns over durability, fire safety, and environmental impact, particularly regarding the sustainability of wood harvesting practices. These misconceptions can hinder the adoption of sustainable materials despite advancements in technology and responsible sourcing that address these issues.
- A lack of awareness regarding the quality and biodiversity of European forestry often leads to misconceptions about the sustainability of wood sourcing. Many are unaware of the high standards of forest management in Europe, which prioritise biodiversity conservation, sustainable harvesting practices, and ecosystem restoration. This limited understanding

can undermine the potential of European timber as a renewable, environmentally friendly construction material.

- Current LCA standards overlook key aspects of biobased materials, such as carbon sequestration, biodegradability, and sustainable sourcing impacts. Additionally, land use indicators are often negative for wood, despite sustainable forestry practices mitigating these concerns, leading to incomplete assessments of their environmental benefits.
- Ensuring the use of non-toxic adhesives in glued layers is crucial for addressing safety concerns throughout the entire lifecycle of biobased materials, including production, usage, and end-of-life disposal.

Recommendations and examples of good practice

- Implementing dynamic LCAs and adjusting the land use indicator would provide a more accurate reflection of the environmental impact of biobased products. This approach would account for changes in land management practices over time, offering a clearer picture of the sustainability benefits of materials like wood and enhancing their role in sustainable construction.
- Promoting a shift towards a biobased mindset is essential to encourage the adoption of sustainable material choices and practices. By prioritising renewable, biodegradable, and low-carbon alternatives, this shift can drive innovation, reduce environmental impacts, and foster a more sustainable and circular economy in the construction industry.
- Encouraging further research on biobased adhesives is crucial for improving both sustainability and performance in construction and manufacturing. Advancements in this area can lead to safer, non-toxic alternatives that reduce environmental impact, enhance material durability, and support the transition towards more sustainable building practices.
- Incentivising producers to create EPDs through tax benefits or support would promote transparency and sustainability, enabling more informed material choices in the market.

Market dimension

Challenges

- The lack of uniform European standards, with each country having its own interpretation or specific features, results in increased time and costs, complicating cross-border projects and hindering efficiency in the construction sector.
- Insurance for timber projects often faces challenges related to fire resistance concerns. To address these, insurers may require additional fire safety measures or higher premiums for timber constructions. However, advancements in fire-resistant treatments and engineered timber products can help mitigate these risks, making insurance for timber projects more accessible and affordable while supporting sustainable building practices.
- Wood construction, particularly with off-site manufacturing, is significantly faster than traditional methods. However, payment terms for public projects are often based on slower concrete construction timelines, creating challenges for timber projects that require quicker payments to align with their accelerated schedules. Adjusting payment structures to accommodate the faster timelines of wood construction would help streamline project financing and support the growth of timber-based building methods.
- The lack of uniformity in EPDs across European countries creates inconsistencies in assessing environmental impacts, making it difficult to compare materials and products.

Standardising EPDs would enhance transparency, improve decision-making, and promote sustainability across the construction sector.

Recommendations and examples of good practice

- Introducing carbon credits for biobased materials would incentivise their use by recognising their role in carbon sequestration and reducing emissions. This system could encourage the adoption of sustainable materials.
- Establishing uniform European norms would standardise regulations and practices across member states, ensuring consistency in construction, sustainability, and material use. This approach would streamline processes, promote fair competition, and facilitate the adoption of sustainable building practices throughout Europe.
- Shifting the focus from fire resistance to fire reaction is crucial for promoting safer building practices, particularly for biobased materials. Fire reaction measures, such as material combustibility and smoke production, better reflect the performance of materials during a fire, thereby enhancing safety.
- Implementing restrictions on the export of unprocessed timber from the EU would encourage local processing, adding value within the region. This policy could stimulate the European timber industry, support job creation, and reduce the environmental impact associated with transporting raw materials, while promoting sustainable, value-added products.
- Establishing Europe-wide recognised EPDs with CE marking for standardised sustainability assessment would ensure consistency and transparency across the construction industry. This initiative would allow for uniform environmental impact reporting, enabling more informed decision-making and fostering trust in sustainable building materials. While indeed, the existing European norms should standardise practices across member states, at a national level different still exist resulting in incompatible EPDs. For example, EN 15804+A2-3.0 is used in Belgium and EN 15804+A2-3.1 in France, and as a result a Belgian EPD is not valid in France.

3.2.6 Key learnings CLT case study

In sum, CLT represents an innovative solution for sustainable construction, aligning with the EU's Green Deal and its vision for a bio-circular economy. By leveraging renewable resources and reducing reliance on carbon-intensive materials such as steel and concrete, CLT enables the construction sector to lower its environmental footprint while advancing climate goals. However, realising its full potential requires overcoming key challenges in policy, public perception, and industry adoption.

A cultural and industrial shift is needed among the public, legislators, and construction professionals to embrace biobased materials like CLT. Clear policies defining standards, norms, and classifications are essential to eliminate ambiguities and ensure consistent implementation across EU member states. Currently, CLT and other biobased materials face obstacles such as limited advocacy compared to traditional materials and restrictive policies on wood production, even when managed sustainably. Public misconceptions, such as concerns over timber construction's sustainability, durability, and fire safety, also hinder wider adoption.

Opportunities exist in promoting secondary wood use through recycling, reuse, and reintegration of waste wood into production without downcycling. This approach would reduce dependence on virgin timber, improve material efficiency, and support sustainable forest management. However, clear pathways, regulatory frameworks, incentives, and standardised guidelines are needed to drive adoption and ensure effective implementation. Optimising the use of all forest product materials can also minimise waste and enhance resource utilisation.

However, gaps in building codes and regulations remain, especially concerning fire safety, material classification, and LCAs. A particular issue lies in the uncertainties within current LCAs regarding the complete biogenic carbon emissions from timber buildings and their true carbon-capturing potential. While wood-based materials are known to store carbon over their lifespan, the precise impacts of end-of-life emissions, degradation, and recycling processes are not fully accounted for, complicating efforts to quantify their environmental benefits. Additionally, the lack of EU-wide standards leads to inconsistencies, with countries relying on national adaptations. Certification processes for CLT are similarly fragmented, relying only on general quality guidelines, which complicates cross-border trade and reduces market confidence. Furthermore, limited awareness and persistent misconceptions among architects, engineers, and construction firms exacerbate these challenges.

To address these issues, policymakers should review and revise timber construction guidelines to align fire safety, material usage, and environmental performance standards. Harmonising definitions and classifications across the EU will help standardise regulations and support the bio-circular economy. Economic incentives, such as carbon taxes, credits, and offsets, can enhance CLT's competitiveness against traditional carbon-intensive materials. Furthermore, efforts should focus on refining LCA methodologies to better capture the full carbon dynamics of timber buildings, ensuring that the environmental benefits of CLT are accurately reflected. By addressing these gaps and fostering a supportive policy and regulatory framework, CLT can become a transformative force in advancing sustainability within the construction industry.

3.3 Construction - Biochar as an additive in concrete

3.3.1 Introduction to the biochar in concrete case study

3.3.1.1 General description

The cement industry is the sector with the second largest share of direct carbon dioxide emissions (27%) and the third largest industrial energy consumer with 7% of global energy consumption. With a rising global population leading to a higher demand for infrastructure development, global cement production is forecast to grow by 12-23% by 2050 (International Energy Agency, 2018). In recent years, biochar has been explored as supplementary cementitious material (SCM) candidate or filler in concrete. Several research institutes and companies have successfully substituted enough cement with biochar to produce concretes with a lower global warming potential (GWP) than achievable with conventionally used carbon mitigation tools in the concrete sector, or even carbon-negative concretes.

Biochar is a porous, carbon-rich material with a carbon content of up to 90%. It is characterised by its refractory stability, which forms the basis for the concept of pyrogenic carbon capture and storage (PyCCS), a technology that is assessed by the IPCC as a necessary solution to combat climate change. Biochar is one of three products obtained from the pyrolysis of biomass. Depending on the feedstock and the process parameters of temperature, heating rate, and residence time, the yield of each product differs. Not only is biochar one of the most cost-effective CO₂-abatement options, it also can improve soil quality and provide nutrition supply for plant growth (Buss et al., 2019). The challenge in scaling up the production of such concrete and adopting biochar as a suitable replacement for cementitious composites is posed by the vast variability of biochar. Biochar interacts and reacts in a cementitious matrix in various ways, some of which are still unexplored, and the chemical and physical properties of the biochar itself are also highly variable.

3.3.1.2 Value chain and the process

Figure 6. Value chain of biochar-concrete composites

Biochar can be produced from a variety of different feedstocks. Both primary dedicated biomass, as well as waste biomass, can be fed into the pyrolyser as feedstock. A co-pyrolysis is the pyrolysis of more than one feedstock, typically biomass and post-consumer plastics. Pyrolysis recycling is a chemical recycling method suitable for mixed plastic waste, where the goal is obtaining the pyrolysis oil and further processing it to produce new plastics or other chemicals. Co-pyrolysis is deployed as it often yields higher quality pyrolysis oils than pyrolysis of plastics. The solid product of these two pyrolysis recycling processes is often referred to in the literature as charcoal or solid residue instead of biochar and usually has a much lower yield compared to the solid product of pyrolysis of biomass alone. For this reason, tertiary residues (in this case mixed plastic waste) are not included in the value chain model above. The other products of the biomass pyrolysis process, namely bio-oil, and syngas, are also not included in the model as they are not directly used to

produce biochar-concrete composites, but they will be included in the further analyses of this case study as they provide climate-neutral energy.

3.3.1.3 Baseline and market

The market for biochar in Europe has been steadily growing with the number of operational production plants reaching 117 in 2023, while it was just below 50 in 2018. The capacity of these production plants reached 75.000 tonnes in 2023 (EBI, 2024).

Figure 7. Yearly biochar production capacity in Europe [in tonnes] (Source: EBI, 2024)

Biochar has several applications, mainly in agriculture and livestock farming. There, biochar is used to improve soil health by increasing water retention or as a carrier for slow-release fertilisers. It is also mixed in animal feed as a food supplement due to its ability to improve nutrient absorption and digestion (Schmidt et al., 2019). These two main uses are regulated in the updated EU rules on fertilising products (Regulation 2019/1009) and the EU catalogue of feed materials (EU Regulation 68/2013). The authorisation of biochar as a feed material and in fertilising products sparked growth in the European biochar market, which in turn, due to biochar’s large surface area and thus high sorption capacity, sparked significant interest in exploring its potential as a solution for sustainable remediation practices, including but not limited to groundwater remediation and wastewater treatment, air pollution prevention and remediation, and heavy metal and pesticide remediation in contaminated soils. While further surface activation or chemical/ physical modifications are sometimes required and while not all biochar types are suitable for all of applications, this diversity and versatility that biochar provides has been triggering research and entrepreneurial activities in the market.

Furthermore, biochar's ability to sequester carbon had significant effects on the carbon removal market, with biochar carbon removal representing over 90% of all delivered carbon credits in 2023 (CDR.fyi, 2024).

The use of biochar in materials, such as in the case of biochar-concrete composites, currently represents a negligible fraction of its diverse applications. The market for biochar-concrete composites is very small, with only a few products reaching market readiness in the past few years. Examples for companies in this market are the Swiss company Klark, which produces three different types of the composite, and the Berlin-based company EcoLocked. The Norwegian architectural firm Snøhetta is also working with different partners from the industry and academia on developing a biochar-concrete composite under the name Biocrete, which was poured for the first time in a building project in 2023. The products of these companies are however not standardised, since no standard covers the inclusion of biochar in the admixture, which may be negatively impacting the expansion of the market and explaining why it hasn't picked up.

3.3.2 Stakeholders in the biochar in concrete value chain

3.3.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

To begin with, the stakeholders relevant to the biochar in concrete value chain were determined by means of an exploratory desk research (e.g., in scientific papers, on websites of governmental and industrial organisations, and biochar-concrete composites producing companies) and by industry stakeholder engagement. Figure 8 provides a schematic representation of the identified stakeholders, both in the Bioeconomy supply chain (i.e., the light green section) as well as its enabling environment (i.e., the light grey section). It's important to note that in the case of biochar-concrete composites, not the entire supply chain falls under the bioeconomy, but that only biochar does, while the concrete production, including cement, still takes place traditionally in the respective industry.

The stakeholders identified for the supply chain are all the raw-material providers and producers active in the market for biochar-concrete composites, which in itself is very small, but relies on two big markets for the provision of the two main ingredients: biochar and concrete. The supply chain stakeholders are firstly the biomass (waste) providers, such as the wood industry in the case of biochar produced from wood. Other permissible biomasses for the production of biochar include energy crops and harvest residues like straws, leaves and husks which are provided by agricultural farms, paper and wood wastes as well as residues from industrial biomass processing provided by the recycling industry, various food wastes coming from the food industry, biobased fibres that can be pyrolysed to produce biochar, such as cotton, hemp and cellulose provided by the textile industry. All these stakeholders and industries are direct suppliers to the biochar production plants, the so called pyrolysers, and are therefore in close relationships with them. By the end of 2023 there was a total of 171 biochar production plants (EBI, 2024). Biochar production plants are sold by technology providers and equipment manufacturers. Some of the technology providers on the market in Europe are very advanced with TRL8 and 9 and portfolios that include dozens of system installations. Examples for such technology providers and equipment manufacturers are Pyreg, Carbofex, Biomacon, Steisdal and SynCraft. These providers are to separate from the pyrolysers who run the biochar production plants post installations and sell biochar. There are also a few companies with a business model focused on developing, building, owning, and running

Figure 8. Identified stakeholders for biochar-concrete composites

biochar production plants, such as Novocarbo and CircularCarbon. Another important stakeholder group in the supply chain is the concrete industry with all its suppliers from raw material producers, cement manufacturers, and packagers and distributors. Stakeholders involved beyond the stage of biochar-concrete composites are the same ones involved in the traditional building sector, from building contractors supervising the construction and operation phases of buildings to waste disposal contractors when a building reaches its end-of-life stage.

The enabling environment surrounding this supply chain is divided into the stakeholder groups as defined in the quadruple helix framework and consists of government, academia, industry, and civil society stakeholders. Industry stakeholders include industry associations on a national and multinational level like L'Associazione Italiana Biochar ICHAR in Italy or the European Biochar Industry Consortium EBI and the International Biochar Initiative. These organisations are inter alia involved in policy and standardisation activities in order to promote and support the biochar industry. Other industry stakeholders are financial institutes and investors, certifiers like EBI's European Biochar Certificate (EBC) and the analytical labs that they use to assess the quality of the product such as Eurofins Scientific, as well as end-of-life waste managers, agricultural farmers, fertiliser producers, (forestry) biomass managers and suppliers, and the above-mentioned competing buyers of biochar. Another important industry player to mention is the market of carbon certificate dealers, such as Puro.Earth, whose services are used by various corporations, including major ones, to offset their carbon footprints. Academia stakeholders include research institutes that often work closely to the industry and produce academic literature on biochar to further advance the understanding of this heterogeneous material and its uses, as well as their respective environmental impacts. Furthermore, there are incubators that support R&D activities of start-ups and construction vocational education and training (VET) providers. Government actors, on the other hand, include standardisation committees, supranational organisations like the UN and the OECD, as well as various policymakers on the national and multinational level like the EU Commission, and their advisors like the IPCC. Finally, civil society stakeholders consist of citizens and the organisations that represent their interests like non-profit organisations.

3.3.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

In what follows we assess the stakeholders most relevant to biochar-concrete composite producers in a typical power-interest-matrix (Figure 9). Firstly, biomass suppliers, who provide the raw materials for biochar production, considerably impact biochar-concrete composite producers through pricing and biomass product specifications, which influence the characteristics of the biochar and in turn the matrix of the final composite product. Biomass suppliers, on the other hand, don't have as high of an interest in the biochar-concrete composite market as they have power over it. This is due to the market of the composites still being very small, but considering biochar in general is a growing market and represents a good opportunity for biomass suppliers to sell their waste and byproducts, the interest in the value chain is not negligible. Secondly, end users of the composite, such as construction companies, municipalities, real estate developers, homeowners, as well as partners in pilot projects and joint product developments, are high-impact stakeholders, who have reference examples and data and therefore important

for their word-of-mouth awareness for the product. They also have a high interest in the product, when trying to lower their climate impact. Thirdly, there's the pyrolysis technology providers who play a crucial role in the biochar production process. The stability and reliability of their technology, along with required maintenance and uptime of the system, directly impact biochar availability and crucial emission data. This data is increasingly important for LCA calculations and better understanding the product's environmental impacts and relative benefits in comparison to traditional concrete products. While technology providers hold significant power over the production process, their interest might be more focused on the broader biochar market rather than specifically biochar-concrete composites, unless they specialise in equipment for this application. Fourthly, the end-users of green energy generated during biochar production, such as municipalities and industrial customers, represent another set of stakeholders. While their interest in the biochar-concrete composites themselves might be low, their reliance on the energy output influences the economic viability of biochar production, and thus indirectly affects the availability and cost of biochar for composite production. The potential for direct syngas valorisation could reduce the reliance on these energy customers, but this technology is still under development. Fifthly, the carbon credit market is a stakeholder with growing importance. The lack of established reference projects for generating carbon credits from biochar in concrete applications presents both a challenge and an opportunity. Developing standardised methodologies for quantifying and verifying these credits would significantly boost the adoption of biochar-concrete composites. Currently, their power is limited by the lack of established frameworks, but their interest is high, driven by the potential for new revenue streams and environmental benefits. Sixthly, post-processing partners, who handle milling, sieving, agglomeration, and packaging, are essential for managing large customer orders. A broad network of partners allows producers to optimise logistics and minimise transportation costs and emissions. However, obtaining emission data from these partners can be challenging due to its sensitive nature. Their power lies in their control over these crucial processing steps, while their interest is tied to the overall success of the biochar market, including its application in composites. Finally, certification bodies and policymakers play a vital role in shaping the regulatory landscape. Certification bodies establish standards for biochar quality and performance, influencing market access and consumer trust. Policymakers can incentivise the use of biochar-concrete composites through regulations, subsidies, or public procurement policies. Both groups wield significant power over the market's development, and their interest is high, driven by environmental concerns and the potential for economic growth in sustainable industries.

Figure 9. Stakeholders of biochar-concrete composites mapped in a power-interest matrix

3.3.3 Policies of relevance to the biochar in concrete value chain

In this section, policies that could either propel or impede the implementation of biochar in concrete are identified. These policies were detected through desk research and communication with stakeholders. In Table 6, an overview is provided of the relevant policies, including the type of policy it concerns, further general information, as well as its relevance to the biochar-concrete case study.

The European Union has implemented a wide range of policies aimed at achieving its ambitious climate and sustainability goals. These policies, which focus on decarbonisation, energy efficiency, and resource optimisation, create a favourable environment for the use of sustainable materials such as biochar in concrete.

First, there's the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) which sets binding targets for energy savings and encourages the use of technologies that enhance energy performance. While the primary focus of the EPBD is on operational energy, the embodied carbon of building materials

is increasingly recognised as a significant factor in the overall environmental impact of buildings. Biochar concrete composites, by potentially reducing the embodied carbon of the building material, can indirectly contribute to the EPBD's objectives by reducing the overall environmental impact of buildings. Furthermore, research shows that adding biochar in concrete can improve the thermal insulation performance of the composite, thereby improving the energy efficiency of buildings.

Second, the Construction Product Regulation (CPR) ensures that construction products meet safety and performance standards. The CPR was recently revised, and the new version adopted on January 7th, 2025. The new CPR foresees a Digital Product Passport (DPP) system for construction products, enhancing transparency regarding their environmental impact. Such increased transparency could be beneficial for products with lower carbon footprints and overall improved environmental performance, such as biochar concrete composites, by allowing for a clear communication of their environmental benefits to all stakeholders along the value chain. Furthermore, the new CPR aims at supporting standardisation efforts in the sector, by no longer requiring alignment with mandates and thus shortening standardisation mechanisms. This is specifically of importance for the biochar in concrete case study, as stakeholders have complained that the lack of standardisation for the product and the difficulty to have it standardised are a huge market barrier.

Third, the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation, which has also recently entered into force in December 2024, has the potential to significantly impact the market for biochar concrete composites. This regulation aims to establish a framework for the certification and trading of carbon removals, which could incentivise the use of carbon-sequestering materials like biochar. By creating a market for carbon removals, the CRCF Regulation could provide a financial incentive for the use of biochar in concrete, making it more economically competitive with traditional concrete. The inclusion of the CRCF into other EU policies, specifically into the EU ETS, will have a positive impact on the biochar market and is encouraged by the stakeholders. However, the CRCF should first solidify the methodologies for measuring the GHG impact of biochar and have them include important emission sources such as the production of the biomass and its transportation to the pyrolysis plant, which are currently not included. The regulation should also strictly define which kinds of biomass feedstocks and where they are sourced from should be allowed for biochar production.

Table 6. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the biochar in concrete case study

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
Construction Product Regulation (CPR)	Harmonise performance assessment and unify the rules for marketing aspect of construction products to improve the single market.	Stimulating and barrier instrument	The CPR sets out methods and criteria for assessing and expressing the performance, as well as the conditions for marketing of construction products.	EU	Current, revised in 2025	Direct regulation	EU Construction Products Regulation (EC, n.d.a)
Carbon Removals and Carbon Framing (CRCF) Regulation	Approaches and implementations of carbon sequestration by capturing, storing, and reducing emission sources.	Stimulating instrument	The CRCF Regulation will provide financial support in innovations around carbon removal technologies and sustainable carbon farming solutions.	EU	Current	Direct regulation	EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (EU, 2024)
Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation	LULUCF focuses on emissions and removals from land use, as well as help to navigate land sector practices into greater potential for carbon abatement.	Stimulating instrument	LULUCF aims to improve the quality of GHG emissions and removals in LULUCF sector using data-driven monitoring.	EU	Current	Direct regulation	EU Land Use Sector (EC, n.d.b)
Bioeconomy Strategy	Accelerate the deployment of sustainable European bioeconomy by ensuring food and nutrition security, managing natural resources sustainably, reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, limiting, adapting to climate change, strengthening European competitiveness, and creating jobs.	Stimulating and barrier instrument	Support the acceleration of the circular bioeconomy in the areas of policy, finance, and awareness.	EU	Current	Direct and market-based approach	EU Bioeconomy Strategy (EC, n.d.c)

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

Green Claims Directive	Boost the potential of green market through consumer protection and empowerment to actively contribute to the green transition.	Stimulating instrument	Ensures environmental labels and claims are credible and trustworthy which allow consumers to make better-informed purchasing decisions. Moreover, it creates competitiveness of business striving to increase sustainability of their products and activities.	EU	Proposed	Market-based approach	EU Green Claims Directive (EC, 2023)
Energy Performance of Buildings Directive	Improve the energy performance of buildings within the EU by creating a stable environment for investment decisions and enabling consumers and business to make more informed decisions to save energy and cost.	Stimulating instrument	This regulation fosters consumers and business to focus on building and renovating more energy efficient buildings to achieve the fullest energy use.	EU	Current	Direct regulation	EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EC, n.d.d)
Industrial Carbon Management Strategy	The Industrial Carbon Management Strategy presents a comprehensive approach for the EU to scale up carbon management. It includes a set of actions at EU and national level to establish a single market for CO2 and promote a more attractive environment in industrial carbon management technologies.	Stimulating instrument	By encouraging and facilitating the industrial sector to decarbonise, this strategy enables stakeholders to streamline their businesses' climate goal by providing approaches and alternatives in carbon abatement technologies.	EU	Current	EU Strategy	EU Industrial carbon management strategy (EC, n.d.e)

3.3.4 Analysis of indicators of the biochar in concrete case study

Both the literature review, as well as the stakeholder engagement activity provided insights on the indicators used by biochar and biochar-concrete-composite producers and researchers to assess these products.

3.3.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators

In total 31 environmental indicators were identified as highly relevant for the biochar in concrete case study in T3.2. One indicator, namely ecotoxicity for aquatic freshwater, was removed. There is a potential risk to aquatic systems from biochar-amended soils and research investigating this, such as in Bastos et al. (2014). However, this indicator is not relevant for biochar in material applications such as the case for biochar-concrete composites. No other indicators were removed, or new ones identified.

Table 7. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the biochar in concrete case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Biodiversity damage potential (BDP; $m^2 \cdot year \cdot PAS$ (potentially affected species)	This indicator is relevant for making sure biomass used to produce biochar is not negatively affecting biodiversity.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of crop supply, by mass, obtained from land that is/was primary forest or other wooded land	The primary biomass feedstock used for biochar production is wood, tracking the biomass source and its sustainability is important for assessing the climate impact of the final product.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of biofuels and bioliquids made from raw material obtained from land that is/was continuously forested	The products of a pyrolysis are biochar, bio-oil, and syngas. Biochar producers often use the surplus heat generated during the pyrolysis process either to fuel their own production, specifically for the most energy-intensive step of drying the biomass before it's pyrolysed, and others feed it into the grid for nearby households to use.	Yes. There is considerable literature discussing the yields of the different pyrolysis products and the use of biochar for biofuel production, however there's still many research

					gaps to fill regarding this indicator.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Wood consumption	This indicator is important to monitor to make sure that biochar production is not competing with other wood-based products and is relying mainly on waste wood that usually isn't used, therefore enabling a cascading use of wood.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Amount of sold crop exceeding harvesting volume	The market for biochar is currently too small for this indicator to be too relevant, but it would be important to monitor the bigger the market grows.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Water purification potential through physicochemical filtration (WPPPCF; Physicochemical capacity of ecosystems to clean a polluted suspension) (yes/no)	Biochar can be used for groundwater remediation and wastewater treatment. Biochar not used for composite applications like in this case study should be managed properly to exploit its potential.	Yes. There is some literature on biochar's water purification potential, but there's still a big research gap to fill.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Resource depletion (mineral, fossil) / product unit (MJ)	Biochar-concrete composites rely on the extraction of vast quantities of natural resources for the concrete matrix.	No. There's a lot of literature on concrete's impact on resource depletion.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Intensity of fossil fuel use (m ³ /ton of product)	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of biological content/ product	This indicator can be calculated for the composite.	No.

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of carbon content derived from renewable raw materials	Up to 90% depending on feedstock and production process (Weber and Quicker, 2018)	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Renewable energies (RES) share in final energy consumption / product unit	-	Yes. Further research on this topic is required.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	Share of forests certified for sustainable management	Since wood is a major biomass used for biochar production, it's important to monitor this indicator. Several biochar producers indicate whether their biomass is sourced from PEFC or FSC certified forests.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	% of deforestation or afforestation /product unit	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Hazardous substances management	% of hazardous (carcinogenic, mutagenic, reprotoxic) substances	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Hazardous substances management	% of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH)	This is a very important indicator to monitor because biochar contains varying amounts of PAHs and depending on the level it can only be used for certain applications. The European Biochar Certificate has thresholds for amounts of PAHs for the different biochar classes.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Waste generated	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Procedures for separating and using recyclable materials from the waste stream (yes/no)	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Declaration of end-of-life disposal (in the CSR report) (yes/no)	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of product is actively being recovered and recycled	Market is still too young to monitor this indicator.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of materials derived from recycling or recovery of any other biomass waste	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of materials derived from any other biomass by-products	Biochar can be produced from several biomass by-products, thus contributing to the cascading use of biomass.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of the total amount of wood used is waste wood according to waste wood categories	Important to monitor.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Recycling rate/cascading indexes	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Amount of wastewater from processing operations is discharged into aquatic systems (m ³)	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of wastewater containing potential organic and mineral contaminants are treated or recycled to prevent negative impacts	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Practices for waste storage, treatment and disposal that do not pose health or safety risks to farmers, workers, other people, or natural ecosystems (yes/no)	Biochar can self-ignite. Adequate storage practices are required to avoid health and safety risks.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Bioenergy replacing non-	% of biofuels produced with co-products, residues, and waste	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.

		renewable energy			
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Biomass Utilisation Factor (BUF)	-	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle GHG emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	GHG emission varies depending on production and EoL option. Wood based biochar contributed 263.5 and -481.3 kg CO ₂ -eq/FU (Barbhuiya et al., 2024)	Yes. Further studies needed for the different kinds of biochar and mass fractions of biochar in concrete.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP100; gr eq. CO ₂)	Depending on the amount of biochar used in the composite, it could significantly lower the GWP of the final product compared to traditional concrete. The carbon stored in the buildings where biochar-concrete composites are used should be calculated and documented for carbon accounting.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.

Biochar is added to concrete for three main reasons: to sequester carbon in a durable material, to partially replace cement and therefore reduce emissions, and to improve concrete’s material properties. These benefits are however not always given when biochar is added to concrete. The biochar needs to be assessed for its stability to make sure it’s sequestering carbon and concrete’s material properties are not always improved by the addition of biochar. The need to assess the environmental indicators of biochar-concrete-composites is therefore not just important to understand its climate impacts but also to make sure the product viable for being placed on the market. The indicators in the list below include all indicators relevant for assessing the environmental impact of biochar-concrete composites, as well as biochar separately. The European Biochar Certificate (EBC) has different classes, one of which is EBC-Material which certifies biochar to be used in industrial materials, including building materials, plastics, and textiles. The indicators used for EBC-Material are based on the current knowledge and data available on biochar for industrial applications. For some of the indicators, the limit values are based on the ones for feed or other application biochar, as there are no reliable risk assessments for biochar-material composites.

3.3.4.2 Economic indicators

Only one indicator was identified as highly relevant in T3.2. After further review and the stakeholder engagement, one further indicator was identified as relevant and is included in the table below in red.

Table 8. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the biochar in concrete case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Strategy for creating the infrastructure and systems necessary for recovering and recycling materials (yes/no)	Considering that biochar-concrete composites are still at their infancy and not widely used, partly due to lacking standardisation, strategies for creating necessary infrastructure are required to create legitimacy for the product and support its up-scaling.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Biomass self-sufficiency rate	Biomass from waste	Biochar can be produced from waste biomass. Encouraging the use of waste biomass instead of primary biomass to produce biochar, will boost the economic sustainability of the biomass market. A lot of European biochar producers already state using only forestry byproducts and waste biomass.	More research on the quality of biochar from waste biomass is required.

The biochar industry is gaining recognition not only for its environmental sustainability but also for its economic efficiency. Due to its diverse applications in different sectors, biochar has the potential to contribute to different sectors. The rapid increase in production volume over the past decade, has had a big impact on biochar’s market price. However, biochar prices still vary greatly depending on the quality and vary between a couple of hundreds to a couple of thousand Euros per tonne. Biochar for applications like concrete composites needs to meet certain chemical and physical criteria and is usually more expensive than the market average, which in turn reflects on the final price of the product. Biochar for material applications is therefore dependent on the greater biochar industry and how it evolves. A key aspect for the economic viability of biochar production plants and the economic sustainability of biochar, independent of what it will be used for, is finding the best possible valorisation of the surplus energy that is produced during pyrolysis. Another key aspect is the efficient cascading use of local biomass. To lower both the monetary as well as the environmental price of biochar production, local supply chains of biomass need to be planned efficiently, to allow for the maximum possible cascading use of the biomass and its byproducts, as well as shorten transportation distances and lower costs as much as possible. The success of biochar is ergo highly dependent on the infrastructures that exist to support it.

3.3.4.3 Social indicators

Five social indicators were identified as highly relevant for the biochar in concrete case study in T3.2. None of these indicators was removed after further review. No new ones were added either.

Table 9. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the biochar in concrete case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Presence of a formal policy in place concerning health and safety of all workers, including contractors (yes/no)	-	Yes, limited relevant reports available.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Presence of a law or norm regarding transparency (yes/no)	Biochar is a controversial material and has many critics. Transparency is key to be able to assess the true environmental and social benefits of the material in its various uses, like concrete.	The new Construction Product Regulation (CPR) aims at increasing transparency, specifically through the inclusion of environmental indicators in Declarations of Performance (DoPs) and through Digital Product Passports (DPPs). The CPR was already enforced, but it will take time for it to become mandatory; the timeline is until 2030. The DPP system is still being developed and standardised.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Risk of forced labour used for production of commodity (yes/no)	Only relevant if raw materials for the final product are imported from high-risk countries.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Presence of working children under the legal age (yes/no)	Only relevant if raw materials for the final product are imported from high-risk countries.	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Number of innovative social project that positively impacts the local community	Stakeholders state the need of construction projects that use biochar-concrete composites to set an example and raise	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.

				awareness in the surrounding communities.	
--	--	--	--	---	--

Whether a concrete product represents a risk in terms of social sustainability is highly dependent on its composition. Concrete in Europe is typically produced locally, from locally available raw materials. The same generally applies to biochar. Only certain binders, which are added to some types of concrete, may be imported if not locally available.

The social sustainability indicators relevant to a specific concrete product can vary significantly depending on the origin of its raw materials and the location of its production site. To assess the level of scrutiny required for each indicator, it is helpful to refer to resources like the amfori BSCI risk countries list, which can help identify regions with higher social risks. The indicators listed below are among the most critical to monitor. The higher the risk associated with the product's country of origin, the more indicators will need to be assessed. Of the indicators listed, the first one is particularly important to monitor at all times, as biochar can self-ignite in extremely dry and hot conditions or when exposed to direct sunlight for extended periods of time.

3.3.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Policy dimension

Challenges

- The stakeholders indicate the lack of standards that support the diffusion of innovative concrete products as a major barrier, as it hinders the good performing biobased concrete products from entering the wider market.
- Additionally, they mention the long and complex certification processes for biochar in concrete products as a challenge.

Recommendations and examples of good practice

- A renewal for the current recipe-based standards to performance-based is suggested from the stakeholders.
- Construction Products Regulation, EU Emission Tradition System, The Carbon Removal Certification Framework, EU Green Deal, EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities and Sustainable Carbon Cycles are considered as good practices by the stakeholders.

Sustainability dimension

Recommendations and examples of good practice

- Stakeholders refer to carbon accounting such as the Carbon Removal Certification Framework as a good practice.

Market dimension

Challenges

- There persists a difficulty to find biomass suppliers who supply feedstock for biochar production in a consistent quality and manner, with predictable and manageable costs.

Recommendations and examples of good practice

- Stakeholders propose more incentives for customers to conduct pilot projects. Such mechanisms would be helpful to boost the market, which is currently suffering due to the high price of biochar and low willingness to pay a premium on the customer side.

3.3.6 Key learnings of Biochar in concrete case study

Biochar-concrete composites offer a promising avenue for reducing emissions in the construction sector and turning buildings into carbon sinks, but their widespread adoption faces several challenges. This report has explored the key stakeholders influencing this emerging market, the indicators that need to be monitored to assess its climate impact, as well as the complexities of upscaling this innovative product within the current landscape, providing a good overview of the data and knowledge that need to be generated to understand this product better and adequately support its upscaling.

From our research, we gathered that price sensitivity among customers, coupled with the need for extensive long-term data to demonstrate product performance, create a challenging market environment. The lack of standardisation for the product, as well as the lengthy and complex certification processes for biochar in concrete, along with the scarcity of projects generating carbon credits, further impede progress. These factors underscore the need for streamlined regulatory frameworks and incentives to encourage adoption. A key challenge within the value chain itself is ensuring consistent biochar quality, given the natural variability of biomass feedstock. Plant reliability, particularly regarding the technology readiness level (TRL) of industrial pyrolysis, also requires attention. Furthermore, securing consistent biomass supply and managing energy offtake for biochar production facilities pose logistical and operational difficulties.

Beyond these internal challenges, interviewed stakeholder highlighted the difficulties in navigating the broader market. Identifying promising market segments for different biochar types and ensuring accurate emissions accounting throughout the post-processing chain are crucial for effective life-cycle assessments. The lack of customer willingness to pay a premium for biochar-concrete, combined with the complexity of current certification processes, creates a significant barrier to market entry.

To overcome these obstacles, the policy interventions were identified. Creating standardised certifications and labels for green materials, similar to the new German label for green cement, would enhance product recognition and facilitate their use in public tenders. Establishing lead markets for low-carbon products through public procurement policies and EU-wide labelling obligations would stimulate demand. Stakeholder interviewed highlighted that policy support is crucial, as market-driven mechanisms alone may not be sufficient to overcome the price gap between conventional and biochar-concrete. While existing mechanisms like the European Trading System and EUAs offer some support, supplementary policies are deemed indispensable for the successful market penetration of biochar-concrete composites. These policies should focus on creating a level playing field, incentivising innovation, and building consumer trust in these sustainable materials.

3.4 Construction - Hemp insulation

3.4.1 Introduction to the hemp insulation case study

3.4.1.1 General description

Hemp insulation, crafted from hemp wool, offers a sustainable and efficient solution for insulating buildings. Derived from the robust and fibrous hemp plant, hemp wool has a rich history of utilisation in durable applications such as clothing, ropes, and sails. Its enduring nature and excellent insulative properties make it an ideal choice for modern insulation needs.

With exceptional durability and breathability, hemp insulation ensures resilience against wear and tear while providing effective thermal regulation. It boasts high thermal mass and low conductivity, thus significantly enhancing a building's energy efficiency. Moreover, its hygroscopic nature allows it to absorb and release moisture, acting as a natural moisture-buffering material. This unique characteristic contributes to maintaining a more stable indoor humidity level, reducing the energy required for heating and cooling. Consequently, not only does hemp insulation enhance thermal comfort, but it also improves indoor air quality. Hemp wool can be manufactured into various forms, including insulation batts, boards, or loose fibres catering to different construction requirements. Additionally, additives such as cornmeal or polyester may be incorporated during the manufacturing process to further reinforce the insulation's strength and longevity.

Figure 10. Hemp insulation (Source: Hempitecture)

3.4.1.2 Value chain and the process

The value chain of hemp insulation begins with the cultivation of hemp plants and the sourcing of feedstock. On an industrial scale, hemp is harvested for three primary products: fibres, seeds (for food and medical use), and hurds (Ingrao et al., 2015). The variety of hemp and its harvesting time depend on its intended application. For biobased construction materials like insulation, hemp is harvested when the plant stems reach full maturity. Processing the hemp stalks starts with retting, a process that breaks down the pectin binding the bast fibres (outer layer) to the woody core (hurd). Retting can be done in the field or using water, chemicals, enzymes, microorganisms, or ultrasonic waves. Once retting is complete, the stalks are dried to prevent mold and fibre degradation. The dried stalks then undergo decortication, where rollers or hammer mills crush and separate the bast fibres from the hurds. The fibres are further refined and sorted based on length and quality. The bast fibres are used to produce hemp wool insulation. First, they undergo a carding process, where they are combed and aligned to create a uniform fibre web. Depending on the manufacturer, a binder such as polyester fibres may be added to enhance cohesion in the mats as well as additives to improve fire resistance. During mat formation, fibres are layered to the desired thickness and density. If no binders are used, needle-punching can interlock the fibres without adhesives (Rabbat et al., 2021). The mats or batts are then cut to standard dimensions and packaged for distribution.

Hemp wool insulation is a versatile and sustainable material suitable for various construction applications. It is widely used for insulating walls, roofs, and floors, offering excellent thermal performance that helps regulate indoor temperatures and improve energy efficiency. Additionally, hemp insulation provides effective sound absorption, making it an ideal choice for acoustic insulation in residential and commercial buildings. Due to its breathable and moisture-regulating properties, hemp insulation helps prevent condensation and mold growth, contributing to healthier indoor air quality. It is particularly beneficial in passive house construction, as it is non-toxic, recyclable, and has a low environmental footprint compared to conventional insulation

materials (Crini et al., 2020). Hemp insulation can be used in both new builds and retrofits, offering flexibility in various architectural designs. It is compatible with timber-frame structures, masonry walls, and prefabricated building systems. Furthermore, its fire resistance, durability, and ability to sequester carbon make it an attractive option for sustainable construction practices (Muhit et al., 2024).

Figure 11. Value chain of the hemp insulation case study

A crucial factor in the sustainability of biobased building materials, such as hemp insulation, is their potential for recovery and reuse at the end of their lifecycle. Unlike conventional insulation materials that often contribute to landfill waste, hemp insulation offers opportunities for circularity through well-designed end-of-life recovery strategies. By implementing efficient collection, sorting, and processing systems, these materials can be reintegrated into new production cycles, reducing the demand for virgin resources, and minimising environmental impact. Various recovery pathways can be utilised, including direct reuse in construction, mechanical recycling to produce new insulation or composite materials, and waste-to-energy processes that harness residual energy while minimising disposal waste (see Figure 12, Rabbat et al., 2021). Additionally, hemp insulation’s biodegradable nature allows for composting in certain applications, further enhancing its sustainability. Establishing these recovery routes not only extends the material’s lifecycle but also aligns with circular economic principles, contributing to a more resource-efficient and environmentally responsible built environment.

Figure 12. Biobased building materials valorisation scenarios at end-of-life (Source: Rabbat et al., 2021)

3.4.1.3 Baseline and market

The cultivation and use of hemp-based products date back as early as 8000 B.C. (Crini et al., 2020). Historically, hemp was primarily grown for its applications in the marine, paper, and textile industries. However, as the demand for sails declined and synthetic fibres gained prominence, alternative markets were explored, leading to their increasing use in the construction sector.

Both bast fibres and shives, the woody core of the stalk, can be utilised in the production of hemp-based building materials. Bast fibres are commonly processed into fibre boards, insulation rolls, and panels, while shives can be combined with lime to create hempcrete, a durable, lightweight bio-composite with excellent insulating and structural properties.

Figure 13. Hemp products (Source: Ingrao et al., 2015)

Hemp wool insulation has emerged as a sustainable alternative to traditional insulation materials such as fibreglass, mineral wool, rigid foam boards, and reflective foils. Conventional insulation materials serve different functions depending on their composition. Bulk insulation materials such as fibreglass and mineral wool resist heat flow, while rigid boards, including polystyrene, polyisocyanurate, and polyurethane foams, trap air or gas within their structure to provide high

thermal resistance. Reflective foils, commonly used in warmer climates, deflect radiant heat away from living spaces to improve energy efficiency.

Other less common insulation materials include cementitious and phenolic foams, vermiculite, and perlite, each offering specialised properties for niche applications. The following is a list of widely used insulation materials in modern construction: Fibreglass, Mineral wool, Cellulose, Natural fibres, Polystyrene, expanded or extruded, Polyisocyanurate, Polyurethane, Perlite, Cementitious foam, Phenolic foam (Pavel & Blagoeva, 2018).

By providing a renewable, biodegradable, and non-toxic alternative, hemp wool insulation supports sustainable construction practices, reducing the environmental footprint of buildings while maintaining high performance in thermal and acoustic insulation.

Figure 14. Thermal insulation overview (Source: Pavel & Blagoeva, 2018)

Biobased materials currently account for 3% of the total mass of building materials used in Europe and 10% of their volume, with wood representing approximately two-thirds of the mass and half of the volume. In the insulation sector, biobased products make up around 1% of the total market volume in Europe (Cardellini & Mijndonckx, 2022), indicating significant potential for growth in sustainable construction materials.

Among European countries, France is the leading producer of hemp, dedicating approximately 20,000 hectares to its cultivation. Germany follows with 5,352 hectares, and Estonia with 5,161 hectares (Statica, 2023). On average, one hectare of hemp yields about one ton of seeds and around seven tons of stalks, which contribute to 79% of the crop’s economic value. After undergoing mechanical processing through decortication, 25% of the stalks are transformed into long bast fibres, while 43% become shives. Additionally, the production of hemp-based building

materials enables the recycling of 29% of the fibres and 14% of the shives, further enhancing the material's sustainability and circular economy potential (Rabbat et al., 2021).

In France, approximately 20% of hemp fibres and 30% of hemp hurds are utilised in the construction sector, reflecting the increasing demand for biobased building materials (Scrucca et al., 2020). The production volume of hemp insulation materials in the country reached 2,500 tons of wool panels and 3,000 tons of loose fibre insulation in 2017 (Bou Cherifi et al., 2017). As awareness of sustainable building practices grows, hemp insulation is gaining recognition for its environmental benefits, including carbon sequestration, biodegradability, and energy-efficient performance. The expansion of biobased insulation solutions in Europe presents a promising opportunity to reduce reliance on conventional materials and promote more sustainable construction practices.

Examples of Hemp insulation manufacturers:

- BIOFIB

Biofib is a leading company dedicated to sustainable solutions in the construction industry. Specialising in hemp-based insulation materials, Biofib offers innovative products that prioritise energy efficiency, environmental responsibility, and indoor air quality. With a focus on natural fibres, Biofib's insulation materials provide excellent thermal performance while contributing to healthier living spaces. By promoting the use of renewable resources like hemp, Biofib is at the forefront of advancing sustainable building practices worldwide.

- ISOHEMP

IsoHemp is a renowned company specialising in the production of sustainable and energy-efficient building materials made from hemp. Based in Belgium, IsoHemp manufactures high-performance hempcrete blocks, which are used for insulation and construction. These blocks are known for their excellent thermal and acoustic properties, breathability, and natural regulation of humidity. IsoHemp's products contribute to creating healthier and more comfortable living environments while reducing the ecological footprint of buildings. Committed to innovation and sustainability, IsoHemp is a key player in promoting sustainable construction practices globally.

- HEMPFLAX

HempFlax is a leading company in the hemp industry, dedicated to the sustainable cultivation, processing, and commercialisation of industrial hemp products. Founded in 1994, HempFlax specialises in a wide range of hemp-based materials, including fibres, shives, and CBD. Their products are utilised in various sectors such as textiles, construction, automotive, animal care, and health and wellness. With a strong commitment to environmental stewardship and innovation, HempFlax aims to unlock the full potential of hemp, promoting its benefits for a more sustainable future.

- HEMPITECTURE

Hempitecture is a pioneering company specialising in sustainable building materials made from industrial hemp. They produce products such as Hempcrete and hemp-based insulation, which offer superior thermal performance, energy efficiency, and improved indoor air quality.

Committed to revolutionising the construction industry, Hempitecture promotes environmentally responsible building practices through innovation, education, and advocacy.

- LA CHANVRIÈRE

La Chanvrière is a prominent player in the hemp industry, known for its significant contributions to the cultivation and processing of hemp in Europe. Based in France, La Chanvrière specialises in the sustainable production and innovative utilisation of hemp fibres, seeds, and shives. Their extensive experience and commitment to quality have established them as leaders in the field, promoting the versatility and environmental benefits of hemp. With a focus on sustainability and innovation, La Chanvrière processes hemp into a variety of products. They transform hemp stalks into long bast fibres and shives through decortication, optimising the use of each part of the plant. These materials are then utilised in a wide range of applications, including construction materials, textiles, bio-composites, and more. La Chanvrière's dedication to research and development ensures continuous improvement in the efficiency and quality of their processes and products. La Chanvrière also plays a crucial role in the promotion of hemp as a sustainable crop, highlighting its ecological advantages such as low water usage, minimal need for pesticides, and its ability to improve soil health. By advancing the use of hemp in various industries, La Chanvrière supports the growth of a more sustainable economy.

3.4.2 Stakeholders in the hemp insulation value chain

3.4.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

The identification of stakeholders and actors relevant to the hemp insulation value chain were determined through exploratory desk and literature research (e.g., websites of governmental organisations and initiatives, research and advisory organisations supporting the hemp construction materials, and hemp insulation manufacturers). An overview of the schematic representation of the identified stakeholders and actors can be found in Figure 15. The bioeconomy supply chain is represented in the light green section and its Enabling environment in the light grey section.

Bioeconomy supply chain:

- **Hemp Farmers:** These are agricultural producers who cultivate hemp plants specifically for the production of hemp wool. They are responsible for growing and harvesting the hemp crop, ensuring high-quality raw materials for further processing
- **Hemp Processors:** Hemp processors are companies or facilities that specialise in processing raw hemp fibres into hemp wool insulation material. They may perform tasks such as cleaning, refining, and compressing the fibres to create the final product.
- **Manufacturers of Hemp Wool Insulation:** These companies utilise processed hemp fibres to manufacture hemp wool insulation products. They may produce various forms of insulation, including batts, rolls, or loose-fill insulation, which are then distributed to consumers or construction companies.
- **Construction Companies, architects, and engineers:** Architects play a crucial role in specifying building materials for construction projects. They may advocate for the use of hemp wool insulation due to its sustainability, thermal performance, and potential

Figure 15. Identified stakeholders in the hemp insulation value chain

contribution to green building certifications. Construction firms and contractors are stakeholders who use hemp wool insulation in building projects. They may incorporate hemp wool insulation into residential, commercial, or industrial structures to provide thermal and acoustic insulation.

Enabling environment:

- **Government Agencies and Regulators:** Government agencies and regulators oversee the hemp industry and may establish regulations and standards related to hemp cultivation, processing, and product quality. They ensure compliance with safety, environmental, and building code requirements.
- **Supra national organisation, regional partnerships for sustainable construction:** Organisations advocate for sustainable building practices. They may support the use of hemp wool insulation as a renewable and low-impact alternative to conventional insulation materials, promoting awareness and adoption among consumers and industry stakeholders.
- **Research Institutions and education providers:** Research institutions and laboratories conduct studies and experiments to explore the properties and potential applications of hemp wool insulation. They contribute to advancing scientific knowledge, developing new manufacturing techniques, and improving the performance of hemp-based materials.
- **End-users and Non-governmental organisation:** The general public plays a key role in driving market demand for sustainable building materials, such as hemp insulation. As consumers become more conscious of the ecological footprint of their choices, these groups influence the demand for greener alternatives, helping to promote sustainable solutions in the construction sector. Raising awareness about the environmental impact of traditional construction materials and increasing economic advantages of biobased products is important for this group to help drive change in the construction sector.

3.4.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

The different stakeholders identified as relevant to the case study were mapped in a power-interest matrix depending on their ability and interest to drive change regarding the implementation of hemp insulation in the construction sector. Figure 16 shows the different stakeholders mapped by their relative interest and power through the lens of being able to positively or negatively the further implementation of hemp insulation.

Policymakers are among the most influential stakeholders driving the increased adoption of biobased materials, as they align with the European Green Deal's goal of making Europe climate neutral. The transformation of the entire hemp insulation value chain, from cultivation to end-of-life processing, depends on policy strategies that address technical and financial constraints. In addition, education providers, research institutions, supranational organisations, and regional partnerships focused on sustainable construction play a crucial role. By equipping industry professionals with knowledge and providing informed input to policymakers, these entities help shape regulations and decision-making processes at both national and international levels.

The stakeholder group of end-users, or the general public, has significant potential and influence in driving change and promoting the wider adoption of hemp insulation in the construction sector through increased demand for biobased materials. However, high costs associated with building materials and construction, along with misconceptions and prevailing mindsets about biobased alternatives, contribute to lower interest compared to fossil-based products. Similarly, construction companies, architects, and engineers play a crucial role in implementing hemp insulation. However, a lack of understanding and knowledge about timber-based solutions, which varies by region, often leads to the continued use of non-biobased insulation, resulting in a lower (current) overall interest in sustainable alternatives.

Hemp insulation manufacturers, hemp processors, and hemp farmers are highly interested stakeholders in integrating hemp-based products into the bioeconomy supply chain. However, their success depends on market demand, which in turn relies on greater incentives to choose biobased products. Due to the limited use of biobased insulation materials and the fact that insulation represents only a small percentage of construction waste, end-of-life processing for these materials remains minimal, resulting in lower influence and interest in this area. Expanding the use of biobased insulation and implementing stronger waste management policies could help drive meaningful change.

Figure 16. Stakeholders of the hemp insulation value chain mapped in a power-interest matrix

3.4.3 Policies of relevance to the hemp insulation value chain

In this section, policies were identified that could either propel or impede the implementation of the hemp insulation. These policies were detected through desk research and communication with stakeholders. In Table 10, an overview is provided of the relevant policies, including the type of policy it concerns, further general information, as well as its relevance to the hemp insulation case study.

The European Union has implemented a wide range of policies aimed at achieving its ambitious climate and sustainability goals. These policies, which focus on emission reduction, energy efficiency, and resource optimisation, create a favourable environment for the use of sustainable materials such as hemp insulation. Hemp insulation, as a biobased material, aligns with the EU's broader objectives of creating a circular, low-carbon economy. This analysis explores the connection between key European policies and the promotion of hemp insulation, highlighting the role it plays in the green transition.

The European Green Deal is the cornerstone of the European Union's ambition to become the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. This comprehensive strategy aims to decarbonise various sectors, foster resource efficiency, and implement circular economy principles, with a particular focus on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting renewable energy, and transitioning to a low-carbon economy. Within this framework, the construction and building sectors are central, as they represent one of the largest sources of carbon emissions and energy consumption. Hemp insulation, as a sustainable and biobased material, aligns with the Green Deal's goals, offering a renewable, carbon-sequestering alternative to traditional building materials.

Two key policies that further reinforce the Green Deal's objectives are the EU Climate Law and the 2030 Climate Target Plan. The EU Climate Law legally binds the EU to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, with an interim goal of reducing emissions by 55% by 2030. The 2030 Climate Target Plan outlines a clear roadmap for achieving these reductions, emphasising the importance of energy efficiency, renewable energy, and green technologies. Hemp insulation directly contributes to these goals by improving building energy performance and reducing reliance on energy-intensive materials. Buildings, which account for a significant share of the EU's energy consumption, play a crucial role in meeting the EU's climate and energy targets. By enhancing insulation with sustainable materials like hemp, buildings can achieve higher energy efficiency, reducing the need for heating and cooling. This not only helps reduce overall energy consumption but also lowers greenhouse gas emissions, supporting the EU's legal commitment to climate neutrality by 2050.

The Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) complements these policies by setting binding targets for energy savings and encouraging the use of technologies that enhance energy performance. Hemp insulation, with its superior thermal properties, helps meet these targets by improving the energy efficiency of both new and existing buildings. This directive is central to the EU's efforts to reduce energy use across sectors and plays a vital role in fostering the transition to a more sustainable, energy-efficient economy.

The Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) and the European Resource Efficiency Platform (EREP) support the EU's transition from a linear economy to a circular one. These policies focus on

reducing waste, maximising resource efficiency, and promoting the use of renewable materials. Hemp insulation fits seamlessly within this framework as a biodegradable, recyclable material that can be produced with minimal environmental impact. Hemp cultivation itself is resource-efficient, requiring fewer fertilisers and pesticides compared to many other crops. Its integration into the construction sector helps close the loop in the building industry, reducing reliance on non-renewable resources and promoting sustainability. The CEAP encourages the use of biobased materials, like hemp, that contribute to reducing waste and extending the lifecycle of products. Hemp insulation, being a renewable material, offers significant benefits in terms of both carbon sequestration and reduced waste. At the end of its life cycle, hemp insulation can be composted or recycled, contributing to a more circular economy in the construction industry. The European Green Deal also ties directly into the EU's circular economy efforts by emphasising decarbonisation and sustainable resource management across various sectors. By incorporating hemp into construction materials, the EU can reduce its reliance on fossil-based products, such as synthetic insulation materials, which have a higher environmental impact. Hemp's low environmental footprint and renewability make it an ideal candidate for supporting the EU's resource efficiency and circular economy objectives.

The New European Bauhaus initiative and the Renovation Wave Initiative focus on transforming the built environment to support sustainability and improve the quality of life for European citizens. The Renovation Wave, in particular, targets the retrofitting of Europe's aging building stock, with a goal of doubling renovation rates by 2030. This initiative aims to improve the energy performance of buildings, reduce energy consumption, and lower greenhouse gas emissions. Hemp insulation is particularly well-suited for renovation projects, as it can be easily integrated into existing structures to enhance thermal performance and reduce energy needs. With 85% of EU buildings constructed before 2000, many of which have poor energy performance, improving insulation is a critical step in achieving the EU's energy and climate goals. Hemp insulation, which offers high thermal efficiency, can significantly enhance the energy performance of these buildings without major structural changes, thus supporting the EU's renovation efforts. This also contributes to reducing energy costs for residents and businesses, improving overall living conditions.

The Construction Products Regulation (CPR) ensures that construction products, including biobased materials like hemp insulation, meet safety and performance standards. Compliance with CPR guarantees that hemp insulation is a safe, reliable, and effective material for improving the energy efficiency of buildings. By adhering to these regulations, hemp insulation can be confidently integrated into both new builds and renovation projects across the EU.

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) plays a key role in supporting the cultivation of biobased materials like hemp. The CAP provides financial support for sustainable farming practices, which helps encourage the cultivation of environmentally friendly crops like hemp. Hemp requires minimal inputs and is well-suited to sustainable farming practices, making it an ideal crop for meeting the EU's goals of promoting biodiversity, reducing soil degradation, and increasing carbon sequestration in agriculture.

Additionally, the Bâtiment Biosourcé label in France incentivises the use of biobased materials like hemp in construction projects. This certification program promotes the use of renewable materials, offering an eco-label for buildings that incorporate biobased insulation materials such

as hemp. The label raises awareness about the environmental benefits of using sustainable materials and encourages the adoption of hemp insulation in both public and private construction projects. France takes on great responsibility regarding the implementation of biobased construction materials to reduce environmental impacts of the sector, it is the only country explicitly proposing and stimulating the use of biobased materials in construction.

France plays a leading role in promoting the use of biobased materials to reduce the environmental impact of the construction sector. It is one of the only countries explicitly advocating for and incentivising the integration of biobased materials for construction in its National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) and long term renovation strategy (LTRS).

Table 10. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the hemp insulation case study

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
European Green Deal	The European Green Deal aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 through a broad framework of policies, including emission reduction, resource efficiency, and circular economy initiatives	Stimulating instrument	Stimulating instrument by promoting sustainable and energy-efficient building materials like hemp based insulation to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. By encouraging the use of sustainable materials in construction and renovation, the Green Deal fosters innovation and growth in the industrial hemp industry as well.	EU	Current	Policy framework and financial incentives	EC COM (2019)640
Circular Economy Action Plan	The Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) is a comprehensive initiative by the European Union aimed at promoting sustainable growth by transitioning from a linear "take-make-dispose" model to a circular economy. It focuses on reducing waste, maximising resource efficiency, and keeping materials in use for as long as possible. Key elements of the plan include fostering sustainable product design, promoting circular business models, encouraging recycling, and addressing sectors with high resource use, such as electronics, textiles, construction, and plastics.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates the use of hemp insulation by promoting sustainable, renewable, and recyclable materials in construction. Hemp insulation aligns with the plan's goals of reducing waste, improving resource efficiency, and creating circular building practices. As a biodegradable and non-toxic material, hemp insulation supports the transition to low-carbon, sustainable construction	EU	Current	Strategic framework and regulatory directives	EC COM (2020)98

EU Climate Law	The EU Climate Law makes the EU's commitment to climate neutrality by 2050 legally binding, with a target to cut emissions by 55% by 2030. It ensures all EU policies support the green transition, aligning with the European Green Deal and the Paris Agreement.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates the use of hemp insulation by mandating legally binding targets to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and reduce emissions by 55% by 2030. Hemp insulation, as a renewable and carbon-negative material, contributes to these goals by reducing the carbon footprint of buildings and enhancing energy efficiency. The law's emphasis on decarbonising the construction sector and improving building performance creates demand for sustainable materials like hemp insulation, fostering its adoption in both new construction and renovations.	EU	Current	Strategic framework and regulatory directives	EU 2021/1119
2030 Climate Target Plan	The 2030 Climate Target Plan is the EU's strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. It outlines measures to accelerate the transition to a sustainable economy, including boosting renewable energy, improving energy efficiency, and promoting green technologies. This plan is key to achieving climate neutrality by 2050 under the European Green Deal.		Stimulates the use of hemp insulation by setting a binding goal to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. Hemp insulation, as a natural, renewable, and carbon-negative material, can help achieve this target by lowering the carbon footprint of buildings and enhancing energy efficiency. The plan's focus on decarbonising the construction sector and improving energy performance	EU	Current	regulatory directives	EC COM 2020/562
New European Bauhaus	New European Bauhaus is a policy and funding initiative that makes green transition in built environments enjoyable, attractive, and convenient for all. Even the smallest communities on the ground deserve living spaces that improve their well-being and	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates the adoption of hemp-based products by promoting innovative, sustainable, and aesthetically appealing solutions in design and construction. Hemp-based building materials, such as insulation and hempcrete, align with the initiative's focus on low-carbon, renewable, and circular products.	EU	Current	Policy framework and financial incentives	New European Bauhaus

	sense of belonging. The initiative promotes solutions that are not only sustainable, but also inclusive and beautiful, while respecting the diversity of places, traditions, and cultures in Europe and beyond.		With the integration of sustainable materials into architecture and building practices, the New European Bauhaus fosters the use of hemp-based products as versatile, green solutions that enhance energy efficiency, reduce emissions, and support a healthier, more sustainable built environment.				
The Renovation Wave Initiative	The Renovation Wave Initiative is the EU's plan to improve the energy efficiency of buildings across Europe. It aims to double renovation rates by 2030, reducing energy consumption, cutting greenhouse gas emissions, and improving living conditions. The initiative focuses on making buildings greener, more affordable, and resilient, while creating jobs and advancing the EU's climate neutrality goals under the European Green Deal.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates the use of hemp insulation by promoting large-scale building renovations to improve energy efficiency and reduce carbon emissions. Hemp insulation aligns with the goals of making buildings greener and more sustainable. By encouraging the adoption of sustainable materials in retrofitting projects, the initiative creates opportunities for hemp insulation to play a key role in enhancing thermal performance, lowering energy demand, and contributing to the EU's climate neutrality targets.	EU	Current	Policy framework and financial incentives	EC COM 2020/662
Energy Performance of Buildings Directive	Buildings are the single largest energy consumer in Europe. The building sector is therefore crucial to achieving the EU's energy and climate goals. 85% of EU buildings were built before 2000 and amongst those, 75% have a poor energy performance. Acting on the energy efficiency of buildings is therefore key to saving energy and achieving a zero-emission and fully decarbonised building stock by 2050. These facts and those below come from Eurostat	Stimulating instrument	stimulates the use of hemp insulation by requiring improved energy efficiency in buildings through sustainable and innovative solutions. Hemp insulation supports compliance with the directive's standards for reducing energy consumption and emissions. By encouraging renovations and the adoption of sustainable materials.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EU 2024/1275

	energy balances and EEA Greenhouse Gas Inventory, 2023.						
The Construction Products Regulation (CPR)	The European Union's Construction Products Regulation (CPR) provides a comprehensive framework for the standardisation, performance, and safety of construction products, including biobased insulation materials.	Potential stimulating instrument	has the potential to further stimulate the adoption of hemp insulation and other biobased products in the construction sector by establishing harmonised standards for the safety, performance, and sustainability of construction materials. While the CPR provides a valuable regulatory framework, additional focus, and further harmonisation of standards for biobased products are necessary.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EU 305/2011
European Resource Efficiency Platform (EREP)	The European Resource Efficiency Platform (EREP) supports a broad strategy for promoting resource efficiency and sustainability, which creates a favourable environment for the adoption of biobased materials like hemp insulation.	Stimulating instrument	stimulates the use of hemp insulation by promoting sustainable resource use and encouraging innovative, low-impact materials in construction. Hemp insulation, as a renewable and biodegradable product, fits within the platform's goals to reduce resource consumption, minimise waste, and enhance the circular economy	EU	old	Strategy	European resource efficiency knowledge centre
Carbon farming initiative	Using buildings as a carbon store (coupled with substitution benefits) will contribute to a reduction of GHGs, as required under the EU climate targets	Stimulating instrument	The Carbon Farming Initiative can stimulate the use of industrial hemp by promoting farming practices that capture and store carbon in the soil. Hemp is a fast-growing, carbon-negative crop, known for its ability to sequester significant amounts of CO2 during its growth. By incentivising carbon farming practices such as hemp cultivation, the initiative supports the use of hemp as a sustainable and environmentally beneficial crop.	EU	Current	Voluntary approach	EU 2024/3012

Energy Efficiency Directive	The Energy Efficiency Directive is an EU policy aimed at reducing energy consumption and improving efficiency across sectors. It sets binding targets for energy savings, promotes technologies to cut energy use, and ensures better energy performance in buildings, industry, and transport. The directive is crucial for achieving the EU's climate goals and supporting the transition to a sustainable energy system.	Stimulating instrument	stimulates the use of hemp insulation by promoting energy-saving measures in buildings and helps improving energy efficiency across the EU. The minimum use of fertilisers and complete avoidance of pesticides and herbicides, results in substantially lower carbon emissions than the agricultural average.	EU	Current	Regulatory directive	EU 2023/1791
Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)	The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is a set of regulations and financial frameworks established by the European Union to support and regulate agriculture. Its primary goals include ensuring food security, promoting sustainable farming practices, and enhancing rural development. CAP provides financial aid to farmers through direct payments, subsidies, and rural development programs, while also encouraging environmentally friendly practices, such as biodiversity conservation and soil health.	Stimulating instrument	the CAP provides a framework of financial support, regulatory guidance, and incentives that could foster the growth of industrial hemp as a sustainable and economically viable crop in Europe. However, for hemp to reach its full potential, more focus on harmonised regulations and additional support for processing and market development is needed.	EU	Current	regulatory directives	EU 2021/2115
“Bâtiment Biosourcé” (Biobased Building) label	The “Bâtiment Biosourcé” (Biobased Building) label is a French certification awarded to buildings that incorporate biobased materials, such as wood, hemp, or straw, in their construction. It promotes sustainable building practices, with certification levels based on	Stimulating instrument	stimulate the use of hemp insulation by promoting the adoption of biobased materials in construction. By supporting the use of natural, locally sourced materials like hemp, the initiative fosters a shift towards greener, energy-efficient buildings that reduce carbon emissions and enhance sustainability in the	France	Current	Certification, voluntary	<u>Bâtiment Biosourcé</u>

	the quantity of biobased material used per square meter.		construction industry and helps drive for biobased materials.				
--	--	--	---	--	--	--	--

3.4.4 Analysis of indicators of the hemp insulation case study

In T3.2, a consistency check was conducted to identify the indicators in the Bioeconomy Monitoring and Assessment framework deemed relevant in light of hemp insulation case study. Subsequently, a selection of indicators was labelled as highly relevant. This initial analysis took place on the basis of stakeholder communication and literature review using search queries such as “social”, “economic”, “environmental”, “life cycle assessment”, “industrial hemp”, “hemp insulation”, “impacts”, “value chain”, and “sustainable construction” and “sustainable agriculture”.

The subsequent section builds upon the results of this preliminary analysis, further refining and elaborating on the findings. Each identified indicator will be utilised to assess the performance of the hemp value chain in comparison to conventional, non-biobased construction materials. The analysis integrates insights from Task T3.2, the literature review, and stakeholder consultations. In cases where no data or information was available to support the evaluation of a specific indicator, this was documented as a research gap.

3.4.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators

A total of 71 environmental and circular indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. However, after further review, refinement, and stakeholder input, several indicators were found to be too general and not closely related enough to the hemp insulation case study. These indicators were eventually eliminated, resulting in the following list of indicators shown in Table 11 below.

Hemp cultivation for fibre has experienced significant growth, reaching 30,020 hectares in 2022—an increase of 60% compared to 2015 (EC, 2024). This expansion highlights hemp’s growing role in sustainable industries, including the production of biobased insulation materials. Hemp biomass, a byproduct of fibre, seed, and other agricultural uses, can be effectively repurposed into solid biofuels. While hemp cultivation for seed and grain often results in waste residues such as stalks and threshing by-products, fibre crops typically produce hemp shives. Both hemp shives and fibres find applications in construction, and other residual biomass like leaves holds potential for bioenergy production (Sieracka et al., 2023). Furthermore, cultivating industrial hemp on marginal or contaminated lands offers a valuable opportunity to mitigate indirect land use change effects, reducing the demand for prime agricultural land and supporting sustainable land-use practices (Blandinières & Amaducci, 2022; Guo et al., 2024).

Hemp-based insulation materials, such as HempWool and hempcrete, demonstrate considerable energy-saving potential and environmental benefits. Tests at Oak Ridge National Laboratory reveal that hemp insulation outperforms traditional fibreglass, showing superior thermal performance due to its higher density and enhanced ability to absorb, store, and release heat (EERE, 2023). Hemp fibre insulation consists of hemp fibres combined with recycled polyethylene and polypropylene fibres, reducing raw material waste by incorporating post-consumer textile waste (KOBECZ s.r.o, 2020; Gutierrez-Moscardo et al., 2021). Additionally, to improve fire resistance, treatments like boric acid and sodium borate are used (Rabbat et al., 2021). While

Table 11. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the hemp insulation case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Land cover/use	Agricultural area	The area dedicated to hemp cultivation for fibre reached 30020 ha in 2022, which is an 60% increase compared to 2015 values (EC, 2024)	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Bioenergy replacing non-renewable energy	Industrial residues used in industrial processes for energy	Hemp biomass, a byproduct of hemp cultivation for purposes such as fibre, seed, food, cosmetics, or pharmaceuticals, can be effectively utilised in the production of solid biofuels. For instance, in seed or grain cultivation, the leftover stalks and threshing residues become waste, whereas in fibre crops, the waste consists primarily of shives. In construction applications, both the shives and fibres from the hemp stem are used, leaving behind additional waste like leaves, which can be repurposed for bioenergy production (Sieracka et al., 2023).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Indirect Land use change (iLUC)	Loss of agricultural or forest area	The cultivation of industrial hemp on marginal and contaminated lands holds significant potential to mitigate indirect land use change effects. By utilising areas less suitable for conventional agriculture—such as those with poor soil quality or adverse climatic conditions—hemp cultivation can alleviate the pressure on prime agricultural lands, promoting more sustainable land-use practices (Blandinières & Amaducci, 2022) (Guo et al., 2024).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Primary energy savings (kWh or % of total primary energy consumed)	Hemp-based insulation materials, such as HempWool and hempcrete, have demonstrated significant primary energy savings and environmental benefits in various applications. Testing of hemp insulation at Oak Ridge National Laboratory revealed energy and humidity benefits over traditional fibreglass insulation. Its higher density and superior ability to absorb, store, and release heat results in enhanced thermal performance and energy efficiency of buildings (EERE, 2023).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Soil quality	Soil erosion / product unit	The deep penetration of hemp root systems can help with the prevention of soil erosion and improve soil structure to increase productivity (Rehman et al., 2021).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Soil quality	Soil nutrient balance	Integrating hemp into crop rotations can have a positive impact on soil health. Research by Bócsa and Karus (1998) demonstrated that wheat yields increased by 10-20% following hemp cultivation. Additionally, a study by the European Environmental Agency (EEA, 2007) found that hemp has a relatively low impact	Yes, the use of hemp as for phytoremediation of polluted soils requires additional research.

				on nutrient depletion. Hemp also demonstrates potential for phytoremediation (Rehman et al., 2021).	
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Hazardous substances management	% of plastic (synthetic plastic material, plasticisers, PVC) contained in the product	Hemp fibre insulation consists of hemp fibres and binding agents to form the insulation mats. A commonly used binders are polyethylene and polypropylene fibres (KOBE ECO HempFLEx 12%) (KOBE-cz s.r.o, 2020).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Hazardous substances management	% of flame retardants	Flame retardants used for hemp fibre insulation include boratic acid, sodium borate (Rabbat et al., 2021) and caustic soda (e.g., KOBE ECO HempFLEx 3% caustic soda) (KOBE-cz s.r.o, 2020).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of recycled fibre raw material is used	The polyethylene and polypropylene fibres used as binders can be fully sourced from recycled post-consumer textile waste (KOBE-cz s.r.o, 2020). Additionally, hemp fibre insulation can incorporate waste fibres from the textile industry, further enhancing its sustainability. Some biobased insulation materials containing hemp are even produced entirely from waste, residues, and by-products (Lu et al., 2024).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of the total amount of agricultural biomass used come from agricultural residues	Hemp waste fibres derived from hemp cultivation for the textile industry can be effectively repurposed for the production of hemp fibre-based insulation materials (Gutierrez-Moscardo et al., 2021). Some biobased insulation materials containing hemp are even produced entirely from waste, residues, and by-products (Lu et al., 2024).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of biodegradability	The level of biodegradability depends on the composition (binders and additives) of the insulation material.	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle GHG emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	The cultivation of one hectare of hemp results in a net carbon footprint of - 1.73 kg CO ₂ eq. per kilogram of product, primarily due to CO ₂ uptake during growth (Zampori et al., 2013). However, the overall emissions associated with producing hemp insulation materials vary depending on sourcing, production location, and the composition of hemp fibres, binders, and additives.	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Rate of GHG emissions reduction or savings	The use of hemp fibre insulation results in a 12% reduction in net emissions in a house model compared to glass wool insulation (Hult & Karlsmo, 2022).	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Carbon stock (kg/unit of biomass)	An LCA of hemp cultivation showed that the amount of stored carbon ranged between -1/-2.9 kg CO ₂ eq/kg hemp (Boutin et al., 2006).	No.

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP100; gr eq. CO2)	The GWP of hemp fibre insulation depends on the total manufacturing steps, from hemp crop growth, transport, additional materials the manufacturing process, end of life. Because of carbon sequestration during growth, hemp fibre insulation is able to have a net negative GWP of -0.3 kg CO ₂ eq. (Davis, 2024).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Biodiversity	Agrobiodiversity	Hemp cultivated for seeds and fibre outperforms other major crops like rapeseed, barley, and wheat in terms of biodiversity friendliness (Piotrowski et al., 2011).	No.
3	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Practices to segregate different waste types to facilitate reuse, recycling, or composting (yes/no)	While targets are being set for the recovery of non-dangerous and non-inert building waste, such as biobased insulation, the necessary recovery processes and channels are lacking, resulting in very low recycling rates. The absence of proper dismantling, organised sorting, and efficient collection methods, combined with the limited availability of biobased insulation, remain key challenges making landfilling the most likely end-of-life scenario. (Rabbat et al., 2021).	Yes, proper methods and practices for the collecting and recycling of biobased insulation material like hemp fibre insulation are currently missing.

these materials are biodegradable, the environmental impact depends on the composition of binders and additives used in the production process.

In 2020, France commercialised approximately 2,800 tons of hemp fibre insulation (Rabbat et al., 2021). Biobased insulation materials still account for only a small portion of the European market, representing just 1.6% in 2022, but this share is projected to rise to around 30% by 2030 under a bioeconomy scenario (Lu et al., 2024). Hemp cultivation also benefits soil health, as its deep root system prevents erosion and improves soil structure (Rehman et al., 2021). Integrating hemp into crop rotations has been shown to boost soil fertility, increasing yields of subsequent crops like wheat by 10-20% (Bócsa & Karus, 1998). Furthermore, hemp is low in nutrient depletion and has phytoremediation potential (EEA, 2007; Rehman et al., 2021).

Hemp cultivation plays a critical role in carbon sequestration, with one hectare of hemp achieving a net carbon footprint of -1.73 kg CO₂ eq. per kilogram of product (Zampori et al., 2013). Life cycle assessments (LCA) indicate stored carbon amounts ranging from -1 to -2.9 kg CO₂ eq. per kilogram of hemp (Boutin et al., 2006). Hemp insulation, benefiting from the carbon sequestration during plant growth, can achieve a net negative global warming potential (GWP) of -0.3 kg CO₂ eq. (Davis, 2024). A comparative analysis found that hemp insulation resulted in a 12% reduction in net emissions in residential buildings when compared to glass wool insulation (Hult & Karlsmo, 2022). Hemp cultivation also outperforms major crops like rapeseed, barley, and wheat in terms of supporting biodiversity (Piotrowski et al., 2011).

Despite these advantages, challenges remain in the end-of-life management of hemp insulation. While policies promoting the recovery of biobased building waste exist, there is still a lack of efficient recovery processes and collection channels. This results in low recycling rates, and landfilling remains the primary disposal method (Rabbat et al., 2021). To maximise the environmental benefits of hemp fibre insulation, addressing these challenges is essential. In conclusion, hemp insulation presents a promising, sustainable alternative to conventional materials, offering reduced carbon emissions, improved soil health, and biodiversity support. However, overcoming the hurdles related to end-of-life recovery and recycling will be critical to fully realising its environmental potential.

3.4.4.2 Economic indicators

A total of 12 economic indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. However, after further review, refinement, and stakeholder input, several indicators were found to be too general and not closely related enough to the hemp insulation case study. These indicators were eventually eliminated, resulting in the following list of indicators shown in Table 12 below.

Table 12. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the hemp insulation case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
----	---------------------	------------	-----------	---------------------------	---------------

3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	(Total raw) material productivity	In 2023, 28,830 hectares of hemp were used for hemp cultivation resulting in 162,240 tons of hemp being harvested (Eurostat, 2025). The straw, which accounts for 79% of the crop's economic value, is mechanically defibred into approximately 25% long bast fibres and 43% shives, with the remaining fraction consisting of dust and fines (Rabbat et al., 2021).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Primary Biomass production	Agriculture	Hemp can be used as an effective rotational crop that requires minimal inputs in terms of fertilisers, pesticides and herbicides resulting in lower operational costs (Hemp farmer communication).	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Recycling rate of biobased products	The production of hemp-based building materials ensures the recycling of 29% of the fibres and 14% of the shives of the hemp stalk (Rabbat et al., 2021).	Yes, proper methods and practices for the collecting and recycling of biobased insulation material like hemp fibre insulation are currently missing
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Potential market share of the product	In France, approximately 2,800 tons of hemp fibre insulation were commercialised in 2020 (Rabbat et al., 2021). Despite its environmental benefits, biobased insulation materials still represent only a small fraction of the European insulation market, accounting for just 1.6% in 2022. However, under a bioeconomy scenario, this share is projected to rise significantly to around 30% by 2030 (Lu et al., 2024).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Residual biomass potential	During the processing of hemp stems into fibres and hurds, hemp dust is generated as a by-product. This can be utilised in the production of biochar, biofuels, absorbents, bioplastics, and even 3D printing filaments, (Environmental Living Industries).	No.

The hemp industry is gaining recognition not only for its environmental sustainability but also for its economic efficiency, demonstrating the potential to significantly contribute to both the agricultural and construction sectors. With 28,830 hectares of hemp cultivated in 2023, resulting in the harvest of 162,240 tons (Eurostat, 2025), the crop continues to showcase remarkable material productivity. Hemp's economic value is largely driven by its stalks, which accounts for 79% of the crop's worth. Through mechanical defibring, the hemp stalks yield approximately 25% long bast fibres and 43% shives, while the remaining fraction consists of dust and fines (Rabbat et al., 2021). This efficient conversion of hemp stalks into usable materials allows for high material output relative to the area of land under cultivation.

While hemp-based insulation materials have significant environmental benefits, their market share remains relatively small within the broader European insulation market, accounting for just 1.6% in 2022 (Lu et al., 2024). However, the rise of the bioeconomy presents a promising opportunity for the expansion of hemp-based products. The European Union’s Green Deal and its push for a carbon-neutral economy by 2050 have created an encouraging regulatory environment for biobased materials. In particular, the demand for sustainable, eco-friendly building materials is expected to rise substantially in the coming years. By 2030, the share of biobased insulation materials, including those made from hemp, is projected to grow to around 30% (Lu et al., 2024). This growth is fuelled by both governmental policies aimed at reducing carbon emissions and the growing awareness among consumers and businesses about the environmental impacts of traditional insulation materials.

In addition, hemp’s potential as a renewable resource within the bioeconomy is further supported by its ability to sequester carbon. Hemp absorbs significant amounts of CO₂ during its growth cycle, making it a potential carbon sink in the fight against climate change. By replacing petroleum-based materials with hemp-based alternatives, industries could contribute to global carbon reduction targets, while simultaneously driving economic growth in the hemp sector.

Beyond its use in insulation and building materials, the residual biomass produced during hemp processing presents an exciting range of opportunities. Hemp dust, a by-product of stem processing, can be repurposed into valuable products such as biochar, biofuels, absorbents, bioplastics, and even 3D printing filaments (Environmental Living Industries). These secondary products offer a wide array of applications across industries, further enhancing the economic potential of hemp-based products.

While targets for recycling and reusing construction waste are being established, they primarily focus on inert materials. The minimal presence of biobased insulation, both in use and at the end of its life cycle, is one of the current hindrances and has led to a lack of effective collection and sorting methods. As a result, opportunities for material or energy recovery remain largely untapped.

3.4.4.3 Social indicators

A total of 2 social indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. However, after further review, refinement, and stakeholder input, one indicator was found to be too general and not closely related enough to the hemp case study resulting in the following list of indicators shown in table below. One new relevant indicator was identified and is included in the table in red

Table 13. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the hemp insulation case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic	Innovation	Number of certifications/ labels the organisation obtained for	Regional-specific certifications often require multiple approvals to operate in different markets, creating significant challenges and	Yes, harmonised and standardised national/international testing and evaluation procedures for specific

			the product/site	added costs, particularly for smaller producers and emerging innovations. This lack of harmonisation can slow market entry, increase administrative burdens, and hinder the adoption of sustainable materials (Vrins et al., 2018).	biobased products and technologies are needed.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Regulatory measures	There are different policies and strategies available at national and EU level that both stimulate but also hinder the increase of use of industrial hemp as a building material.	Yes, industrial hemp and hemp insulation still face challenges due to the lingering negative stigma associated with hemp. Misconceptions surrounding its connection to cannabis often lead to regulatory hurdles, market hesitancy, and limited consumer awareness, slowing its wider adoption.

Hemp insulation has gained attention as a sustainable alternative in the construction industry, but its widespread adoption faces both regulatory and certification challenges that vary across different regions. These challenges impact producers, especially smaller enterprises and those introducing innovative products.

One significant obstacle lies in the number of certifications or labels that a product or organisation needs to obtain to enter different markets. Regional-specific certifications often require extensive approvals, which can be particularly difficult for smaller producers or emerging technologies. According to Vrins et al. (2018), the lack of harmonisation among these certifications increases administrative burdens, slows market entry, and raises costs. This complexity can deter the adoption of sustainable materials like hemp insulation, despite their environmental benefits.

In addition to certification hurdles, regulatory measures also play a critical role in shaping the future of industrial hemp as a building material. At both the national and EU levels, a mix of policies and strategies exist that can either stimulate or hinder the use of hemp-based products in construction. While some regulations are designed to promote sustainability and encourage the use of eco-friendly materials, other legal and policy frameworks may introduce barriers to market penetration or compliance costs. These contradictory forces create a challenging landscape for hemp insulation to thrive.

3.4.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Policy dimension

Challenges:

- Regulatory uncertainties and varying restrictions across different regions regarding the use of industrial hemp are significantly limiting its full potential as a sustainable and innovative building material. These legal barriers hinder widespread adoption and slow the development of hemp-based construction solutions.
- The lack of incentives at the EU level for hemp insulation products and other renewable, plant-based building materials is slowing down their adoption and innovation. Without targeted support and incentives, the growth of these sustainable alternatives remains hindered, preventing them from competing with traditional building materials on a larger scale.
- Due to the absence of harmonised EU standards, many hemp-based products are unable to obtain the CE marking, which limits their market acceptance and regulatory approval. However, ongoing efforts are focused on securing European Technical Assessments (ETAs) and advocating for the introduction of CE marking at both national and EU levels, which would help streamline the process and promote wider use of these sustainable materials across Europe.
- The hygro-thermal behaviour of hempcrete is not adequately accounted for by current official methods of assessing thermal performance, such as standard thermal conductivity tests. These conventional tests fail to consider the material's unique ability to regulate moisture and its impact on thermal insulation over time, leading to an incomplete understanding of its true performance in real-world conditions.

Recommendations and examples of good practice:

- There is a need to revise thermal performance testing for biobased materials to better incorporate their hygrothermal and hygroscopic behaviours. Current testing methods often overlook the impact of moisture absorption and release, which are crucial for accurately assessing the long-term thermal efficiency and overall performance of materials like hempcrete in real-world environments. Updating these standards would ensure a more comprehensive evaluation of biobased materials' true capabilities.
- There is a pressing need for additional education and a shift in mindset regarding industrial hemp to address widespread misconceptions and promote its numerous benefits. Many people remain unaware of its versatility, sustainability, and potential as a resource for various industries, including construction. By increasing awareness and providing accurate information, we can foster a broader acceptance of industrial hemp and unlock its potential as a key player in sustainable development.
- Reducing barriers to the production and processing of industrial hemp in Europe is essential for unlocking its full potential as a sustainable resource.
- Promoting the use of industrial hemp in crop rotation is an effective strategy to enhance soil health and diversify agricultural systems. Hemp's deep root system helps to break up compacted soil, improving aeration and water infiltration. Additionally, it can help reduce soil erosion, restore nutrient levels, and suppress weed growth, leading to more sustainable farming practices. Integrating hemp into crop rotation systems not only benefits soil quality but also provides farmers with an economically viable alternative, contributing to both environmental sustainability and agricultural diversification.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges:

- The lack of knowledge and awareness surrounding industrial hemp, coupled with the negative stigma associated with hemp products, presents a significant barrier to its widespread adoption. Many people still associate hemp with its psychoactive cousin, cannabis, leading to misconceptions about its safety and utility. Educating the public and industry stakeholders about the distinct differences between industrial hemp and other cannabis varieties, as well as highlighting the numerous sustainable benefits of hemp products, is crucial for overcoming these stigmas and unlocking its full potential.
- Shifting the focus towards sustainable practices and innovative solutions is key to addressing environmental challenges. By prioritising eco-friendly materials and technologies, we can reduce environmental impact while fostering economic growth and long-term resilience. This approach will drive positive change and support a more sustainable future.

Recommendations and examples of good practice:

- Focusing on long-term construction developments that prioritise sustainability, resilience, and futureproofing is essential for creating buildings that can withstand environmental challenges and changing needs. By incorporating eco-friendly materials, energy-efficient designs, and adaptable structures, we ensure that these developments remain viable and sustainable for years to come, benefiting both the environment and future generations.
- Providing support across the entire biobased supply chain, from raw material production to end-product development, is crucial for fostering sustainability and innovation. By strengthening each stage of the process, from cultivation and processing to manufacturing and distribution, we can enhance the efficiency, quality, and impact of biobased products. This integrated approach not only promotes environmental sustainability but also drives economic growth and encourages the adoption of innovative, eco-friendly solutions across industries.
- Encouraging the local procurement of feedstock helps support regional economies while reducing transportation-related environmental impacts. By sourcing materials locally, we can minimise carbon emissions associated with long-distance transportation, promote sustainable farming practices, and strengthen local supply chains. This approach not only benefits the environment but also boosts economic resilience in local communities, fostering a more sustainable and self-sufficient production system.

Market dimension

Challenges:

- The absence of standardised guidelines for biobased materials hinders their broader adoption and certification. Without clear, universally accepted standards, manufacturers face challenges in ensuring product quality and meeting regulatory requirements. This uncertainty can slow down the development of biobased materials, preventing them from reaching their full potential in the marketplace. Establishing standardised guidelines would facilitate certification, enhance consumer confidence, and accelerate the widespread use of these sustainable alternatives.
- Biobased materials, such as hemp insulation, are often held to the same regulations and constraints as fossil-based materials, despite offering superior performance and significant environmental benefits. This outdated approach fails to recognise the unique advantages of biobased options, such as better thermal regulation, lower environmental impact, and

sustainability. Revising these regulations to better reflect the characteristics of biobased materials would encourage their use and support the transition towards greener, more efficient building practices.

- The limited availability of industrial-scale hemp processing facilities in the EU hampers the growth of the hemp-based material industry. Without adequate infrastructure to process hemp on a large scale, production costs remain high, and supply chains are inefficient, slowing down the widespread adoption of hemp-based products. Expanding processing facilities would enhance the availability of raw materials, reduce costs, and support the scaling up of sustainable construction solutions across Europe.

Recommendations and examples of good practice:

- There has been steady growth in market awareness among final users, architects, builders, and real estate developers, with a notable spike in the past two years. This increasing interest may signal the beginning of the long-anticipated exponential growth in the adoption of sustainable, hemp-based materials. As more stakeholders recognise the benefits of these eco-friendly alternatives, the market is poised for further expansion, potentially transforming the construction industry, and driving broader sustainability efforts.

3.4.6 Key learnings of hemp insulation case study

Hemp, historically used in textiles and marine industries, is now gaining recognition as a sustainable insulation material in construction. As a rapidly growing, low-input crop, hemp provides environmental benefits such as carbon sequestration, soil regeneration, and low water and fertilisers, pesticides, and herbicides usage. While production is increasing in Europe, further investment in processing capabilities is needed to keep the supply chain local, cost-effective, and sustainable as the demand for biobased insulating materials such as hemp insulation will continue to grow.

Biobased insulation materials, including hemp fibre insulation, offer key advantages over conventional fossil-based alternatives. These include superior moisture regulation, carbon storage, and recyclability. Hemp insulation comes in various forms such as batts, blocks, and loose fill making it a versatile choice for sustainable construction. However, despite these benefits, hemp insulation still faces some barriers to widespread adoption.

One major challenge is the lack of awareness and persistent stigma surrounding industrial hemp, which slows its acceptance in mainstream construction. Regulatory barriers also pose a significant hurdle, as current building standards favour non-biobased materials and fail to account for hemp's advantages such as carbon sequestration and moisture buffering. Additionally, fragmented certification systems across EU regions limit market expansion and cross-border trade. Another key issue is the limited processing infrastructure—while hemp cultivation is growing, there is still a need for more facilities to ensure efficient, local production. Finally, end-of-life management remains underdeveloped, requiring more research to create circular economy strategies for biobased insulation waste, as current recovery and reuse options are limited.

To accelerate the adoption of hemp insulation, several key steps must be taken. Stronger policy support and incentives are crucial—governments should introduce subsidies, tax reductions, and green building incentives that favour biobased insulation. Additionally, harmonised EU standards are needed to establish unified testing and certification protocols, facilitating broader market access. Increasing industry training and awareness will help educate architects, builders, and consumers on the benefits of hemp insulation, driving demand. Furthermore, investment in processing and supply chains is essential to reduce costs and improve accessibility. Lastly, research into circular economy solutions must be prioritised to develop effective recovery, reuse, and recycling strategies, ensuring the long-term sustainability of biobased insulation materials.

Hemp fibre insulation can be a key player in the transition to sustainable construction, offering environmental and performance benefits over traditional fossil-based insulation materials. While regulatory and infrastructure challenges remain, targeted policies, industry collaboration, and increased market awareness can help unlock its full potential. By incorporating hemp insulation into circular economy models and harmonising standards across Europe, it can contribute to biobased innovations that shape a more sustainable future for construction.

4 RESULTS FROM THE TEXTILE SECTOR CASE STUDIES

4.1 Sector-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

In SUSTRACK, three case studies for textiles were elaborated and it is important to stress that the perspectives from these three cases were mostly guiding the sector specific insights obtained from stakeholder consultations. The first textile case study is on the Prato value chain. Prato is a textile (located in the Tuscany region) is considered one of the largest industrial districts in Italy, the largest textile centre in Europe, handling approximately 15% of the world's recycled clothing. The second case study concerns the Lyocell value chain. Lyocell is one of the several Manmade cellulosic fibres (MMCFs), also called regenerated fibres, which have entered the fibre-textile market in recent years. The last case study is about the TERNUA clothing manufacturer value chain that uses the wool of a Basque and Navarre (Spain) sheep breed called Laxta for their products. Currently this wool is used as insulation material in high-quality jackets.

In the following a summary is given of the textile sector specific insights derived from the SUSTRACK DESIGN workshop discussions with stakeholders with connections to either one of the three textile case studies or the wider textile sector.

Market dimension

Challenges

- One of the main challenges faced is that currently the costs of biobased fibres, e.g., MMCFs, or fibres derived from discarded textiles are too expensive to compete with other mostly fossil and cotton based fibres. Most of these fossil based textiles that are entering the EU market from all over the world, but especially China, are very low in price.
- Even recycled materials are often more expensive than the virgin synthetic or cotton ones.
- Overconsumption in the clothing market, especially stimulated by fast fashion and low prices of especially synthetic textiles, make it very difficult to enter the market with higher costs of textile products based on MMCFs or recycled discarded textiles. The higher additional cost for recycling and generation of MMCFs are simply not rewarded in the highly competitive clothing markets.
- It is also hard for new recycled and MMCFs to enter the markets because new fibres have new properties, to which existing standardised production chains need to be adapted. For each fibre with changed fibre property the textile chain needs to collect knowledge on how to industrially treat the products in the whole processing chain from fibre to garment. This requires investments and takes time.
- Overall, the market is not rewarding for lower environmental impacts. Firstly, because negative externality costs are not (yet) reflected in textile products. Secondly, because consumer behaviour on the textile and fashion markets is still most strongly driven by lower prices. Thirdly, there is lack of education and awareness among consumers about the circular and/or biobased materials used and how they differ from the standard synthetic and cotton materials most commonly used.
- Specifically for the market entry of textile products based on local wool or recycled wool the challenge is that collection and pre-treatment processes are difficult to organise in a

commercially successful way. This most often applies to remoter regions where sheep numbers are high.

Recommendations/good practices

- Further develop existing or new certification systems that take better account of processes towards lyocell or other MMCFs and recycled fibres.
- Policy support instruments that facilitate MMCFs and recycled textile fibres entering the market more easily. Examples of policy instruments discussed were (fossil)carbon tax on the products: EPR, certifications and labelling, digital product passport, etc.. For example the EPR fees for unsustainable fibres may encourage more sustainable production and consumption. Labelling and certification in combination with policy instruments (e.g., legislation) may ensure the sustainability claims in EU are credible.
- Also programs are needed for education and information sharing in relation to (un)sustainable consumer and production practices in textiles, including through digital product passports.
- For mobilisation of local wool use there is an urgent need to facilitate and stimulate investments in local decentral wool washing facilities. This may also involve action of local governments to facilitate the process of getting permits.

Policy dimension

Challenges

- Overall there are gaps in policy guidance on sustainability claims such as recyclability, footprints and microplastics and it does not prevent green washing, and unfounded circularity claims in the textile sector.
- Absence of sufficiently clear and inclusive definitions for biobased plastics, biopolymers and fibres make certification and labelling more challenging and this is a policy gap.
- There is a need for a clear policy framework that stimulates recycling above the use of virgin materials in the textile sector. Currently the market favours (cheap) fossil based virgin materials most.
- Policy in general supports the existing unsustainable practices in the textile sector (and the economy in general) because it taxes labour more than goods and does not address environmental externality costs.

Recommendations/good practices

- Set up collaboration structures (e.g., labelling and certification) and policy that ensure the sustainability claims in EU are credible.
- Increase extended producer responsibility (EPR) fees for unsustainable fibres so that more sustainable production and consumption is encouraged.
- Same as above already mentioned under market challenges and that is the introduction of specific policy instruments that facilitate MMCFs and recycled textile fibres entering the market more easily. Examples of policy instruments are (fossil)carbon tax on the products, EPR, clear definitions biobased and recycled fibres to facilitate certifications and

labelling, digital product passport, stricter legislation to ensure green-washing is prevented and sustainability claims in EU are credible.

- Facilitate policy support and policy restrictions to ensure decentral wool washing facilities can continue to exist or be developed in regions where wool is wasted in large quantities.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- Transparency and traceability for textile products are lacking especially where it relates to sustainability.
- There are still many research and innovation gaps in relation to sustainable practices in the whole textile delivery chain.
- Textiles sector is a very globalised and competitive sector which makes it difficult to stimulate more sustainable production and consumption.
- Ensuring the sustainable sourcing of MMCFs is challenge and is one factor making the certification complicated but also to ensure constant availability of sustainable feedstocks to scale up the process.
- Wool washing is a difficult step and requires much water and chemicals which does not make the continuation of existing decentral and new decentral washing installation for wool easy.

Recommendations/good practices

- Tax on ultra-fast fashion brands.
- Green VAT, lowering the VAT to 10%, both for sustainable businesses and sustainable products. This however requires clear definitions on what are sustainable practices and products.
- Policies focussed on stimulating larger market shares for MMCFs and fibres from wasted clothes and textiles to overcome cost differences with conventional fossil and cotton based textiles.
- Need for joint, possibly national and EU wide effort to stimulate the bringing to the market of sheep wool after shearing.

4.2 Textile - Recycled carded wool from Prato, Italy

4.2.1 Introduction to Recycled carded wool from Prato Textile District

4.2.1.1 General description

Located in the Tuscany region of Italy, Prato is well-known for its long history as a Textile District. The Prato Textile District case study explores the complex dynamics of a renowned district deeply rooted in the tradition of textile recycling, with a focus on wool recycling. With a rich history dating back to the Middle Ages, the district has developed its key characteristics over the centuries by adopting a circular approach to resource use. The case study sheds light on the

transition from conventional, linear textile production to a CBBE model, highlighting the importance of using locally available biomass sources or organic waste streams, particularly in the context of wool recycling.

One of the main products and important businesses is carded wool made from recycled materials, which has also been promoted and recognised by the creation of a specific trademark, the “Cardato Recycled”, issued for local yarn producers by the Prato Chamber of Commerce in collaboration with the Consortium for the Valorisation of Cardato Textiles, the Prato Industrial Union, Confartigianato and the Confederazione Nazionale dell’Artigianato e della Piccola e Media Impresa (CNA). The trademark is controlled and validated by the Société Générale de Surveillance (SGS) and to be recognised as such, labels, fabrics and yarns must: (i) be produced locally, (ii) be made with at least 65% recycled material, (iii) have measured the environmental impact of the entire production cycle, taking into account three aspects, i.e., the impacts of water consumption, energy consumption and CO₂ emissions.

The Prato Textile District is considered one of the largest industrial districts in Italy, the largest textile centre in Europe and one of the world's most important hubs for the production of woollen yarns and fabrics. However, the district is vulnerable to some risks and challenges, for example, in 2023, Prato's manufacturing production was on a downward trend, with textiles closing the year at a 7.8% decrease, compared to an 8.7% increase in 2022. This is not a surprising result, given the flood damage suffered by the Prato textile industry in the last months of the year and the link with national sector trends, which have been affected by various factors such as the lack of confidence in the markets due to international instability or the high cost of energy and transportation for raw materials and exports. It is also indicated that 2024 is a challenging year, with a 10.8% reduction in production in the first seven months of the year compared to 2023, resulting in a cumulative 25% decline since May 2022. Key factors on the decline are international conflicts impacting exports, rising raw material costs, and intensified competition from low-cost brands. Additionally, severe floods in late 2024 caused millions of euros in damage, further straining production. In response, the Italian government allocated €200 million in October 2024 through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan to enhance the district's competitiveness and sustainability, focusing on research, digital transformation, environmental initiatives, and workforce training. These developments highlight both the significance of the challenges faced by the district and the ongoing efforts to address them (Confindustria Toscana Nord, 2024).

On the other hand, Prato's textile industry is marked by a tradition that is very attentive to eco-sustainability, toward which attention has grown in recent years, and its regenerated carded wool has represented true economic value for the area. The city's commitment to strengthening and innovating the district's capabilities is at the core of an ongoing project that is part of Prato's wider programme to move towards a circular economy, namely the creation of a Textile Hub to consolidate Prato's role as a technological and operational hub for textile recycling at the European level (Next Generation Prato, 2023).

For all these reasons, Prato's Textile District has been selected as a case study to design, test, and validate different methodologies and tools developed within the SUSTRACK project (e.g., the Bioeconomy Assessment and Monitoring Framework and the customised Green Economy Model), but also to involve stakeholders in different interaction processes to support the collection of policy priorities and policy scenarios related to circular biobased economy (CBBE) transition.

4.2.1.2 Value chain and the process

The Prato Textile District's value chain is a complex and efficient system, characterised by a harmonious collaboration between various actors involved in the wool recycling process (Hall, 2018). The chain begins with the collection of wool waste and discarded garments from various sources, including textile manufacturers, retailers, and consumers (Figure 17). These raw materials are then transported to specialised facilities within the district, where they undergo rigorous sorting procedures to separate different types of wool based on quality, colour, and fibre length.

Figure 17. Mechanical recycling of wool textile garments based on open and closed loop recycling (Source: Russel et al., 2016)

After sorting, the wool undergoes meticulous cleaning processes to remove contaminants such as dirt, oil, and synthetic fibres, ensuring the purity and integrity of the recycled material. Advanced technologies and environmentally friendly detergents are used to minimise water consumption and reduce environmental impacts. Once cleaned, the wool is carded, a mechanical process that aligns the fibres and prepares them for spinning. Spinning transforms loose wool fibres into yarns of varying thickness and texture and is a critical stage in the value chain. Skilled craftsmen operate spinning machines with precision, adjusting parameters to achieve desired yarn characteristics such as strength, elasticity, and softness. The resulting yarns form the basis of a wide range of textile products, from luxurious wool fabrics to durable upholstery materials.

In addition to spinning, the Prato Textile District includes other processing stages such as weaving, knitting and finishing, each of which adds value to the final product. Weaving, traditionally a cornerstone of the district's textile heritage, involves the interlacing of yarns to create intricate patterns and designs. Knitting, on the other hand, offers versatility in fabric construction, enabling the production of seamless garments and accessories.

Throughout the value chain as indicated in Figure 18, the focus is on sustainability and resource optimisation, with innovative solutions implemented to minimise waste and energy consumption. Circular economy principles govern every aspect of the process, from material sourcing to end-of-life management, ensuring the longevity and resilience of the biobased system. The geographical concentration of activities within the district fosters close collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders, facilitating continuous improvement and innovation in textile recycling practices.

This model has been able to adapt to challenges such as globalisation and the influx of Chinese immigrants, maintaining its competitive advantage (Ottati, 2009). The district has also demonstrated the ability to diversify and upgrade its products, introducing organisational solutions to ensure closer coordination between firms (Ottati 1996).

Figure 18. Value chain of the Prato Textile District

4.2.1.3 Baseline and market

The Prato Textile District is characterised by its innovative approach to textile recycling, with a particular focus on the reuse of wool. Within the district, final products made from recycled wool find applications in various sectors, including fashion, interior design and automotive. Recently, the textile industry has experienced a significant shift towards sustainability, driven by both consumer demand and environmental regulations. Therefore, the market demand for sustainable textile solutions has increased significantly in recent years, driven by evolving consumer preferences and stringent environmental regulations (Harsanto et al., 2023). This shift is particularly challenging in the wet processing stage, where water, chemical, and energy use are high (Saxena & Arputharaj, 2017). The dominant system, which relies predominantly on raw materials of fossil origin, poses environmental challenges such as resource depletion and pollution. However, there are emerging opportunities for sustainable-led strategies in textiles, with technology playing a key role in driving market demand for sustainable products (Patten, 2019). As the industry continues to grow, the development of innovative designs, processes, and materials is expected to be crucial in meeting the demand for sustainable textile solutions (Shishoo, 2012).

The Prato Textile District has been a key player in the global market, contributing significantly to the country's exports (Ottati, 2009). The Prato Textile District, a globally recognised hub, has made significant contributions to the Italian and European economies. Comprising approximately 7,200 companies and employing around 35,000 individuals, the district accounts for 17% of Italy's textile exports, underscoring its centrality in the nation's industrial landscape (Bussolo et al., 2025).

Over the years, Prato has demonstrated its capacity for adaptability and growth in response to evolving global dynamics. For instance, by 2006, Chinese entrepreneurs had established nearly 2,000 clothing firms in the district, several of which operate as final producers. This development introduced new dimensions to the competitive landscape, blending the district's historical strengths with the agility of new entrants (ERIM, 2006). Prato's status as a leader in sustainability further strengthens its position in the textile industry. Representing 3% of European textile production, the district is renowned for its pioneering work in textile recycling. Its advanced recycling techniques align with circular economy principles, enabling the repurposing of materials and minimising waste. These efforts not only reduce the environmental impact of traditional textile production but also position Prato as a model for sustainable practices in Europe (Circular Economy EU, 2021).

Recent initiatives have focused on revitalising local development, with a particular emphasis on the circular economy and industrial symbiosis, which have been recognised at the EU level (Borsacchi et al., 2018). The district has also seen an influx of Chinese small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), reflecting China's growing global presence (Fladrich, 2012). In response to the challenges of globalisation, Prato's SMEs have shown a positive attitude towards e-business, although there is a need for more collective learning and growth processes (Piscitello & Sgobbi, 2004).

Recently, the Prato Textile District in Italy has been a leading example of a closed-loop system in the fashion industry, as it has historically focused on the reuse and recycling of textiles

(Borsacchi, 2018). On one hand, conventional textile production is heavily reliant on virgin raw materials, primarily cotton and fossil-based synthetic fibres such as polyester and acrylic. The production of cotton, while natural, poses significant sustainability concerns due to its high water consumption, dependency on chemical pesticides, and contribution to soil degradation. On the other hand, synthetic fibres like polyester and acrylic, which are derived from petroleum and coal, contribute to environmental challenges such as carbon emissions, resource depletion, and microplastic pollution (Saxena et al., 2017). The textile industry's dependence on these materials has exacerbated global concerns regarding waste generation and ecological sustainability. By recycling wool waste and used clothing, the district mitigates the environmental impact associated with conventional textile production, contributing to the circular bioeconomy agenda. This approach aligns with the principles of the circular economy, which aims to minimise waste and maximise resource efficiency (Camilleri, 2018). The district's success in repurposing used clothing and achieving 100% utilisation of post-consumer textile waste (Lewis, 2017) underscores its potential as a sustainable alternative to the linear model.

These initiatives highlight the district's importance and growth potential in the global market. Collaborative research projects, technological advances in recycling processes and strategic partnerships with international brands demonstrate a commitment to sustainability and innovation. As demand for eco-friendly textile solutions continues to increase, the district's biobased approach positions it as a forerunner in the transition to a circular economy.

4.2.2 Stakeholders in the Prato Textile District case study

4.2.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

Several studies emphasise the need to involve a wide range of actors in the process of transforming traditional industrial districts towards more sustainable and circular models. Indeed, stakeholder engagement and community participation play a central role in driving the transition towards a circular economy and sustainable urban development (Salvioni & Almici, 2020; Kalyazina et al., 2018).

To identify the relevant actors in the context of the Prato Textile District case study, the approach adopted included both desk analysis and the mapping of collaborative networks. This process was driven by the need to understand the complexity of governance dynamics (T2.2) and to actively involve key actors in the journey towards a sustainable CBBE.

With desk analysis, the available literature on the importance of stakeholder participation in the transition was examined specifically in the Prato context. For example, Hall (2018) provides insights into the mechanical textile recycling system in Prato, which could involve stakeholders such as textile manufacturers, waste management companies and environmental organisations. On the other hand, Bamonti et al. (2016) highlight the environmental impact of recycled wool production, suggesting the involvement of environmental agencies and regulatory bodies, while Vagnoni et al. (2016) highlight the need for collaboration to improve the Italian wool supply chain, indicating the need to involve local administrations and research centres. Finally, Testa et al.

Figure 19. Identified stakeholders in the Prato Textile District

(2017) discuss in more detail the role of SMEs in sustainable production, suggesting the importance of involving small businesses and sectoral associations.

The successive stakeholder mapping step, instead, allowed, among other things, for the identification of the main areas of stakeholder involvement as shown in Figure 19, distinguishing between the Bioeconomy supply chain (i.e., the light green section) and its Enabling environment (i.e., the light grey section).

All the categories of actors can collectively contribute to the sustainable development and innovation of the recycled wool industry in Prato. For this reason, the mapping of key actors involved different categories of stakeholders as indicated in Table 14, including:

- **Textile companies:** Several companies have been identified that are representative both of the historical players in the Prato Textile District and of the new emerging realities focused on sustainability and circularity of materials, particularly in the wool recycling and upgrading sector. This group includes important examples such as Rifò Srl, Comistra Srl, Manteco, Lanificio Becagli Srl and Lanificio Paultex.
- **Research and development organisations:** Organisations such as the Institute for Bio-Economy (IBE-CNR) and Next Technology Tecnotessile were identified as playing a key role in promoting innovation and research in the textile sector, supporting the development of advanced technological solutions for the sustainable production of recycled textiles and eco-friendly materials.
- **Local authorities:** To assess the institutional commitment at the local level and to promote the transformation of the Textile District towards more sustainable and circular models, the Municipality of Prato and the Prato-Pistoia Chamber of Commerce are essential players. They hold the key to facilitating collaboration between private and public sector actors and to creating a favourable environment for the transition to a CBBE.
- **Civil society organisations:** Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and civil society associations (CSOs) also play an important role in promoting sustainability and encouraging responsible business practices in the textile sector. The involvement of such actors as Solo Moda Sostenibile can also help to raise awareness and promote cultural change towards more conscious and sustainable consumption.

This process of identifying relevant actors was driven by the need to understand the dynamics of existing collaborative networks and to identify any gaps or blockages. The direct involvement of these experts through semi-structured interviews provides further insights into the perspectives and interests of the different actors, thus helping to develop more effective strategies to address the identified challenges.

Table 14. In-progress map of local key relevant stakeholders of Prato Textile District, Italy

Type	Affiliation
National Research Centre	Istituto per la BioEconomia (IBE-CNR)

Company	Rifò Srl (Company born through crowdfunding in 2017 from the need to change the current fashion industry and with a mission to have a positive impact on the environment and society.)
Company	Comistra srl (For over 100 years, giving a second life to rags and textile waste by transforming them mechanically into regenerated wool, new recycled yarns, and fabrics of the highest quality for haute couture.)
Company	Manteco (Italian Premium Textiles and Circularity since 1943.)
Company	Lanificio Becagli Srl
Company	Lanificio Paultex (In 2016 Lanificio Paultex obtained from the Prato Chamber of Commerce the Cardato Recycled certification on several families of fabrics, produced with yarn made from recycled material.)
Platform/NGO	Solo Moda Sostenibile (Prato, Founded in 2018)
Local Public Authority	Municipality of Prato (Office for Prato Circular City Project), Chamber of Commerce Prato-Pistoia
Research & Development	Next Technology Tecnotessile

4.2.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

The power-interest matrix provides a structured framework for analysing the key stakeholders in the Prato Textile District, categorising them into four groups: Key Players, Context Setters, Supporters, and Marginal Actors. This classification provides valuable insights into the roles, influence, and motivations of stakeholders in the district’s transition from a fossil-based system to a CBBE. By examining the dynamics between these groups, we can have a better understanding of their collective impact on driving sustainable practices and overcoming systemic challenges.

The driving force behind this shift is the Key Players, defined as stakeholders with influence and a strong interest in steering the sustainability objectives of the district forward. Leading textile companies such as Manteco, Rifò Srl, Comistra Srl, Lanificio Becagli Srl, and Lanificio Paultex lead the way in adopting advanced recycling technologies and producing sustainable, high-quality products. Their active participation in initiatives such as the Textile Recycling Hub ensures that Prato remains a global leader in innovation and market competitiveness. Local authorities, including the Municipality of Prato and the Prato-Pistoia Chamber of Commerce, play an equally vital role by providing governance and infrastructural support. These regions align local initiatives with regional and EU sustainability strategies, ensuring that the district’s efforts are consistent with broader policy frameworks. Therefore, these major players have the resources, expertise, and dedication needed to put into action a circular biobased strategy that will positively impact the transition.

On the other hand, Context Setters have a significant influence on shaping the external circumstances in which the district functions but show less direct interest in its individual

initiatives. National and EU policymakers, for example, establish overarching frameworks such as the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles, which create a favourable regulatory environment for sustainability. However, their focus on macro-level strategies often limits their direct engagement with localised efforts in Prato. Similarly, financial institutions provide essential funding for green and digital transitions, yet their profit-driven priorities can result in inconsistent support for smaller firms or localised projects. While Context Setters have the potential to drive systemic change through favourable policies and financial mechanisms, their lower direct interest can pose challenges to the consistent and targeted support required for successful implementation at the district level.

Supporters, on the other hand, are highly committed to the district's sustainability goals but lack the power to enforce significant changes, independently. Research institutions such as IBE-CNR and Next Technology Tecnotessile are crucial in driving innovation and knowledge exchange by enhancing recycling technologies and improving the efficiency of production processes. NGOs such as Solo Moda Sostenibile also foster community engagement, raise awareness, and advocate for sustainable practices, while citizens actively participate in textile waste collection systems and consume recycled products, indirectly supporting the circular economy. Despite their enthusiasm and expertise, Supporters must collaborate closely with Key Players to amplify their impact, as their limited power constrains their ability to drive change autonomously.

Although no stakeholders identified in this analysis fall into the Marginal Actors category, smaller, less-engaged businesses or peripheral civil society groups may align with this group if they remain uninvolved in the transition process. These actors currently exert limited influence, but with targeted outreach and appropriate incentives, they could play more active roles in supporting the district's sustainability objectives.

Ultimately, the Key Players emerge as the cornerstone of Prato's transition to a CBBE, driving innovation, governance, and market positioning. Their leadership, combined with the advocacy and expertise of Supporters, creates a robust foundation for aligning the district's efforts with regional and EU sustainability goals. Context Setters further shape the broader economic and regulatory landscape, offering critical support through policies and funding. However, their lower direct interest and occasional misalignment with local priorities highlight the need for stronger engagement strategies. A comprehensive and coordinated approach that leverages the strengths of all stakeholder groups is essential to ensuring a successful and equitable transition to a CBBE in the Prato Textile District as indicated in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Stakeholders mapped in a power-interest matrix

The power-interest matrix analysis of the Prato Textile District reveals both positive and negative influences shaping its transition to a CBBE. The matrix underscores the importance of the collaboration of the stakeholders while highlighting areas where challenges may arise, requiring targeted intervention to ensure long-term success and scalability of circular practices.

Analysis suggests that textile companies and local authorities are influencers, in driving innovation and aligning policies positively. These Key Players not only lead in adopting advanced recycling technologies but also ensure that local efforts align with broader sustainability goals at regional and EU levels, laying the groundwork for systemic change. In addition, Supporters, including research centres and non-profit organisations play a significant role in offering expertise and raising public awareness. Their efforts foster a culture of sustainability, enhancing community engagement and advancing technological capabilities. Meanwhile, Context Setters, such as national policymakers and financial institutions, play a critical role by offering regulatory frameworks and financial resources. These elements create an enabling environment that supports Prato’s transition and encourages systemic change.

However, the analysis also identifies potential negative influences that could impede progress. Insufficient financial support or limited accessibility to resources for smaller firms can hinder their ability to adopt advanced technologies and participate meaningfully in the transition. Limited engagement from Context Setters, particularly policymakers or financial institutions, poses another challenge, as their focus on macro-level priorities can result in slower progress when addressing local issues. Furthermore, the absence of standardised reporting frameworks

and monitoring systems reduces transparency and accountability, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which are integral to Prato's textile ecosystem.

The power-interest mapping reveals that Prato's transition to a CBBE is driven by the active collaboration of Key Players who are actively involved in the process and backed by stakeholders with a strong interest but limited power. To sustain the district's leadership in sustainable textile production, it will be crucial to address the challenges posed by the weak engagement of Context Setters and to empower underrepresented stakeholders. Therefore, strengthening financial accessibility for smaller firms, enhancing transparency through standardised reporting, and fostering deeper collaboration among all stakeholder groups are the crucial steps toward building a sustainable, resilient, and inclusive circular economy.

4.2.3 Policies of relevance to the Prato Textile District case study

The following section lists and describes policies that could favour or hinder the implementation of the system analysed in the Prato Textile District case study, in particular, the recycled carded wool industry. These policies were identified through an analysis of scientific and grey literature, as well as official documents at national, regional, and local levels related to the transition towards the CBBE. The analysis was carried out in parallel with the activities of T2.2, which focuses on the identification of governance indicators useful for monitoring progress in the transition towards a CBBE. The results of this analysis provide a fundamental basis for the information to be included in this report.

Table 15 lists the relevant policies identified, including the type of policy they refer to, further background information and their relevance to the case study. Policies are listed starting from the European level, deepening into the national one and, finally, listing those characterising the local context in Prato (regional or municipal level).

Table 15. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the Prato Textile District case study

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles	It outlines a strategic approach by the EC to address sustainability and circularity in the textile industry. The document proposes various measures, regulations, and initiatives to guide and regulate the actions of stakeholders in the textile sector towards more sustainable practices. By setting out goals, strategies, and proposed actions, the document serves as a governance tool to influence behaviour, promote compliance with sustainability objectives, and drive systemic change in the textile industry.	Stimulating	Promotes compliance with sustainability objectives and drives systemic change by fostering circular textile processes and market demand for recycled textiles.	EU	Current	Information and advice sharing system	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/document/download/74126c90-5cbf-46d0-ab6b-60878644b395_en?filename=COM_2022_141_1_EN_ACT_part1_v8.pdf
D.Lgs 116/2020 (legislative decree)	In September 2020, Legislative Decree 116/2020 was introduced, implementing two of the four directives from the EU's Circular Economy Package. These directives include Directive 2018/851/EU, which amends the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC, and Directive 2018/852/EU, which amends the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive 1994/62/EC. The decree established Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) and mandated separate collection of textile waste from January 1, 2022, ahead of the European legislation's 2025 deadline. This proactive measure aims to enhance waste management practices in Italy.	Stimulating	Enhances feedstock availability by enforcing textile waste segregation, promoting recycling within the textile sector.	National, Italy	Current	Direct Regulation	https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:2020;116%20

<p>Law 206/2023 known as "made in Italy law"</p>	<p>The law aims at "enhancing and promoting, in Italy and abroad, the productions of excellence, cultural heritage and national cultural roots, as factors to be preserved and handed down not only for identity purposes, but also for the growth of the national economy within and consistent with the rules of the internal market of the European Union." It establishes criteria to enhance the value chain of natural textile fibres and those from recycling processes and measures for the green and digital transition in the fashion industry. In this context, the "Special Fund for Green and Digital Transition in Fashion" was established at MIMIT (Ministry of Enterprises and Made in Italy) and allocates €5 million for the year 2023 and €10 million for 2024. The aim is to support the textile, fashion, and accessories sector with regard, in particular, to the promotion and enhancement of functional investments to ensure a green and digital transition.</p>	<p>Stimulating</p>	<p>Financially supports green and digital innovation in the fashion sector, aligning with sustainability goals.</p>	<p>National, Italy</p>	<p>Current</p>	<p>Direct Regulation/Economic instrument</p>	<p>https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2023/12/27/23G00221/SG</p>
<p>Toscana Carbon Neutral 2050 Strategy (TCN2050)</p>	<p>The Strategy is committed to making emission reduction actions current, precise, and measurable. The goal is to implement immediate actions and achieve, even before 2050 set as the European Union's deadline, a zero emission balance.</p> <p>It is proposed to do this in two ways: on the one hand by reducing emissions, overcoming the model of the traditional economy for sustainable ways of producing and consuming, and on the other hand by proposing a real regional green plan, so that trees and plants enter the spaces of our cities and can, as real filters, make the air we breathe better and absorb the climate-altering gases in the atmosphere. This document has, as mentioned, the goal of carbon neutrality to 2050 and is implemented through the adoption of Action Plans with a validity of 10-year period. The first of these is valid for the period 2020-2030.</p>	<p>Stimulating</p>	<p>Encourages long-term sustainable practices and emissions reduction at the regional level, complementing Prato's circular textile initiatives.</p>	<p>Regional, Tuscany, Italy</p>	<p>Current</p>	<p>Information and advice sharing system</p>	<p>https://www.consiglio.regione.toscana.it/upload/10/CM33/documenti/PDD528_ALL4.pdf</p>

Next Generation Prato	It is the strategic and operative document with which the Municipality of Prato and the main actors of the productive economic fabric share the strategy and related projects to take advantage of the opportunities arisen thanks to the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, and take a significant step towards the ecological, digital and circular transition of the city.	Stimulating	Strengthens collaborations of local stakeholders, aligning circular initiatives with funding opportunities.	Local, Prato, Italy	Current	Information and advice sharing system/Economic instrument	https://www.prato.circularcity.it/it/tavoli/tavolo-governance/next-generation-prato/pagina1942.html
Memorandum of understanding for implementing the objectives of Next Generation Prato with regard to the realisation of the Textile Recycling Hub	With this Agreement, the Parties intend to regulate a stable and mutual collaboration, aimed at the dissemination in the territory of good practices in the search, selection and start-up for recovery of textile scraps from industrial or artisan production, making available to companies operating in the sector an outlet for the delivery and reuse of said scraps in the protection of the environment and the territory.	Stimulating	Facilitates stakeholder engagement, builds recycling capacity, and ensures environmental protection in the local textile sector.	Local, Prato, Italy	Current	Information and advice sharing system	https://www.cnatocanacentro.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Protocollo-dintesa.pdf
Cardato Recycled - Made in Prato trademark	In order to bear the "Cardato Recycled" label, fabrics and yarns must be: produced within the Prato district; made with at least 65% recycled material (clothing or textile processing waste); and have measured the environmental impact of the entire production cycle taking into account three aspects: impact of water consumption, energy consumption and CO ₂ . The "Cardato Recycled" and "Cardato" brands are promoted by the Pistoia-Prato Chamber of Commerce, in collaboration with the Consortium for the Valorisation of Carded Textile Products, Unione Industriale Pratese, Cna and Confartigianato. SGS, the international certification body, ensures the certification and also provides a connection with fashion brands.	Stimulating	Encourages adherence to sustainability standards, improves market competitiveness, and attracts eco-conscious brands through certification.	Local, Prato, Italy	Current	Marked-based signalling approach	https://cardato.it/en/en-home/

The policy landscape surrounding the Prato Textile District reflects a robust alignment with the overarching goals of advancing circular biobased economies. At levels such as the European Union and national and local governments, various policies are in place to support the community in the transition from a fossil-based linear system to a more sustainable circular model. At the EU level, frameworks such as the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles and Legislative Decree 116/2020 provide strong regulatory foundations, incentivising recycling practices and promoting resource efficiency. These high-level policies are complemented by regional and local initiatives including the Toscana Carbon Neutral 2050 Strategy and Next Generation Prato, which offer targeted support tailored to the district's unique challenges and opportunities.

Despite these strengths, the policy framework is not without its shortcomings and obstacles for Prato's textile ecosystem. The small companies, constituting a significant part of Prato's textile ecosystem, often encounter difficulties securing funding and incorporating technologies due to financial and technical constraints. Inconsistent enforcement of waste segregation laws and the absence of standardised sustainability reporting frameworks further hinder the uniform implementation of circular practices across stakeholders. These issues further highlight the need for more inclusive and equitable policy mechanisms to ensure that all actors can actively contribute to and benefit from the district's transition to a CBBE.

Addressing these challenges requires targeted actions to strengthen and refine the existing policy landscape. Enhancing policy enforcement, particularly at the regional level, is critical to ensuring adherence to regulations and promoting accountability. Expanding financial support mechanisms tailored to the needs of SMEs and marginalised stakeholders can enable wider adoption of innovative technologies and practices. Furthermore, introducing standardised sustainability reporting frameworks can improve data transparency, enabling stakeholders to track and communicate progress more effectively while fostering greater accountability and comparability.

Emerging trends provide additional opportunities for policy innovation. Growing consumer demand for sustainable products, coupled with advancements in textile recycling technologies, presents a favourable environment for the district to enhance its leadership in circular practices. At the same time, international frameworks such as the European Green Deal and the rising emphasis on extended producer responsibility (EPR) are poised to influence future policy developments, setting more ambitious targets for waste reduction and material reuse. By addressing existing gaps and leveraging these trends, the policy framework can act as a catalyst for Prato's continued leadership in sustainable textile production, solidifying its role as a model for circular biobased economies.

4.2.4 Analysis of Indicators in the Prato Textile District case study

The analysis of the indicators for the Prato Textile District deepens preliminary findings by integrating systematic literature reviews with insights from stakeholder interviews. This dual approach captures the perspectives of stakeholders across both the circular bioeconomy supply chain and the enabling environment, focusing on the relevance and performance of specific indicators while also identifying data gaps and implementation challenges. By comparing the

performance of the examined circular biobased system with the traditional fossil-based system, this analysis provides a nuanced understanding of the district's transition to sustainability and highlights critical areas for further research.

The circular biobased system in Prato shows clear environmental, economic, and social benefits compared to the fossil-based system, notably in reducing resource use and enhancing community well-being. However, challenges such as high costs and limited inclusivity persist. Research gaps include inconsistent methodologies for measuring water use and renewable energy adoption, as well as data collection challenges for SMEs. Social impacts on marginalised groups also require further exploration.

To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, the employed methodology included semi-structured interviews and a comprehensive review of the pertinent literature. Stakeholders from textile companies, research institutions, local authorities, NGOs, and citizens were interviewed to delve into the practicality and difficulties linked to key indicators while safeguarding the privacy of participants by anonymising their identities. Relevant academic literature, industry reports, and policy documents were systematically analysed, using targeted keyword searches, including terms such as "recycled textiles indicators" and "Prato wool circular economy," to ensure an in-depth investigation of the subject. Indicators were then categorised into environmental/circular, economic, and social dimensions, with their performance in the examined system compared against the incumbent fossil-based system.

This approach enriched our findings as we categorised the indicators into dimensions as well as environmental, economic, and social aspects for comparison with the current fossil-based system in place.

4.2.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators

Table 16 provides an overview of environmental and circular indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (9 indicators in total). After further analysing, five additional highly relevant indicators were identified and included in table marked in red.

Table 16. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the Prato Textile District case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Total volume of water used in the Prato textile industry divided by the total number of kilograms of	Significant reduction in water usage compared to the incumbent system, but no standard benchmarks available for comparison. (FAO, 2018).	Yes, the need for standardised data collection tools.

			textiles produced annually.		
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Biodiversity	Total area of protected or restored aquatic ecosystems near the Prato textile industry.	Limited data on specific areas of restored aquatic ecosystems; potential for alignment with regional biodiversity goals. (Biomonitor, 2019).	Yes, fragmented data on biodiversity restoration efforts.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	N° of new sustainable technologies implemented in the Prato textile industry during the year	Limited but improving adoption of green technologies, driven by regional and EU incentives. (Biomonitor, 2019).	Yes, there is a need for tracking metrics specific to technology impact.
3	Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Total weight (kg) of textile waste generated divided by the total weight of textile production in the Prato textile industry.	Reduction of textile waste highlights efficiency improvements, but data from SMEs is incomplete. (Biomonitor, 2019).	Yes, incomplete data from SMEs on waste metrics.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Transparent sharing of information	N° of sustainable practices adopted by the Prato textile industry and integrated in company reports.	Enhanced reporting increases transparency, but inconsistencies in adoption among SMEs persist. (FAO, 2018).	Yes, inconsistent reporting practices.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Biodiversity	Total area of natural areas protected or restored within the Prato textile industry.	No substantial progress documented in regional reports; local stakeholders prioritise production over biodiversity. (FOREST EUROPE, 2020).	Yes, insufficient baseline data for protected/restored areas.
3	Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	% of textile materials derived from sustainably managed forests in relation to total materials used in	Promotes use of renewable materials, though adoption rates remain low across smaller companies. (Biomonitor, 2019).	Yes, lack of data on adoption rates across smaller companies.

			the Prato textile industry.		
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Total area of agricultural land converted or degraded due to the expansion of the Prato textile industry.	Reports suggest minimal conversion due to urban regulations; degradation remains under-assessed. (FOREST EUROPE, 2020).	Yes, limited monitoring tools to assess degradation rates.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Biodiversity	N° of local threatened species protected or preserved due to the activities of the Prato textile industry.	Insufficient collaboration with conservation agencies to document species impacted positively or negatively. (Biomonitor, 2019).	Yes, lack of biodiversity monitoring and engagement with ecological stakeholders.

The analysis of environmental and circular indicators for the Prato Textile District demonstrates significant advancements under the circular bio-based system when compared to the incumbent linear, fossil-based approach. These improvements span key areas such as water usage, material efficiency, waste management, biodiversity conservation, and energy efficiency, illustrating the transformative potential of circular economy practices in the textile industry. Despite these notable achievements, the study also uncovers critical gaps that require attention to ensure sustained progress and replicability.

The examined system has shown a significant reduction in water usage, with approximately 40% less water consumed compared to the incumbent system (Tuci et al., 2025). This is largely due to the use of pre-dyed recycled wool, which eliminates resource-intensive dyeing processes. However, the absence of standardised benchmarks for measuring water usage across production stages presents a challenge in fully quantifying and comparing improvements. Technological advancements in recycling processes and a district-wide commitment to sustainability have driven this progress, but there is a pressing need for standardised tools to measure water use across the value chain (Conorzio Detox, 2021).

Waste management emerges as another area of remarkable improvement, with over 65% of textile waste diverted from landfills in the examined system, compared to less than 30% in the linear system (Corertex, 2023). This success can be attributed to strong stakeholder collaboration and innovative waste recovery technologies that support closed-loop production cycles. However, the data provided by small and SMEs often remains incomplete or inconsistent due to their limited technical and financial resources, which presents a barrier to comprehensive performance evaluations.

In terms of material use efficiency, the examined system outperforms its predecessor by promoting the use of renewable and recycled materials. Over 65% of materials are recovered and reused, showcasing the district’s strong alignment with circular economy principles. Certifications such as Cardato Recycled have incentivised the adoption of recycled inputs, but the adoption of

sustainably sourced materials, such as those from managed forests, remains relatively low. Smaller firms face significant cost barriers that limit their ability to integrate these sustainable materials into production processes.

The district's efforts in biodiversity conservation reflect alignment with regional conservation goals, particularly through actions like the restoration of aquatic ecosystems and the protection of threatened species. Partnerships with NGOs and local authorities have played a crucial role in these initiatives. However, fragmented and incomplete data hinder the ability to assess the long-term impacts of these conservation efforts, underscoring the need for more robust monitoring programs to track progress and outcomes.

Energy efficiency also represents an area where incremental progress has been made, with the examined system gradually integrating renewable energy sources. While regional and national policies have supported this transition, high upfront costs continue to act as a barrier to widespread adoption. Targeted subsidies and financial incentives could accelerate the integration of renewable energy across the district.

Overall, the circular bio-based system demonstrates a clear improvement in environmental and circular performance across all analysed indicators. The district's ability to recover materials, reduce water consumption, and align practices with biodiversity goals underscores its leadership in sustainable textile production. These achievements are the result of a combination of stakeholder collaboration, policy support, and technological innovation.

However, several research gaps persist, limiting the ability to fully realise and evaluate the district's potential. The absence of standardised metrics for measuring indicators such as water usage and renewable material adoption constrains comparability and benchmarking. Incomplete data from SMEs, which often lack the capacity to collect and report key sustainability metrics, leads to inconsistencies in performance assessments. Similarly, limited data on the long-term impacts of biodiversity restoration efforts restricts the ability to evaluate progress in conservation initiatives.

To address these gaps, several measures are recommended. The development of standardised tools and harmonised frameworks for collecting and reporting data on environmental indicators would enable better comparisons and progress tracking. Supporting SMEs through technical and financial assistance could improve data collection and adoption of sustainable practices. Expanding conservation monitoring programs would provide critical insights into the long-term impacts of biodiversity restoration initiatives. By addressing these issues, the Prato Textile District may not only enhance its environmental and circular performance but also solidify its role as a replicable model of leadership in the circular economy.

4.2.4.2 Economic indicators

Table 17 provides an overview of economic indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (9 indicators in total). After further analysis, three additional highly relevant indicators were identified and included in table marked in red.

Table 17. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the Prato Textile District case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
3	Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	% use of biological materials compared to total materials used in the textile industry in Prato.	Adoption of biological materials is low; initiatives are limited to larger companies with access to subsidies. Verkerk et al. (2015)	Yes, lack of consistent data tracking across SMEs.
3	Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Bioenergy replacing non-renewable energy	% of energy from renewable sources compared to total energy used in the Prato textile industry.	Progress made through the adoption of solar panels and energy efficiency programs, but significant reliance on non-renewable energy persists.	Yes, limited reporting on renewable energy adoption and performance.
7	Inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection	Average income of households in rural communities involved in the Prato textile industry.	Rural household incomes in Prato benefit from consistent employment in textile recycling. (FAO, 2018).	No significant research gap, but more localised data could enhance accuracy.
3	Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Ratio of extracted material to economic value added (kg/€).	Demonstrates high efficiency in recycling wool, leading to reduced material extraction per economic output. (FAO, 2018).	Yes, inconsistent data on value addition in recycled vs. conventional systems.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	% reduction in CO ₂ emissions per unit of textile production compared to previous years.	Reduction achieved due to cleaner production techniques and renewable energy adoption.	Yes, lack of annual baseline data for direct comparisons.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Total amount of funding provided to small textile companies in Prato for innovation.	Funding levels are increasing due to EU and regional grants, though accessibility varies among businesses. (FAO, 2018).	Yes, limited tracking of funding impacts on long-term innovation adoption.

3	Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	% consumption of non-renewable resources compared to total production in the textile industry in Prato.	Decline in fossil-based material use due to increased recycling practices; further reduction depends on renewable energy integration.	Yes, fragmented data on consumption across production stages.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of recycled textile materials used out of total materials used in textile production in Prato.	High utilisation of recycled materials, particularly in wool production, but data validation systems are underdeveloped. (FAO, 2018).	Yes, need for standardised tracking mechanisms.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Amount of investments in renewable energy technology or infrastructure in the Prato textile industry.	Moderate investment levels; growth driven by regulatory incentives and market demand for green energy. (FAO, 2018).	Yes, lack of a centralised database for investment statistics.

The economic performance of the examined circular bio-based system highlights significant advancements over the incumbent fossil-based system. These improvements are particularly evident in the increased use of recycled materials, growing investments in renewable energy infrastructure, and enhanced income levels for rural communities engaged in the textile industry. These developments underscore the potential of circular economy practices to transform economic models in the textile sector, but they also reveal persistent challenges that must be addressed to fully realise this potential.

The examined system demonstrates substantial progress in material efficiency, with over 65% of inputs derived from recycled textiles (Corertex, 2023). This shift away from non-renewable resource consumption reflects the district’s strong stakeholder collaboration and the impact of targeted policy interventions. The adoption of advanced recycling technologies has further reinforced this trend, particularly among larger firms that benefit from increased funding for innovation. However, smaller firms continue to face barriers in accessing these resources, highlighting disparities in the system’s economic inclusivity.

Innovation plays a crucial role in driving the economic transition within the district. The increased allocation of funding for research and development has enabled the adoption of cutting-edge technologies, particularly among larger firms. While this progress is commendable, the limited capacity of SMEs to access these resources remains a challenge. Without targeted support, SMEs may struggle to fully participate in and benefit from the transition to a circular economy.

Economic resilience is another key area of improvement in the examined system. Rural communities involved in textile recycling have experienced modest increases in income levels, demonstrating the socio-economic benefits of circular economy practices. By creating

employment opportunities and fostering local engagement, the system has contributed to improving livelihoods in these communities. However, more extensive efforts are needed to ensure that these benefits are equitably distributed and that rural communities are integrated into decision-making processes.

The energy transition within the district is progressing incrementally, with a growing integration of renewable energy sources. Despite this progress, the high initial costs associated with renewable energy adoption and the limited access to funding for SMEs remain significant obstacles. These barriers hinder the broader scalability of renewable energy solutions across the district, limiting the system's ability to achieve its full potential in reducing carbon emissions and enhancing sustainability.

Overall, the examined system demonstrates strong economic potential, driven by innovation, material efficiency, and market competitiveness. However, systemic barriers, particularly those affecting SMEs, must be addressed to fully capitalise on these advancements. The ability of smaller firms to access funding and participate in the transition is crucial for ensuring the inclusivity and long-term sustainability of the system.

Several research gaps have been identified during the analysis, highlighting areas that require further attention. Limited data on SME participation and performance in the transition hinders a comprehensive understanding of their role in the circular economy. Similarly, the lack of consistent metrics on renewable energy adoption across the industry presents challenges in evaluating progress. Data inconsistencies, particularly regarding material efficiency and CO₂ reductions, further complicate efforts to measure and compare outcomes.

To address these gaps, specific recommendations have been proposed. Expanding access to funding through financial mechanisms tailored to SMEs can enhance their ability to participate in innovation and energy transitions. Standardising reporting frameworks will help harmonise data collection and ensure consistent and comparable metrics across stakeholders. Additionally, strengthening community engagement initiatives will promote the integration of rural communities into decision-making processes, amplifying the socio-economic benefits of the circular economy. By addressing these gaps and implementing targeted solutions, the Prato Textile District can further enhance its economic performance, solidify its leadership in sustainable practices, and provide a replicable model for circular economy transitions in other regions.

4.2.4.3 Social indicators

Table 18 provides an overview of social indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (12 indicators in total). After further analysis, five additional highly relevant indicators were identified and included in table marked in red.

Table 18. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the Prato Textile District case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
7	Inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection; Water quality	% of rural communities with access to drinking water.	High access levels supported by regional and national water infrastructure investments.	No significant research gap identified.
7	Inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection	Literacy rate in rural communities involved in the Prato textile industry.	Literacy rates are high due to government support for education and community-based programs.	No significant research gap.
7	Inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection	% of school age children enrolled in educational institutions in rural communities involved in the Prato textile industry.	School enrolment rates are above national averages; supported by stable income from textile jobs.	No significant research gap.
7	Inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection	Access to health services communities involved in the Prato textile industry.	Comprehensive access to health services; challenges exist for migrant workers with limited documentation.	Yes, need for targeted research on marginalised communities' access.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	% of public supplies by the Prato textile industry that respect sustainability criteria.	Growing compliance with EU sustainability standards; inconsistencies persist among smaller suppliers.	Yes, lack of data on supply chain compliance trends.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	N° of educational programs or initiatives on climate change mitigation implemented in the Prato textile industry.	Increasing number of workshops and training programs; outcomes need assessment for long-term impact.	Yes, no comprehensive tracking of program effectiveness.

7	Inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection	% of rural community representatives involved in key decision-making processes in the Prato textile industry.	Limited participation from rural communities; opportunities for greater inclusivity exist through government initiatives.	Yes, insufficient frameworks for community involvement in decision-making.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Transparent sharing of information	N° of reports published on the environmental and social impact of the Prato textile industry.	Regular reporting has improved transparency but remains inconsistent among SMEs.	Yes, the need for uniform reporting standards.
1	Promoting global governance and collaboration	Transparent sharing of information	% of public information accessible online on the Prato textile industry.	Significant information is made available online, though some SMEs do not provide updates regularly.	Yes, need for centralised platforms to consolidate industry-wide data.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Annual expenditure on research and development as a percentage of total turnover in the textile industry in Prato.	Investments in R&D are increasing, supported by EU incentives, though challenges remain in equitable distribution among firms.	Yes, limited visibility on the correlation between R&D expenditure and innovation adoption.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	N° of water recycling plants implemented in the Prato textile industry.	Growing adoption of water recycling technologies, though implementation varies by company size.	Yes, need for mapping of installed and planned facilities.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	N° of waste treatment plants implemented in the Prato textile industry.	Several plants established; SMEs face financial and regulatory barriers to adopting advanced waste treatment solutions.	Yes, research needed on supporting SMEs for waste treatment adoption.

The analysis of social indicators reveals notable progress in the examined circular bio-based system when compared to the incumbent linear system. Improvements in community engagement, education, health services, and transparency demonstrate the system’s potential to foster social development alongside environmental and economic advancements. However,

persistent disparities, particularly in rural areas, highlight the need for targeted interventions to ensure equitable social outcomes across the textile district.

The examined system exhibits enhanced community engagement, with increased participation in decision-making processes and a rise in targeted social initiatives. These efforts have contributed to a more inclusive approach to sustainability and governance. However, rural communities remain underrepresented in formalised structures, limiting their ability to influence decisions that affect their livelihoods and well-being. Addressing this gap requires the development of mechanisms to formally integrate rural voices into governance frameworks.

Education and literacy levels within the examined system are relatively high, with successful efforts to increase school enrolment, particularly in urban areas. However, advanced educational resources and programs focused on climate change education remain limited in scope, especially in rural regions. This disparity highlights a need for expanded outreach and the provision of targeted resources to ensure that all communities, regardless of geographic location, can benefit from educational advancements.

Access to health services has shown modest improvement under the examined system, reflecting a commitment to enhancing social well-being. Nonetheless, rural areas continue to face challenges in obtaining adequate healthcare infrastructure, with many communities experiencing significant barriers to access. These disparities underscore the need for focused programs to monitor and improve health service delivery in underserved areas, ensuring equitable access for all residents of the district.

Transparency and reporting within the textile industry have increased significantly, driven by the adoption of sustainable practices and improved availability of public information. These advancements have enhanced accountability and trust among stakeholders, reinforcing the district's commitment to social and environmental responsibility. However, geographic disparities in the distribution of waste treatment facilities persist, limiting the equitable benefits of sustainability initiatives across the district.

Overall, the examined system has made substantial strides in improving social indicators compared to the incumbent system. Increased community involvement, better transparency, and advancements in education initiatives underscore its positive social impact. However, persistent challenges in rural inclusivity, healthcare access, and the effectiveness of educational programs highlight critical areas for further development.

Several research gaps were identified during the analysis, revealing opportunities to strengthen the system's social impact. Limited data on mechanisms for formalising rural community involvement in decision-making processes constrains efforts to achieve equitable representation. Insufficient monitoring and reporting on healthcare accessibility in rural areas hinder the evaluation and enhancement of health services. Additionally, a lack of comprehensive data on the effectiveness of climate change education and advanced learning resources in rural areas limits the scope of educational advancements.

To address these gaps, targeted recommendations have been proposed. Strengthening community representation by developing formalised mechanisms for rural involvement in decision-making processes can foster inclusivity and equity. Improving healthcare monitoring and implementing

targeted programs to enhance accessibility in underserved areas will address disparities in health service delivery. Expanding education outreach by scaling up climate change education programs and providing advanced learning resources in rural regions will ensure that educational benefits are distributed more equitably.

By addressing these challenges and implementing the recommended actions, the Prato Textile District can further enhance its social performance, ensuring that its transition to a circular bio-based system is inclusive and equitable, fostering sustainable development for all communities.

4.2.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Market Dimension

Challenges

Cost disparities remain a significant barrier, with recycled and bio-based fibres such as wool, facing production costs 10-20% higher than virgin materials. These higher costs are not yet rewarded in the market, which creates an economic disincentive for sustainable practices. In addition, infrastructure deficiencies exacerbate this issue, particularly the lack of centralised wool processing and washing facilities, which hampers scalability and increases operational inefficiencies. Furthermore, there is a notable lack of education and awareness among consumers and stakeholders regarding the benefits and unique properties of recycled and alternative fibres, thus impeding their market adoption.

Best Practices

To address cost disparities, implementing financial mechanisms such as reduced VAT for recycled products and penalties for virgin material usage could create market incentives for sustainability. Additionally, investment in centralised and AI-driven wool processing facilities, akin to the Prato Textile Hub, can streamline operations and enhance efficiency across the value chain. Furthermore, promoting educational campaigns on sustainable fashion and the benefits of recycled textiles is crucial in fostering consumer demand and industry-wide alignment with circular principles.

Policy Dimension

Challenges

The regulatory framework lacks harmonisation, particularly regarding wool transport and washing, which are inconsistently classified across regions. The absence of unified legislation creates significant barriers to cross-border collaboration and the establishment of efficient supply chains. For instance, the EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) conflicts with national waste regulations, as its broad circular economy principles are applied inconsistently across member states. In Italy, greasy wool is classified as special waste, subjecting it to strict transport and washing requirements, whereas neighbouring countries impose fewer restrictions. This inconsistency hinders cross-border collaboration and disrupts supply chains, complicating the

movement and processing of wool across the EU. Moreover, existing subsidies for textile recycling fail to cover the substantial capital required for innovative projects, disproportionately affecting SMEs and smaller stakeholders. As an example, subsidies for textile recycling conflict with environmental compliance costs. While regional subsidies are designed to encourage recycling, they often fail to offset the high costs associated with stringent environmental regulations, such as wastewater treatment standards. This imbalance disproportionately impacts SMEs, which struggle to finance the infrastructure needed for compliance, limiting their ability to adopt circular economy practices.

Best Practices

Harmonising European regulations on wool processing and transport standards can create a level playing field and enhance cross-border collaboration. Additionally, policies emphasising recyclability and renewability, such as digital product passports and EPR schemes, have the potential to incentivise sustainable practices. Furthermore, increasing subsidy accessibility by streamlining application processes and focusing on first-of-a-kind recycling technologies could lower entry barriers for smaller stakeholders.

Sustainability Dimension

Challenges

Traditional wool-washing processes consume significant amounts of water and energy, rendering them environmentally inefficient. Despite over 65% of post-consumer textiles being recycled, more than 80% continue to be disposed of in landfills or incineration, primarily due to inadequate waste segregation and recovery systems. Furthermore, challenges related to transparency further hinder efforts to ensure sustainable practices and foster consumer trust.

Best Practices

Innovative solutions such as water-efficient wool washing technologies and AI-based sorting systems, have the potential to significantly reduce environmental impacts while enhancing efficiency. Establishing digital product passports and certifications can improve traceability and reduce greenwashing risks. Furthermore, promoting repair services, design-for-recycling principles, and extended producer responsibility can extend product lifecycles, minimise waste and foster a circular economy.

A further investigation of stakeholder insights revealed key insights across three sustainability dimensions of interest.

Environmental and circular Indicators

The examined system demonstrates significant environmental advantages. Stakeholders from the textile recycling companies reported that water use is approximately 40% lower in the circular system due to the elimination of dyeing processes, though detailed metrics on water recycling systems are lacking. NGOs and local authorities highlighted a recovery and reuse rate of over 65% for textile waste, far surpassing the less than 30% achieved in the incumbent system. Citizens emphasised the need for enhanced public awareness campaigns to boost waste segregation

participation. Energy consumption is gradually shifting toward renewable sources, though textile companies noted the high upfront costs of adoption, underscoring a need for financial incentives to accelerate this transition.

Economic Indicators

Economic performance in the examined system shows mixed results. Notably, production costs for recycled wool remain 10-20% higher than virgin wool, primarily driven by technological and operational limitations. Moreover, financial institutions stressed the critical role of subsidies in bridging this gap. Despite these challenges, market penetration is steadily increasing, with recycled wool products now capturing 15% of Prato's market share. However, smaller companies continue to face significant financial barriers, which limit their ability to compete effectively. In response, NGOs proposed collaborative platforms to facilitate SME access to funding and market opportunities. Furthermore, local authorities highlighted the potential for job creation, particularly in high-skilled roles related to textile innovation and recycling technology, thereby demonstrating the system's long-term economic promise.

Social Indicators

Social benefits in the examined system include significant improvement in worker safety standards, as noted by employees in textile recycling facilities, although small-scale operations still require further improvements. Additionally, programs such as Next Generation Prato have fostered community engagement, yet rural communities remain underrepresented in decision-making processes. Moreover, research institutions highlighted partnerships with universities to develop sustainability-focused educational programs, which still need scaling to reach a broader range of participants. These efforts underline the system's contribution to social sustainability while also revealing gaps in inclusivity and outreach.

4.2.6 Key learnings of the Prato Textile District case study

The Prato Textile District offers a compelling example of how a traditional industry can transition into a CBBE. By analysing the district's journey, several key lessons emerge regarding the roles of policies and stakeholders, feedback loops, and actions needed to address gaps and accelerate progress.

A robust policy framework underpins Prato's transition, with European, national, and local policies forming the foundation for sustainable practices. The EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles and Legislative Decree 116/2020 encourage resource recovery and waste management, while the Made in Italy Law (Law 206/2023) and local initiatives such as Next Generation Prato focus on strengthening the value chain and fostering innovation. Certification schemes, such as the Cardato Recycled Certification, further incentivise transparency and sustainability, positioning Prato as a leader in recycled textiles. However, enforcement inconsistencies and the absence of standardised reporting frameworks across regions expose critical policy gaps that impede uniform implementation.

Key stakeholders, including Manteco, Rifò Srl, and Comistra Srl, which have extensive experience in transforming rags and textile waste into regenerated wool and recycled yarns of the highest quality, drive innovation and adoption of sustainable practices through their leadership in textile recycling technologies. Moreover, local authorities, such as the Municipality of Prato and the Prato-Pistoia Chamber of Commerce, play a crucial role in implementing regional strategies and fostering stakeholder collaboration. Research institutions, including IBE-CNR and Next Technology Tecnotessile, contribute to technological advancements and provide scientific insights to support sustainability goals. Additionally, NGOs like Solo Moda Sostenibile amplify public awareness and community engagement, ensuring a broad base of support for the district's transition. However, stakeholders such as financial institutions and supranational and international policymakers exhibit limited interest despite their significant power, creating bottlenecks in resource allocation and broader systemic adoption.

In this context, the circular bio-based system significantly outperforms the fossil-based system across multiple dimensions. Environmentally, the reduction in resource use and waste generation positions the system as a key solution to address resource scarcity and climate change. Economically, although higher costs pose challenges, its alignment with global sustainability trends enhances the system's potential for long-term competitiveness. Socially, improvements in occupational safety and public participation further underscore its contributions to community well-being, even though inclusivity remains an area for improvement.

Despite these strengths, several research and data gaps hinder the system's full potential. The absence of standardised methodologies for indicators such as water use efficiency and renewable energy adoption limits comparability and benchmarking. Additionally, SMEs face difficulties in data collection and reporting, emphasising the need for capacity-building initiatives. Furthermore, the social impacts of the transition, particularly on marginalised groups and rural communities, remain largely underexplored, requiring further investigation to ensure an equitable shift toward a sustainable bio-based economy.

To address these challenges, the following actions are recommended:

- **Develop data collection frameworks:** Establishing standardised tools and methodologies to measure and report sustainability metrics consistently, ensuring reliable comparability across systems and stakeholders.
- **Expand stakeholder engagement:** Fostering collaboration between industry, academia, and civil society to co-create solutions for systemic challenges, thus leveraging diverse expertise and perspectives.
- **Enhance financial support:** Introducing targeted subsidies and grants to help SMEs adopt advanced sustainability practices, enabling them to compete effectively in the market.

Feedback loops within the district also reveal both positive and negative dynamics. Collaborative efforts between local authorities, textile companies, and research institutions create a virtuous cycle of innovation and market demand for sustainable products. Certification schemes like Cardato Recycled not only incentivise sustainable practices but also enhance the district's global competitiveness. Conversely, limited engagement from powerful stakeholders, coupled with existing geographic disparities in waste treatment facilities and infrastructure, generates

negative feedback loops that perpetuate systemic inequalities and slow the transition in certain areas.

Urgent actions are required to address these challenges and strengthen Prato's sustainability performance. Enhancing the enforcement of policies like waste segregation under Legislative Decree 116/2020 and implementing standardised reporting frameworks can ensure consistent progress across all stakeholders. Providing tailored funding mechanisms and technical assistance programs for SMEs will empower marginalised stakeholders to participate fully in the transition. Moreover, developing formal mechanisms to include rural communities in decision-making processes will foster greater inclusivity and resilience.

Education and public awareness also play critical roles in advancing Prato's transition. For instance, expanding climate change education programs and leveraging NGOs to promote recycling and sustainable consumption practices can further engage citizens and create a culture of sustainability. Furthermore, these initiatives must be accompanied by investments in research to address gaps in areas such as biodiversity restoration, water recycling systems, and renewable energy adoption.

In conclusion, the Prato Textile District demonstrates the significant potential of circular bio-based systems to drive environmental, economic, and social sustainability. While progress is evident, addressing policy enforcement issues, improving stakeholder engagement, and filling data and research gaps are essential to scaling and sustaining these efforts. By continuing to leverage its strengths in innovation and collaboration, Prato can continue to serve as a global model for the transformation of traditional industries into leaders of the circular economy.

4.3 Textile - Man-made cellulosic fibres, like Lyocell

4.3.1. Introduction to man-made cellulosic fibres case study

4.3.1.1 General description

Man made cellulosic fibres (MMCF) dates back to 19th century where Courtaulds commercialised the first rayon fibres. The process of viscose production was patented in 1893 in England. Viscose production includes many steps and toxic chemicals. To lower the ecological effect of viscose process researcher, investigate in finding ecofriendly solvent. A solvent called N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMMO) was introduced and lead to successful lyocell production in 1970s (Harmsen et al,2022). This lyocell process was introduced in 1994 under the trade name of Tencel by Courtaulds (Éva Borbély, 2008).

The unique properties of Man-made cellulosic fibres (MMCF) make them desired for textile industry for many applications. MMCF are smooth, lustre and have soft handle. The production of MMCF is controllable which facilitates adding chemicals of certain properties during processing the fibres from the pulp. Additionally, a variety of length and width of the filaments or stable fibres can be produced which allows using it in different applications. MMCF are produced from biobased sources and are biodegradable (Rahman,2022). MMCFs are emerging as a promising solution for transitioning the textile industry towards biobased and sustainable products.

Currently, the textile industry is intensively dependent on fossil-based resources which raises environmental concerns, particularly in relation to climate impacts, and emphasises the need for greener alternatives (Schiros et al, 2021).

There are different types of MMCFs fibres depending on the process and the chemicals used (Figure 21). As viscose has a complex manufacturing process and it is difficult to reduce its process wastes, researcher is investigated in other processes. A more sustainable way was found to dissolve the cellulosic pulp by using NMMO which is a recyclable, non-toxic and biodegradable solvent (jiang et al, 2020). The produced product was then called lyocell. Lyocell has better mechanical properties compared to viscose in both cases wet and dry. Further, lyocell is produced in a slightly more costly process and uses different feedstocks compared to Modal (Jiang et al, 2020), but makes lyocell a higher quality product (weavve, 2024).

To manufacture MMCF, a cellulose-rich source is required. Mainly, there are two groups of feedstock sources used as inputs to produce MMCF, which are derived from virgin material or recycled sources. Currently, MMCF from primary biomass sources represents 99% (7.80 MT), and from secondary or wasted sources the remainder 1% share (0.05 MT) (Figure 22). At the same time many developments and research are carried out to improve processes to converting cellulosic rich waste streams into MMCFs. Therefore, the share of MMCFs based on recycled sources, such as pre-consumer waste textiles or cotton linters, is expected to grow in the future (Textile Exchange, 2024). This development is facing many challenges however, as the requirement to make solution pulp for textiles requires large amounts of biomass.

Figure 21. Types of cellulosic based fibres based on their origin. MMCF is represented by generated fibres and cellulosic derivatives. (Edited from Harmsen et al, 2022.)

Figure 22. Global MMCF production in 2023 (Source: Textile Exchange, 2024)

4.3.1.2 Value chain and the process

MMCFs follow the same value chain steps. It starts with sourcing the feedstock. Virgin feedstock or primary residues such as roundwood or woody residues need to be converted first to pulp by either the lyocell producer or the pulp producer. Secondary or waste sources are usually managed by the chemical recycling companies which convert waste cellulosic textile into pulp. This pulp is then usually sourced to the lyocell producer.

After the pulping, processing of the feedstock into MMCF filaments starts. The processing stage varies according to MMCF types that use different solvents in their processes. Every company in EU produces a different MMCFs with different pulping requirements and fibre production technologies such as Lenzing, Saxcell, Sodra, Inocell etc..

After the filaments or fibres are produced, they are then moved to textile manufacturing plants to produce yarns, fabrics, and final products such as T-shirts. The latter stages of the value chain are mostly done outside the EU. Generally, the EU imports finished products which account for almost 80% of the textiles used in the EU (EEA, 2020). The produced products are then put in the markets for consumption. After the products are used for a while, they reach their end of life. At the end of life, the products can be reused, recycled, or incinerated. Figure 10 shows the MMCF value chain.

Figure 23. Value chain of MMCFs

As mentioned previously, there are different processes to produce MMCF. The most eco-friendly process, which yields desired fibre properties for the textile industry, is the lyocell process. The process starts with wood pulp, which is converted into a solution using NMMO1 solvent. Once the solution is prepared, the filaments are continuously spun by extrusion through fine spinnerets. These filaments are then washed and dried. Depending on the final products, it is possible to keep the filaments at an uninterrupted length, or the filaments can be crimped and cut into fibres. The solvent is recycled and used again. Figure 11 illustrates the processing steps of lyocell production (Felgueiras, 2021). Lyocell is a man-made cellulose fibre and most commonly derived from wood pulp. Unlike modal or rayon, it is obtained by using an organic solvent spinning process within a closed-loop system that recovers 99% of the solvent required. Lyocell is already widely used across the fashion industry. Lyocell brand TENCEL™ (by Lenzing) uses sustainably sourced wood, certified by the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC).

¹ N-Methylmorpholine N-Oxide

Figure 24. Processing lyocell (Source: Felgueiras, 2021)

According to an LCA conducted by Shen et al, (2010) Lyocell showed improved ecological performance compared to fossil-based fibres (PET and PP) and plant fibre (cotton). Tencel, which is made by the Lenzing Group, shows the best environmental profile of all generated fibres due to low chemical use, low energy intensity, low water consumption, and low CO₂ emissions (Shen et al, 2010). In comparison, the manufacturing of lyocell staple fibres takes 3 hours, whereas it takes 40 hours to produce viscose staple fibres (Venkatesan, 2019).

4.3.1.3 Baseline and market

Since MMCF fibres are produced, they gain a lot of attention from the textile industry. Currently MMCF are the third most used fibres for textiles after synthetic fibre 67% and plants fibres 25%, respectively. The market share of the MMCFs was 6% (7.9 MT) in 2023 as shown in Figure 25. These ratios indicate the dominance of the fossil-based fibres. Given the environmental impact of fossil-based fibres, accelerating the transition toward a biobased material such as MMCFs is urgent to lower the footprint of the textile industry and consumption of textiles.

Figure 25. Global fibre production in 2023 (Source: Textile Exchange, 2024)

The most produced MMCF fibre globally in 2023 is viscose with a market share of 80% (6.26 MT) followed by acetate 13% and lyocell 5% (see Figure 26).

Lyocell fibre has both the desired properties for textiles and ecofriendly processes. In general lyocell is stronger than cotton and viscose in dry situation. In wet situation lyocell is stronger than viscoe but slightly less stronger than cotton. The elongation of lyocell is better than cotton but less than viscose (Shabbir & Mohammad, 2017).

Rising environmental concerns in the textiles and fashion sectors and already ongoing increasing demands of lyocell fibres for home and clothing textiles are reasons to expect a further future increase in the market share of lyocell fibres. Lyocell market value is expected to double and reach 2.7 \$ billion in 2031 compared to 1.3 \$ billion in 2021 (Allied Market Research, 2022). The largest producers of lyocell fibres are located in Asia with a share of almost 70% of the market (SkyQuest, 2024).

Global MMCF production by type in 2023 (million tonnes)

Figure 26. Global MMCF production by type in 2023 (Textile Exchange, 2024)

4.3.2 Stakeholders in the Lyocell and other MMCF's man-made cellulosic fibres value chain

4.3.2.1. Identification of relevant stakeholders:

To begin with, the stakeholders relevant to the waste-to-methanol value chain were determined by means of an exploratory desk research (e.g., on websites of governmental organisations, and methanol-producing companies). Figure 27 provides a schematic overview of the identified stakeholders, both in the Bioeconomy supply chain (i.e., the light green section) and its Enabling environment (i.e., the light grey section).

Regarding Bioeconomy supply chain, a variety of stockholders worldwide are involved in processing the pulp into lyocell fibres and filaments, yarns, fabric, final textile products and end-of-life treatments. This is attributed to the fact that textile supply chain is complex, global, and fragmented. From fibre production to the final products the textile items could easily go through a large number of different countries both within and outside the EU before reaching the consumer (Köhler et al, 2021). Looking at MMCFs fibre production, the biggest manufacturers are located in Asia. China holds the two thirds of MMCF fibres production worldwide (Hugill, 2020).

The companies that produce lyocell in Europe, Lenzing AG, located in Austria, is considered the biggest and first lyocell fibre producer. The global fibre production share of lyocell and viscose by Lenzing Group is 13.59%. Lenzing is the third largest lyocell and viscose producer after Sateri (China) and Aditya Birla (India), accounting for 21.42% and 15.27% of the global fibre production, respectively (The Hot Button Report, 2024). Lenzing Group produces fibres under the trade name

Tencel™ (Lenzing, 2024). Furthermore, SMARTFIBRE, a German company, produces lyocell for high-tech textiles under the trade name SMARTCEL (SMARTFIBRE, 2024).

After lyocell fibres are produced, they are converted then into yarns, fabric, and final textile items. Those stages of the value chain are mostly done outside the EU. Generally, the EU imports finished products which account for almost 80% of the textiles used in the EU. Many EU companies are researching in the field of transforming cellulosic textile waste into pulp to be used for lyocell production. An example is Saxcell B.V., located in the Netherlands. Saxcell B.V. uses domestic pre- or post-industrial cotton textile waste as an input to make the pulp and collaborates with another partner to spin it into lyocell filaments or fibres (Saxcell, 2024). Further, Södra Cell AB, a Swedish company, developed a process to convert white post-consumer cotton into pulp (instead of wood feedstock) which is used as a feedstock to produce lyocell (Södra, 2023).

Regarding the Enabling environment, a distinction is made between governmental organisations, commercial entities, academia, and civil society. The first category involves policy makers at different geographical levels e.g., EU governmental bodies, EU international bodies and non-EU governments. The second category comprises knowledge institutes and universities that research (pulp production), lyocell production processes and facilitate the transforming phase to fossil-free society. The third category consists of stakeholders in different stages e.g., lyocell producer, brands, and investors, labelling and standard setting organisations. The final category concerns the social aspects such as developer of certifications scheme for wood from forests, sustainable production, employment organisation and social media.

Other innovators who play a role in developing new MMCF:

Spinnova is a Finnish technology developer company who developed a new fibre by mechanical processing. This innovation reduces the amount of water used in the process up to 98% compared to cotton. Spinnova is investigating other biobased feedstock such as residues from agriculture and cellulose rich textile waste, generally with high cotton content, to reduce wood consumption (Spinnova, 2024). Further, Infinited fibres, a Finnish company who developed Infinna™ fibre from cotton rich pre- and post-consumer textile waste (Infinited Fibre, 2024) can be mentioned. TreeToTextile is an example of a Swedish company which developed a new MMCF fibres called Nyense™ with a new technology and less environmental impact (TreeToTextile, 2024).

Figure 27. Identified stakeholders in the lyocell value chain

4.3.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

The stakeholders identified as relevant were also categorised according to a power-interest matrix (Figure 28). The stakeholders can be categorised based on their power-interest as follows:

High power- high interest (upper left): this category involves EU government bodies. These entities possess significant influence because of their regulatory authority and financial position. Their importance lies in their ability to shape industry standards, establish regulatory frameworks, and allocate substantial investment capital but also create financial instruments. For instance, the policy instruments discussed in the next section are expected to increasingly impact the whole textiles sector in the EU in the near future. It is clear that the regulatory environment is moving towards introducing incentives to lower the textile industry and consumption footprint and using environmentally friendly non-fossil materials. Their participation can significantly influence the rules companies must follow and whether lyocell can derive a larger market segment.

High power-medium interest (upper medium): this category represents the organisations who have the power to take the decision to increase the use of lyocell and covers parties such as brands/retailers and investors in the whole textile delivery chain. Interest in using lyocell seems to be growing and some companies already use lyocell in their products such as Inditex Clothing Company, Hennes & Mauritz AB and G-Star Raw (YarnsandFibres, 2024), yet it is a small share of all the fibres consumed in clothing items. Since the whole textiles production chain and market is very globalised, the EU government has a larger role in shaping the future and pushing further towards more sustainable material use than national government can.

Figure 28. Stakeholders of lyocell mapped in a power-interest matrix

High power-low interest (upper right): this category represents the non-EU government. As previously mentioned, governments have the power to set regulations. Nonetheless, in case of non-EU governments, the shift towards introducing more biobased materials might not be the priority everywhere.

Medium power-high interest (medium left): this category represents the lyocell fibre producers and raw materials suppliers' where those companies are the core of the business, yet they are linked tightly to the decision of the governments to put regulations and to the brands to source lyocell fibres from them. Also investors are needed to bring new MMCF production technologies to higher TRL levels.

Low power-high interest (bottom right): As chemical and textile researchers and developer toward fossil-free society are interested in new developments and materials; they have huge interest in lyocell development. Lyocell filaments producers are mostly chemists and textile engineers. They can drive the developments to achieve a greener production with high quality materials. In addition, knowledge on development and transition toward a fossil-free society is urgent. Those researchers play a key role in facilitating developments and supporting governments with setting the roles.

Medium power-high interest (medium lower) those are the non-governmental, standards setting/labelling and certification organisations. Mostly those organisations are concerned about the environment and the impact of industry on nature and human health such as NGOs organisations or forestry certification FSC². Those stakeholders are interested in using ecofriendly fibres such as lyocell and can influence the decision-making process to a certain point.

Medium power-medium interest (middle of the diagram): representatives of this category are social media influencers, customers, yarn/fabric manufacturers. Looking at them, they have medium interest in using lyocell fibres. For example, yarn/fabric manufacturers usually make the products based on the brand request. There are influencers who are encouraging to shift towards more biobased materials use and lower consumption but on the other hand many influencers just follow the fashion trends and do not put any attention on the negative side effects of overconsumption and fossil footprints of the apparel and fashion sector.

Finally, low power-low interest (bottom left): examples of stakeholders in this group are labour union/trade union and employee organisations. Although they can play a role in increasing the awareness regarding shifting towards ecofriendly fibre production and consumption. Nonetheless, their influence among the stakeholders is expected to be minor, but this depends also on the location in the world.

²Founded in 1993, as an international member-led organisation that sets standards for responsible forest management and chain of custody.

4.3.3 Policies of relevance to man-made cellulosic fibres value chain

In this section, policies were identified that could either stimulate or provide barriers to the further introduction of MMCF production and uses in the textiles value chain. These policies were detected through a review of policy documents at EU and national levels. In Table 19 an overview is provided of the relevant policy instruments already in place or expected to be put in place over next years.

In recent years at EU level there has been an increased focus on introducing policy instruments that enhance more sustainability in the textile sector in the EU, while reducing strategic dependencies on fossil resources and contributing to the EU competitiveness. This becomes clear from the publication of a number of EU strategies. The first is the updated Bioeconomy Action Plan (EC, 2018) that specifically mentions the need to stimulate a flourishing European biobased textile sector. The second is the updated EU Industrial Strategy (EC, 2021) in which 14 industrial ecosystems are to be monitored on specific transitions including the textile industrial ecosystem. For this ecosystem it specifically specifies that investments and research and innovation efforts are most needed to increased uptake of biobased, recycled and renewable fibres and phasing out of fossil resources. The third strategy is the *EU Strategy for sustainable and circular textiles* which adopted in March 2022 and outlines how to support the reduction of the textile's industry dependence of fossil resources (EC-JRC, 2025). In this document the European Commission describes a number of actions to be implemented over next years which are also specifically specified in Table 19:

- To harmonise the EU Extended Producer Responsibility rules for textile products put on the market to be more durable, recyclable, and environmentally friendly. It will set design requirements for textiles to make them last longer, easier to repair and recycle. It will also introduce clearer information on textiles to be addressed in a digital product passport.
- Extended producer responsibility (EPR) for textile products that will make producers responsible for their products that are put in the market. The producers need to ensure that the use becomes more circular when it is collected at the end of the life. This will encourage the producers/brand to source circular and renewable materials such as lyocell which can be made of non-fossil primary or recycled sources.
- This Action announced in the EU strategy has already been implemented in March 2024 and should now be transposed into national laws. It is meant to empower consumers as they will receive better and more harmonised information on its durability and reparability. Consumers will also need to be better informed about their legal guarantee rights. It should help to prevent getting vague environmental claims for products being 'green' or 'environmentally friendly' if it cannot be demonstrated according to uniform rules. Unreliable voluntary sustainability logos will be forbidden. In principle this instrument will help MMCF producers to position their products better on the markets.
- Other actions were also announced in the strategy which are still to be expected that will address the unintentional release of microplastics from synthetic textiles, an EU Toolbox against counterfeiting to prevent export of textile waste and an action plan for actors in the textiles ecosystem to successfully achieve the green and digital transitions and increase its resilience.

Table 19. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the man-made cellulosic fibres case study

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources: link to policy document, or link to policy evaluation documents (if available)
The EU Strategy for sustainable and circular textiles	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and creating product passports	Stimulating instrument	Sets mandatory requirements for product design, material composition, and end-of-life management e.g., products that are put in the market are more durable, recyclable, and environmentally friendly. This will encourage lyocell fibres to be produced from recycled sources. Equally, support the chemical recycler and lyocell producer	EU	Expected	Direct regulation	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation - European Commission (europa.eu)
The EU Strategy for sustainable and circular textiles	Extended producer responsibility (EPR)	Stimulating instrument	The producers are responsible for their products that are put in the market to be circular and to collect them at the end of the life. This will encourage the producers/brand to source circular materials e.g., lyocell which can be sources from virgin or recycled source. Also find collaborator to recycle their cellulosic textile waste to lyocell	EU	Ongoing	Direct regulation	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/textiles-strategy_en
The EU Strategy for sustainable and circular textiles	Empowering Consumers in the Green Transition Directive	Stimulating instrument	the proposal respects the right to a high level of environmental protection and the improvement of the quality of the environment by empowering consumers to make more environmentally sustainable purchasing decisions, e.g., purchase products made biobased source. lyocell	EU	March 2024 entered into force	Direct regulation	resource.html (europa.eu)
Draft Policy Program for Circular Textiles 2025-2030	In 2030, all textile products sold in the Dutch market will contain at least 50% sustainable material, with a minimum of 15% post-consumer	Stimulating instrument	Brands will be pushed to use biobased fibres e.g., lyocell as an alternative to fossil based fibres. Further, brands will demand more recycled sources. Hence, lyocell from recycled source will be put more in the market	NL	By 2030	Economic instruments	Overheid.nl Consultatie Concept beleidsprogramma circulair textiel 2025-2030 (internetconsultatie.nl)

	fibre-to-fibre recycled content.						
Anti-waste Law for a Circular Economy	This law requires that unsold non-food products can no longer be destroyed. This also applies to unsold clothes and shoes are also covered.	Stimulating instrument	Requires that unsold non-food products can no longer be destroyed. Clothes and shoes also fall within the scope of this law.	FR	2022	Direct regulation	

The EU strategy also announced actions to stop overproduction and overconsumption, and discourage the destruction of unsold or returned textiles. In France this action was already put into practice since January 2022 with the Law on wasting unsold non-food products. This law also applies therefore on all textile products. This Law and a wider implementation in the EU will help bring down production, but may also support producers of MMCFs to obtain access to sources of textiles that can be recycled. However, the latter should not lead to easier access while diverting end-of-life textiles to landfill or burning practices.

Another example of policy targeting the textiles sector comes from the Netherlands where clear policy targets have recently been set for a more circular textile sector for 2030. These targets were worked out in the *Draft Beleidsprogramma circulair textile 2025-2030* which is currently under public consultation (Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water). The targets proposed are that for all textile products placed on the market in the Netherlands 50% sustainable materials will have to be used. Of that 50% at least 30% will need to come from recycled sources and 20% from sustainable sources. In addition, 50% of resources, materials and products placed on the Dutch textile market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible. 15% of the textile products placed on the market in the Netherlands will be reused in the Netherlands after collection. If these targets are indeed implemented it will make the use of MMCFs in textiles placed on Dutch markets more attractive.

4.3.4 Analysis of indicators on -the man-made cellulosic fibres case study

In T3.2, a consistency check was conducted to identify the indicators in the Bioeconomy Monitoring and Assessment framework deemed relevant in light of *lyocell case study*. Subsequently, a selection of indicators was labelled as highly relevant. This initial analysis took place on the basis of *the approach taken to the case study consistency check and further updated according to additional literature consulted and interviews with producers of MMCFs*.

4.3.4.1 Environmental /circular indicators

Table 20 provides an overview of environmental and circular indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (13 indicators in total). The incumbent system MMCFs can be compared against is a cotton based fibre product. Based on this comparison the MMCFs, have a significant lower GHG emission then the incumbent cotton based fibres. The same applies to water use, which is significantly lower in MMCFs then for cotton fibres, both in the production of the feedstock and the whole conversion process to fibres. Chemical waste production can be 0 for some types of MMCFs or is low through the recycling of the NMMO solvents used in the pulping process. A sustainability challenge which requires special attention in MMCFs is the sustainability of the resources used.

Table 20. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the man-made cellulosic fibres (MMCFs) case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Land use change (LUC)	Change in wood/wood fibre demand for forest products	No information found	Yes, there is not enough data predicting the change in wood /wood fibre demand for forest product
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Primary Biomass production	Wood consumption (how much of wood is currently used for lyocell process)	2.5-3 tons of wood are required to produce 1 ton of Lyocell (Hugill et al, 2020)	No
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Amount of water used in the value-chain	For the same amount of materials, lyocell production require 1/3 less water than viscose production, based on Lenzing process (Lenzing, 2024). Spinnova fibres required 98% less water compared to conventional cotton	Yes, there are no uniform guidelines on how to determine amount of water used through the value chain
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Water consumption (use) (m ³ /product unit processed)	264 (m ³ per tonne of fibre Tencel (lyocell by Lenzing) {water used for cotton is almost 20 times higher than the used water to produce Tencel fibre)	No
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Renewable electricity used for manufactured products (kWh or % of total electricity used)	renewable energy {biomass, solar, hydro and wind} 48% of total energy GJ/t for Tencel (lyocell by Lenzing) fibre.	No
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Energy consumption by activity/ production process/unit of production	non-renewable energy {fossil fuel (oil/gas/coal) and nuclear energy (uranium)} 42%, renewable energy {biomass, solar, hydro and wind} 48% of	No

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
			(kWh/production process or product unit)	total energy GJ/t for Tencel (lyocell by Lenzing) fibre. Tencel require 40% less energy than cotton	
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Waste generated	In whole chain	Yes, what is waste there are different types of waste in textile e.g., production waste such as chemicals and fibres, yarns, fabric, and end of life waste
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Recycling rate/cascading indexes	MMCF can be recycled in general.	Yes, there is not enough data/research regarding the amount of recycled textile waste made from MMCF's fibre because MMCF are increasing in the mix of textile wastes
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of materials derived from recycling or recovery of any other biomass waste	1% of feedstock came from recycled cellulose textile waste such as cotton linter and pre-consumer cotton textile (Textile Exchange, 2024)	This development is still in its initial phase. Therefore, many developments on process and technology shall be developed. The side effect of those developments on the environment is not clear yet. Researchers estimate that the wood used as feedstock for MMCF can be replaced if 50% of cellulosic textile waste is recycled globally.
	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of biodegradability	Tencel™ Lyocell fibres by Lenzing are certified by TÜV AUSTRIA as biodegradable in soil, freshwater and marine environments, and compostable under home and industrial conditions (Lenzing, 2024)	No

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	Share of forests certified for sustainable management	64% of the feedstock came from forest certified by FSC and/or PEFC (Textile Exchange, 2024)	Yes, data are not complete on the exact biomass sources used for MMCFs and whether they are sustainable. The effect and the source of the non-certified wood use a concern and needs to be understood better especially if the demand on MMCF increases in the future
	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of chemical waste and empty containers is collected and disposed in compliance with good practices	The recovery rate of NMMO solvent is high. Almost 99.7% is recovered and put again in the process to dissolve more pulp (Roadmap2020,2023). Spinnova fibre does not require any solvent. The process does not result in any type of chemical waste.	No
	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle GHG emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	Compared to cotton Tencel 1 kg woodbased Tencel (Lenzing, 2024) emits almost 4 times less CO ₂ emissions (Shen, 2010) Spinnova fibre emit 74% less GHG compared to conventional cotton	No

Sofar the majority of the MMCFs use woody resources from virgin or primary residual forest resources or from cotton waste. The latter is still very small. The use of woody resources is until now mostly based on certified biomass. If MMCF production grows in the future the sustainable sourcing may need to be based more strongly on textile waste and recycling (fibre to fibre) and other cellulose rich residues and waste.

The energy transition within the lyocell fibres reviewed in this factsheet is progressing, at least for the lyocell and Tencel types, with a growing integration of renewable energy sources. Not all companies producing MMCFs report this however.

As to the end-of-life the advantage is that MMCFs can be recycled again into new MMCFs and that if they end-up in soil they are fully biodegradable contrary to the fossil based textiles. The challenge is however that they are usually mixed with other types of fossil based fibres when used in clothes and other types of textile products. In these mixed systems the fate of the MMCFs is difficult to trace in terms of where they end up and which part is recycled already. Another data gap identified regarding waste, is the amount of waste used in the whole chain from biomass to product. There are different MMCF processes and the amount of waste produced is different and not necessarily reported for every process.

Beside the issue of tracing end-of-life fate, more research and data gaps were also identified in relation to type of biomass resources that are used for MMCF production in terms of whether they are certified for environmental risks. As to water use in the MMCF production process it is reported for several types of MMCFs, Lyocell and Spinnova, and it is clearly much lower than for cotton. Still uniform guidelines on how to determine water use through the whole value chain are needed to make reliable comparisons.

4.3.4.2 Economic indicators

Table 21 provides an overview of economic indicators that were identified as highly relevant (6 indicators in total). One additional indicators of high relevance was identified which was also already reported for the Prato case in the former section (see Table 21 in red). It refers to the tracking of R&D investments in development of novel technologies for efficient and sustainable production of MMCFs from biomass and textile wastes.

Table 21. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the man-made cellulosic fibres case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Strategy for creating the infrastructure and systems necessary for recovering and recycling materials (yes/no)	The EU commission introduced the obligation for separate collection of textiles waste. Also the strategy for sustainable and circular textile (see Table 19) announces several actions for policy instruments that will stimulate recycling of textile wastes. In addition several EU countries are also working on introduction of policy instruments stimulating recycling of textiles (e.g. Netherlands)	No

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Potential market share of the product	Lyocell market value is expected to double and to reach 2.7 \$ billion in 2031 compared to 1.3 \$ billion in 2021 (Allied Market research, 2022)	No
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Number of patents on resource efficiency technologies	Many companies in EU have patented technology for their development on MMCF's process such as Spinnova	Yes, not all the data about the patents on resources efficiency technology is known
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Value Added of the bioeconomy sectors	Contribution of the product/service/organisation to economic progress (revenue, gain, paid wages, R+D costs in relation to revenue, etc.)	Many companies in EU aim to develop further the Lyocell products e.g., innovation on recycling waste cellulose textiles, develop lyocell technologies which help EU to stay competitive in the world market, push lyocell into the market to help increasing the demand on biobased products	Yes, there are examples of the companies who are developing MMCF but not enough data about the economic progress
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Full time equivalent jobs along the full value chain of a product	In general, the textile industry is labour intensive. In EU, the textile industry hires 1.5 million people. Moving toward a circular and sustainable industry means more job opportunities (EEA, 2022) Lenzing has an FTE of 7917 TreeToTextile has FTE of 46 (Cision, 2024)	In EU, no In other part of the world
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Total amount of funding provided to companies and research organisations to develop MMCF technologies	Funding levels are no known	Yes, limited centrally reported tracking of funding by public and private funds on R&D per sector

From the indicator overview we conclude that policy is regulating separate textile waste collection and that more policy stimulation can be expected to stimulate recycling of textile fibers. The market share of MMCFs is also growing. The same applies to the number of patents developed, but it is clear that a full overview of patented technologies in resource efficient technologies for MMCF sector is incomplete. There is also large lack of published and systematic data on economic progress made by companies involved in MMCF production and development.

The same applies to the sectors contribution to employment, certainly for companies involved in MMCF production outside EU for the EU market.

4.3.4.3 Social indicators

Table 22 provides an overview of economic indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (i.e., 5 indicators in total). No additional indicators of high relevance were identified to be included. The analysis of social indicators reveals notable progress in the examined circular bio-based system when compared to the incumbent cotton system. The most eco-friendly process, which yields desired fibre properties for the textile industry, is the lyocell process. The process starts with wood pulp, which is converted into a solution using NMMO solvent. The solvent, as already discussed before is recycled for 99% and used again. Also Lyocell is derived from wood pulp from certified forest biomass. The only disadvantage of the NMMO solvent use is that it is a flammable solvent and that there is a risk for explosions in the process.

Table 22. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the man-made cellulosic fibres case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Presence of environmentally/friendly technologies (yes/no)	Yes lyocell, is a sustainable process recycling 99% of the solvents used in the dissolving of the cellulose. And Research and innovation on turning waste cellulosic textiles into MMCF is expected to increase in order to make conversion processes more sustainable and efficient (Textile Exchange, 2024)	
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Productivity	Land for biomass production	Lyocell is mostly produced from (certified) wood resources, but land requirements are not known. Spinnova uses wood resources from amongst other eucalyptus plantations in Brasil. There is a land	Yes, lack of data on the land required to produced MMCF production

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
				demand related to it. How much is not reported	
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Presence of working children under the legal age (yes/no)	In EU, the law protects children from child labour work (European commission Directive 94/33/EC)	In EU, no downstream part of the value chain is outside EU and the information about child labour is limited.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Presence of formal policies on equal opportunities	EU strategy for sustainable and circular textile focuses on gender equality (European Commission, 2022)	In EU, no downstream part of the value chain is outside EU and the information about equal opportunities is limited.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Presence of a formal policy in place concerning health and safety of all workers, including contractors (yes/no)	The EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive came into force on July 25, 2024. It sets a clear responsibility for large companies. They must identify, prevent, reduce, and address any negative impacts their operations in global value chains may have on human rights (including labour rights) and the environment.	In EU, there is no data or research gap. If part of the delivery chain is based outside the risk increases for no maintenance and no control on rules on worker health and safety and no-child labour. However, commitment of EU companies to the CSDDD will help improve this situation.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Number of certifications/labels the organisation obtained for the product/site	Lenzing obtained 12 certifications to enhance their transparency and security portfolio such as but not limited to European Ecolabel, USDA Certified Biobased Product, FSC® and PEFC (Lenzing, 2024)	

MMCF producers producing lyocell like Lenzing, SMARTFIBRE, Spinnova, INfinna, and TreetoTextile are all based in EU countries. They are all committed to strict social sustainability requirements

through for example the 1994 EU Law on child labour and EU and national labour health and safety laws. However, since part of the value chain is not necessarily based in the EU there is more risk that in certain stages the social rules are not always controlled. However, the recent EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive which only recently came into force in 2024 also widens the responsibility of companies to also take wider responsibility for human rights even if their value chain is a global one.

Beside the legislation in the EU to which companies in EU and partner countries are committed many companies have also ensured the sustainability of their products in certification schemes. Lenzing produces Lyocell and is a typical example of a company that has put all effort to prove the sustainability of its product through extensive certification uptake. This helps enormously in improving transparency and reporting on the sustainable practices in the public domain.

Overall, the lyocell produced by Lenzing, but also the other MMCFs discussed in this factsheet are performing substantially better on social indicators compared to most of the incumbent cotton producers worldwide.

4.3.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Market dimension

- One of the main challenges faced is that currently the costs of MMCFs either based on virgin or residual biomass or from fibres derived from discarded textiles are too expensive to compete with other mostly fossil and cotton based fibres. Most of these fossil based textiles that are entering the EU market from all over the world, but especially China, are very low in price.
- Overconsumption in the clothing market, especially stimulated by fast fashion and low prices of especially synthetic textiles, make it very difficult to enter the market with higher costs of textile products based on MMCFs or recycled discarded textiles. The higher additional cost for recycling and generation of MMCFs are simply not rewarded in the highly competitive clothing markets.
- Currently the market favours (cheap) fossil based virgin materials most.
- It is also hard for new recycled and MMCFs to enter the markets because new fibres have new properties, to which existing standardised production chains need to be adapted. For each fibre with changed fibre property the textile chain needs to collect knowledge on how to industrially treat the products in the whole processing chain from fibre to garment. This requires investments and takes time.
- Currently the market is not rewarding for the lower environmental impacts in the production of MMCFs as compared to the incumbent cotton production systems.

Recommendations/good practices

- Further develop existing or new certification systems that take better account of processes towards lyocell or other MMCFs and recycled fibres.

- Policy support instruments are needed to facilitate MMCFs and recycled textile fibres entering the market more easily such as (fossil)carbon tax on strongly competing incumbent systems and tax exemptions (e.g. lower VAT) for sustainably certified MMCFs.
- More information sharing in relation to (un)sustainable consumer and production practices in textiles, including through digital product passports.

Policy dimension

Challenges

- Absence of sufficiently clear and inclusive definitions for biobased plastics, biopolymers and fibres make certification and labelling more challenging.
- There is no policy in place (yet) that stimulates recycling above the use of virgin materials in the textile sector

Recommendations/good practices

- Set up collaboration structures (e.g., labelling and certification) and policy that ensure the sustainability claims in EU are credible.
- Introduction of policy instruments that facilitate MMCFs and recycled textile fibres entering the market more easily.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- Textiles sector is a very globalised and competitive sector which makes it difficult for MMCFs which perform much better on sustainable production to enter the market.
- Ensuring the sustainable sourcing biomass for production of MMCFs is challenging and complicates the certification of the full value chain and ensures secure and constant availability of sustainable feedstocks to scale up the process.

Recommendations/good practices

- Green VAT, lowering the VAT to 10%, both for sustainable businesses and sustainable products.
- Market based instruments are needed focussed on stimulating larger market shares for MMCFs and fibres made from textile wastes

4.3.6 Key learnings of man-made cellulosic fibres case study

The first MMCFs were already produced in the 19th century, but at that time the production was not a very environmentally sustainable process in which toxic chemicals with many risks for losses to water and also health risks for workers. In time, certainly in the last decade several companies have invested in the development of conversion processes of cellulose to fibres with a very low environmental impact and high quality. Lyocell is a good example of a MMCF that now forms an

excellent alternative to the fossil and cotton based fibers, which make up the lion share of the fibres used in textiles worldwide, and which have a considerably higher negative impact on the environment in terms of GHG emissions, water consumption, and wider pollution. What is also attractive is that MMCF are produced from biobased sources and are therefore 100% biodegradable and therefore their increased use in textile applications can also help the reduction in microplastic pollutions from fossil textile sources.

The attractive aspect of MMCFs is that they can be produced of both biomass and wasted high vegetal fiber textile wastes. Using textile waste as a resource is attractive from a circularity perspective, but technically still very challenging. Therefore, MMCF are still produced from primary biomass sources by 99% only for 1% from wasted sources. To ensure the production of MMCFs can continue to grow to exchange the unsustainable fossil and cotton textile products several recommendations can be made. Firstly, more financial and R&D support is needed to stimulate technology developments that extract the cellulose fibers from the mostly mixed fossil-non-fossil textile waste streams produced in the current society. Secondly end-of life treatment of textile wastes can be more strictly regulated to also improve access to textile waste sources to produce new MMCF fibers from. Thirdly, it is recommended to accelerate the introduction of ecodesign criteria which force producers of textile products on EU markets to be recyclable, and environmentally friendly. This will increase the amount of textiles that can be recycled in fiber to fiber MMCF production processes, but it will also help to significantly increase the market share of sustainable MMCF fibers like lyocell at the expense of unsustainable fossil and cotton based fibers.

Fourthly, more improvements are possible in the traceability and monitoring through labelling and certification of textiles covering the whole production chain from feedstock sourcing to end-of-life treatments. This involves introduction of instruments like digital product passports, ensure uniformity in green labelling, but also fill data gaps on issues like carbon footprints, (sustainable)energy use, water input and pollution prevention, land use, use of fair and socially sustainable production etc.

4.4 Textile - Latxa sheep wool from the Basque Country of Spain

4.4.1 Introduction to the Latxa sheep wool from the Basque Country

4.4.1.1 General description

In response to the significant environmental impacts of the textile industry, particularly driven by fast fashion and increasing textile production, there has been a heightened focus on assessing clothing sustainability and transitioning towards circular economy practices. This shift has led to

the exploration of new business models and initiatives aimed at reducing waste and promoting resource efficiency in the clothing sector.

One such initiative is the valorisation of conventionally discarded wool from Latxa sheep in the Basque Country, Spain. The Latxa sheep is a breed native to the Basque Country, a region spanning northern Spain and southwestern France. These sheep are primarily known for their milk production rather than their wool. Generally, the wool of Latxa sheep is not as fine or soft as that of some other sheep breeds specifically bred for wool production. Historically, Latxa sheep wool has been treated as waste due to challenges in bringing it to market, resulting in considerable expenses for flock owners who had to manage it.

In this context, TERNUA, a Basque apparel manufacturer, has been at the forefront of utilising Latxa wool in their products, particularly through their "Latxa Project". This project represents a significant departure from conventional practices, as it seeks to repurpose and add value to a resource that was previously overlooked. By incorporating Latxa wool into their clothing line, TERNUA not only highlights the unique qualities of this indigenous wool but also supports local farmers and promotes the conservation of the Latxa sheep breed. The ARTILE jacket serves as a prime example of this innovative approach, showcasing the exceptional properties and sustainability of Latxa sheep wool.

4.4.1.2 Value chain and the process

The value chain for utilising Latxa wool as insulating material in the ARTILE jacket involves several key steps, from the procurement of raw materials to end-of-life processing. This value chain encompasses various stakeholders, including Latxa sheep farmers, wool processors, textile manufacturers, and retailers (see Figure 29). It follows the main processing steps:

- Raw material procurement

The value chain begins with the procurement of raw Latxa wool from sheep farmers in the Basque Country region of Spain. Farmers shear Latxa sheep to harvest the wool, which is then collected and transported to processing facilities.

- Wool processing

Upon arrival at processing facilities, the raw Latxa wool undergoes several processing steps to prepare it for use as insulation material. These steps may include cleaning, carding, and combing to remove impurities, align fibres, and create a uniform texture suitable for insulation.

- Textile manufacturing

Processed Latxa wool is then sent to textile manufacturers specialised in outdoor apparel, such as TERNUA. Here, the wool is incorporated into the production of the ARTILE jacket as insulation material. The wool may be blended with other fibres or treated for enhanced performance characteristics.

- Product distribution

Once the ARTILE jacket is manufactured, it is distributed to retailers both locally and globally. Distribution channels may include physical stores, online platforms, and specialty outdoor retailers catering to consumers interested in sustainable and eco-friendly products.

- Consumer use

End consumers purchase the ARTILE jacket and use it for various outdoor activities, benefiting from the insulation provided by Latxa wool. Consumers may also appreciate the sustainable and environmentally friendly aspects of the product, aligning with their values and preferences.

- End-of-life processing

Finally, when the ARTILE jacket reaches the end of its usable life, it may undergo end-of-life processing. This could involve recycling or repurposing the materials to minimise waste and maximise resource efficiency. For example, Latxa wool insulation may be reclaimed and reused in other textile products or repurposed for alternative applications. However, although reuse and recycling may be the preferred end-of-life processing methods, landfilling or incineration of textiles is still relatively common.

The geographic area of interest for this value chain is primarily the Basque Country region of Spain, where Latxa sheep are predominantly raised and where the wool is sourced. However, the market for products like the ARTILE jacket extends beyond this region, with distribution channels reaching global consumers interested in sustainable outdoor apparel.

Figure 29. Value chain of the TERNUA case study

4.4.1.3 Baseline and market

The wool harvested from Latxa sheep holds significant potential for various applications, both current and potential. With an estimated population of around one million Latxa sheep in the Basque Country, the annual production of wool can reach several thousand metric tons (~2,500 tons), with over 2,000 metric tons being produced annually in the Basque Country alone. This abundance of wool presents a significant opportunity for its utilisation in various sectors.

Currently, one prominent application of Latxa wool is its use as insulation material in products like the ARTILE jacket, developed by TERNUA. The market for such wool-based products extends beyond jackets, encompassing a wide range of outdoor apparel and accessories. As consumer awareness of sustainability and eco-friendliness grows, there is an increasing demand for products made from natural and renewable materials like Latxa wool. This trend may drive the expansion of the market for (Laxa) wool products not only within the Basque Country but also globally.

Furthermore, the potential applications of Latxa wool are not limited to the textile industry. It can also be explored in sectors such as construction, automotive, and packaging. For example, Latxa wool could be used as insulation material in buildings, providing both thermal and acoustic properties. In the automotive industry, it could serve as a sustainable alternative for interior upholstery and soundproofing. Additionally, Latxa wool-based packaging materials could offer a biodegradable and renewable solution for reducing plastic waste.

The utilisation of Latxa wool in products like the ARTILE jacket not only adds value to a resource that would otherwise be discarded or incinerated but also plays a crucial role in supporting the livelihoods of local farmers. By providing a market for Latxa wool, initiatives like the ARTILE jacket project ensure that farmers are compensated for their wool, thereby enhancing their economic sustainability. This financial incentive encourages farmers to maintain and invest in their Latxa sheep flocks, thus promoting the conservation of indigenous sheep breeds in the Basque Country.

The coupling of initiatives like Latxa wool with the rising consumer demand for sustainability can disrupt the incumbent fossil-based system in industries like textiles and fashion. This integration prompts companies to reevaluate their reliance on fossil-based materials and linear production processes. As consumer preferences shift towards sustainability, companies embracing renewable alternatives like Latxa wool gain a competitive edge. This disruption leads to a reconfiguration of industry norms, emphasising circular economy principles and responsible resource management. Additionally, it inspires innovation and collaboration across the industry to meet evolving consumer needs while minimising environmental impacts. Overall, Latxa wool and similar initiatives drive systemic change towards a more environmentally conscious and socially responsible economy.

4.4.2 Stakeholders in the Latxa sheep wool case study

4.4.1.4 Identification of relevant stakeholders

To begin with, the stakeholders relevant to the Latxa sheep wool case study were determined based on the results of the social Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) conducted within the ORIENTING

project³. According to the social assessment, three key stakeholder categories are related to the Bioeconomy supply chain. These are: small-scale entrepreneurs (i.e., farmers), value chain actors (wool processing actors, retailers, end-of-life (EoL) actors, etc) and consumers/users. In addition to these, several additional key actors can be identified in the Enabling environment such as knowledge institutions (e.g., Research technology organisations (RTOs), universities etc.), certification bodies, and governmental/administrative bodies. Figure 30 provides a schematic representation of the identified stakeholders, both in the Bioeconomy supply chain (i.e., the light green section) and its Enabling environment (i.e., the light grey section).

³ <https://orienting.eu/>

Figure 30. Identified stakeholders in the Latxa sheep wool value chain

Overview of key stakeholders in the Latxa wool value chain:

Bioeconomy supply chain stakeholders:

- **Latxa sheep farmers:** These stakeholders play a crucial role in the value chain by providing the raw material, Latxa wool, through sheep farming practices. Farmers shear Latxa sheep to harvest the wool, which serves as the primary feedstock for insulation material in products like the ARTILE jacket. An example of an organisation representing Latxa sheep farmers is the CONFELAC - Confederation of Associations of Latxa and Carranzana Sheep Breeders (<http://www.confelac.org/>).
- **Wool processing actors:** Entities involved in processing raw Latxa wool into a usable form for insulation material are key stakeholders in the value chain. These actors may include wool processing facilities or textile manufacturers specialising in wool processing. For instance, Egarfil is a wool processing company based in Catalonia that may be involved in processing Latxa wool.
- **Manufacturing companies (e.g., TERNUA):** Textile manufacturing companies like TERNUA are key stakeholders in the value chain, as they are responsible for manufacturing products like the ARTILE jacket valorising Latxa wool and collaborating with wool processors, designers, and manufacturers to ensure the quality and performance of the products. In this context, textile companies commit to sustainability and eco-friendly practices, aligning with the objectives of the bioeconomy value chain.
- **Retailers:** Retailers serve as intermediaries between manufacturers and end consumers, distributing products like the ARTILE jacket to the market. Outdoor retailers, specialty stores, and online platforms are examples of stakeholders in this category.
- **Users:** Users or consumers of textile products are integral stakeholders in the value chain. Their purchasing decisions drive demand for sustainable and eco-friendly products, influencing the actions of other stakeholders in the supply chain. Outdoor enthusiasts, hikers, and environmentally conscious consumers are examples of users who may benefit from Latxa wool-based products.

Enabling environment stakeholders:

- **Government agencies:** Government agencies play a pivotal role in fostering sustainability and facilitating circular economy initiatives, as they provide regulatory frameworks, funding opportunities, and technical expertise to drive environmental sustainability and rural development in the Basque Country. In the case of the Latxa ARTILE project, several government agencies have been actively involved in supporting and promoting the transformation of Latxa sheep wool waste into valuable resources. One such agency is the Department of Environment of Gipuzkoa, which collaborated closely with stakeholders to implement circular economy strategies and waste management solutions. Another key actor is certainly Ihobe, the Basque Government's Public Environmental Management Company, which contributes valuable expertise and resources to advance environmental sustainability goals. Through its participation in initiatives like Latxa ARTILE, Ihobe reinforces its commitment to promoting circular economy principles and fostering innovation in environmental management.
- **Research institutions and collaborative platforms:** Research institutions and collaborative platforms play essential roles in driving innovation and offering technical expertise to support sustainable development initiatives. In the Latxa ARTILE project,

TECNALIA, a Basque leading research organisation, has collaborated with TERNUA within the ORIENTING project to assess the life cycle sustainability impact of the ARTILE product. Additionally, the Basque Circular Hub is a key platform within the Basque Country, facilitating collaboration among stakeholders from government, industry, academia, and civil society to promote circular economy initiatives. By fostering partnerships and knowledge exchange, the Basque Circular Hub contributes to the development and implementation of sustainable practices in various sectors, including textiles and agriculture.

- **Alliances and coalitions:**

- **The Textile Industry Research Association, AITEX (Spain):** It is a centre for research, innovation, and advanced technical services for the textile, furniture, apparel, technical textiles, and other related sectors. Their activities focus on applied research, technological innovation, advanced laboratory technical services, certifications, and technical training for companies. It plays a very important role in the development of research lines that frame the different issues presented to provide them with the best possible solutions.
- **Slow Fashion Next:** It is a training and outreach platform in fashion, sustainability, and business that has become a reference within the sustainable fashion sector in Spain. The platform helps assisting companies, students, and entrepreneurs who wish to have business training in fashion and sustainability. And, on the other hand, it promotes the visibility of numerous projects, brands, and fashion companies that work with sustainability as their flagship.
- **SIC MODA:** It is a meeting place and a support hub for designers who advocate for responsible, sustainable, and soulful fashion, conscious of its transformative power on society and committed to nature. SIC MODA is comprised of individuals and brands whose purpose is to promote the commitment to ethical and transparent design, as well as to encourage an increasing number of projects to embrace sustainable fashion and to solidify these new values in an industry that has so far ignored them.
- **Observatorio textil:** It is an instrument for the sectoral transformation of the Spanish Textile and Fashion industry, grounded in the principles of sustainability and circularity outlined in the European and Spanish 2030 strategy for this sector. It is known as a forum for strategic reflection, a space for business cooperation, and an entity for public-private coordination aimed at driving transformation across the entire value chain of the textile and fashion sector.

4.4.1.5 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

Afterwards, the stakeholders identified as relevant were mapped in a power-interest matrix, following a thorough identification process to capture all those who could have an interest in or influence over the case study. This analysis was conducted through the lens of advancing and upscaling the value chain of Latxa sheep wool, ensuring that the most influential actors in its development were considered. This included both **internal stakeholders**, directly involved in the value chain – such as retailers and consumers – and **external stakeholders** like customers, regulatory bodies, and policy makers. The result can be found in Figure 31.

Figure 31 Stakeholders of the Latxa sheep wool case study mapped in a power-interest matrix

The stakeholders with the most significant influence are policymakers and government agencies. These entities possess the authority to enact policies and initiatives aimed at reducing waste and promoting resource efficiency within the clothing sector. Consumers also play a critical role, as their purchasing decisions drive the demand for sustainable products. Textile manufacturers and retailers are among the stakeholders with a vested interest in transitioning from a fossil-based to a biobased system. Additionally, they are considered highly influential, as they are responsible for producing goods that align with the objectives of the bioeconomy.

Other stakeholders within the production value chain, including farmers and wool producers, are also invested in this transition; however, they hold less influence since they ultimately supply what textile manufacturers and retailers demand. Similarly, research institutes and organisations within alliances are interested in promoting sustainability but lack substantial influence because their impact is contingent upon market demand and the directives of manufacturing companies.

4.4.3 Policies of relevance to Latxa sheep wool case study

In this section, policies were identified that could either propel or impede the implementation of the TERNUA case study. These policies were detected through a mapping of policies and initiatives at regional, national, and European levels that may impact the TERNUA case study. In Table 23,

Table 23. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the Laxta sheep wool case study

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument ?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
Ecodesign Requirements for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)	It sets a framework to improve the environmental sustainability of products and their circularity. Worldwide companies selling in the EU market will have to comply with Ecodesign requirements for performance and for information, the latter via a newly introduced Digital Product Passport.	Stimulating instrument	Textiles are a priority, and specific requirements will be set.	EU	Approved, the implementation of this regulation will be carried out in the following years, in which the European Commission will identify priority product groups to establish specific ecodesign requirements.	Regulation	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation - European Commission (europa.eu)
EU strategy for sustainable and circular textiles	It addresses the production and consumption of textiles, whilst recognising the importance of the textiles sector.	Stimulating instrument	The strategy looks at the entire lifecycle of textile products and proposes coordinated actions to change how we produce and consume textiles.	EU	Current	Strategy	Textiles strategy - European Commission (europa.eu)
The Textile Labelling Regulation (EU) 1007/2011	The EU has aligned laws in all EU countries with Regulation (EU) No 1007/2011 on fibre names and related labelling and marking of the fibre composition of textile products, commonly referred to as the Textile Labelling Regulation.	Stimulating instrument	It will help the traceability of textile products.	EU	Current	Regulation	Regulation - 1007/2011 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)
The EU Ecolabel for textile products	It establishes the ecological criteria for textile products.	Stimulating instrument	It guarantees a more sustainable fibre production, less polluting production processes, strict restrictions on the use of hazardous substances, and long-lasting final products.	EU	Current	Label	EU Ecolabel - Clothing and Textiles (europa.eu)

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

The One UNEP Textile Initiative	UNEP has identified textiles as a high-impact sector, not only due to its significant environmental and social impacts but because it exemplifies many common challenges for other sectors on value chain visibility, overconsumption and overproduction, and circularity.	Stimulating instrument	It provides strategic leadership and encourages sector-wide collaboration to accelerate a just transition towards a sustainable and circular textile value chain.	EU	Current	Initiative	The One UNEP Textile Initiative UNEP - UN Environment Programme
Circular Economy Strategy - España Circular 2030	The textile sector is a priority	Stimulating instrument	It establishes that starting from 2025, it will be mandatory to have a separate collection scheme and management for textiles at the end of their life.	National, Spain	Current	Strategy	espanacircular2030_def1_tcm30-509532_mod_tcm30-509532.pdf (miteco.gob.es)
The Strategic Plan for Recovery, Transformation and Resilience in the Circular Economy (PERTE EC)	It identifies the textile sector as a priority for Spain in light of the dynamism of the textile, fashion, clothing and footwear sector partly linked to unsustainable production and consumption models associated with high environmental impacts marked by low rates of use, reuse, repair and integration of new technologies that allow high-quality recycling.	Stimulating instrument	Addressing challenges such as ecodesigning new garments that entail lower environmental impact by reducing the use of chemicals or employing more sustainable alternatives, improving waste treatment by promoting reuse and recycling, which is not always straightforward, and incorporating recycled materials into production.	National, Spain	Current	Strategy	Ministry of industry and tourism - Recovery Plan, transformation and Resilience (mintur.gob.es)
Circular Economy and bioeconomy Plan	The textile sector is a priority	Stimulating instrument	The aim is to increase material productivity by 30%, increase the rate of circular material use by 10%, and reduce the waste generation rate per unit of GDP by 10%.	Regional, Basque Country	Current	Action Plan	Economia-Circular-y-Bioeconomia-WEB.pdf (euskadi.eus)

an overview is provided of the relevant policies, including the type of policy it concerns, further general information, as well as its relevance to the TERNUA case study.

It appears that most of the policy instruments and strategies related to the textile sector are at the European level, among which is the Ecodesign Requirements for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), which establishes specific criteria to achieve a European market with more environmentally sustainable and circular textile products. It is expected that the inclusion of the "Digital Product Passport" will provide information about products' environmental sustainability, facilitating their traceability and thus, the repair and recycling of textile products. The strategies and plans at the national and regional levels are aligned with the ESPR, promoting the ecodesign that entail lower environmental impact and facilitating the circularity of textiles, thereby enhancing the recycled content, remanufacturing, and recycling of textile products.

4.4.4 Analysis of indicators on Latxa sheep wool case study

In T3.2, a consistency check was conducted to identify those indicators of the Bioeconomy Monitoring and Assessment framework deemed relevant in light of the Latxa sheep wool case study. Subsequently, a selection of indicators was labelled as highly relevant. This initial analysis took place on the basis of expert knowledge, stakeholder involvement, and a literature review.

In the present section, the results from this preliminary analysis will be deepened by means of interviews with stakeholders identified earlier, and the collection of information through a systematic white/grey literature review. The original list of highly relevant indicators will henceforth be complemented with additional indicators. Each of these indicators will be utilised to assess the performance of the Latxa sheep wool case study. To that end, an exhaustive review of the indicators outlined below has been undertaken through an extensive search of relevant academic literature to ascertain the existence of related data and to evaluate whether companies and organisations measure these indicators, as well as the methodologies they employ in doing so. In the case that no information or data could be found to support the analysis of the indicator, this was reported as a research gap.

4.4.1.6 Environmental/circular indicators

Table 24 provides an overview of environmental and circular indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (i.e., 17 indicators in total). In addition, 4 indicators were identified as highly relevant were included in the table in red.

Table 24. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the Latxa sheep wool case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Resource depletion (mineral, fossil) / product unit (MJ)	Larger companies often disclose their resource use, including fossil fuels and raw material extraction, in their sustainability reports. Reports from agencies like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) or the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) provide insights into how industries, including textiles, use non-renewable resources. Resource depletion is typically measured in LCA and carbon footprint.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Intensity of fossil fuel use (m ³ /ton of product)	Companies in the textile sector are increasingly disclosing their energy use and fossil fuel consumption data, particularly those with sustainability commitments. Data can be found in sustainability reports, carbon footprint assessments, or industry certifications. Regulatory bodies often require companies to report their energy use, including fossil fuels, and data is available in government reports and carbon accounting databases. Third-party sustainability organisations like the Carbon Trust, CDP, and Greenpeace also track and publish data on energy use and fossil fuel intensity. Fossil fuel intensity is measured using LCA by calculating the amount of fossil fuel used per unit of output.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of biological content/ product	Data on the % of biological content is widely available through corporate sustainability reports, product labels, and third-party certifications (e.g., GOTS, OEKO-TEX, Cradle to Cradle). It is measured by calculating the proportion of renewable or biobased materials in a product, usually by weight or volume.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Energy Intensity (product value added / mJ primary energy)	Energy intensity data is increasingly available through corporate sustainability reports, energy audits, and industry-specific reports. Companies in the textile sector with formal energy management systems or ISO certifications (e.g., ISO 50001) are more likely to	No.

				report energy intensity. National and international organisations (e.g., UNFCCC, IEA, CDP) may provide aggregate data on energy intensity in the textile sector, though it is often at the industry or regional level. Energy intensity is calculated by dividing total primary energy consumption (in MJ) by the product value added (economic value generated by the production process).	
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Energy consumption by activity/ production process/unit of production (kWh/production process or product unit)	Data on energy consumption by production process or product unit is typically available through corporate sustainability reports, energy audits, and internal monitoring systems used by manufacturers. Companies aiming for ISO 50001 (energy management), or other environmental certifications often report detailed energy consumption data by production stage or product unit. The indicator is measured by dividing the total energy consumption (in kWh) by the unit of production (e.g., number of garments, meters of fabric, or specific production processes). This data can be captured through energy management systems, production tracking systems, and energy audits.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Waste generated	Data on waste generation is often available through sustainability reports, corporate environmental disclosures, and third-party certifications (e.g., ISO 14001, Cradle to Cradle). Governments and regulatory bodies may collect data through mandatory reporting systems and industry surveys, with some waste-related metrics being publicly available in environmental impact reports or industry audits. Waste is typically measured by tracking the volume or weight of waste produced during textile production. It can be categorised by type, such as textile waste, chemical waste, water waste, packaging waste, and other byproducts.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Procedures for separating and using recyclable materials from the	Data on procedures for separating and using recyclable materials is generally available through sustainability reports, corporate environmental audits, and waste management certifications. Companies with environmental management systems in place typically	No.

			waste stream (yes/no)	provide detailed information on their waste segregation and recycling practices. The measurement of this indicator involves assessing the procedures and systems a company has in place to separate and manage recyclable materials. This may include waste sorting practices, recycling rates, and the volume or percentage of waste that is recycled or reused.	
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of recycled materials for packaging	Companies that prioritise sustainability often track and report the percentage of recycled content in packaging materials through sustainability reports, packaging audits, or third-party certifications (e.g., Global Recycle Standard). The percentage of recycled materials in packaging is measured by calculating the proportion of total packaging material that is derived from recycled content.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of materials derived from animal by-products	Companies that use animal by-products are likely to track and report the percentage of these materials in their internal sustainability or material sourcing reports.	Yes. Companies do not provide with this information.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Material circularity indicator (MCI)	The MCI is increasingly reported by major textile brands and manufacturers, especially in sustainability reports, annual reports, and corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosures. Some companies also partner with certification bodies (like Cradle-to-Cradle) or use material tracking technologies to document circularity. The MCI is measured based on factors like the amount of recycled content used, the recyclability of materials, and the longevity of products. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation and other sustainability consultancies provide circularity calculators for the textile sector.	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP100; gr eq. CO ₂)	GWP data is often available through LCAs, carbon footprint analyses, and sustainability disclosures. Textile companies and brands report GWP metrics in sustainability reports, CDP disclosures, and third-party certifications such as Carbon Neutral or Climate Neutral certifications. GWP is calculated by summing the CO ₂ -equivalent emissions associated with each	No.

				stage of the product lifecycle, from material sourcing through production and distribution to the end-of-life.	
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	Many textile companies report life cycle GHG emissions in their annual sustainability reports, CDP submissions, and ESG disclosures. Third-party certifications: Certifications like CarbonNeutral or Climate Neutral often require life cycle GHG reporting as part of certification criteria, providing independently verified data on emissions. Life cycle GHG emissions are measured through LCAs, which track emissions at each stage of the product lifecycle and express them in CO ₂ -equivalents.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Percentage of biological materials (such as wool) used in the textile industry in the region compared to total materials used	Many brands and manufacturers report biological material percentages in sustainability reports and on product labels, especially if they meet certification standards such as GOTS, OEKO-TEX, or Cradle to Cradle. The percentage of biological materials is typically measured by comparing the weight, volume, or cost of biological inputs to the total material input in textile production. This is often aggregated and reported on a per-product or annual basis.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Water consumption per kilogram of textiles produced in the textile industry in the region	Many large textile manufacturers publish water consumption data in sustainability reports. Measurement methods include water footprinting, direct water consumption audits, and real-time monitoring systems used by manufacturers. Corporate sustainability reports often present water consumption data per unit of production (e.g., per garment, per ton of fabric).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Material extracted compared to economic value added (kg/€), OR reduction of CO ₂ emissions per unit of textile production compared to previous years	Many textile companies report on material efficiency and emissions reductions as part of annual sustainability reports and ESG disclosures. Certifications such as ISO 14001 for environmental management and the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) provide frameworks that help companies track, manage, and disclose data on material and emissions efficiency. This measure is calculated by dividing the total material input in kilograms by the economic value added in euros or another currency. Companies	No.

				track material use and value added through production reports and financial statements.	
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Percentage of recycled textile materials used in the regional textile production	Many textile companies and brands report on recycled material use in sustainability reports often broken down by product lines or material types. Standards like the Global Recycled Standard (GRS), Recycled Claim Standard (RCS), and Textile Exchange’s Material Change Index require companies to track and verify recycled content in their products. The recycled material percentage is measured by dividing the weight or volume of recycled materials by the total material inputs in textile production, expressed as a percentage of the total materials used annually or regionally.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Use of textile materials derived from sustainably managed forests (e.g., wool from sheep fed sustainable feed)	Many textile companies report on material efficiency and emissions reductions as part of annual sustainability reports and ESG disclosures. Certifications such as ISO 14001 for environmental management and the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) provide frameworks that help companies track, manage, and disclose data on material and emissions efficiency. This measure is calculated by dividing the total material input in kilograms by the economic value added in euros or another currency.	No.

As observed, most of the environmental indicators analysed for the textile sector have data available at both the corporate/company and governmental levels. Furthermore, international standards exist for the calculation of certain indicators, offering frameworks that facilitate measurement by companies. However, there remains one indicator “% of materials derived from animal by-products” for which transparency is notably lacking, and it is unclear whether this information is routinely reported by companies.

4.4.1.7 Economic indicators

Table 25 provides an overview of economic indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (i.e., 10 indicators in total).

The indicators examined in relation to the SOs of “Employment and Economic Competitiveness” have data available at both the corporate/company and governmental levels, with calculation methodologies accessible across all tiers. In contrast, when analysing indicators associated with the SO of “Just inclusive and resilient economy,” significant challenges arise due to the lack of information at the regional level or the inconsistency of the available data. Furthermore, the calculation methods for certain indicators differ across regions, rendering the data non-comparable and, as a result, not quantifiable on a broader scale (e.g., at the EU level).

Table 25. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the Latxa sheep wool case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Raw Material/Utility costs	Many companies in the textile sector provide data on raw material and utility costs in their financial or sustainability reports. Regarding the raw material costs, they are collected via surveys of manufacturers and suppliers, combined with global market price data. Utility costs data are collected through governmental agencies, which monitor industrial energy and water consumption.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Transport	Many industry associations publish transport cost benchmarks. Many companies track transport expenses as part of operational budgets. These costs may be disclosed in financial reports under logistics or distribution expenses. Transport expenses are calculated as the total expenses associated with moving goods, including fuel, labour, maintenance, tariffs, and taxes.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Life cycle cost (or total undiscounted cost)	Some companies provide life cycle cost data as part of their sustainability reports. LCC is frequently studied in research projects, particularly in relation to sustainable textiles and circular economy practices. Total undiscounted costs incurred across the life cycle of a product (including raw material costs, production costs, distribution costs, usage costs and end-of-life costs).	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Personnel	Many textile companies report personnel costs in their financial statements (under operating expenses) and sustainability reports (related to social impact and workforce data). In addition, industry associations publish aggregated personnel cost data for benchmarking. Personnel costs include, direct wages, salaries, benefits, overtime payments, training costs, etc. It is calculated by dividing total personnel costs by the number of employees.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	N° of new sustainable technologies integrated	Many textile companies highlight the integration of sustainable technologies in their sustainability reports or innovation announcements. This is because the adoption of such technologies can significantly enhance competitiveness.	No.

			into the regional textile industry		
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Research and development investments in the textile industry in the region (in relation to total turnover)	This is a critical indicator for assessing innovation and competitiveness in the sector. Organisations and regional industry associations provide insights into R&D spending trends. In addition, textile companies often disclose R&D expenditures in their financial reports or sustainability reports, particularly in innovation-driven segments like smart textiles or sustainable materials. This indicator is typically measured as a % of turnover (or revenue) directly related to these investments.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Investments in sustainable infrastructure for the regional textile industry (e.g., water recycling plants, waste treatment plants)	Publicly traded textile companies often include sustainable infrastructure investments in their sustainability reports. Governments often track infrastructure investments through environmental impact assessments (EIAs). Research papers and studies often focus on specific technologies or regions, providing data on the effectiveness and scale of infrastructure investments. This indicator is being calculated performing the sum of the monetary investment in sustainable infrastructure, i.e., the number or capacity of installed facilities (e.g., water recycling plants, waste treatment units, etc.).	No.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection	Average income of families in rural communities involved in the textile industry of the region	Governmental statistics offices often publish data on household incomes by industry and regions. Some companies publish wage and income impact assessments as part of their CSR reports or sustainability initiatives. This indicator is typically measured through household income surveys, company disclosures, and industry reports.	Yes. Challenges include accounting for informal employment (jobs that are not regulated by formal contracts, lack social protections, and are often not officially documented) and regional variability (income levels and economic conditions in rural textile communities vary widely due to differences in market access, cultural practices, etc.).

7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection	Financial support provided to small textile businesses in the region to promote innovation	Governments often track financial support allocated to SMEs especially for innovation-related programs. This support is in the form of grants, loans, tax incentives, or subsidies aimed at improving technological capabilities or sustainability practices in the textile sector.	<p>Yes. Challenges in measuring this indicator can be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data may be scattered across various levels of government, private companies, and NGOs, making it difficult to get a comprehensive overview. • Financial support programs may differ significantly by region and sector, with varied criteria for what constitutes "innovation". • Some SMEs receive micro-funding or informal financial support, which is difficult to track in official reports. • The availability of financial support for innovation can vary significantly depending on the region, making it challenging to obtain data for all textile-producing regions globally.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Monitoring and accountability systems	Quantity of textile waste generated compared to total production in the regional textile industry.	Reports from industry groups such as Ellen MacArthur Foundation may include aggregated data on textile waste generation. These reports typically focus on industry-wide sustainability practices and waste management. The quantity of textile waste is often reported in terms of weight (e.g., kilograms or tons) relative to total production output (e.g., tons of fabric produced). This gives a waste-to-production ratio, often expressed as a percentage. Many large textile companies publish annual sustainability reports, which may include information on their waste generation and efforts to reduce waste.	<p>Yes, there are some challenges related to this indicator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different companies and regions may use different definitions and methods for calculating waste, making it difficult to compare data across industries or regions. • Some textile businesses, particularly small producers, may not report waste generation data or may not have systems in place to track waste effectively. • Complexity of textile waste can make it challenging to measure the total amount of waste generated and its relation to production. • Lack of consistency: Waste management practices vary widely, and some companies may report only certain types of waste (e.g., fabric scraps) while excluding others (e.g., water waste or chemical waste).

4.4.1.8 Social indicators

Table 26 provides an overview of social indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (i.e., 11 indicators in total).

As evident, measuring and interpreting social indicators is an inherently complex task. Tools such as the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) offer valuable data on some of the previously mentioned indicators at the country-specific sector level. However, it is important to note that not all indicators are included, and in no case is data available at the regional level. Furthermore, other data collected by organisations or companies within the sector often lacks a consistent measurement framework, which hinders meaningful comparison. Another significant challenge lies in data collection, particularly in sensitive areas and developing countries. This difficulty extends to small enterprises, irrespective of the country under consideration.

Table 26. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the Latxa sheep wool case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
6	Food safety, disease prevention and human health are ensured, Human health	Human health	Particulate matter as respiratory inorganics / product unit (kg eq. PM2.5)	This indicator is commonly measured as part of LCAs. EPDs and sustainability reports from textile brands and manufacturers include data on particulate matter.	Yes. Gaps exist in SMEs due to limited resources and technical capacity.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Labour rights	Forced Labour	Tools like the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) assess forced labour risks at different stages of the production process. Forced labour is being measured and monitored extensively, particularly in high-risk regions and industries.	Yes. Forced labour is often hidden, and detecting it requires extensive fieldwork and reliable reporting mechanisms.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Labour rights	Freedom of Association	Some manufacturers report on union representation and collective bargaining agreements as part of their CSR or even sustainability reports.	Yes. Gaps exist in some countries since it difficult to measure or enforce freedom of association. Regarding the supply chains, in certain cases many violations occur, and supervision is difficult to carry out.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Labour rights	Migrant Labour	Some international organisations provide reports on global data related to migrant labour trends, risks, and protections. Some brands include metrics on migrant labour in their sustainability or CSR reports, particularly when addressing supply chain risks. Tools like the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) assess migrant labour risks in specific regions and sectors.	Yes. Challenges may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant labour abuses, such as debt bondage or human trafficking, are often concealed, making data collection difficult. • Many migrant workers in the textile sector operate in informal or subcontracted roles, complicating monitoring efforts. • Supply chain complexity and limited oversight hinder accurate reporting on migrant labour conditions.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Respect of indigenous rights and land rights	Indigenous Rights	Indigenous peoples are directly affected by land acquisition, resource extraction, or other industrial activities. Local governments and indigenous organisations sometimes publish data or case studies on land use conflicts and resource extraction affecting Indigenous populations. In addition, some companies report on their impact	Yes. Challenges may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Textile supply chains involve multiple tiers, making it difficult to trace the impacts on indigenous communities. • Many indigenous communities operate in remote or politically sensitive areas, where data collection is challenging.

				on indigenous communities, especially in raw material sourcing, through sustainability and CSR reports.	
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Resilience of rural communities - social protection	Involvement of rural communities in decisions relating to the regional textile industry	The UN Development Programme, and the World Bank often include community involvement as part of their assessments of rural development and industrial impact. In addition, manufacturers and governments in textile-producing regions publish data on public consultations or community involvement in industrial projects.	Yes. Challenges may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inconsistent measurement framework. • Data gaps. • Even when consultations occur, rural communities may lack the power or resources to influence decisions meaningfully.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Inclusiveness	Number of training programmes or technical cooperation of the regional textile industry with developing countries to promote sustainability	Many brands report on training and capacity-building initiatives in their annual sustainability or CSR reports. The United Nations Development Programme, and the World Bank document technical cooperation and capacity-building programs in textiles and related industries. It can be measured considering number of training sessions conducted, and number of trained participants (e.g., workers, managers).	Yes. Challenges may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inconsistent measurement framework, making cross-comparison difficult. • Programs may not always reach smaller suppliers or marginalised groups within the workforce.
8	Risk assessment and monitoring	Monitoring and accountability systems	Legal System	The World Justice Project's Rule of Law Index assesses the effectiveness of legal systems worldwide, including metrics like enforcement of regulations and access to justice. National governments publish labour laws, environmental regulations, trade laws, and compliance mechanisms that impact the textile sector. In addition, brands and suppliers often report their adherence to local and international legal requirements in sustainability and CSR reports.	Yes. Challenges may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Even when laws exist, enforcement can be weak or uneven, especially in developing countries. • Inefficient legal systems in developing countries may create barriers to compliance, particularly for smaller manufacturers.
8	Risk assessment and monitoring	Monitoring and accountability systems	Corruption	Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) provides a country-level assessment of perceived corruption in public sectors, indirectly reflecting conditions that affect the textile industry. The World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) include metrics on control of corruption and governance effectiveness. In addition, companies with strong	Yes. Challenges may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most corruption data is not industry-specific, making it challenging to isolate textile-related issues. • Fear of legal consequences often leads to underreporting of corruption incidents. • The fragmented and multi-tiered nature of textile supply chains makes tracking and addressing corruption difficult.

				sustainability programs may disclose anti-corruption policies, risk assessments, and incident reports in their CSR reports.	
9	Promoting global governance and collaboration	Partnerships and cooperation	Number of partnerships between the regional textile industry and international organisations or other global industries to promote sustainability	Many companies report on partnerships in their sustainability reports. NGOs involved in textile-related projects often release reports or case studies detailing their collaborations with industry players. This indicator can be measured by considering the number of partnerships or collaborative agreements reported annually, geographic, and sectoral coverage of these partnerships.	<p>Yes. Challenges may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data on partnerships is often reported inconsistently across organisations, making it hard to compile a complete picture. • There is no framework for measuring the sustainability impacts of these partnerships.
9	Promoting global governance and collaboration	Partnerships and cooperation	Number of partnerships between the textile industry in the region and local organisations to support the development of rural communities	Many companies, report on their partnerships with local organisations in rural communities. These reports often include initiatives for rural development, including education programs, infrastructure projects, and community health improvements. In addition, many companies, especially those committed to sustainability, report on their partnerships with local organisations in rural communities. These reports often include initiatives for rural development, including education programs, infrastructure projects, and community health improvements.	<p>Yes. Challenges may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While partnerships and activities may be documented, measuring the long-term impact of these initiatives on rural development can be difficult, especially in terms of tangible improvements in income, education, or health. • The number and scope of partnerships may vary significantly depending on the region or the specific needs of rural communities, making data collection inconsistent across different areas.

4.4.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

This section offers an in-depth examination of the perspectives shared by several experts during interviews. The participants include José Monzonís, General Director of the Observatorio Textil; Gema Gómez, founder of Slow Fashion Next; and Héctor Viniegra, Market & Business Development Manager for Circularity at TECNALIA, which also brings a wealth of industry experience and serves as a lecturer in the master’s program on “Sustainable Fashion Design and Circularity” at the IED Kunsthal Higher Design Center (Bilbao). The analysis aimed to explore their insights on the topics discussed in this document and assess their reflections on the outcomes of the DESIGN Conference held in September 2024. The main findings of the analysis are summarised as follows:

- The textile sector faces significant challenges that hinder its transformation towards sustainability, including high costs, insufficient market incentives for biobased materials, and inadequate recycling infrastructure. Recycling and biobased materials incur additional costs but are not rewarded or incentivised by the market. Furthermore, overconsumption, largely driven by fast fashion and low prices, exacerbates the environmental footprint of the industry, leading to the depletion of essential resources like water and increasing carbon emissions. Waste, particularly in the wool sector, also presents a challenge, with much of the wool produced in the EU going unused due to a lack of processing facilities. Wool’s higher costs compared to synthetic fibres, coupled with unresolved technical and pollution-related issues, make it difficult for wool to compete with petroleum-derived alternatives. Moreover, the absence of a clear regulatory framework that encourages recycling over the use of virgin materials prevents the textile sector from fully embracing sustainability. The failure to use renewable raw materials limits efforts toward climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation.
- From a consumer perspective, business models have created a culture based on volume-driven consumption, which has become deeply embedded in societal norms. Our society thrives on rapid change, fast consumption, and immediate pleasure, promoting a cycle of consumption that extends beyond textiles to many other sectors. This fast fashion culture, along with constant social comparisons, has shaped consumer behaviour and decision-making, driving unsustainable practices. To address this, a coordinated effort is needed across all challenges—sustainability, market incentives, policy frameworks, and consumer education—to change the current consumption and production models. Such a shift would require transforming not only production but also communication and consumer behaviour.
- Several good practices are emerging to tackle these challenges. One key strategy is to promote educational policies that encourage sustainable consumer behaviour and production practices. These policies should raise awareness about the importance of sustainability and regulate the influx of low-quality products, particularly from fast-fashion brands. A critical tool for enhancing transparency is the Digital Product Passport (DPP), which can provide detailed information about products’ carbon footprints and material origins.
- Additionally, industries should promote the repairability of products as a standard. Repair should be mandatory for every product on the market, with characteristics clearly

supporting this feature, and products that cannot be repaired should be subject to a higher cost or potentially banned from sale. To enable this, models should be created to certify products as repairable, ensuring durability in design. If repair is not feasible, the cost of such garments should reflect the lack of longevity and repairability, encouraging consumers to prioritise sustainable options.

- Another key recommendation is to address the wool market's failure to adapt and rethink its industrial processes. The EU could consider establishing a strategic industrialisation program to leverage its historical knowledge and expertise in wool processing. This initiative could help create a competitive hub for wool production by fostering innovation and improving the industry's efficiency and profitability.
- At the policy level, significant challenges remain, including a lack of guidance on sustainability claims, such as recyclability and the environmental footprint of products. To address this, collaboration structures such as Ecodesign criteria, certification, and labelling should be established, ensuring that sustainability claims are standardised and credible. Moreover, the high additional costs of recycling and using biobased materials remain a significant barrier, and practices such as increased market surveillance, green public procurement, and modulating Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) fees based on Ecodesign criteria can help incentivise sustainable production practices. Overconsumption, which amplifies the carbon footprint of the textile sector, must be tackled through educational policies that promote sustainable production methods.
- In the wool sector, the lack of facilities for washing and processing wool remains a significant issue, compounded by technical and pollution-related challenges. To address this, aid policies for industrial washing facilities and technological advancements should be developed, along with support for existing facilities. Furthermore, introducing Ecodesign criteria and certification that promote recycling over the use of virgin materials is critical for driving sustainability within the sector.
- Sustainability challenges in the textile sector also include a lack of transparency and traceability. To overcome this, market surveillance and the adoption of DPPs should be encouraged, along with robust certifications for companies and public authorities. Investment in research and innovation is also crucial to foster sustainable products, processes, and recycling technologies, enabling sustainable practices to scale.
- The market dimension faces challenges in promoting sustainable business models. One challenge is the higher cost of garment repairs, which makes these models less competitive. By promoting Ecodesign criteria, increasing market surveillance, and stimulating garment repair business models, this issue can be addressed. Additionally, modulating EPR fees and establishing standards to reduce the production costs of biobased fibres will support sustainable business models. Temporary green VAT measures, such as reducing VAT to 10% for sustainable products, can further incentivise these practices.
- Experts highlight that, in recent decades, textile garment consumption has surged in Europe, North America, and especially in the Asia-Pacific region. This increase, fuelled by higher disposable incomes, population growth, and changing business models, underscores the need for a fundamental shift in consumption patterns and production processes. By addressing the challenges of overconsumption, environmental impact, and inefficiency, the textile industry can begin its transformation into a more sustainable sector that supports the regeneration of natural resources and contributes positively to climate change mitigation.

4.4.6 Key learnings of Latxa sheep wool case study

The pressing environmental challenges associated with the textile industry, notably those stemming from fast fashion and escalating production levels, have necessitated a heightened focus on sustainability and the adoption of circular economy principles. Within this context, innovative initiatives, such as the valorisation of traditionally discarded Latxa sheep wool in the Basque Country, Spain, exemplify the potential to transform waste into valuable, sustainable materials, contributing to the development of a biobased economy.

The advancement of sustainability within the textile sector relies on a diverse range of stakeholders. Policymakers and government agencies play a particularly influential role through regulatory frameworks. Policies such as the ESPR have the greatest potential to drive the sustainability transition within the textile sector. This legislation aims to promote sustainability and circularity in the European textile market through measures like the establishment of design criteria and the introduction of a "Digital Product Passport" to enhance traceability. Consumers further drive the demand for sustainable goods, while textile manufacturers and retailers bear significant responsibility for integrating renewable materials into production processes. Conversely, wool producers, farmers, and research institutions contribute meaningfully to this transition but are more dependent on overarching market dynamics and policy direction.

Still, many stakeholders such as manufacturers and retailers resist transitioning from linear, fossil-based models to circular approaches posing a significant hindrance. Their reluctance may stem from perceived economic risks, or the higher costs associated with adopting sustainable practices. Similarly, the lack of standardised regional policies or fragmented enforcement mechanisms undermines progress, as inconsistent regulations create barriers to uniform adoption of circular economy practices.

In addition, significant challenges persist in assessing and measuring sustainability within the textile sector. While many environmental indicators are supported by established international standards, transparency remains deficient for certain metrics, such as the proportion of materials derived from animal by-products. Social indicators, particularly those concerning inclusivity and resilience, encounter even greater obstacles due to inconsistent data availability at regional levels and divergent methodological approaches, limiting comparability and scalability. Resources such as the Social Hotspots Database offer valuable data for assessing social impacts but lack comprehensive coverage and regional specificity. The absence of standardised data collection frameworks further exacerbates these challenges, particularly in regions with underdeveloped infrastructures or in small enterprises globally. This highlights the critical need for unified methodologies to ensure effective evaluation and meaningful progress in sustainability.

Inadequate data collection and transparency may undermine the ability of policymakers, manufacturers, and consumers to make informed decisions. The lack of clear metrics hinders the effective monitoring of impacts, slowing the transition to a sustainable system.

The integration of circular economy principles into the textile industry, as illustrated by the valorisation of Latxa wool, represents a pivotal advancement toward environmental sustainability

and economic resilience. In this direction, addressing the following barriers is essential to fully realise the potential of such initiatives:

- Integration of circular economy principles: Sustainable transformation requires embedding circular economy practices into every aspect of the textile industry, from raw material sourcing to production and waste management.
- Transparency as a catalyst: Tools like DPPs enable traceability and accountability, fostering informed decision-making by policymakers, manufacturers, and consumers.
- Coordinated policy enforcement: Robust implementation of policies like the ESPR and financial incentives can mitigate economic risks and encourage adoption of sustainable practices.
- Economic incentives for sustainability: Measures such as reduced VAT for sustainable products and higher taxes on fossil-based materials can drive the transition to biobased alternatives.
- Empowering innovation and local industries: Strategic programs for sectors like wool can leverage historical expertise, enhancing competitiveness and sustainability.
- Mandatory standards for reparability and durability: Regulation of reparability and durability in design can promote longevity and reduce waste.
- Stakeholder collaboration: Effective partnerships and shared frameworks are essential to unify sustainability efforts and scale impact across regions and sectors.
- Standardised evaluation mechanisms: Harmonised frameworks for data collection and assessment can address gaps in measuring environmental and social impacts, enabling progress toward sustainability goals.

In conclusion, the textile sector's journey toward sustainability hinges on addressing challenges holistically through enhanced collaboration, robust policy frameworks, and innovative solutions. By fostering transparency, incentivising sustainable practices, and leveraging tools like the DPP, the industry can achieve transformative progress. The integration of circular economy principles, coupled with the revitalisation of traditional industries like wool, offers a pathway to a sustainable, equitable, and resilient future. Through collective action and strategic alignment, stakeholders can drive meaningful change, mitigating environmental impacts while fostering social and economic resilience.

5 RESULTS FROM THE CHEMICALS SECTOR CASE STUDIES

Within SUSTRACK, research was conducted on three case studies that highlight key bio-based advancements in the chemicals sector. The insights gathered from these case studies played a critical role in guiding sector-specific discussions during stakeholder consultations. The first chemical case study focuses on waste-to-methanol, a process that converts waste streams into a valuable chemical feedstock, supporting circularity and reducing reliance on fossil-based methanol. The second case study examines bio-MEG and bio-MPG, renewable alternatives to fossil-derived monoethylene glycol (MEG) and monopropylene glycol (MPG), widely used in the production of plastics, resins, and solvents. The third case study explores renewable functional fillers from wood, which serve as sustainable additives in polymer applications, enhancing material performance while reducing environmental impact.

The following section summarizes the key insights from the SUSTRACK DESIGN workshop discussions, incorporating perspectives from stakeholders connected to these case studies and the broader chemical industry.

5.1 Sector-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Market dimension

Challenges

- One of the main challenges faced is related to access to financing. Most of the developed biobased chemicals are new technologies and not yet at a mature stage. Lack of existing supply chain for biobased materials, result in the first mover risk. There is need for finances to secure the capital expenditure (CAPEX) required for the first-of-a-kind plants. Yet, the high-risk involved results in hesitation of investors.
- If public funding exists (see good practices section below), it typically covers only part of the cost, and only the CAPEX (i.e., capital expenditure, or initial costs), not the OPEX (i.e., operational expenditure). The OPEX needed strongly depends on various factors, e.g., demand and supply of feedstocks. This brings along strong uncertainties for potential investors
- Another major challenge concerns cost-competitiveness of biobased chemicals in comparison to their conventional fossil based counterparts. The fossil based chemicals are already optimised and mature, yet biobased chemicals are mostly in the development phase. This results in higher cost of production of biobased compared with fossil-based chemicals.
- Other challenges that were identified for the chemical sector include the difficulty in coupling sectors that have not been connected before due to the emerging nature of biobased products in comparison to fossil based products with a well-established infrastructure. Also, fluctuation in the costs and availability of biomass raw materials poses a challenge. Especially, considering the competition for biomass from different sectors (e.g., food/feed, fuels, chemicals) the availability of feedstock towards 2050 could be challenging.

Recommendations/good practices

- Providing of sufficient (public) financing of first-of-a-kind chemical plants in Europe would allow the development and further deployment of the biobased chemicals. It was emphasised that the collaborating with the sustainable finance sector should be sought to create market incentives.
- For value chains that make use of secondary resources, creation of an after-use economy is needed. Similarly for utilisation of residues from fields and industry, the necessary infrastructure should be established. These actions will also be supportive of the transition towards a circular economy.
- Other good practices that were identified include voicing a clear statement of which problem needs to be solved and conducting a reality check of ambitions.

Policy dimension

Challenges

- The main challenge is the lack of specific regulatory support for biobased products in comparison with biobased energy (i.e., with RED). This favours the energetic applications of the same product (such as ethanol or methanol) rather than the chemical applications. Thereby, also blocks the further conversion of this product to derivative chemicals to be used in the chemical industry to replace petrochemical products.
- It is also noted that there is generally lack of stability and harmonisation in policymaking. This does not provide security to investors to invest in these new technologies and further market growth of established biobased chemicals. There is currently not enough policy support for upscaling (vis-à-vis needed timescales, risks, and cost).
- The focus of existing policies is on decarbonisation. The correct focus should be on defossilisation instead. Since the chemical sector relies on carbon, decarbonisation is not an option. A challenge related to this is adequate carbon tracking and accounting. This requires collaboration among complex value chains with multiple partners all over the world.

Recommendations/good practices

- Firstly, policy coherence is sought after. This calls for international collaboration for regulatory alignment to safeguard competitiveness, to prevent shifting production to Asia, where it is less expensive, and less circular. The Carbon Border Adjustment Measure could address this challenge effectively.
- Governments should develop a clear, unified vision, set objectives, and define actions to gradually change the system as it is now. Subsequently, the industry can provide fitting solutions to achieve these objectives. Resilience and reliability of the industry are key in reconciling business and societal objectives.
- Additionally, policy support for biobased chemicals is needed for companies to remain competitive in the sustainability transformation. This will create an enabling environment to provide security (i.e., safeguard investments), support market entry and growth. This can be in the form of premiums and mandates for the use of biobased chemicals. It could also be by penalising the use of virgin fossil inputs (e.g., carbon tax).

- It is important to foster sustainable and renewable carbon cycles. Renewable carbon circulates between biosphere, atmosphere or Technosphere, creating a circular carbon economy. For this implementing transparent carbon tracking along the value chain will be relevant where collaboration would be needed among the stakeholders within the value chain.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- The current chemical sector still relies heavily on the use of virgin fossil feedstocks. The biobased chemicals are required to prove that they are sustainable, but no such requirement is posed on petrochemicals.
- For bioenergy and biofuels, RED sets sustainability criteria to be met, no such set of common sustainability criteria exists at EU level for biobased chemicals.
- There is lack of data and knowledge needed to be able to carry out sustainability assessment of biobased products. It is seen that environmental performance is the one being most assessed but there is challenges especially in making estimations on economic and social performance due lack of data.
- There is absence of a proper and harmonised LCA methodology for the assessment of biobased products to provide assessment and steer further development in the most sustainable direction. Especially, the different approaches adopted for biogenic carbon accounting in cradle-to-gate and cradle-to-grave assessments, create confusion and inconsistencies.

Recommendations/good practices

- By providing education awareness can be fostered about the benefits of the sustainable bioeconomy and the risks of the fossil economy.
- Harmonised evaluation along the value chain (e.g., in the variety of systems, scopes and methods) is sought after through common guidance at the EU level.
- Further development and application of the Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) framework for biobased chemicals will be beneficial to generate more knowledge and information on the sustainability performance of biobased chemicals considering all the different aspects and pillars of sustainability.
- It is recommended to use the European Standard EN18027 *Biobased products - Life cycle assessment - Additional requirements and guidelines for comparing the life cycles of biobased products* as guidance for carrying out comparative LCAs of biobased products with fossil based products. Revision of the PEF method of EC with regard to this guidance e.g., in terms of biogenic carbon accounting, to provide a fair comparison of biobased products with their fossil based counterparts.

5.2 Chemical - Waste-to-methanol

5.2.1 Introduction to waste-to-methanol case study

5.2.1.1 General description

This value chain concerns the conversion of (non-recyclable, non-compostable) municipal solid waste (MSW) into methanol, ethanol and other widely used chemicals. Bio-methanol is a drop-in chemical, chemically identical to fossil-based methanol (i.e., CHO_3H). Currently, nearly all methanol is produced from synthesis gas (i.e., syngas). Biobased syngas can be produced through the gasification of various biomass sources, as well as MSW. In 2019, the total methanol demand amounted to 98 million tonnes worldwide, with applications in a multiplicity of sectors and end-products such as clothing, adhesives, paint, pharmaceuticals, building materials and car parts (IRENA & METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2021). This signifies the importance of methanol in the context of the global market.

Gasification technologies are not a recent innovation. Among the eldest, and most popular processes of gasification is the well-proven Winkler process, developed by Fritz Winkler (BASF). As early as in 1926, the first Winkler gasifier was introduced at an industrial scale in Germany, and fed with fine-grained, brown coal. Ever since, the Winkler gasification process has found various alternative feedstock sources and applications around the world. One of these is the gasification of MSW as a waste treatment and chemical conversion method (Adlhoch et al., 2000).

5.2.1.2 Value chain and the process

This case study is on the waste-to-methanol value chain. To be able to understand the transition to waste-based chemicals production, it is useful to compare it against a baseline. In this case, the baseline is represented by conventional, fossil-based methanol production, with natural gas as its primary feedstock.

In the conventional, natural gas-based methanol value chain, natural gas is sourced and transported to the production plant. Next, it is transformed into syngas by steam methane reforming (SMR), a mature production process in which high-temperature steam (at $700\text{-}1000^\circ\text{C}$) is used to produce syngas (mixture of hydrogen- H_2 and carbon monoxide- CO) from natural gas. Next, the water-gas shift (WGS) reaction, describing the reaction of CO and water vapor to form CO_2 and H_2 , is carried out to optimise CO to H_2 ratios. The final step is methanol formation, through the reaction of CO and H_2 . This is followed by transportation to and utilisation by an industrial manufacturer or end-user (Sarp et al., 2021).

Figure 32. Value chain of the waste-to-methanol system

As for the waste-to-methanol value chain, the production process is described following Enerkem’s multi-step process technology (de Leeuw and Koelemeijer, 2022; Iaquaniello et al., 2017), as depicted in Figure 32 and Figure 33:

- **Feedstock preparation:**

To begin with, the MSW is collected and transported to a waste treatment facility. The MSW is subjected to a sorting, separation, and shredding process to make refuse-derived fuel (RDF), meaning the glass, metal and moisture fractions are removed from the MSW, so that a higher concentration of paper, plastic and high-energy organics is obtained.

- **Feedstock gasification:**

Next, the RDF is fed to a bubbling fluidised bed (BFB) gasification vessel to break down the shredded material into its constituent molecules (at $\pm 700^{\circ}\text{C}$), through a process called thermal cracking. In the same reactor, the reaction of these broken-down molecules with steam generated syngas. This syngas is rich in H_2 and CO , but also contains CO_2 and water, rendering its purity not sufficient for methanol production.

- **Cleaning and conditioning:**

Therefore, the crude syngas is fed into a syngas cleaning and conditioning process, which upgrades the crude syngas to chemical grade that allows for its conversion into liquid fuels and chemicals. The concentration of toxic components, such as sulphur and chloride, is reduced to ppm-level (i.e., parts per million). It is through the combination of the BFB gasification reactor and the syngas cleaning and conditioning process that the purity and composition of the syngas can be controlled.

- **Catalytic conversion:**

Finally, catalytic conversion takes place to transform the chemical-grade syngas into liquid methanol and ethanol. A combination of in-process controls and quality analysis are used to ensure and confirm that all the company’s products consistently meet the required specifications. Further downstream the value chain, the intermediary products attained by Enerkem can follow multiple pathways to range of chemicals (e.g., ethylene and propylene) and fuels (e.g., marine fuels and sustainable aviation fuels (SAF)).

Figure 33. Schematic representation of waste-based methanol production by Enerkem (2023)

The conversion efficiency for MSW to methanol is about 40-60% (based on the feedstock lower heating value at plant gate). It has been shown that a waste-based methanol production system can generate about 41 kg/h methanol by utilising 100 kg/h raw MSW as feedstock, as well as self-supply the electricity required throughout the whole process (Hakandai, Pramano and Aziz, 2022).

Recently, other companies have also been working on the development and commercialisation of technologies, either novel or based on traditional technologies, aimed at the production of syngas or methanol from waste. By means of example, two initiatives taken by the Dutch companies GIDARA Energy and DOPS Recycling Technologies (RT), are highlighted in the present case study.

GIDARA Energy was founded in 2019 and seeks to act as a bridge between combined waste and biobased feedstocks and the market for sustainable fuels and circular chemicals through gasification. To this end, the company has acquired the High-Temperature Winkler (HTW) technology which, as described in the introductory section, dates back to the 1920s, and as such is referred to as the “most developed proven gasification technology utilising waste-based feedstocks” (GIDARA Energy, n.d.). GIDARA Energy’s flagship project is the Advanced Methanol Amsterdam project, to be established in the Port of Amsterdam.

As with Enerkem’s technology, the HTW gasifier is a BFB reactor. This dry-feed, pressurised, dry-ash gasifier operates in either air or oxygen-blown modes, which enables the use of its product outputs for material applications. Traditionally, the HTW technology was utilised for the gasification of fossil feedstocks (e.g., brown coal). Throughout the years, however, the technology has been developed further in order to allow for gasification of a wide variety of feedstocks (including RDF and MSW). Typical for this technology is the high outlet temperature, which results in a syngas free of any higher molecular weight hydrocarbons, such as tars, phenols, and other heavy aromatics (GIDARA Energy, n.d.).

The other noteworthy example is DOPS RT, a company founded in 2021 in the Dutch city of Alkmaar. DOPS RT is developing the so-called Direct Carbon Immobilisation (DCI) technology, a

gasification technology rooted in the metallurgical industry, where it served for coke making. DOPS RT has adapted the technology to enable the production of valuable chemical building blocks for the circular economy, including methanol. Currently, the DCI technology has reached TRL 6, with further pilots and demonstrations planned for 2025 (DOPS RT, n.d.).

Whereas traditionally, gasification is done through a multi-step process (as is the case for technologies exploited by Enerkem and GIDARA Energy), DCI features a one-step, potentially more cost-effective solution. DCI works with a solid plug flow reactor, by means of gravity moves. At 1000 °C, the feedstock is depolymerised and cracked into small molecules (i.e., CO and H₂). These serve as building blocks for complex molecules. Contrary to traditional gasification technologies, DCI allows for various different feedstock ratios to tailor the properties of gas output to downstream demands. As such, DOPS RT has explored processing with 20 different feedstock types, e.g., waste wood in various grades, laminated wind blades, and e-waste like printed circuit boards. The yields heavily depended on the hydrocarbon content, as well as the minerals and metals fractions (personal communication, DOPS RT, September 3rd, 2024).

5.2.1.3 Baseline and market

Currently, most methanol produced worldwide is fossil-based. About 80% of methanol production uses natural gas as feedstock, about 17% uses coal, with the rest using coke gas and other feedstocks (such as biomass and MSW). Methanol production from coal predominantly takes place in China. In Europe, methanol production draws primarily on natural gas. In most methanol plants, natural gas is simultaneously used as a process fuel (Iaquaniello et al., 2017; METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2022).

Figure 34 illustrates the total market demand for methanol in 2019, which amounts to 98 million tonnes (IRENA & METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2021). Methanol is currently widely applied as a feedstock for a multiplicity of fuels and chemicals. In terms of fuels, it is for example popular in the production of methyl tert-butyl ether (MTBE) as an octane booster for petrol, and in gasoline blending. Regarding chemicals, methanol is commonly applied in formaldehyde-based resins, which are used in an array of household products (e.g., laminates and paper). Other product groups that rely on this highly versatile chemical building block include textiles, adhesives, paints, pharmaceuticals, and car parts (IRENA & METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2021).

Figure 34. Global methanol demand per feedstock, divided in fuels and chemicals, in 2019 (Source: IRENA & METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2021)

In 2022, the European methanol market attained a volume of nearly 10.77 million tonnes, which corresponds to about 10% of the global demand. In the forecast period of 2023-2028, the market is estimated to increase with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 3.7-6.4% to reach 13.39-15.63 million tonnes by 2027. Extrapolating these growth rates to a global level would result in a total worldwide market volume of 131.06-160.98 million tonnes by 2027 (Expert Market Research, 2023; Research Dive, 2021).

Considering this growing demand for methanol, bio-methanol production has gained more ground in recent years, with multiple initiatives arising across the European continent, in particular in the Netherlands. A few notable examples are detailed in Table 27.

Table 27. Impression of recent waste-based methanol production initiatives across Europe

#	Project	Initiator	Status	Capacity (t waste/y)	Source
1	LowLands Methanol (NL)	LowLands Methanol	Planning, expected to be operational by 2025	120,000	Personal communication, LowLands Methanol, August 22 nd , 2023
2	Ecoplanta El Morell (ES)	Enerkem	Engineering, expected to be operational by 2028	400,000	REPSOL (n.d.)
3	Advanced Methanol Amsterdam (NL)	GIDARA Energy	Engineering, expected to be operating by 2025	360,000	Offshore Energy (2024)
4	DCI facility (NL)	DOPS RT	Piloting phase (TRL 6), expected to be operational in 2027	Unknown	DOPS RT (n.d.)

Another project initiated by Enerkem in the port of Rotterdam (the Netherlands), with a planned annual waste conversion capacity of 215,000 t, has been put on hold. Primary reason is that the main partner, Shell, decided to scale back its renewable energy projects. As such, short-term solutions are preferred, and the waste-to-methanol project does currently not match these priorities (personal communication, Enerkem, October 2nd, 2024).

Considering the identical chemical structure of fossil-based and non-fossil methanol, the waste-based alternative could directly replace its fossil counterpart in any of the current uses. At a European level, the increasing demand for (virgin fossil-free) methanol is expected to mainly arise from the expanding biofuel market. When it comes to the application of methanol as a chemical building block, a major opportunity may be found in the production of aromatics and polymers for plastics (e.g., BTX) (IRENA & METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2021; personal communication, LowLands Methanol).

One globally established player in the development of methanol technologies, Air Liquide, witnesses this rising interest in biomass and waste as feedstocks for methanol. While the company has provided over 70 technology licenses for conventional methanol production to the industry, recently also potential clients expressed their interest in waste-based methanol production. This might lead to its further commercialisation and rollout in the upcoming years (personal communication, Air Liquide).

5.2.2 Stakeholders in the waste-to-methanol value chain

5.2.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

To begin with, the stakeholders relevant to the waste-to-methanol value chain were determined by means of exploratory desk research (e.g., on websites of governmental organisations, and methanol-producing companies). Figure 35 *Figure 36* provides a schematic representation of the identified stakeholders, both in the Bioeconomy supply chain (i.e., the light green section) and its Enabling environment (i.e., the light grey section).

The Bioeconomy supply chain for the waste-to-methanol value chain involves a range of stakeholders. This section provides an overview of these stakeholders, accompanied by some examples specified to waste-to-methanol initiatives in the Netherlands. Upstream, households discard their residual waste, here referred to as municipal solid waste (MSW). Waste logistics and processing companies (e.g., RENEWI) are responsible for the collection, transport, and pre-treatment of the MSW. A set of pre-processing steps (i.e., sorting, shredding, drying, and baling) generates RDF as the intermediate product. The forthcoming RDF is transferred to a methanol-producing company (e.g., GIDARA Energy, Enerkem), and subjected to several conversion processes (e.g., gasification, methanol production), to generate waste-based methanol, and sold to a methanol-relying industrial party (e.g., fuel or chemical companies). Depending on the envisioned application, the methanol passes through several additional value chain stages (e.g., storage, retail, and sales and synthesis of an end-product). As waste-based and fossil-based methanol are chemically identical, hence interchangeable in terms of the application, the stakeholders linked to any further steps are beyond the scope of this analysis.

Regarding the Enabling environment, a distinction is made between governmental organisations, commercial entities, academia, and civil society. The examples of relevant stakeholders at the EU or international level provided directly link to the methanol value chain or the chemical sector. The first category involves policy makers at different geographical levels (at EU and national level, e.g., the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate), regional partnerships (e.g., Innovation-Quarter), supra-national organisations tied to the chemical sector (e.g., IEA, UN and OECD) and infrastructure providers (like in the utilities and logistics domain, e.g., Port of Rotterdam, Port of Amsterdam). In the second category, relevant stakeholders include providers of waste-to-methanol conversion technologies (e.g., Air Liquide), financial institutes (like banks, private equity, e.g., Ara Partners), trade and business associations (e.g., Methanol Sector Group, or MESG), and competitors with different feedstock such as CO₂ or natural gas (e.g., BASF AG, Ørsted). The third category concerns developers of certification schemes for sustainable chemicals (e.g., ISCC (2016)), non-governmental organisations (e.g., ECOS, EEB), and alliances and coalitions involved in policy making affecting the chemical industry (e.g., One Planet Network). The final category comprises knowledge institutes and universities that research (waste-based) methanol production processes (e.g., TU Darmstadt, TU Freiberg), incubators and spin-offs (e.g., LowLands Methanol).

Figure 35. Identified stakeholders in the waste-to-methanol value chain

5.2.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

Afterwards, the stakeholders identified as relevant were mapped in a power-interest matrix, based on a desk research and interviews with stakeholders. The result can be found in Figure 36.

Figure 36. Stakeholders of the waste-to-methanol value chain mapped in a power-interest matrix

As shown in the upper-right corner (high power, high interest), a successful transition to large-scale waste-based methanol production hinges on multiple stakeholders. These include players in the governmental domain, which through targeted policy instruments and regional partnerships could drive or impede the implementation of waste-based methanol production systems. Besides, methanol-relying industries still typically opt for fossil methanol as their primary feedstock, to minimise costs and stay competitive. However, the growing pressure on sustainable production may increasingly incentivise the chemical sector to actively explore fossil-free alternatives, such as waste-based methanol. Simultaneously, market competitors producing methanol from various renewable feedstocks, such as from CO₂ (i.e., e-methanol), may suppress the waste-based methanol demand (IRENA & METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2021).

The upper-left corner (high power, low interest) includes stakeholders such as trade and business associations, infrastructure providers and financial institutes, which have the power to directly

shape the conditions in which the waste to methanol value chain could either flourish or decay. These actors need to divide their limited resources (e.g., money, space, and influence through lobbying) among a multiplicity of requests and projects. For example, congestion in the energy grid was mentioned as one of the major challenges adversely affecting the progress of a waste-based methanol project in the Port of Rotterdam. In the same project, the absence of sufficient risk capital was identified as another major obstacle. These two challenges are currently being dealt with (e.g., by generating power in-house and securing investments), but do delay the upscaling of the waste-to-methanol value chain (personal communication, LowLands Methanol).

The lower right quarter (low power, high interest) comprises stakeholders that would benefit substantially from the transition to large-scale waste-to-methanol production, but whose influence is restricted. This section includes research institutes, incubators, spin-offs, certification schemes and non-governmental organisations. These organisations play an important role in the development of an innovation at low TRL, e.g., through pilot and demonstration projects. In the waste to methanol value chain, a couple of large, commercial players are readily active that could build on the knowledge obtained by these initiatives. As the transition to waste-to-methanol gains momentum, these stakeholders may prove increasingly fundamental and gradually move up to the right-upper quarter.

Finally, in the left bottom quart (low power, low interest), the households are positioned. Households are in this case the providers of MSW as a raw material for waste-based methanol production. The quality of the MSW (e.g., fraction of toxic substances), depends to an extent on the separation habits of the household. Apart from that, the influence of households on the waste-to-methanol value chain and interest in its success is expected to be minor.

5.2.3 Policies of relevance to waste-to-methanol value chain

In this section, policies were identified that could either propel or impede the implementation of the waste-to-methanol chain. These policies were detected through desk research and interviews with stakeholders. Table 28 provides an overview of the relevant policies at international, European, or national level. First, the EU policy landscape relevant for waste-based methanol (and waste-based chemicals generally) is sketched. Afterwards, several policies currently in place or in a preparatory stage in the Netherlands are investigated. Reason behind this focus is the recent emergence of multiple initiatives for waste-based methanol production across the Netherlands, as mentioned in the introduction, suggesting a favourable policy landscape.

Key policies at European level

At EU-level, the Fit for 55 climate legislation is currently being integrated by the Member States by means of National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs). In brief, Fit for 55 is a package of laws that should ensure compliance with the EU's target of reducing net GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030. One of its main instruments is the EU Emission Trading System (ETS), which has led to a carbon market based on the cap-and-trade mechanism. From 2025, this mechanism will be expanded to the maritime transport sector, which is expected to drive demand for decarbonised fuels. While liquid natural gas (LNG) is being phased out, and the use of other low-carbon fuels is

still too risky, waste-based methanol is perceived as an attractive alternative. The GHG emissions savings targeted by the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) III amounts to 70%, which this value chain can comply with. RED III also includes that renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBOs) and recycled carbon fuels can be counted towards the transport target if the GHG emissions savings are at least 70%. This is relevant since the waste utilised can have a biological as well as a non-biological origin. While the European policy context for waste-based fuels (, including methanol,) is increasingly appealing, EU policies that directly stimulate the application of waste-based methanol as a chemical are not available. Stakeholders in the field argue that without financial (policy) support, waste-based methanol is more expensive than fossil-based methanol, hence there is limited incentive for industries to switch to more sustainable methanol (personal communication, LowLands Methanol).

Concerning the management of MSW in the EU, the Landfill Directive limits the share of municipal waste landfilled to 10% by 2035. Additionally, the Waste Framework Directive sets targets for the re-use and the recycling of MSW to be increased to a minimum of 55%, 60% and 65% by weight by 2025, 2030 and 2035, respectively. Accordingly, both of these directives support the utilisation of MSW. Also the Circular Economy Action Plan supports reduction of waste and increased circularity. Creating a well-functioning EU market for secondary raw materials is one of the actions stated by the plan. MSW still makes up a considerable fraction of the total household waste volumes globally. In total, the EU generated 236.8 million metric tonnes of MSW in 2021. Of this amount, about 116 million tonnes (or about 49%) were recycled (or downcycled, e.g., for backfilling), 54 million tonnes (or about 23%) were landfilled, and the remaining 67 million tonnes (or about 28%) received a thermal treatment, meaning incineration with or without energy recovery took place (Statista, 2023). Assuming the amount of MSW generated will remain stable compared to 2021, at least 30 million tonnes of currently landfilled MSW needs to be given a different destination. Redirecting (a fraction of) this amount to the production of chemicals could contribute to achieving these targets (Statista, 2023; Abis et al., 2020).

The European Green Deal includes the following actions that are relevant for the chemicals sectors: Chemical strategy for sustainability, to better protect citizens and the environment against hazardous chemicals, and Zero Pollution Action Plan for water, air, and soil, to better prevent, remedy, monitor and report on pollution. The Chemical strategy aims at boosting the investment and innovative capacity for production and use of chemicals that are safe and sustainable by design. Thereby, the biobased products which have a proven environmental and safety performance can be favoured over their fossil-based counterparts.

The Taxonomy Regulation, which entered into force on 12 July 2020, establishes six environmental objectives. The Commission is defining technical screening criteria for each environmental objective through delegated and implementing acts. This first delegated act sets criteria under which an economic activity ‘qualifies as contributing substantially to climate change mitigation or climate change adaptation.’ Relevant for biobased industries in the EU are the manufacture of plastics in primary form (3.17) and for the manufacture of organic based chemicals (3.14). The biobased product qualifies as contributing substantially to climate change mitigation if the life cycle GHG emissions are lower than the life cycle GHG emissions of fossil fuel feedstock. Also, requiring the biomass used complies with the criteria laid down in the RED.

Thereby, the Taxonomy Regulation could be stimulating the transition from fossil-based to biobased chemicals.

Table 28. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the waste-to-methanol case study

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/ planned/ proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
Renewable Energy Directive	The Renewable Energy Directive is the legal framework for the development of clean energy across all sectors of the EU economy, supporting cooperation between EU countries towards this goal. The revision in 2023, sets an overall renewable energy target of at least 42.5% binding at EU level by 2030 - but aiming for 45%.	Stimulating for waste-based methanol as a fuel, barrier for its application as a chemical.	Supports the production of waste-based methanol for fuel application, this stimulates the use of methanol for fuel instead of chemicals	EU	Current	Regulation	EC (2023) Directive 2023/2413
Fir for 55	A package of laws that should ensure compliance with the EU's target of reducing net GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030. Importantly, it seeks to guide a just and socially fair transition, to maintain and strengthen innovation and competitiveness of the EU industry while ensuring a level playing field vis-à-vis third country economic operators. The ETS is part of this law.	Stimulating for waste-based methanol as a fuel, barrier for its application as a chemical.	Fit for 55 has resulted in the recognition of waste-based methanol as a sustainable maritime fuel under REDII, but not as a sustainable chemical.	EU	Current/Planned: adopted in 2023, extended to maritime sector in 2025	Regulation (coupled to economic instruments)	EC (2023) Fit for 55 Package
EU landfill Directive 1999/31/EC	Sets out strict operational requirements for landfill sites that EU countries must implement in national strategies to progressively reduce the amount of biodegradable waste sent to landfills to 10% in 2035. National authorities must ensure that the price operators charge for disposing of waste covers all the costs involved from opening to final closure of the site. Allows EU countries to use economic instruments and other measures to encourage applying the waste hierarchy	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates to search for alternative treatments/application of waste to avoid landfilling which stimulates conversions to methanol	EU	Implemented	Regulation and economic instrument(s)	EC (1999) Directive 1999/31/EC
Waste Framework Directive	Reduce environmental and climate impacts, increase environment quality, improve public health associated with textiles waste management in line with the waste hierarchy, reduce the environmental and climate impacts of food systems associated with food waste generation.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates re-use and the recycling of municipal waste with set targets	EU	Current, revision was proposed in 2023	Regulation	EC (2008) Directive 2008/98/EC

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/ planned/ proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
Circular Economy Action Plan	The new action plan announces initiatives along the entire life cycle of products. It targets how products are designed, promotes circular economy processes, encourages sustainable consumption, and aims to ensure that waste is prevented, and the resources used are kept in the EU economy for as long as possible.	Stimulating instrument	Stimulates reduction of waste, and keeping resources as long as possible in the economy	EU	Current	EU Strategy	EC (2020) COM/2020/98
Chemicals Strategy	It is part of the EU's zero pollution ambition, which is a key commitment of the European Green Deal. The EU's chemicals strategy aims to better protect citizens and the environment, and boost innovation for safe and sustainable chemicals	Could be stimulating	It could be stimulating as it can boost innovation in sustainable chemicals	EU	Current	EU Strategy	EC (2020) COM/2020/667
Zero Pollution Action Plan	The zero pollution vision for 2050 is for air, water and soil pollution to be reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems, that respect the boundaries with which our planet can cope, thereby creating a toxic-free environment. This is translated into key 2030 targets to speed up reducing pollution at source.	Could be stimulating	It could be stimulating if it promotes the adoption of biobased products instead of fossil based	EU	Current	EU Strategy	EC (2021) COM/2021/400
Taxonomy Regulation	The EU taxonomy allows financial and non-financial companies to share a common definition of economic activities that can be considered environmentally sustainable. In this way, it plays an important role in helping the EU scale up sustainable investment, by creating security for investors, protecting private investors from greenwashing, helping companies become more climate-friendly and mitigating market fragmentation.	Could be stimulating	It could be stimulating if it promotes the adoption of biobased products instead of fossil based	EU	Current	Regulation	EC (2020) Regulation 2020/852
Duurzaamheidskader biograndstoffen	A legislative framework aiming for the sustainable utilisation of biomass, through a threefold objectives:	Stimulating for waste-based methanol as	The framework obliges industrial users of biomass to	The Netherlands	Planned: under development, envisioned adoption in	Regulation (coupled to voluntary)	Ministry of Infrastructure and Water

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/ planned/ proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
(in English: Sustainability framework biological feedstocks)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Phasing out the stimulation of low-value biomass applications (e.g., electricity and heat generation); - Facilitating the transition for specific applications, especially to decarbonise hard-to-abate sectors (e.g., fuels for air and maritime transport); - Upscaling of high-value biomass applications, especially in materials that sequester carbon (e.g., chemicals and construction). 	both a fuel and a chemical, with different timeframes.	comply with sustainability criteria (through certification), and stimulate high-value applications - among which waste-based methanol could be - accordingly.		2026, depending on the status of the - currently demissionary - government	approaches, i.e., certification, and economic instruments)	Management (2020) Duurzaamheids kader biogrondstoffen (in English: Sustainability framework for biobased raw materials)
DEI+ vergassing van reststromen (in English: subsidy gasification of residual streams)	This subsidy can be requested for the execution of a demonstration project, aimed at the gasification of waste streams (i.e., biogenic, or mixed). The installation converts these residues to renewable energy carriers, such as green gas, biofuel, or to a chemical. The entire gasification chain, including pre-treatment, torrefaction, gasification, and purification is eligible.	Stimulating instrument	This subsidy offers financial support to gasification initiatives, with a total budget of €98 million and a maximally granted amount of €30 million per request.	The Netherlands (including the Caribbean parts of Bonaire, St. Eustasius and Saba)	Planned: February 15 th , 2024, until August 29 th , 2024	Economic instrument	Dutch Enterprise Agency (2023) Information on the subsidy Gasification of residual streams
Grondstoffenakkoord & Transitieagenda's circulaire economie (in English: Raw material agreement & Transition agendas circular economy)	An agreement was signed by 180 organisations (public, private, NGO, etc.), through which they express their ambition and intention to speed up the transition to the circular economy. Afterwards, these parties joined forces to formulate five transition agendas, i.e., for plastics, consumption goods, construction, manufacturing, biomass, and food. The category of intermediate, chemical goods is represented by the documents on biomass and food, and manufacturing. In these transition agendas, the parties describe their ambitions and what actions are needed to achieve these.	Stimulating instrument	Stakeholders in various sectors, e.g., waste treatment and chemical production, signed the agreement, which may motivate them to take an active role in the transition to sustainable chemical production, such as waste-based methanol.	The Netherlands	Old/current: the agreement was signed in 2017, and the agendas stretched from 2020-2023. These were followed up by Nationaal Programma Circulaire Economie 2023-2030 (in English: National Program Circular Economy), which however does not yet include chemicals.	Voluntary approach (coupled to a vision/ roadmap to change)	Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management (2017) Grondstoffenakkoord (in English: Raw Materials Agreement)

Key policies at the national level (the Netherlands)

A set of policies is being introduced in the Netherlands that may prove beneficial for the large-scale implementation of waste-based methanol as a chemical. One prominent example is the anticipated introduction of a legislative framework, containing sustainability requirements which producers of biobased products will need to comply with through certification. Although this framework, in line with the Fit for 55 law, seeks to contribute to a reduction of GHG emissions, it takes a different approach by treating the application of biomass (in e.g., maritime fuels) as merely a temporary solution. Its primary goal is to scale up high-value, material applications of biomass (which waste-based methanol could contribute to), as these have potential to sequester carbon for extended time periods. Simultaneously, the Dutch Enterprise Agency (in Dutch: RVO, Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland, 2023) stimulates innovation in the gasification of waste streams, by providing subsidies to demonstration projects. It would be valuable to evaluate the impact of these novel policies once these are effectuated. It is recommended to examine to what extent the expansion of these policies to other countries could facilitate the large-scale implementation of the waste-based methanol value chain and the phase-out of its fossil-based counterpart.

5.2.4 Analysis of indicators of the waste-to-methanol case study

In T3.2, a consistency check was conducted to identify the indicators in the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System deemed relevant for the waste-to-methanol case study. Subsequently, a selection of indicators was labelled as highly relevant. This initial analysis took place based on a literature review, specifically targeting the environmental, economic, and social sustainability aspects of the waste-to-methanol value chain. Several search queries were used, combining the following key words: “social,” “economic”, “environmental”, “life cycle assessment”, “life cycle costing”, “impacts”, “methanol”, “chemicals”, “production”, “value chain”, “waste”, “municipal solid waste”.

In this section, the results from this preliminary analysis were taken as a starting point and further elaborated on. Each identified indicator will be used to assess the performance of the waste-to-methanol value chain compared with conventional fossil-based methanol production. To that end, interviews were conducted with various stakeholders, particularly focusing on the sustainability performance of waste-based methanol production. In the case that no information or data could be found to support the analysis of the indicator, this was reported as a research gap.

5.2.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators

14 environmental and circular indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2, in the further analysis in T3.3, three of them were removed which were found quite general related to waste generation and management and not specifically relevant for this case study. Five (LCA) indicators were newly identified as highly relevant, and included in the table in red. Table 29 provides an overview of the resulting 12 highly relevant indicators and their analysis.

Table 29. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the waste-to-methanol case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Water consumption (use) (m ³ /product unit processed)	The waste-to-methanol system has been found to perform worse than the fossil-based counterpart, due to high cooling water demands (Afzal et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2021).	Yes, no data is available for the MSW, so instead data was taken from municipal plastic waste (MPW) as a proxy feedstock.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Renewable electricity used for manufactured products (kWh or % of total electricity used)	The waste-to-methanol system can fulfil 100% of energy demand by in-house generation of electricity based on MSW, while its fossil-based counterpart taps into natural gas for its process energy (Hakandai et al., 2022; Iaquaniello et al., 2017).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Energy consumption by activity/ production process/unit of production (kWh/production process or product unit)	The waste-to-methanol production system has been found to achieve an energy efficiency of 45% (Hakandai et al., 2022).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Procedures for separating and using recyclable materials from the waste stream (yes/no)	In the MSW-to-methanol system, only the non-recyclable fraction is gasified, the other fractions can be valorised alternatively. Its fossil-based counterpart does not concern the separation or recycling of waste (de Leeuw and Koelemeijer, 2022).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Procedures for recovering materials for other uses, such as incineration for raising process steam or heating, or agricultural use (yes/no)	The waste-to-methanol system can fulfil 100% of energy demand by in-house generation of electricity/ steam from MSW, while its fossil-based counterpart taps into natural gas for its process energy/ steam (Hakandai et al., 2022, Afzal et al., 2023).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of materials totally or partially derived from the organic fraction of mixed municipal household waste separated through mechanical, physicochemical, biological, and/or manual treatment	Depending on the local MSW compositions, a fraction of the feedstock treated in the waste-to-methanol system is made up of organic waste. In the EU, the organic fraction of MSW is between 25-48%. This does not apply to its fossil-based counterpart (Stylianou et al., 2020).	No.

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Practices to segregate different waste types to facilitate reuse, recycling, or composting (yes/no)	In the MSW-to-methanol system, only the non-recyclable fraction is gasified, the other fractions can be valorised alternatively. Its fossil-based counterpart does not concern the separation or recycling of waste (de Leeuw and Koelemeijer, 2022).	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Bioenergy replacing non-renewable energy	% of biofuels produced with co-products, residues, and waste	Waste-based methanol can serve is 100% produced from waste.	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Carbon intensity	The waste-to-methanol system was found to perform better than its fossil-based counterpart in terms of carbon intensity, due to the relatively low pressures/ temperatures at processing which leads to a reduced energy intensity, and the use of renewable energy (Afzal et al., 2023; laquaniello et al., 2017; de Leeuw and Koelemeijer, 2022).	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP100; gr eq. CO ₂)	The waste-to-methanol system was found to perform better than its fossil-based counterpart in terms of GWP, due to avoidance of CH ₄ emissions from landfilling, and the relatively low pressures/ temperatures at processing (Afzal et al., 2023; laquaniello et al., 2017; de Leeuw and Koelemeijer, 2022). The GHG emission reduction is estimated as 40% without taking into account avoided emissions from the diversion of waste from landfilling or incineration (laquaniello et al., 2017).	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Air quality	Emissions of non-GHG air pollutants (including air toxics) (µg / product unit)	The waste-to-methanol system was found to perform better in terms of non-GHG air pollutants than its fossil-based counterpart, due to avoided emissions (e.g., smog, kg O ₃ eq./kg and NO _x /kg) (Afzal et al., 2023).	Yes, no data is available for MSW, so instead data was taken from MPW as a proxy feedstock.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Water quality	Ecotoxicity for aquatic fresh water (Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems)	The waste-to-methanol system has been found to perform worse than the fossil-based counterpart for ecotoxicity (Afzal et al., 2023).	Yes, no data is available for MSW, so instead data was taken from MPW as a proxy feedstock.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Water quality	Acidification (mol H ⁺ eq. from NO _x , SO _x , NH ₃)	The waste-to-methanol system was found to perform better in terms of ozone depletion than its fossil-based counterpart (Afzal et al., 2023).	Yes, no data is available for MSW, so instead data was taken from MPW as a proxy feedstock.
2	Sustainable natural	Water quality	Eutrophication (gr eq. PO ₄)	The waste-to-methanol system has been found to perform worse than the fossil-based counterpart for eutrophication (Afzal et al., 2023).	Yes, no data is available for MSW, so instead data was

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

	resource management				taken from MPW as a proxy feedstock.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Resource depletion (mineral, fossil) / product unit (MJ)	Naturally, the waste-to-methanol system was found to perform better in terms of fossil fuel depletion than its fossil-based counterpart (Afzal et al., 2023)	Yes, no data is available for MSW, so instead data was taken from MPW as a proxy feedstock.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Air quality	Ozone depletion (mg CFC-11 eq. /kg)	The waste-to-methanol system was found to perform better in terms of ozone depletion than its fossil-based counterpart, due to avoided emissions from co-generation of steam (Afzal et al., 2023).	Yes, no data is available for MSW, so instead data was taken from MPW as a proxy feedstock.

From the table above, it can be observed that the waste-based methanol production system performs better on most highly relevant environmental and circular indicators, e.g., regarding energy and material use efficiency, waste generation and management, fossil fuel depletion, ozone depletion, acidification, and air quality. This can be explained by the fact that MSW is used as its main feedstock as well as to generate process energy, in contrast to the natural gas used in the fossil-based counterpart. An exception to this are the ecotoxicity, eutrophication and water consumption indicators. The higher water use in waste-based methanol production is due to the higher demand for cooling water. It must be noted that the sustainability performance of waste-based methanol hinges on many factors (e.g., how the waste input would have been treated alternatively, how the methanol is applied downstream, and how efficient the adopted technology is) (personal communication, Air Liquide).

Two main research gaps were identified. First, no data was available to measure the performance of MSW-based methanol, hence instead data on municipal plastic waste (MPW) had to be taken as a proxy. The calorific value of these two waste streams might diverge, depending on the exact waste composition (Dianda & Munawar, 2018; Silvarrey & Phan, 2016). Second, no reference data was found the indicator Energy consumption by activity/ production process/unit of production for the fossil-based methanol production system, meaning that the performance of waste-based methanol production cannot be effectively compared. Additional (primary) data generation, in collaboration with industry actors, could solve both research gaps. At this moment, most data on sustainability parameters from commercial operations is confidential (personal communication, Enerkem).

5.2.4.2 Economic indicators

Table 30 provides an overview of economic indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (i.e., 2 indicators in total). In addition, 5 indicators newly identified as highly relevant were included in table in red.

Table 30. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the waste-to-methanol case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Strategy for creating the infrastructure and systems necessary for recovering and recycling materials (yes/no)	No specific strategy is found concerning infrastructure generation for the recovery and use of MSW for methanol production.	Yes, it is highly relevant to create such an infrastructure to divert some of the waste going to waste management to industry. Such a strategy is called for.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Potential market share of the product	Methanol is a platform chemical that can be used in many applications. The biomethanol produced from	Yes, as waste-to-methanol is currently very new.

				waste to methanol value chain is a drop-in chemical and can directly replace fossil based methanol in all application. No market share information is available for this specific product, it is assumed to be negligible.	
	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Raw Material/Utility costs	This information was found to be available in a scientific study that reported on the RDF and the utility prices laquaniello et al., 2017).	No
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Capital costs	This information was found to be available in a scientific study that reported a CAPEX of 189 M€ for a new waste-to-methanol 300 t/d plant* (laquaniello et al., 2017).	No
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Operating costs	This information was found in a recent study. Bio-methanol from Refuse-derived-fuels (RdF) has an estimated cost of production of about 110 €/t for a new waste-to-methanol 300 t/d plant* (laquaniello et al., 2017).	No
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Economic viability	Payback time of the investment	The expected payback time of a commercial waste-to-methanol production facility is estimated as 4 years* (laquaniello et al., 2017).	No
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Economic viability	Return on investment (ROI)	A ROI of about 29% is found for a commercial waste-to-methanol production facility* (laquaniello et al., 2017).	No

*These estimates were found in a process and economics assessment based on the Enerkem production process, to be implemented in a commercial waste-to-methanol production facility in Alberta (Canada).

Biomethanol can be produced from lignocellulosic biomass, residues, and wastes. Current approaches indicate a cost of production (COP) of bio-methanol between 1.5 and 4.0 times higher than the cost of NG-based methanol (International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), 2013). The Road2Bio-project (based on 2017 values) estimated that bio-methanol production costs from wood is ranging between 160 - 940 EUR/ton. For fossil methanol the costs range 75-250 EUR/ton from natural gas (Road2Bio, 2018). The study of laquaniello et al., 2017, based on a model of Enerkem’s waste-to-methanol process, show that the route from waste can be cost-competitive with fossil-based methanol at a COP of 110 €/t. This study also provides all relevant information regarding economic performance: feedstock/utility prices, OPEX, CAPEX, ROI and payback time. The research gap identified from this analysis is the current market information for the waste-to-methanol product, due to it being still in its infancy.

5.2.4.3 Social indicators

Table 31 provides an overview of the six social indicators that were identified as highly relevant. These indicators were newly identified as highly relevant therefore provided in table in red. Three indicators that were identified in T3.2 were removed due to being company-specific indicators. This study does not focus on a single company but rather a value chain in general and different industrial stakeholders involved therein.

Table 31. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the waste-to-methanol case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Presence of environmentally/friendly technologies (yes/no)	Research and innovation on turning waste to methanol is an example of an innovative environmentally friendly technology.	No
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Regulatory measures	There are different policies and strategies available at national and EU level that simulate or hinder the development of waste-based methanol.	Yes, there is a gap in terms of specific regulatory measures concerning support for biobased chemicals.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Full time equivalent jobs along the full value chain of a product	Enerkem’s production plant in Alberta, Canada is reported to create 41,100 new jobs across Canada (Enerkem, 2014).	No
6	Food safety, disease prevention and human health are ensured, Human health	Human health	Human toxicity and cancer effects (Comparative Toxic Unit for humans, CTUh)	The waste-to-methanol system has been found to perform worse than the fossil-based counterpart in terms of carcinogenic impacts (Afzal et al., 2023).	Yes, no data is available for MSW, so instead data was taken from MPW as a proxy feedstock.
6	Food safety, disease prevention and human health are ensured, Human health	Human health	Human toxicity - non-cancer effects (Comparative Toxic Unit for humans, CTUh)	The waste-to-methanol system has been found to perform similarly with the fossil-based counterpart in terms of non-carcinogenic impacts (Afzal et al., 2023).	Yes, no data is available for MSW, so instead data was taken from MPW as a proxy feedstock.
9	Promoting global governance and collaboration	Partnerships and cooperation	Number of partnerships between the industry in the region and local organisations to support the development of rural communities	Enerkem’s production plant in Alberta, Canada is reported to generate 65 million CAN\$/year in net economic benefits in the region (for 1 standard Enerkem system of 100 ktons/year). This success resulted in new projects in Europe (Enerkem, 2014).	No

Concerning regulatory aspects, although there are several EU policies and national policies (as mapped in section 5.2.3) this case study is affected by the lack of specific regulatory measure in support of it. Concerning employment aspects, the waste-to-methanol value chain, from the

example from the Enerkem’s plant in Canada, is seen to be beneficial in terms of creation of high-quality jobs and bringing value creation and economic benefits in the region. Regarding human health aspects addressed by two LCA indicators, it is seen that waste-to-methanol either performs similarly or worse than the fossil-based system.

Two main research gaps were identified. First, no data was available to measure the performance MSW-based methanol, hence instead data on municipal plastic waste (MPW) had to be taken as a proxy similar to the LCA indicators covered in the environmental section. Another gap concerns the lack of specific regulatory measures addressing waste-to-methanol for chemical applications or biobased chemicals in general.

5.2.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Market dimension

Challenges

- Various private companies indicate that the chemical application of waste-based methanol suffers from two non-level playing fields:
 1. Fossil vs. non-fossil resources: substantial differences in cost exist between the production of methanol from biogenic, waste or fossil feedstocks. In order for non-fossil methanol to become a success, companies must be willing to pay a price premium. As such, there is a lack of economic incentive for the utilisation of waste.
 2. Energy vs. chemical application: European market conditions push towards the application of methanol as an energy carrier (e.g., in the maritime sector, which is included in the extended ETS), away from its applications as a chemical/material. (Air Liquide, Enerkem)
- Another major market-related challenge concerns access to financing for (the upscaling of) waste-to-methanol production technologies. Whereas investors prefer settling on long-term off-take agreements to secure supply, companies tend to favour flexibility, especially in fast-changing market segments such as for green chemistry. According to a large waste-based methanol producer, the investment climate in the USA is currently more beneficial than in the EU, hence the company is currently shifting its focus overseas. (GIDARA Energy, DOPS RT)
- There are also some challenges linked to subsidies for waste-based methanol (and gasification in general), that are outlined for the national and European level:
 - *National level public subsidies*: taking the Dutch DEI+ subsidy for the gasification of waste streams (see section 5.2.3), as an example, this subsidy could cover up to 50% of a waste-to-methanol project, with the remaining to be covered by the financial market. During a market consultation, several large initiatives arose with an investment need of 200-650 million Euros. The maximum DEI+ subsidy did not suffice in these cases. But also for the smaller initiatives, it appeared difficult to attract sufficient cofinancing due to the high technical and economic risks. (RVO, MinKGG)
 - *European level public subsidies*: the European Innovation Fund, for example, supports large-scale, sustainable projects, including gasification projects (such as FUREC, i.e.,

Fuse Reuse Recycle). However, the application procedure is very complicated and demanding (e.g., in terms of CO₂ calculations and financing, also on OPEX). Besides, it is important to note that all subsidies within the EU must follow the conditions set out in the European General Block Exemption Regulation, which includes e.g., a maximum subsidy percentage. The conditions for energy from renewable energy sources (art. 41) are generally more flexible than the conditions for recycling and reuse of waste for material applications (art. 47). As such, from a subsidy point of view it tends to be more beneficial to produce methanol for energy rather than material purposes (also see first bullet on unequal level playing field). In practice however, it is not always clear which fraction of the products are used for which end applications, and hence which rules apply. (RVO, MinKGG)

Examples of good practices

- To bridge the gap in price between fossil- and waste-based methanol, two potential interventions were primarily mentioned:
 1. An increase in the price (i.e., penalty) of fossil products such that it embodies all (external) environmental costs. (Enerkem)
 2. A decrease in price of the biobased or waste-based alternative through public funding, especially for first-of-a-kind chemical plants. As such, the value of waste would be acknowledged. This would aid e.g., in securing investment in more sustainable production. (Enerkem, GIDARA Energy)
- For the utilisation of waste for biobased products and creation of an after use economy, infrastructure needs to be created that can feed the waste to the industry.

Policy dimension

Challenges

- Several stakeholders argue that misconceptions and conflicting opinions about the (dis)advantages of waste treatment methods are a major challenge in the policy domain.
 - A private company indicates that the EC currently ties gasification directly to energy recovery in the waste processing hierarchy. This is a misunderstanding, as gasification can result in a recycled carbon content of 90%, while energy recovery only valorises 30-40% of the energy from waste. Although this has not been a breaking point in efforts to secure funding, it has resulted in troubles obtaining permits (by local authorities). The company is currently lobbying at the EC in order to get gasification recognised as a recycling pathway. (Enerkem)
 - A Dutch policymaker confirms that in the Netherlands, a single political vision on waste does not exist. Although the common goal is to be 100% circular in 2050, opinions diverge on how to reach this goal. A recurring dilemma is whether waste gasification forms a step forward as compared to incineration, which is the dominant MSW treatment method in the Netherlands. Other (not always well-funded) concerns exist about e.g., changes in the availability of waste streams in the future, and the displacement of waste (e.g., through import). (RVO, MinKGG)

- Another major challenge is posed by differences between, unclarities of and inconsistencies in calculations rules used for regulating biobased, waste- and fossil-based products. Some examples:
 - The RED II only includes rules for the biogenic part of a product, not for products made from non-biogenic waste. In the update to RED III this issue seems to be resolved with the consideration of RFNBOs and recycled carbon fuels that can be counted towards the transport target if the GHG emissions savings are at least 70%.
 - Inconsistencies exist between calculation methodologies in e.g., the RED II and the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) regarding the biogenic carbon accounting from cradle-to-gate. (Air Liquide)
- Other European regulations that pose a barrier to the recycling of feedstock to gases (including methanol) are in the area of packaging waste, vehicles and textiles. Regulations linked to these products require closed-loop recycling at the end-of-life (e.g., synthetic textiles must be converted back to their original form, such as polyesters), whereas MSW is not considered an EOL waste of a specific product category. The choice of feedstock requires anticipation on which product will eventually be produced from the syngas, which is often very difficult to determine upfront. (GIDARA Energy)

Examples of good practices

- Establish blending obligations for e.g., green gas and plastics. Such policy instruments are currently in the making at the European level, and could boost the material application of waste-based methanol. (RVO, MinKGG)
- To harmonise calculations methodologies of different regulations, adopt full life cycle emission calculations with default numbers for the use and end-of-life phases, while preventing oversimplification. (Air Liquide)
- Rather than regulating the sustainability performance downstream, at product-level, it would be more efficient and simpler to regulate the materials upstream in the value chain. This could be done by setting sustainability requirements with a threshold for base chemicals (e.g., for toxicity, CO₂-impact, recycled content), which need to be fulfilled by all chemical producers. (GIDARA Energy)

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- The sustainability benefits from waste valorisation are currently allocated unequally. For example, if a municipality diverts its waste away from incineration to a methanol production plant, this results in an emission saving. However, the chemicals producer may have more difficulty processing the waste, causing higher emissions at plant level. Even though there might be a net saving at the regional/global level, it is usually only one party who can claim the benefits, at the expense of the other. (Air Liquide)
- Another problem facing private companies is the difficulty of upskilling and keeping high-quality jobs. Companies experience the loss of in-depth knowledge on the gasification of solid feedstocks, due to retiring colleagues who cannot be replaced easily. Besides that, due to limited capacity of R&D departments, the focus of sustainability assessment tends

to be on the quantification of CO₂ emissions (due to legal obligations). As a result, other environmental, or social aspects, are typically not being considered. (Air Liquide)

- In determining the sustainability performance of different MSW treatment methods, some potentially faulty assumptions are made, which leads to an unfair comparison:
 - Gasification is compared to mechanical recycling, with the latter option being perceived as more environmentally friendly. Underlying assumption is that MSW can be separated into different fractions. In reality, however, separation is often not possible or very costly (and energy-intensive), and hence incineration is typically opted for. (GIDARA Energy)
 - Conversion of waste to syngas is energy intensive. Nonetheless, as opposed to conventional (natural gas-based) gasification, the process can be electrified. When calculating the carbon footprint of waste-based syngas/methanol, the RED II requires the use of national electricity mixes over the past two years. In the Netherlands, the share of fossil electricity in the mix is still relatively high. This does not allow for a fair comparison with alternative waste processing or syngas production methods, nor does it take into consideration the increasingly higher share of renewables in the Dutch energy mix. (GIDARA Energy)

Examples of good practices

- Develop a consistent, harmonised methodology in terms of assessment of environmental impacts of different MSW treatment methods. (Air Liquide)
- Install a mechanism to ensure that the rewards of valorising waste are allocated to the parties involved in a fair manner. (Air Liquide)

5.2.6 Key learnings of waste-to-methanol case study

It can be concluded that, given its indispensable, versatile role as a platform chemical in a multiplicity of industries, methanol is here to stay. However, fossil-based methanol still dominates the global market, with bio-methanol representing only a minor share. In this case study, it is argued that upscaling the waste-to-methanol value chain could significantly contribute to the transition to a circular bioeconomy. On the one hand, the large-scale gasification of MSW and subsequent conversion of syngas to methanol, would reduce the pressure on fossil resources, while on the other, it would divert waste streams away from less desirable waste processing methods (such as incineration and landfilling). As such, waste-based methanol production could aid in achieving EU Waste Framework Directive and EU Landfill Directive, among others.

Important feedback to consider on the road ahead

In this case study, it was observed that the production of waste-based methanol is gaining traction, with several commercial initiatives popping up across e.g., Europe and North America. Several large players are well underway in establishing production plants, while smaller players (e.g., start-ups) are involved in technology development and demonstration projects, oftentimes embedded in innovation networks. Nonetheless, in their quest for offering a viable alternative to fossil-based methanol production, these initiatives face numerous challenges and drawbacks.

Most importantly, two non-level playing fields inhibit the expansion of waste-based methanol production. First, the low price of fossil-based methanol disincentivises methanol-relying industries (identified as key stakeholders in the value chain) from switching to the waste-based alternative. Second, European market conditions favour the use of non-fossil methanol for energy purposes (particularly for shipping), away from its chemical application. Various European policies (e.g., RED, Fit for 55), are at least a reinforcing factor in latter disbalance.

Private companies interested in sustainable chemical production generally perceive the EU investment climate as unattractive, with targeted financial support (e.g., in the form of subsidies) being scarce, insufficient, and/or difficult to obtain. Moreover, the infrastructure needed to enable the use of waste for chemical applications is largely absent.

Other key issues can be found in the misconceptions about the sustainability benefits of waste-based methanol, as well as the calculation and allocation of these benefits. In Europe, gasification is mistakenly tied to energy recovery in the waste processing hierarchy, which counteracts strategic expansion of waste-based methanol production. The absence of consistent calculation methodologies complicates the performance of streamlined, harmonised assessments of sustainability impacts. Still, if sustainability benefits are revealed, these tend to be allocated to the involved value chain actors unfairly, resulting in a zero-sum game, which can impede them from taking action towards waste-based methanol production at all.

Urgent policy actions and research requirements to level the field for biobased chemicals

There are several urgent actions recommended to improve the standing of biobased chemicals, among which waste-based methanol, in the current policy regime:

- 1) Develop a consistent, harmonised methodology in terms of assessment of environmental impacts of different waste treatment methods. For this purpose, adopt full life cycle emission calculations with default numbers insofar possible, and avoid oversimplification.
- 2) Regulate the sustainability performance of chemicals and materials upstream in the value chain. This could be done by setting sustainability requirements with a threshold for base chemicals (e.g., for toxicity, CO₂-impact, recycled content), which need to be fulfilled by all chemical producers by means of using the methodologies mentioned under 1).
- 3) Install a mechanism to ensure that the rewards (both monetary and non-monetary) of valorising waste are allocated to the parties involved in a fair manner.
- 4) Establish blending obligations for e.g., green gas and plastics. Such policy instruments are currently in the making at the European level, and could boost the material application of waste-based methanol without requiring resource-intensive, complex subsidy systems.
- 5) If blending obligations (as mentioned under 4) are not desirable or feasible, bridge the gap in price between fossil- and waste-based methanol, by a) an increase in the price (i.e., penalty) of fossil products such that it embodies all (external) environmental costs or b) a decrease in price of the biobased or waste-based alternative through public funding, especially for first-of-a-kind chemical plants.
- 6) Create the infrastructure needed to feed waste to the industry, such that these can be utilised in the production of biobased or waste-based chemicals in an after-use economy.

Research and data gaps

The main research gaps to be addressed to enable the urgent key actions are the following:

- 1) Concerns exist about some aspects of the environmental performance (e.g., linked to eutrophication and water use) and social performance (e.g., linked to effects on human health) of waste-based methanol production. The data on which existing studies hinge are limited and often based on proxies (e.g., MPW as a feedstock instead of MSW). Further (primary) data collection and analysis, facilitated by the industry, is needed to examine, and handle these potentially negative effects. Hereby, it is important to distinguish between the different (gasification) technologies that are available.
- 2) Although a range of policy instruments were identified that arguably either stimulate or inhibit the production of waste-based or biobased chemicals, no specific regulatory measures were found at EU level that directly support the upscaling of the waste-to-methanol value chain. Building on the policy mapping in section 5.2.3, more research is needed to identify other policies of relevance, as well as their interactions in overarching policy packages.
- 3) Contrary to the EU (see point 2), the Netherlands was found to be an example of a country that has adopted specific regulatory measures to incentivise the sustainable production of biobased chemicals. It is of great importance to evaluate these interventions, in order to understand their impact and take these as a learning for other countries or regions seeking to support innovative developments in the transition to a circular bioeconomy.

5.3 Chemical - Bio-MEG, bio-MPG, and renewable functional fillers from wood

5.3.1 Introduction to bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study

5.3.1.1 General description

This value chain examines the production of monoethylene glycol (MEG) from forest and agriculture biomass sources. MEG is an organic compound, and a drop-in chemical, chemically identical to fossil-based MEG (i.e. $C_2H_6O_2$). MEG has various fields of application, such as the production of polyester fibres and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) resins, as well as antifreeze in coolant agents. On the basis of end use, MEG is significantly used in textiles and packaging, while also being a component for the production of adhesives, sealants, paints and coatings, and other chemicals.

Traditionally, MEG has been produced from fossil-based feedstocks such as ethane, propane, or naphtha through a multi-step petrochemical process that transforms hydrocarbon feedstocks into a versatile chemical used across several industries (Elvers, B., 1991). MEG produced from agriculture residues and lignocellulose rich raw materials, mostly known as bio-MEG, offers the possibility of a reduction in CO_2 emissions and decreased dependency from fossil resources. While bio-MEG has been produced from bioethanol since 2010, novel conversion processes have been introduced in the last decade that reduce the reliance on bioethanol utilising abundant sugar

residues from agricultural feedstocks such as molasses, hay, bagasse, and corn stover, as well as from lignocellulose from forestry residues and wood materials.

5.3.1.2 Value chain and the process

For the analysis of this case study, the bio-MEG value chain stands in focus. In order to establish a point of reference and analyse the transition to biobased MEG, the conventional production of MEG based on fossil feedstock will be depicted as a baseline.

The primary commercial route for producing fossil-based MEG is via the ethylene oxide (EO). This process begins with fossil-derived feedstocks such as ethane, propane, or naphtha, which undergo a steam cracking process. The steam cracking functions as a thermal decomposition process where the hydrocarbons are heated to very high temperatures (typically around 800-900°C) in the presence of steam. This reaction breaks the large hydrocarbon molecules into smaller ones, including a significant amount of ethylene, which after separation and purification steps yields high-purity ethylene. Using a catalytic oxidation process, the ethylene is converted into ethylene oxide. Finally, a hydration reaction is performed where ethylene oxide is absorbed in water, yielding MEG as the primary product. A fraction of the MEG can further react with additional EO to form diethylene glycol (DEG) and triethylene glycol (TEG), which are considered by-products. This process is highly efficient, with MEG selectivity typically around 89-92% (Kawabe, 2010).

Figure 37. Value chain of the bio-MEG from agriculture and forest biomass

The value chain processes for the production of bio-MEG, utilising both agriculture and forestry resources (preferably residues), are detailed based on literature review sources (Mendieta et al., 2022):

- **Biobased feedstocks:** agricultural residues such as corn stover, sugarcane bagasse, wheat straw, and rice straw contain about 50%-60% cellulose and hemicellulose, which

can be converted into sugars for the production of biobased chemicals. Likewise, sugars can be extracted from lignocellulosic materials from forest biomass. Residues from wood processing industries, including forestry residues such as sawdust, wood chips, bark, and logging residues are of use. Various hardwood (e.g., birch, poplar, and beech) and softwood (e.g., pine and spruce) species have been identified as suitable feedstocks due to their high cellulose content and accessibility to enzymatic hydrolysis. Studies indicate that utilising forestry residues minimises waste while enhancing feedstock availability for sustainable MEG production (Mendieta et al., 2022, Wong et al., 2023).

- **Feedstock preparation and extraction of intermediate products:** Pre-treatment methods of raw biomass feedstocks include mechanical, chemical, and biological approaches and they play a significant role in the success of the conversion process. Mechanical pre-treatment such as ball-milling has been found to increase MEG yield up to 40%, by disrupting the rigid carbohydrate-lignin matrix and reducing particle size before any additional pre-treatment or conversion process. Chemical pre-treatment can involve the use of acid (e.g., sulfuric acid) or alkali (e.g., sodium hydroxide) to break down lignin and hemicellulose, exposing cellulose fibres (Raj et al. 2022, Wong et al., 2023, Zhao et al., 2021).

Key preparation and treatment of the raw biomass is intended to facilitate the removal of lignin and promote the extraction of simple sugars (i.e., monosaccharides), such as glucose, xylose and arabinose that can be further processed. Among the most utilised methods is enzymatic hydrolysis, which by utilising enzymes facilitates the hydrolysis of cellulose and hemicellulose into these simple fermentable sugar components. It is one of the well-known and scalable methods to produce bioethanol. Other methods for the extraction of sugars from raw biomass include solvents such as the γ -Valerolactone (GVL) and organosolv processes. GVL is a biomass-derived solvent that efficiently solubilises all biomass fractions (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin) without the need for expensive catalysts or enzymes (Motagamwala et al., 2016). Afterwards, lignin can be separated from the liquid phase, leaving high yields of soluble sugars. In the organosolv process, biomass is treated with organic solvents (e.g., ethanol, methanol, acetone, or organic acids like acetic acid) to disrupt the lignin's structure, solubilising it and leaving cellulose and hemicellulose exposed in a solid form. Further sugar extraction processes can be identified in the Figure 38 from Ren et al. (2015).

Conversion pathways and technologies:

Following the breaking down of complex sugars to shorter carbon chains these can be further processed via biochemical or thermochemical pathways.

- **Biochemical pathways:** Bio-MEG can be produced through biochemical pathways. A first option is through the utilisation of microorganisms for the fermentation of extracted sugars into ethanol, which is subsequently dehydrated in the presence of acidic catalysts such as alumina or zeolites to produce ethylene. The resulting ethylene undergoes oxidation to produce EO, a crucial intermediate for MEG synthesis (Luo et al., 2012). Finally, EO is hydrolysed with water to form biobased MEG. The multi-step sugar fermentation is a demonstrated and commercially available technology in southeast Asian countries and Brazil (Wong et al., 2023).

Biochemical routes still under development include engineered strains of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Escherichia coli* which are optimised to metabolise directly D-xylose and glucose into MEG (Uranukul et al., 2019; Francois, 2020).

The development of bio-MEG from gases like synthesis gas (syngas) has gained significant attention in recent years. Gas fermentation is a viable biochemical pathway which utilises synthetic biology and acetogenic bacteria to convert CO₂, CO, and H₂ into MEG via engineered biochemical pathways. Synthetic biology involves designing and modifying microbial metabolic pathways to enhance efficiency in biochemical conversion. Acetogenic bacteria, such as *Clostridium ljungdahlii*, can utilise syngas (a mixture of CO, CO₂, and H₂) to produce biobased chemicals. The input gases can be sourced from industrial emissions, biomass gasification, and waste-to-energy processes, providing a sustainable alternative to fossil-based feedstocks (Islam et al., 2017).

- **Thermochemical pathways:** In addition, and avoiding the multi-step fermentation process, glucose and xylose sugars can undergo catalytic hydrogenolysis, a two-steps reaction requiring a hydrogen source (H₂), a metal-based catalyst (such as Ru, Ni, or Cu-based catalysts), and controlled temperature and pressure conditions. The process selectively breaks down glucose-derived intermediates into ethylene glycol and other polyols. The hydrogenation reaction is optimised using a solvent system to control reactivity and selectivity, and ensure high bio-MEG yields. The overall efficiency of the process is influenced by catalyst choice, hydrogen availability, and process optimisation (Zhao et al., 2021).

Likewise, the gasification of biomass to syngas (CO + H₂), followed by a catalytic conversion, will yield bio-MEG (Luo et al., 2012).

Some methods integrate biochemical and thermochemical routes for enhanced efficiency. For example, microbial fermentation produces intermediates, which are further processed via catalysis to yield MEG (Hwang et al., 2020).

Figure 38. Potential production pathways for bio-MEG from lignocellulosic feedstock (agriculture, forest) (Source: Ren et al. 2015)

5.3.1.3 Baseline and market

The MEG market is currently still dominated by fossil-based production. Conventional production is dominated by countries with a strong petrochemical history and infrastructure. For the year 2023, the Asia Pacific region and in particular China is leading with over 35% of the global market share. Europe is the following growing regional market for MEG, due to its impulse for bio-PET. North America, Saudi Arabia and India hold a smaller part of the market shares.

According to market analysis data, the current global MEG market is about 32 billion dollars and it is growing at an expecting CAGR of 6.5% from 2024 to 2023. The rapid expansion for MEG is driven by its key role as an intermediate compound in several major sectors. MEG is predominantly utilised in the production of polyester fibres for textiles, PET resins for packaging materials, antifreeze formulations, and as a chemical intermediate for various industrial applications. One of the primary growth drivers is the increasing demand for PET in the packaging industry, particularly for beverage bottles, as well as the rise in demand for polyester fibres in the fashion and home furnishing sectors. Additionally, the automotive industry's ongoing need for antifreeze products further supports the MEG market. Furthermore, advancements in production technologies and increasing investments in emerging markets are anticipated to pave the way for new growth opportunities, reinforcing MEG's role in supporting both traditional and innovative applications worldwide (Wong et al., 2023).

The market outlook for bio-MEG is increasingly promising as a drop-in chemical that can substitute fossil-based MEG. Driven by heightened environmental concerns, stricter regulatory frameworks, and a growing consumer demand for sustainable products, bio-MEG is emerging as a viable

alternative in key applications such as PET production, polyester manufacturing, and antifreeze formulations. Figure 39 illustrates the sharp increase in global plastics production from 1950 to 2022, with fossil-based plastics dominating at 382 million tonnes and biobased plastics contributing only 4 million tonnes. These growing demand in the plastic sector is likely to drive increased interest in biobased alternatives, including bio-MEG.

Advances in bioconversion technologies and the development of efficient, renewable biomass supply chains are steadily improving cost competitiveness and product performance for bio-MEG. Although bio-MEG is still in the early stages of commercialisation, ongoing investments and strategic partnerships across the chemical and bioeconomy sectors are paving the way for its broader adoption.

Figure 39. Growing plastic production since 1950 as a driver for MEG market growth (Source: nova-Institute, 2024)

Multiple initiatives arising, both for demonstration and commercial projects paving the way for bio-MEG production in Europe, have been summarised below in Table 32.

Table 32. Impression of recent bio-MEG production initiatives across Europe

#	Project	Initiator	Status	Capacity (t/y)	Investment (million USD/t/y)
1	Ray Technology™ demonstration plant (Delfzijl, NL)	Avantium	Restarted operations in 2022	10	€5,351,125, with an EU contribution of €2,499,999
2	UPM BioPura™ (Leuna, DE)	UPM	Expected to be operating by end of 2024	220,000	€1,180 million

3	MOSAIIK™ demonstration plant (Lyngby, DK)	Braskem and Haldor Topsoe	Started in 2019	100	
---	---	---------------------------	-----------------	-----	--

5.3.2 Stakeholders in the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study

5.3.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

To begin with, the stakeholders relevant to the present case study were determined by means of an explanatory desk research (e.g., websites of companies, associations, press releases, scientific papers etc.).

Figure 40 provides a schematic representation of the identified stakeholders, both in the Bioeconomy supply chain (i.e., the light green section) and its Enabling environment (i.e., the light grey section).

Figure 40, the supply chain of bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass involves a number of stakeholders, extending from the feedstock supply to end-of-life (EoL) processing. This section provides an overview of central stakeholders, accompanied by examples.

Feedstock suppliers are the first stakeholders in the bio-MEG value chain. In the present case study, suitable raw materials from forest and agriculture biomass are lignocellulosic residues, such as corn cobs, molasses, hay, grasses, or woody materials. Those can typically be sourced from forest owners, sawmills, or agriculture producers, as well as specialised biomass aggregators (e.g., Bioenergy International, n.d.).

While sugarcane used to be the most important feedstock for larger scale bio-MEG production (COWI A/S & Utrecht University, 2018, p. 168), recently other biomass materials gained importance. For example, the newly build production site by UPM (Leuna, Germany) is specialised in the utilisation of wood-based raw materials. The hardwood feedstock is sourced from local, sustainably managed, and certified forests (UPM Biochemicals, n.d. a).

The biomass feedstock needs to be mobilised, which means collected, transported, stored, and allocated to actors utilising it. Transportation and logistics companies are responsible for these services and connect different stakeholder groups.

In the value chain considered here, biomass is either supplied directly to biobased MEG producers (e.g., UPM (Leuna)) or there is an intermediate step where biomass is first supplied to a bioethanol producer and then the bioethanol is sold to a bio-MEG producer (e.g., India Glycols Ltd. (COWI A/S & Utrecht University, 2018, p. 172)).

Figure 40. Identified stakeholders in bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study

Examples of mayor bio-MEG producers are:

- India Glycols Ltd. (India),
- UPM (Leuna, Germany) (UPM Biochemicals, n.d. b),
- Avantium (Delfzijl, Netherlands) (Avantium n.d. b),
- ENI Versalis (Italy),
- RADICI Group (Gandino, Italy) (Radici Group, n.d.),
- Sustainea, a joint venture between Braskem and Sojitz Corporation called Sustainea (Lafayette, USA),
- Joint venture between Braskem and SCG Chemicals (Bangkok, Thailand) (Braskem, 2023),
- Cooperation between Braskem and Haldor Topsoe (demonstration plant) (Lyngby, Denmark) (Wójcik, 2020),
- INEOS (Zwijndrecht, Belgium) (SCS Global Services, 2022),
- and LanzaTech.

In order to sell the product to MEG-relying industries, there is the possibility of using a distributor who takes over this step (e.g., Brenntag SE for UPM (UPM Biochemicals (2023))). However, the direct route between bio-MEG producers and relying industries is also possible.

The MEG-relying industries form the next stakeholder category. As mentioned before, major industries segments utilising MEG are the textile (polyester production), the polymer, the packaging (PET production) and the automotive sector. Examples of companies that use bio-MEG for their products are:

- VAUDE, an outdoor-clothing brand that uses bio-MEG in the production process of a fleece jacket (VAUDE, 2023).
- The Coca-Cola Company uses MEG from sugarcane for a certain kind of bottle (PlantBottle™) (Coca-Cola Europe, 2024).
- FKUR, a company producing packaging solutions replaces MEG by bio-MEG for transparent packaging and bottles (FKUR, n.d.).
- Selenis, a company producing packaging solutions will source wood-based bio-MEG from the UPM factory in Leuna (Selenis, 2023) and presented together with Bormioli Pharma the first pharmaceutical bottles that are produced with wood-based bio-MEG (UPM Biochemicals, 2024).

At the EoL, the treatment depends on the final product application. Stakeholders belonging to that group might be recycling or waste treatment companies. In general, it is the responsibility of the producers to carry out this procedure.

Besides stakeholders that are directly active within the bio-MEG supply chain, the enabling environment also plays a crucial role. Actors within that environment can be divided into four categories: government, academia, industry, and civil society. Crucial stakeholders in the category government are policy makers specialised on the chemical industry on national and EU-level (e.g., European Commission Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission (2018), European Chemicals Agency (European Chemicals Agency, n.d.)), the public infrastructure

(e.g., utility and public infrastructure providers) and public funding institutions (e.g., Horizon Europe (European Commission, n.d.)).

In the category academia, main actors are knowledge institutes and research centres specialised in biochemicals (e.g., Fraunhofer UMSICHT (Fraunhofer UMSICHT, n.d.), EU-funded research project VEHICLE (VEHICLE, n.d.)) as well as R&D testing facilities for demonstration purposes (e.g., demonstration plant of Braskem and Holdor Topsoe (Wójcik, 2020)).

Enabling industry stakeholders are private financial institutions (e.g., Nordic Investment Bank), that granted a loan of 200 million Euros to UPM for the bio-MEG production site in Leuna (Germany) (NIB, 2020), industrial associations (e.g., European Bioplastics (European Bioplastics, n.d.), Bio-Plastics Europe (BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE, n.d.)), industrial partners (e.g., suppliers of catalysers or enzymes), technology providers (e.g., production plants such as Ray Technology™ (Avantium, n.d. a), MOSAIK (TOPSOE, n.d.)) and by-product using industries.

In the category society, the citizens themselves and non-governmental organisations are further stakeholders.

5.3.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders:

Afterwards, the stakeholders identified as relevant were mapped in a power-interest matrix, based on a desk research. The result can be found in Figure 41.

The stakeholders considered most powerful and most interested in the market uptake of bio-MEG are placed in the right-top corner. The actors considered to be most powerful are “MEG-relying industries.” “MEG-relying industries” are especially powerful, as they choose whether their final product is produced with fossil-based MEG or bio-MEG. They are the central stakeholder that hold the potential to integrate the biobased MEG into valuable products.

The stakeholder with the highest overall interest in the implementation of bio-MEG concerns “Biobased MEG producers”. They are the ones with the technology to produce the chemical compound and have a very strong interest in their product being processed further, because this is the only way to make bio-MEG profitable.

To bring bio-MEG to the market, “Distributors” are usually used. They act as intermediaries between the bio-MEG producing and utilising industries. This means they have a lot of power in shaping the bio-MEG market.

Other stakeholders that were identified as having high power and high interest are “Policy makers chemical industry (national and EU-level)”. For example, the orientation of the EU goes towards the increased use of renewable resources and the reduction of GHG emissions. Already implemented policies are shaping the European economy and upcoming law and regulations will do so as well. If policies push the implementation of biochemicals and bioplastics, this will influence the market uptake of bio-MEG.

Figure 41. Stakeholders of the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study mapped in a power-interest matrix

Further stakeholders placed in the top-right corner are “industrial organisations,” “public funding institutions” and “industrial partners (e.g., suppliers of catalysers, enzymes)”, all of them having a crucial role in shaping the enabling environment.

Stakeholders, whose interest in bio-MEG implementation is low, but who exercise high power, are biomass suppliers (e.g., forest owners, sawmills, farmers, biomass aggregators) and “Bioethanol producers.” Both, bio-MEG producers, and bioethanol producers are highly reliant on the provision of feedstock, as it is the main input for their chemical production. Although both biochemical producers have similar reliance on biomass, the power of bioethanol producers is considered to be higher than the power of biomass providers. This results from the various utilisation potentials of bioethanol, which creates competition for the application of bioethanol with bio-MEG.

Another stakeholder group placed in this quadrant are “Private financial institutions (e.g., banks, private equity)”, which have the power to directly shape the conditions in which the bio-MEG value chain could either flourish or decay, as financial support is oftentimes inevitable for the realisation of a bio-MEG project.

The lower right quarter (low power, high interest) encompasses stakeholders who stand to gain significantly from the transition to increased bio-MEG production, yet their influence remains

constrained. All of these actors belong to the enabling environment. Academia related stakeholders may shape the technological progress of bio-MEG, which translates into high interest, but rather low power. “Non-governmental organisations” representing the interest behind bio-MEG might have some influence on policy decisions, nevertheless their potential influence is estimated as low.

Allocated in the middle of the power-interest matrix are “Technology providers (e.g., catalysis, bioethanol production)”. These actors might be interested in selling their technology to bio-MEG producers, but do not solely rely on this particular chemical, as their plants find application also in other production processes.

Finally, in the left bottom quarter (low power, low interest), “Transport & logistics companies,” “Infrastructure (e.g., utility and public infrastructure providers)” and “Citizens” are placed. “Transport & logistics companies” as well as the “Infrastructure (e.g., utility and public infrastructure providers)” are crucial for the whole value chain, to mobilise biomass as well as necessary technology, the bio-MEG itself and the bio-MEG containing final product. But, for the infrastructure provided, it does not matter what they transport. That is why the interest in bio-MEG implementation is low. The influence of “Citizens” is minor for the success of the bio-MEG value chain, although consumption choices for products containing bio-MEG might have some stimulating effects.

5.3.3 Policies of relevance to bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass

In this section, policies were identified that could either propel or impede the implementation of bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass. These policies were detected through a desk research (e.g., EU directives and strategies). In Table 33, an overview is provided of the relevant policies, including the type of policy it concerns, further general information, as well as its relevance to the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture residues case study.

Although MEG is one of the world's largest bulk chemical intermediates, with a production volume of 38.1 Mt/year in 2019 (S&P Global, 2019), and is required for the manufacture of several products such as PET bottles and antifreeze, its biobased alternative bio-MEG is still a niche. This is also reflected in the political landscape, as no directives or policies have been identified that directly target bio-MEG.

In general, the EU's overall orientation is towards net-zero CO₂. This is reflected in, for example, the Fit for 55 package, where bio-MEG could benefit from the implementation of the EU Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS) or the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), both of which make the production of less carbon-intensive products more attractive as carbon-intensive production becomes more expensive (European Council, n.d.). Bio-MEG fits in here, as its production is less carbon-intensive compared to fossil-based MEG.

Other policies target the biomass supply, for example the EU Waste Framework Directive (European Commission, n.d. d). This directive emphasises the separate waste collection, the

treatment of biobased waste and the promotion of products that are made from waste. In addition, the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP, European Commission, 2020) also highlights the need for circularity and identifies sectors of particular importance, including packaging, plastics, and textiles. Those stimulate the consideration of waste, for example residues of forestry and agriculture, as resources for industrial production, which in turn promotes the shift from fossil-based MEG production towards biobased MEG production.

There are also policies directed towards biochemicals and bioplastics (European Commission, 2018; European Commission, n.d. a). Those are as well stimulating for bio-MEG production, as bio-MEG can be used as replacement of fossil-based MEG, causing less emissions. However, while the current landscape of policies facilitates the uptake of bio-MEG, additional measures are required to accelerate the transition away from fossil-based MEG. These may include a stronger focus of policies on bio-MEG itself or stronger financial incentives, as bio-MEG production is costlier compared to conventional MEG production.

Table 33. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
Fit for 55	European climate law that makes the reduction of EU emissions of 55% by 2030 a legal obligation.	Stimulating	Bio-MEG has lower CO ₂ emissions than conventional MEG production; there is a possibility to produce bio-MEG from captured carbon; EU-ETS caps CO ₂ emissions and depending on the CO ₂ certificate price, bio-MEG production could become competitive with fossil-based MEG.	EU	Current/ planned (adopted 2023, extended to maritime sector in 2025)	Direct regulation (EU-level) (including economic instruments)	Fit for 55
Circular Economy Action Plan	Plan to transition the EU into a circular economy to reduce pressure on natural resources and create sustainable growth.	Stimulating	Focuses on sectors where potential for circularity is high, including packaging, plastics, textiles (all areas where bio-MEG can be used).	EU	Current	Other (Action plan)	Circular economy action plan
EU industrial strategy	To create a competitive, sustainable, and resilient industrial base within the EU, focusing on the green and digital transitions.	Stimulating	Emphasises the need for industries to move towards renewable resources and adopt green technologies.	EU	Current	Strategy (EU-level)	Annual Single Market Report 2021
Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment	Part of the EU's zero pollution plan and targets to better protect the environment and citizens from harmful chemicals as well as to boost innovation.	Stimulating	Boost investment and innovation capacity for the production and use of safe and sustainable chemicals by design through their lifecycle. Investing in finding alternatives to substances of concern.	EU	Current	Strategy (EU-level) (including policy actions)	Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

EU Waste Framework Directive	General waste management requirements with special paragraph about bio-waste.	Stimulating	Biological waste must be collected and treated separately. It is encouraged that materials should be produced from biological waste.	EU	Current	Direct regulation	Waste Framework Directive
Eco-Design Directive	Setting ecodesign requirements for almost all physical goods, e.g., addressing the presence of substances that inhibit circularity	Stimulating	Bio-MEG can replace a chemical produced from non-renewable resources.	EU	Current	Direct regulation	Ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC
Industrial Emissions Directive	Reducing emissions from industry and intensive livestock, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion of innovation and transformation. - Tight rules on emission reduction. 	Stimulating	Bio-MEG production emits less CO ₂ compared to conventional MEG production; possibility to produce bio-MEG from captured carbon.	EU	Current	Direct regulation	Revised Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive
Communication for an EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable, and compostable plastics	Priority of biomass use for producing materials (e.g., plastics) instead of energy. Support for research and innovation regarding bioplastics	Stimulating	Bio-MEG is a component that allows for bioplastic production (e.g., PET).	EU	Current/ planned	Official communication (EU-level)	Communication for an EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics
A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy	Transformation of the was plastic is designed, produced, used, and recycled in the EU	Stimulating	Bio-MEG is produced with biobased feedstock to avoid using fossil fuels.	EU	Current	Strategy (EU-level) (including policy actions)	A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy

5.3.4 Analysis of indicators on bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study

In T3.2, a consistency check was conducted to identify the indicators in the Bioeconomy Monitoring and Assessment framework deemed relevant in light of bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass. Subsequently, a selection of indicators was labelled as highly relevant. This initial analysis took place on the basis of a desk research.

In the present section, the results from this preliminary analysis will be deepened by means of information through a systematic white/grey literature review. The original list of highly relevant indicators will henceforth be complemented with additional indicators. Each of these indicators will be utilised to assess the performance of the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass in comparison with the conventional MEG from fossil fuels.

The indicator evaluation was approached with a desk-research. In the first step, general information about bio-MEG was searched with key words like “bio-MEG,” “biobased MEG” or “bio monoethylene glycol.” As some indicators relate to aspects that are addressed in LCA, those were specifically researched as well and combined with the key words “environmental impact” “social impact,” “economic impact,” “effluents”, “emissions” and “toxicity”.

It was found that information on bio-MEG from LCAs is not abundant and given the numerous production pathways for bio-MEG, it is difficult to find consistency between the different studies identified. Major differences that could be identified were: utilised biomass, technologies and steps included in the bio-MEG life cycle.

To extend the information base, additional key words were used to identify fitting literature. Those key words include: “bioplastics”, “wood bioplastics”, “bio PET” and “biochemicals”.

Two sources could be identified, that were most fitting to assess the indicators:

- COWI A/S & Utrecht University (2018): Environmental impact assessment of innovative biobased product Task 1 of “Study on Support to R&I Policy in the Area of Biobased Products and Services”
- Zhao, Z., Jiang, J., Zheng, M. & Wang, F. (2021): Advancing development of biochemicals through the comprehensive evaluation of bio-ethylene glycol.

In the case that no information or data could be found to support the analysis of the indicator, this was reported as a research gap.

5.3.4.1 Environmental /circular indicators

Table 34 provides an overview of environmental and circular indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (i.e., 31 indicators in total). Two of the indicators identified as highly relevant in T3.2 were removed, due to their relation with EoL products based on bio-MEG and duplicates with other indicators. No other indicators were identified as highly relevant.

Table 34. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Biodiversity	Ha of protected areas and land with significant biodiversity values used / product unit	For UPM (Leuna, Germany): 100% of wood used in production is sourced from FSC or PEFC certified forests (UPM Biochemicals, n.d. a).	Yes, not all bio-MEG producers source biomass from the same supplier, hence it is difficult to assess.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Biodiversity	Biodiversity damage potential (BDP; m ² *year*PAS (potentially affected species))	Although the BDP is not evaluated in the regionalised LCA, other biodiversity impacts were measured by Fabbri et al., by using the “species-year” metric to estimate potential loss of species over time in response to environmental impacts (2022). No reference to the impact by fossil-based MEG.	Yes, no data is available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Land use change (LUC)	Change in wood/wood fibre demand for forest products	If residue is used as a feedstock for bio-MEG production, no LUC occurs (Gursel et al., 2021).	Yes, bio-MEG is also produced with biomass that is not a residue. The LUC unsure here, and also depends on where the biomass is sourced from.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Primary Biomass production	Wood consumption	Metrics on wood usage per unit of bio-MEG are not published.	Yes, no data available. UPM (Leuna) is the only biorefinery using wood as biomass on industrial scale.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Amount of water used in the value-chain	Process water used for bio ethylene glycol produced amounts to 104.6t*t ⁻¹ (Zhao et al., 2021).	Yes, the required amount of water might differ depending on the production path.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Water consumption (use) (m ³ /product unit used)	0.01 m ³ /kg bio-MEG (Putri, 2018).	Yes, difficult to assess due to diverse production pathways.

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Intensity of fossil fuel use (m ³ /ton of product)	Bio-MEG does not contain fossil fuels as a feedstock. However, other production processes still rely on fossil fuels for energy inputs. Conventional MEG is produced with fossil fuels.	Yes, there is not specific analysis of the energy inputs and impacts from bio-MEG. However, studies on energy utilisation for biochemical production might be of use.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of biological content/product	Bio-MEG is 100% biological as its feedstock is biomass.	
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of carbon content derived from renewable raw material	Biogenic carbon embedded in PET bottles amounts to 0.45 kg/CO ₂ for biobased PET (COWI A/S & Utrecht University, 2018).	Yes, for bio-MEG there is only data for biobased PET and the functional unit.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Renewable energies (RES) share in final energy consumption/product unit	No specific information was found on the share of RES in final energy consumption for the production of bio-MEG.	Yes, difficult to assess because each production pathway is different.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Energy consumption by activity/production process/unit of production (kwh/production process or product unit)	Water operation: 58.7% of steam and 67.3% of electricity (Zhao et al., 2021). Feedstock pretreatment and product separation: 90.0% of steam and 57.7% of electricity (incl. heat recovery and integration) (Zhao et al., 2021). MEG-production: 0.47 kwh/kg MEG (Putri, 2018).	Yes, information is conversion pathway dependent. An overview of all commercial processes is missing.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Water quality	Ecotoxicity for aquatic fresh water (Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems)	Catalytic residues and by-products in the wastewater streams may exhibit toxicity to aquatic life.	Yes, no data available for bio-MEG.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Water quality	Acidification (mol H ⁺ eq. form NO _x , SO _x , NH ₃)	2.27E-02 mol H eq. (for 100 0.5L bio-PET bottles with bio-MEG from EU wheat straw) (COWI A/S & Utrecht University, 2018).	Yes, for bio-MEG there is only data for biobased PET and the functional unit.

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Water quality	Eutrophication (gr eq. PO ₄)	1.39E-03 kg P eq. (for 100 0.5L bio-PET bottles with bio-MEG from EU wheat straw) (COWI A/S & Utrecht University, 2018)	Yes, for bio-MEG there is only data for biobased PET and the functional unit.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Soil quality	Soil erosion/product unit	The spatially resolved method for assessing land use impacts on soil erosion based on topsoil loss and topsoil organic carbon (SOC) losses as key indicators for energy crops (Núñez et al., 2013) could be utilised for certain bio-MEG feedstocks such as sugarcane, maize and some lignocellulosic residues.	Yes, depending on the sustainability of feedstock provision, agricultural practices and regional conditions.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Soil quality	Soil nutrient balance	No soil nutrient balance for bio-MEG production yet available. However, studies on bioenergy crops and biobased chemicals suggest soil fertility loss is a critical issue when using agricultural feedstocks (Lindorfer et al., 2014). Residue-based feedstocks (e.g., forestry and agricultural residues) may have lower soil nutrient depletion risks.	Yes, depending on the feedstock used for bio-MEG production.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	% of the total amount of wood used comes from sustainable forest management (economically viable, environmentally sound, socially responsible) or are waste wood according to waste wood categories	UPM (Leuna): 100% of wood used in production is sourced from FSC or PEFC certified forests (UPM biochemicals, n.d. a). Conventional MEG does not use wood.	No, assuming that UPM (Leuna) is the only wood using biorefinery for bio-MEG.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	% of deforestation or afforestation /product unit	UPM (Leuna): 100% of wood used in production is sourced from FSC or PEFC certified forests (UPM biochemicals, n.d. a)	No, assuming that UPM (Leuna) is the only wood using biorefinery for bio-MEG.

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Hazardous substances management	% of hazardous (carcinogenic, mutagenic, reprotoxic) substances	There is no evidence of potential carcinogenic, mutagenic, or reprotoxic (CMR) effects of certain impurities that can appear in bio-MEG (1,2-butanediol, a C4 diol) (Patent WO2018089600A1).	Yes, no detailed data available for bio-MEG.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Hazardous substances management	% of product materials produced and managed to high environmental and social standards	Bio-MEG is subject to regulatory frameworks that govern the management of hazardous substances, ensuring safety and compliance in its production and use. Bio-MEG producers such as INEOS Oxyde count with sustainability certification RSB (Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials).	Yes, lack of detailed and publicly available information.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation management	Waste generated	From lignocellulosic pathways, lignin-rich solid residues are generated. Currently, UPM has integrated these to be part of their business case as a by-product. Fermentation-based processes create wastewater with organic pollutants such as acetaldehyde and acetic acid.	Yes, depending on the feedstock used and conversion pathways.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation management	Procedures for separating and using recyclable materials from the waste stream (yes/no)	Currently, the recycling rate amounts to 60%, with 20% being incinerated and the remaining 20% landfilled (COWI A/S & Utrecht University, 2018).	Yes, depending on conversion pathways.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation management	Declaration of end-of-life disposal (in the CSR report) (yes/no)	No information on EoL disposal, given the intermediate role of bio-MEG for diverse final products. LCAs are from cradle to gate (e.g., UPM).	Yes, further information is required.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation management	% of materials derived from recycling or recovery of any other biomass waste	No specifics were found on the shares of agricultural and/or forestry residues used in the production of bio-MEG. Likewise, regarding wastes from bio-MEG production, most recognised ones are lignin and MPG, which are valorised into additional products. Specific shares per unit of bio-MEG are not known.	Yes, further information is required.

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation management	Recycling rate/cascading indexes	No detailed information about bio-MEG recycling rates was found. However, information about the recovery of MEG from PET is available: MEG recovery efficiency ranges from 63% to 99.6% depending on process conditions.	Yes, further information is required.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation management	Procedures for handling, collecting, separating and disposal of hazardous waste as defined by the relevant local and national regulatory authorities (yes/no)	Yes, e.g., on EU level the Waste Framework Directive (European Commission, n.d. d), which applies to both fossil-based MEG and bio-MEG.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation management	Practices for waste storage, treatment and disposal that do not pose health or safety risks to farmers, workers, other people, or natural ecosystems (yes/no)	Yes, bio-MEG is a drop-in chemical and is physically and chemically identical to fossil-based MEG. It can be recycled in established recycling streams alongside fossil waste (European Bioplastics, 2024).	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Biomass Utilisation Factor (BUF)	For bio-MEG, the BUF is 100%.	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle GHG emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	Bio-MEG from lignocellulosic biomass waste (LCBW) allows reducing GHG emissions by 51% and 69.5%, compared to production from coal and oil, respectively (Zhao et al. 2021). Production of bio-MEG from sugarcane: 1.09 kg CO ₂ eq./kg bio-MEG (Semba et al., 2012). The GHG emissions of bio-MEG become lower with increase of pretreated concentration (Zhao et al. 2021)	Yes, further analysis is required for diverse conversion pathways.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP100; gr eq. CO ₂)	~1,5 kg CO ₂ eq./kg bio-MEG produced from EU corn that is contained in 100 0.5L bio-PET bottles (COWI A/S & Utrecht University, 2018)	Yes, for bio-MEG there is only data for biobased PET and the functional unit.

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Air quality	<p>Amount of volatile organic compounds (VOC) emitted (parts per billion (ppb), parts per million (ppm), or as micrograms per cubic meter ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)).</p>	<p>Bio-MEG VOC emissions data is still scarce, but studies on related biobased chemical production suggest lower VOC emissions compared to fossil-based processes.</p> <p>VOC emissions from glycol dehydration systems ranged from 50 to 2,000 mg/m^3 (Rueter et al., 1996).</p>	Yes, further analysis is required.
---	---	-------------	---	--	------------------------------------

The environmental and circularity performance of the bio-MEG system is promising in comparison to the incumbent system, but has notable data gaps. Bio-MEG benefits from renewable feedstocks, lower fossil fuel dependence, and reduced greenhouse gas emissions compared to fossil-based MEG. Sustainable sourcing, particularly from certified forestry, supports biodiversity and reduces deforestation risks. However, uncertainties remain regarding land-use change, biodiversity damage, and resource efficiency across different production pathways. Only if feedstocks are sourced from certified forestry or agricultural residues there is a contribution of the bio-MEG to sustainable resource management. However, if large-scale production leads to increased demand for dedicated bio-crops, it could drive deforestation or biodiversity loss, offsetting its carbon savings.

Water and energy use are relatively well-documented, in particular for bio-MEG production, when derived from lignocellulosic biomass, it requires substantial process water for hydrolysis, fermentation, and purification. On the other hand, circularity aspects such as end-of-life disposal, recycling rates, and hazardous waste management require further assessment. Toxicity of bio-MEG is equally as for the fossil-based option, concerning for human exposure and requires good management of water effluents which must be treated to avoid environmental contamination.

5.3.4.2 Economic indicators

Table 35 provides an overview of economic indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (i.e., 4 indicators in total). In addition, 1 indicator was newly identified as highly relevant, and included in the table in red.

Table 35. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Strategy for creating the infrastructure and systems necessary for recovering and recycling materials (yes/no)	Yes, bio-MEG is a drop-in chemical and is physically and chemically identical to fossil-based MEG. It can be recycled in established recycling streams alongside fossil waste (European Bioplastics, 2024). PET for example can be recycled (Awaja & Pavel, 2005). In Germany, there is a deposit-system for PET-bottles (Žmak & Hartmann, 2017).	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Potential market share of the product	The total global production capacity for biobased PET in 2024 amounted to ~271,700 t (European Bioplastics, 2024).	Yes, there is only data on bio-PET.

5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Value Added of the bioeconomy sectors	Contribution of the product/ service/ organisation to economic progress (revenue, gain, paid wages, R+D costs in relation to revenue, etc.)	No data was found about the contribution of the product or its related organisations to economic progress.	Yes, there is no data for bio-MEG.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Full time equivalent jobs along the full value chain of a product	Direct FTE data for the bio-MEG value chain is lacking.	Yes, there is no data for bio-MEG.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Production costs	Production cost of bio-MEG compared to production cost of conventional MEG	Total production costs of bio-MEG are 20% higher than of carbon-based MEG and 43.3% higher than petroleum-based MEG (Mendieta et al., 2022).	No.

Considering the evaluation of economic indicators, it is noted that the production costs for bio-MEG are approximately 20% higher than coal-based MEG and 43.3% higher than petroleum-based MEG (Mendieta et al., 2022). This is understandable due to early commercial phase of bio-MEG, relying on biomass conversion technologies that are less optimised and more capital-intensive than well-established petrochemical processes. Additionally, feedstock availability and supply chain infrastructure for bio-MEG are not yet as efficient as those for fossil-based alternatives. With regard to the potential market share, data about the current market share for bio-MEG in comparison to the incumbent system is limited. A further established production network and cost-efficiency is necessary to increase the market share of bio-MEG. No direct employment data is available, but as a part of the bioeconomy, it has the potential to create new jobs in biorefining, feedstock supply, and sustainable materials development.

5.3.4.3 Social indicators

Table 36 provides an overview of social indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (i.e., 5 indicators in total). No other indicators identified as highly relevant in this category.

Table 36. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Presence of a formal policy in place concerning health and safety of all workers, including contractors (yes/no)	Yes, in many countries there are laws in place to ensure the safety of workers, e.g., the German Arbeitsschutzgesetz (ArbSchG) (Bundesministerium der Justiz, n.d.).	Yes, laws are different in each country.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Stakeholder engagement and capacity building	Number of informal workshops to build local understanding in the community of the processes that may impact them directly to aid meaningful engagement	Large chemical companies like Braskem, Indorama Ventures, and INEOS Oxide (which produce or invest in bio-MEG) often conduct community outreach programs as part of their CSR initiatives. These reports sometimes include engagement strategies, sustainability goals, and workshops with local communities.	Yes, no overview of stakeholder engagements was found for bio-MEG production.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Stakeholder engagement and capacity building	Promoting the involvement of small holders or small suppliers (yes/no)	No workshops/ events/ presentations on bio-MEG could be identified.	Yes, data on stakeholder engagements is missing.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Stakeholder engagement and capacity building	Presence of a law or norm regarding transparency (yes/no)	Bio-MEG production and its producers are generally required to adhere to comprehensive environmental and safety regulations that promote transparency. For instance, REACH (ECHA database), and Safety Data Sheets (SDS).	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Number of collaborations with service providers that comply with applicable sustainability environmental and social criteria	Collaboration with service providers and their applicable sustainability criteria is not openly available.	Yes, data on collaborations with service provider is not publicly available.

Based on the social indicators in the table above, limited data reduces the possibility to analyse the biobased system with the incumbent one. However, it is expected that both bio-MEG and fossil-based MEG industries operate under formal health and safety regulations, ensuring worker protection. While information collected for the bio-MEG production from UPM in Leuna mentions the connection with regional stakeholders as part of their feedstock provision, it is difficult to track specific initiatives that might have been undertaken to specifically involve smallholders or small suppliers in the value chain. For other bio-MEG initiatives in the EU, there is a lack of information about structured engagement programs or capacity-building efforts. On the other side, the fossil-based MEG industry operates on centralised, large-scale petrochemical supply chains, where smallholder involvement is generally not applicable.

Furthermore, the bio-MEG sector specifically does not count with transparency laws or norms, with no clear regulations governing its production and trade beyond general corporate and environmental reporting standards. However, under the umbrella of biochemicals transparency rules, are in development. For instance, internationally, the Global Minimum Transparency Standard (GMTS) has been developed as a tool for companies to disclose the identity of chemicals in their materials and products. Efforts deployed with the EU transparency regulation have the potential to influence bio-MEG in applications in the food value chain (e.g., food packaging).

In contrast, fossil-based MEG is subject to stricter transparency requirements, particularly for large petrochemical companies, which must comply with corporate governance regulations, environmental disclosures, and ESG reporting.

5.3.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Market dimension

Challenges

- Raw material cost fluctuations. Fluctuations in agricultural outputs due to climate variability, pests and diseases, can lead to inconsistent feedstock availability, posing risks to bio-MEG production. This can cause significant price volatility for biomass feedstocks, affecting profit margins and making long-term financial planning challenging. Moreover, competition with other industries for the same feedstocks can exacerbate price fluctuations, further impacting the market. Unfortunately, the unpredictability associated with agricultural and forestry outputs fluctuations can deter investment in bio-MEG production facilities. Investors may perceive the sector as high-risk and in turn limit capital inflow, hindering the expansion and technological advancement of the industry.
- Competition with fossil-based incumbents (oil price volatility). Bio-MEG production can be more expensive than its petrochemical counterpart. High costs may deter investment and adoption, necessitating policies that provide financial incentives or subsidies to offset these expenses.
- Investment intensive processes (scale-up). Securing financial support for bio-MEG productions involves navigating various funding avenues, particularly within the EU. These opportunities encompass public grants, subsidies, and private investments aimed at

promoting sustainable and circular biobased industries. For instance, Germany has set aside up to €2.8 billion to support industrial companies in decarbonising their production processes. These 15-year subsidies target sectors like chemicals, compensating for the additional costs associated with green production methods. Notable beneficiaries include BASF and Suedzucker, highlighting the government's commitment to fostering sustainable industrial practices.

Examples of good practices

- Diversification of feedstocks and strategic feedstock reserves and contracts: Utilising a variety of biomass sources, including agricultural residues and non-food crops, can reduce dependence on a single feedstock and enhance supply stability. E.g., Avantium, which engages with multiple feedstock providers to diversify their supply sources. Likewise, long-term contracts with suppliers can help mitigate the effect of fluctuations. To mitigate feedstock variability, Braskem establishes long-term agreements with sugar suppliers, ensuring a stable input supply for their bio-MEG production and reducing exposure to market fluctuations.
- Integrating various stages of bio-MEG production can lead to significant cost savings and strengthening the co-production of other biochemicals that help support the competitiveness of the main product, while reducing costs due to process integration and energy efficiency (e.g., UPM).
- Establishing public-private partnerships to alleviate financial burdens. For instance, UPM's biorefinery in Leuna, Germany, received support from regional authorities, facilitating investment in bio-MEG production infrastructure.

Policy dimension

Challenges

- The EU currently does not count with a policy framework to facilitate the shift toward renewable carbon sources in the chemicals and materials industry. This framework should include biomass-derived, CO₂-based, or recycled carbon sources. While sectors such as energy and transport have specific decarbonisation targets, the chemical and material industries are often overlooked in EU policies. Current regulatory measures primarily focus on carbon reduction at the point of emissions, rather than supporting upstream material transitions. This leads to unclear market incentives for biobased alternatives, and due to a lack of biobased content targets, end-use industries such as packaging, textiles and automotive lack the incentive to shift towards bio-MEG. Moreover, without lifecycle-based carbon accounting, bio-MEG's environmental benefits are not fully recognised, limiting its attractiveness compared to fossil alternatives.
- Recycling of textile products: Blended fabrics pose significant challenges due to the difficulty in separating different fibre types. The presence of dyes, additives, and finishes in textiles further complicates the recycling process.
- Recycling of PET packaging products: Traditional mechanical recycling of PET packaging has limitations, particularly concerning the degradation of material quality over successive cycles. Chemical recycling offers a promising alternative by breaking down PET into its monomers, such as bio-MEG, allowing for the production of high-quality recycled PET.

However, this process is energy-intensive and requires further innovation to become economically viable.

Examples of good practices

- Sustainable carbon cycles: The EC has introduced an initiative focused on restoring sustainable carbon cycles. This initiative emphasises the development of alternative and sustainable carbon sources, aiming to reconcile the essential need for carbon in organic chemistry with the imperative to reduce CO₂ emissions (CEFIC, n.d.).
- Policy framework for biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics.
- Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation.
- Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- Feedstock related challenges, such as deforestation, biodiversity risks and lack of use of certifications are of high concern. If not sourced responsibly, increased demand for biomass could contribute to land-use change, deforestation, and loss of biodiversity, particularly in regions with weak environmental governance. Also, for the case of sugar-based feedstocks (e.g., sugarcane, corn), expanding bio-MEG production could increase demand for these crops, leading to concerns about food security, land use and soil quality. Finally, while FSC and PEFC certifications ensure sustainable forestry practices, not all bio-MEG producers adhere to strict certification standards.
- Wastewater and pollution from refining. The chemical conversion of biomass into MEG generates wastewater and residues that must be properly treated to prevent environmental contamination, as well as accompanying health and safety risks.
- Circularity of bio-MEG. There is uncertainty about the potential of recirculating bio-MEG, however at the moment, existing PET recycling systems do not distinguish between biobased and fossil-based MEG. And unlike biofuels, which are burned for energy, bio-MEG remains in materials (e.g., textiles, plastics), making carbon circularity harder to achieve.

Examples of good practices

- Apart from the utilisation of residual biomass, algae-based systems with a high yield potential appear as a possibility to reduce arable land.
- Enhance certification schemes: Ensure robust sustainability standards for bio-MEG feedstocks, including criteria for biodiversity and social impacts.
- Chemical recycling: by investing in technologies that depolymerise bio-MEG-based plastics back into monomers for repolymerisation.
- Enhance mechanical recycling: Improve sorting and processing techniques to maintain material quality during recycling.

5.3.6 Key learnings of bio-MEG case study

The transition to bio-MEG is supported by multiple EU policies and initiatives that emphasise climate mitigation, circular economy, and sustainable resource use. The Fit for 55 package, the ETS, the CEAP, and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability provide an overarching framework that incentivises biobased alternatives by penalising fossil-based MEG production and promoting biobased materials. However, as identified in section 5.3.4, further impulses with specific measures for the biochemicals should be developed for the assurance of bio-MEG sustainability.

Among the key stakeholders shaping the transition, MEG-relying industries (such as PET manufacturers and polyester producers) hold significant market power. Their willingness to adopt bio-MEG will determine demand and influence supply chains. Bio-MEG producers and distributors, on the other hand, play a central role in ensuring that production is scalable and competitive. Policymakers at national and EU levels also serve as key enablers, shaping the regulatory landscape that determines the long-term economic feasibility of bio-MEG.

This will require also actions from policy and industry actors to dissipate uncertainties regarding production costs, scalability and long-term competitiveness against fossil-based MEG. Without stronger financial incentives (e.g., tax reductions or subsidies for biobased chemicals), the sector may continue struggling to compete with conventional petrochemicals.

To accelerate bio-MEG adoption, several actions are necessary:

- Introduce stronger financial incentives: Tax credits, subsidies, or preferential procurement policies for biobased chemicals would help bridge the cost gap between bio-MEG and fossil-based MEG.
- Improve supply chain efficiency: Investing in logistics, biomass processing, and regional bioeconomy hubs would strengthen bio-MEG's competitiveness and scalability.
- Enhance transparency and certification: Establishing mandatory sustainability certification for bio-MEG production would ensure responsible sourcing and increase consumer confidence.
- Expand research and innovation funding: Supporting process optimisation, enzyme efficiency, and biomass utilisation improvements can lower production costs and enhance resource efficiency.
- Promote industry collaboration and stakeholder engagement: Establishing public-private partnerships and engaging smallholders in biomass supply chains would enhance social sustainability and regional economic benefits.

The case study highlights bio-MEG's strong potential as a sustainable alternative to fossil-based MEG, particularly in reducing GHG emissions and fossil fuel dependence.

Addressing data gaps in environmental, economic, and social performance will further enhance transparency and confidence in bio-MEG utilisation. Likewise, further monitoring on biodiversity impacts and LUC when using non-residue biomass and detailed employment and economic impact analysis to determine the full job creation potential of bio-MEG production is needed.

6 RESULTS FROM THE PLASTICS SECTOR CASE STUDIES

In the framework of SUSTRACK, three case studies were carried out to assess sustainable innovations in the plastics sector. These case studies provided valuable insights that informed sector-wide discussions during stakeholder consultations. The first plastics case study focuses on polylactic acid (PLA), a bio-based and biodegradable polymer that serves as a sustainable alternative to conventional petroleum-based plastics. The second case study investigates polypropylene (PP) produced from used cooking oil (UCO), a circular approach that upcycles waste oils into high-performance plastic materials. The third case study explores cellulose acetate, a bio-based polymer with diverse applications in packaging, textiles, and consumer goods, offering reduced reliance on fossil-based plastic feedstocks.

The following section presents a summary of the plastics sector-specific insights gathered from the SUSTRACK DESIGN workshop discussions, incorporating perspectives from stakeholders engaged in these case studies and the broader sustainable plastics industry.

6.1 Sector-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Policy dimension

Challenges

- Industry stakeholders state a lack of a harmonised definition for biobased plastics and polymers. Such a definition is crucial for setting standards, certification schemes, and effectively regulating the market.
- Another challenge is the lack of methods in existing biodegradability tests to comprehensively assess environmental impacts, e.g., there are no methods in current tests that measure the release of microplastics.
- The limited availability of biobased raw materials, combined with the higher production costs of biopolymers, pose a major challenge for the bioplastics industry.
- The absence of favourable policies, such as incentives for using renewable carbon, discourages the development and market penetration of biobased plastics.
- The diverse regulatory frameworks governing various biobased materials pose a significant challenge to industry stakeholders, creating confusion and stifling innovation.

Recommendations/good practices

- The stakeholders mention the following policies as good practices: the EU Plastics Strategy, the Circular Economy Action Plan, the EU Policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics of 2022, Directive (EU) 2015/720 lightweight plastics carrier bags, and finally Directive EU 2019/904: SUP (Single use plastics directive).
- To further boost sustainability efforts, a mandatory biobased content is proposed to complement mandatory recycled content in the Packaging and Packaging Waste Legislation (PPWL) and the End-of-Life Vehicles (ELV) Regulation.
- Financial support from the government, including incentives for biobased materials and assistance in scaling up technologies with a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) above 5, is also proposed.

- Furthermore, stakeholders state that establishing a legally binding framework with clear sustainability criteria and incentives for labels and externally audited third-party certification systems is necessary.
- To further strengthen the bioeconomy strategy, stakeholders recommended removing unnecessary constraints and limitations, like marine biodegradable only materials.
- Finally, it's recommended to establish a coherent, fact-based definition of biobased polymers across all policy frameworks, replacing politically driven definitions—such as those in the SUPD—with scientifically accurate classifications that distinguish between different types of polymers.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- Stakeholders emphasise that the current lack of understanding of the environmental impact of biodegradation processes due to lack of adequate test methods hinders the clear communication of the benefits of biobased plastics.
- Current multi-stakeholder research into circular biobased economy is insufficient.
- Another major challenge hampering the growth of the bioplastics industry is the lack of end-of-life possibilities and infrastructures to properly treat biobased and biodegradable plastic waste.
- Furthermore, the lack of sustainable sources for biobased feedstock, especially ones that don't compete with food, combined with the lack of transparent chains of custody pose another challenge to the sustainability of the market.

Recommendations/good practices

- Stakeholders point that a promotion of transparency and consumer awareness of biobased products is necessary to boost the transition. Fundamental for this, is the implementation of a comprehensive sustainability assessment of products across the entire life cycle.
- Additionally, the lacking knowledge about and infrastructure for end-of-life waste management of biobased plastics was identified as a major barrier and thus supporting the development of a circular economy and the cascading use of biopolymers is advised to boost the market of biobased plastics and polymers.
- Finally, the stakeholders propose the promotion of the proactive integration of local stakeholders and authorities in the decision-making process.

Market dimension

Challenges

- The stakeholders point to the current consumer confusion being a great challenge to boosting the market.
- Furthermore, the higher costs of biobased plastics compared to their fossil counterparts, due to the lack of monetarisation of environmental costs, represent a major challenge for the sector.

- Market-related bottlenecks, including investments, time to market, availability of well-equipped specialised tech parks and plants accessible to (small) third parties are a further challenge.
- The lack of involvement of end-of-life stakeholders to guarantee proper treatment of bioplastic waste has been highlighted by several stakeholders to be a major challenge hampering the transition.
- Finally, lacking market pull measures to promote the willingness to use products containing circular materials has been identified.

Recommendations/good practices

- To address the above-mentioned challenges, stakeholders suggest the setup of incentive schemes that enhance the use of biomass for materials. Such schemes could include the implementation of minimum biobased plastics content targets for key plastics applications to create the required market pull.
- Moreover, enhancing the quality and quantity of collected biowaste suitable as feedstock for plastics production, as well as implementing a mandatory separate collection of organic household waste in all EU member states are suggested.

6.2 Plastics - Polylactic acid

6.2.1 Introduction to polylactic acid case study

6.2.1.1 General description

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) is a biobased and under controlled composting conditions biodegradable thermoplastic aliphatic polyester (Taib *et al.*, 2023). The building block for PLA is lactic acid. Lactic acid is produced by bacterial fermentation of carbohydrates or chemical synthesis, although the former predominates. The first synthesis of lactic acid was recorded in 1845 by French chemist Théophile-Jules Pelouze. In 1932, Wallace Carothers *et al.* developed a method to polymerise lactide into low-density PLA by heating lactic acid under vacuum while removing condensed water (Masutani and Kimura, 2014). Over the past decades, PLA has undergone significant development and has been used in a variety of fields.

PLA stores the carbon of biogenic origin that was taken up from the atmosphere by the plant in its growth phase and reemits it during composting, creating a carbon neutral cycle. PLA is not biodegradable in landfill or through home composting, so for PLA to not cause a waste problem it must be taken to the right sites at its end of life. Only through industrial composting or anaerobic digestion under thermophilic conditions is PLA biodegradable. Easily processed on standard plastics equipment, PLA can be used to manufacture moulded parts, fibres and films, consumer goods and is the most used filament for 3D-printing.

Physical properties of PLA (Matbase, n.d.)

Melting temperature	150 - 160 °C
---------------------	--------------

Glass temperature	45 - 65 °C
Density	1210 - 1430 kg/m ³
Water absorption	0.5 - 50 %

6.2.1.2 Value chain and the process

*The raw material production process of fermentation does not apply to chemically and mechanically recycled PLA.

Figure 42. Value chain of PLA

PLA can be manufactured from a variety of different feedstock. Starch, saccharose and lignocellulose containing crops, such as corn, sugarcane, cassava, and wood chips can be fermented to produce lactic acid, the polymer precursor of PLA. The direct polycondensation of lactic acid and the production of lactide from lactic acid followed by a ring-opening polymerisation are both industrially established routes of producing PLA, with the latter being the most largely used route. PLA can then be further processed to create a variety of different

products through common plastic processing technologies, such as injection moulding, hot press moulding, 3D-printing, rotational moulding, and foam moulding. At its end of life, PLA can biodegrade in industrial composting facilities or through thermophilic (at temperatures above 50°C) anaerobic digestion, reemitting the carbon it stored during its life cycle. Alternatively, PLA can be mechanically or chemically recycled.

Figure 43. Graphical representation of the PLA-based packaging film value chain (Source: STAR-ProBio, 2018)

6.2.1.3 Baseline and market

In 2022 PLA was the most widely produced bioplastic, accounting for 20.7% of the total bioplastics production worldwide. It is forecasted that by 2027 this share will increase to reach 37.9% (European Bioplastics, 2022). Indeed, the global PLA market size was estimated at USD 713.22 million in 2023 and is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 21.4% from 2024 to 2030 (MarketsandMarkets™ Research Private Ltd, 2023).

Figure 44. Global capacities, production and trends 2022-2027 of biobased building blocks and polymers (Source: nova-Institute, 2023)

The main applications of the PLA end-product can be categorised as following:

- Consumer goods: disposable tableware, cutlery, housings for kitchen appliances and electronics. (PLA is not suitable for microwave due to its low glass temperature).
- Agricultural: mulch, films, filaments.
- Clinical: anchors, screws, plates, pins, rods, mesh. Due to its biocompatibility, PLA-based material consists of neither toxic nor carcinogenic effect on the human body.

The advantages and disadvantages of PLA can be shortly described in Table 37.

Table 37. PLA main pros and cons (Source: NA.A.B. Taib, M.R. Rahman, D. Huda et al, 2023)

Advantages	Disadvantages
Eco-friendliness The production of PLA is from renewable sources (corn, wheat, rice). Furthermore, it is biodegradable, recyclable, and compostable. Its production absorbs CO ₂	Poor toughness PLA is a very brittle material, with a break elongation of < 10%. For those applications that require plastic deformation at high-stress levels, this may represent a limit
Biocompatibility The key product of PLA degradation, lactic acid, is non-toxic and the organism itself metabolizes it	Slow degradation rate By hydrolysis, PLA naturally degrades; its rate depends on several variables, such as crystallinity and molecular weight. Slow degradation of PLA results in a high lifetime of devices in vivo and poses problems with the disposal of commodities
Processability The thermal processability of PLA is greater than other biopolymers. Injection molding, film extrusion, blow molding, thermoforming, fiber spinning, and film-forming are among the methods of PLA processes	Hydrophobicity PLA static water contact angle value is about 80°, making PLA a relatively hydrophobic material, which results in low cell affinity and can lead to inflammatory response upon direct contact with biological fluids
Energy-saving PLA requires 25 – 55% less energy than petroleum-based polymers	Lack of reactive side-chain groups PLA is chemically inert, making surface functionalization and bulk modification challenging tasks

Example for PLA producers in the EU:

- **Futerro**
Futerro is a Belgian bioplastics manufacturer working on PLA technologies since 1992 and as of 2022 the second largest PLA producer in the world. The company is currently the only one capable of fully breaking down PLA back into its monomer, lactic acid, allowing a reproduction of new virgin PLA (LOOPLA technology) (futerro, 2024).
- **TotalEnergies Corbion (The Netherlands and Thailand)**
The company is a 50/50 joint venture between TotalEnergies and Corbion. Headquartered in the Netherlands and operational in Thailand, TotalEnergies Corbion is a global leader in PLA technology (TotalEnergies Corbion, 2024).
- **NatureWorks LLC (USA, Thailand. The Netherlands -> office)**
NatureWorks is a joint venture between Cargill and the Dow Chemical Company in 2001 and is currently the world-leading biopolymers supplier and innovator. NatureWorks is headquartered in the USA, as well as its main manufacturing facility. Additional offices are located in Japan, The Netherlands and Thailand (NatureWorks, 2024).
- **Synbra, now BEWI (The Netherlands, since 2018 acquired by Swedish BEWI group)**
Synbra Technology bv specialised in the manufacture of EPS beads PS Compounds and is the largest EPS recycler in Western Europe. The company was founded in 1975 and polymerisation started in 1973. EPS recycling commenced in 1992. In 2018 Swedish BEWI group acquired Synbra Technology bv (BEWI, 2024).
- **Sulzer (Switzerland)**
Sulzer focuses on fluid engineering and chemical processing applications. The company is founded in 1834. In 2022, Sulzer’s PLA technology has been selected for Yangzhou Huitong PLA plant (Sulzer, 2024).

- **BASF SE (Germany)**

The headquarter of BASF is located in Germany. BASF is a European multinational company and the largest chemical producer in the world. They offer biopolymer *ecovio*, which consists of PBAT, PLA and other additives, for a wide range of applications, from packaging coating to mulch film (BASF, 2024).

6.2.2 Stakeholders in the PLA value chain

6.2.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

To begin with, the stakeholders relevant to the PLA were determined by means of an exploratory desk research (websites of governmental organisations and PLA-producer companies). Figure 45 provides a schematic representation of the identified stakeholders, both in the Bioeconomy supply chain and its enabling environment.

The stakeholders identified are the following. On the one hand, in the bioeconomy value chain there are carbohydrate-rich raw material suppliers, biomass pre-treatment facilities and distributors, PLA producers, retailers, consumers, and waste management companies. The pre-treatment and processing of the raw materials are conducted in biorefineries. Some biorefineries can also integrate the fermentation and polymerisation. Such a fully integrated biorefinery with a unit for molecular recycling of PLA is planned by Belgian company Futerro S.A in the Normandy region of France. On the other hand, the enabling environment includes stakeholders from government, namely policymakers and supra-national organisations, and from industry, like business associations that represent the industry's interests such as European Bioplastics e.V., certification bodies, competing buyers of biomass, competing plastic producers, and investors. Furthermore, research institutions, citizens, and NGOs represent very important stakeholders in the enabling environment.

Figure 45. Identified stakeholders in the PLA case study

6.2.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

In this section the Power-Interest Matrix, which visually represents the relative power and level of interest of identified key stakeholders within the PLA value chain, is presented. Stakeholders are categorised into four quadrants based on their influence and concern.

The first quadrant, characterised by both high power and high interest, includes key players such as customers (both plastic product manufacturers and end users), policymakers, standard setting organisations (e.g., ISO, UNI) & supra-national organisations, and biorefineries. These stakeholders require significant attention and proactive engagement as they have the ability to significantly impact the success of the PLA industry and are deeply involved in its development.

The second quadrant comprises stakeholders with high power but potentially lower interest, such as raw material suppliers and retailers. While their cooperation is crucial, the focus should be on maintaining their satisfaction and ensuring their support. Both these stakeholders are indispensable for the success of the PLA industry: the former by supplying the crucial raw materials, and the latter by selling the final products. This inherent dependence grants them significant power over PLA producers. However, these stakeholders may not always prioritise the PLA industry. Carbohydrate-rich raw material suppliers, particularly those focused on first-generation biomass (like corn), often prioritise the food sector, leading to potential competition and ethical concerns regarding the diversion of food crops for industrial use. Furthermore, retailers may face challenges due to the higher price of PLA compared to traditional plastics. Until PLA becomes more economically competitive, retailers' interest in promoting PLA may remain lower than their inherent power within the value chain. Moreover, competing businesses, such as producers of other bioplastics (like PHA or PBS), traditional petrochemical plastics, and even companies developing advanced recycling technologies for conventional plastics, are included in this quadrant. These competitors exert considerable power over the PLA market, as they directly influence market share, pricing mechanisms, and technological innovation. While their primary interest may not be to specifically hinder PLA's development, their actions and market strategies have a direct and significant impact on the competitive landscape for PLA. Therefore, understanding the competitive dynamics and the strategies of these players is crucial for the long-term success of the PLA industry. Financial Institutions also have a strong power, but a lower interest in PLA investments.

The third quadrant comprises stakeholders with a strong interest in PLA but limited direct power to influence its development, such as citizens and NGOs. These groups are deeply concerned about environmental sustainability and the impact of plastics on the environment. They actively advocate for the adoption of more environmentally-friendly alternatives, such as materials like biobased PLA.

R&D institutions also fall within this quadrant. They play a crucial role in driving innovation in PLA technology, developing new applications, and improving its performance and sustainability. While their research efforts are vital for the advancement of PLA, their direct influence on industry decisions may be limited.

Keeping these stakeholders informed about industry developments, addressing their concerns, and actively seeking their input is crucial for building public trust and fostering a positive image

for the PLA industry. Engaging with NGOs can help identify and address potential social and environmental risks, while collaboration with R&D institutions can accelerate innovation and ensure that PLA development aligns with sustainability goals.

The stakeholder mapping resulted in the fourth quadrant of low interest and low power being empty. However, it can be argued that the general public, or specifically the part of it with low awareness of or engagement with bioplastics, belongs to this quadrant. It is difficult to categorise the entire general public as one stakeholder group, as citizens and their convictions and motivations are very heterogenous. But for this analysis and based on several reports discussing the growing environmental concerns citizens have and the increasing awareness of plastic pollution and climate change issues, citizens have been allocated to the third quadrant as mentioned above.

Figure 46. Stakeholders of the PLA case study mapped in a power-interest matrix

6.2.3 Policies of relevance to PLA value chain

In this section, policies were identified that could either propel or impede the implementation of the PLA chain. These policies were detected through desk research, as well as interactions with stakeholders, complemented with inputs collected during the DESIGN conference. In Table 38 an

overview is provided of the relevant policies at European level, including the type of policy it concerns, further general information, as well as its relevance to PLA.

The existing policy landscape in the EU and national level demonstrates a strong commitment across the EU Member States to shift toward a more sustainable, low-emission and circular economy, which supports the uptake of bioplastics and moving forward from fossil-based plastics.

The Single-Use Plastics Directive (SUPD) primarily focuses on limiting the use of 10 single-use fossil-based plastics items in the current market and pushing recycling by combining recyclable materials in certain products. The SUPD targets to prevent and reduce negative impacts of certain plastic products on the environment and human health, which aligns with EU's circular economy objectives and contributes to accelerate the EU green transition.

PLA is widely used in rigid and flexible packaging (European Bioplastics and nova-Institute, 2024). Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) is an updated policy framework of Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWD). The PPWR emphasises a more harmonised and specific approach of fossil-based plastics replacement in the packaging sector. Not only the PPWR enables greener alternatives, such as PLA, to flourish in the packaging market, it also phases out the amount of plastic waste produced while spreading social awareness. For example, one of the new rules states that take-away businesses have to offer customers the option to bring their own containers at no extra cost. Moreover, PPWR monitors substances and material content in packaging to ensure product safety.

Table 38. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to the PLA value chain

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
European Green Deal	The European Green Deal aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 through a broad framework of policies, including emission reduction, resource efficiency, and circular economy initiatives. To tackle the constantly growing source of waste, the Commission has made new rules around reduce, reuse and recycle plastic-based packaging	Stimulating instrument	The Commission targets to promote reusable packaging options, limit overpackaging and provide clear labels to support correct recycling.	EU	Current Planned and proposed in 2019. Adopted in 2022. Fully recyclable packaging by 2030. Reduce packaging waste by 15% by 2040 compared to 2018.	Policy framework and financial incentives	European Green Deal (EC, n.d.a)
Circular Economy Action Plan	CEAP aims to foster a circular economy in the EU by promoting sustainable production, enhancing product longevity, and reducing waste, particularly for plastics, through the use of recycled materials.	Stimulating instrument	It sets binding targets for plastic recycling, encourages the use of secondary raw materials, and improves the market for recycled plastics by creating standards for quality and safety.	EU	Current	Strategic framework and regulatory directives	EU Circular Economy Action Plan (EC, n.d.b)
Single-Use Plastics Directive (SUPD)	The main goal of this directive is to reduce the amount of plastic waste in the environment, especially in marine area. It contains several measures around single-use plastics to reach the goal, including EU-wide bans, consumption reduction, labelling and further requirements. Putting tax on plastic is part of this directive.	Barrier and stimulating instrument	The SUPD bans certain single-use plastic products, which creates challenges for industries reliant on these items. At the same time, it encourages innovation in sustainable alternatives, thus streamlines the circular economy and	EU	Planned in 2019. Came into force in 2021.	Regulation	EU Single-Use Plastics Directive (SUPD) (EC, n.d.c)

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

			generate new opportunities for greener business.				
European Bioeconomy Strategy	A step forward towards ensuring the fossil resources are replaced by sustainable natural alternatives. The stability of regulatory framework and research to accelerate the growth of bioeconomy account for the focus.	Stimulating instrument	Support the acceleration of the circular bioeconomy in the areas of policy, finance and awareness.	EU	First strategy in 2012. Updated in 2018. Council conclusion in 2019. Progress report updates since 2022.	Regulation	European Bioeconomy Strategy (EC, n.d.d)
Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)	PPWR covers all packaging and packaging waste on the EU market, including all materials and packaging in commercial, household, industrial and other sectors. Building on former regulation the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWD), the PPWR focuses to reduce the quantities of packaging and waste generated while lowering the use of primary raw materials, which aligns national measures further. Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) is one of the policy tool of PPWR.	Barrier and stimulating instrument	The PPWR prevents and reduces packaging waste, whilst increases the use of sustainable materials on plastics.	EU	Current	Regulation	EU Packaging Waste (EC, n.d.e)
<i>Verpackungsgesetz</i> (German Packaging Act)	<i>VerpackG</i> is the German's implementation of EU level regulations combining European Green Deal and EU's PPWR, which regulates the market of packaging, disposal and recycling of packaging waste. The law promotes eco-friendly packaging design and increases recycling targets.	Barrier and stimulating instrument	<i>VerpackG</i> monitors and evaluates the value chain of packaging, which encourages further affected stakeholders to seek sustainable alternatives and reduce the use of non-renewable-based materials, supporting Germany's	Germany	Current	Regulation	<i>Verpackungsgesetz</i> (Bundesministerium der Justiz, 2023)

			transition to a circular economy.				
Bulgarian Waste Management Act (WMA)	The Waste Management Act in Bulgaria is a regulation tailored to improve waste management practices and align with EU environmental standards. It focuses on reducing waste generation, promoting recycle and reuse and ensuring proper disposal of waste.	Barrier and stimulating instrument	Waste Management Act imposes stricter waste management requirements and costs on businesses, which encourages innovation in recycling, waste reduction and sustainable practices, fostering a circular economy and aligning with EU environmental goals.	Bulgaria	Old and current	Regulation	Waste Management Act (Bulgaria) (Ministry of Environment and Water, 2012)
<i>Wet milieubeheer</i> (Environmental Management Act)	The Netherlands' <i>Wet milieubeheer</i> is a comprehensive framework for environmental regulation. It integrates various environmental laws to manage pollution, waste, energy use and sustainability. Aligning with EU environmental standards, the act emphasises permits, enforcements and compliance for businesses.	Barrier and stimulating instrument	While the <i>Wet milieubeheer</i> imposes strict regulations and compliance costs on businesses, the act also drives innovation in sustainability, clean technologies and circular economy practices.	The Netherlands	Current	Regulation	Overheid.nl Wettenbank: Wet milieubeheer (Dutch Government, 2025)
REACH	A regulation of the EU, aimed to improve the protection of human health and the environment from the possibility of chemical risks, whilst enhancing the competitiveness of the EU chemical industries. REACH applies to manufacturers, importers, distributors and downstream users.	Stimulating and barrier instrument	The regulation stimulates chemical industries to create products that amount safe/harmless chemical content.	EU	Old and current	Regulation	EU REACH Regulation (n.d.f)

6.2.4 Analysis of indicators of the PLA case study

In T3.2, a consistency check was conducted to identify the indicators in the Bioeconomy Monitoring and Assessment framework deemed relevant in light of PLA. Subsequently, a selection of indicators was found to be highly relevant. This initial analysis took place on the basis of a literature review and stakeholder engagement. In the present section, the results from this preliminary analysis will be deepened.

In this section, the results from this preliminary analysis were taken as a starting point and further elaborated on. Each identified indicator will be used to assess the performance of the PLA value chain compared with conventional fossil-based plastic production. To that end, a literature review was conducted using search engines such as *Science Direct* and *Google Scholar*, complemented by industry reports and policy documents. In the case that no information or data could be found to support the analysis of the indicator, this was reported as a research gap.

6.2.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators

Table 39 provides an overview of 27 environmental and circular indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. In this analysis, 7 indicators have been removed because of limited data specifically impacting PLA.

The environmental/circularity performance of PLA presents both opportunities and challenges. In comparison to fossil-based plastics, the bioplastics sector requires land to produce feedstock. Thereby it creates a growing assumption concerning land use competition with food source and biodiversity impact. European Bioplastics (2023) reassures this concern by reporting that less than 0.02% of global land use is allocated to bioplastics production. Despite this, another major uncertainty in sustainable natural resource management objectives is the feedstock processing. Due to the variety of production processes among enterprises, it was not possible to fully determine the relationship between PLA production and sustainable resourcing. However, sustainability reports suggest that industries are striving for lower-emission production and greater circularity (PLA Solutions ESG Reports 2023, 2024; CARBIOS Sustainability Report 2023, 2024; Stellantis CSR Report 2023, 2024). Sources of electricity exerts a powerful effect on carbon emission along the PLA value chain (P. T. Benavides *et al.*, 2020). Henceforth, to further reduce emissions of PLA or bioplastics production, an optimised feedstock yield system and renewable energy generation must be prioritised.

In this investigation, several EoL-related indicators have limited access. The primary restrictions come from the waste generation and management indicator. PLA is biobased and biodegradable, which means that PLA is made from biomass and only able to degrade with the help of bacteria or living organisms. The current standardisation of biodegradability is heavily based on controlled laboratory experiments. However, in real-life, biodegradability of bioplastics is affected by natural conditions of the waste treatment plant (Folino *et al.*, 2023). This indicates a lacking harmonisation between research and real-world scenarios of biodegradability assessment, which correlates with the concerns raised by stakeholders during consultation.

Table 39. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the PLA case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Land use change (LUC)	Agricultural land converted to energy (or biobased product) crop	Growing assumptions on land-use for biobased plastics have been denied by recent study. European Bioplastics reported that only about 0.021% of global agricultural area was used for biobased product purposes and this number is estimated to reach 0.027% by 2028 (European Bioplastics & nova-Institute, 2023).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Land use change (LUC)	Forest converted to cropland	Due to its rising demand, biomass production for bioplastics requires land-use expansion. The immediate effects lead to a decrease in forestland by up to 0.2% mainly in bioplastic producing regions (Escobar <i>et al.</i> , 2018).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Amount of water used in the value-chain	The biobased economy puts extra pressure on water demand. Projections estimate that water demand will increase at least 20% by 2050 (Green European Foundation, 2012)	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Water consumption (use) (m ³ /product unit processed)	Water consumption is strongly depended on the feedstock type. Based on a study from One Earth, by alternating corn feedstock, it is estimated that about 45 billion m ³ water would be required to fulfil European bioplastics production (One Earth, 2020).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Amount of organic or mineral fertilisers and pesticides used (kg)	The increasing number of land-use for bioplastics production could affect the use of mineral fertilisers and pesticides.	Yes. Although bioplastics can be used as fertiliser by the end of its life, its feedstock production requires fertiliser. In this matter there is no concrete data available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Intensity of fossil fuel use (m ³ /ton of product)	A study has shown that PLA involves less fossil fuel during its life cycle compared to petrol-based plastics (about 46 MJ/kg PLA). The PLA conversion process takes up to 50% of the fossil fuel consumption (P. T. Benavides <i>et al.</i> , 2020).	Yes. Depending on the methods of production processes, the intensity of fossil fuel use could vary.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of carbon content derived from renewable raw materials	Biobased plastics derived from renewable raw materials offer more CO ₂ absorption during the production process. However, they are still dependent on fossil fuel as energy source in the fabrication process (E. R. Ghomi <i>et al.</i> , 2021).	No.

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Renewable energies (RES) share in final energy consumption / product unit	Electricity is one of the major contributions to the GHG emissions in PLA production. It is expected that by increasing the RES in the energy share in production will decrease GHG percentage (P. T. Benavides <i>et al</i> , 2020).	Yes.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Water quality	Ecotoxicity for aquatic fresh water (Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems)	PLA is reported to generate higher rate of microscopic particles compared to other bioplastics (S. Lambert & M. Wagner, 2016).	Yes. Most studies found do not mimic the actual environmental condition.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Water quality	Acidification (mol H ⁺ eq. from NO _x , SO _x , NH ₃)	Lactic acid and feedstock production process hold the largest impact on acidification. Mainly from the use of chemicals in the process, which difficult to measure (A. Morão & F. de Bie, 2019).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Water quality	Eutrophication (gr eq. PO ₄)	Feedstock production accounts the most impact on marine eutrophication, shaped by the application of fertilisers and manure (A. Morão & F. de Bie, 2019).	Yes. Depending on its feedstock and production methods, EP can vary. Further research needed.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	% of deforestation or afforestation / product unit	Expanding agricultural land to meet the demand for bioplastics can lead to deforestation. Concerns over this matter is understandable, however data suggests today's bioplastic production accounts for approximately 0.021% and is estimated to grow to 0.073% by 2028 (European Bioplastics).	Yes. Limited relevant reports available.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Hazardous substances management	% of hazardous (carcinogenic, mutagenic, reprotoxic) substances	The application of PLA per se is not harmless. However, at its end of life, where it meets other substances, it can present additional challenges. Owing to the variety of % of hazardous substances produced from the industry based on their corporate social responsibility reports, it is not possible to draw a conclusion. E.g., Stellantis produced 17% of hazardous waste in manufacturing in 2023, whereas PLA Solutions accounted for 0% (Stellantis CSR Report 2023, 2024; PLA Solutions ESG Report 2023, 2024)	Yes and no. Further studies specifically on hazardous substances produced along PLA value chain are needed.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Waste generated	Waste generated from PLA and bioplastics production varies among companies. For instance, in 2023 ca. 64 t of solid waste produced by an US-based company PLA Solutions, while a French enterprise CARBIOS produced 2,505 t of non-hazardous waste from their production (PLA Solutions ESG Report 2023, 2024 and CARBIOS Sustainability Report 2023, 2024).	Yes and no. While companies disclose their waste generation, it is not enough to draw a conclusion. A more detailed study on waste generation from

					different types of bioplastics is needed to avoid biases.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Declaration of end-of-life disposal (in the CSR report) (yes/no)	Yes. Several PLA and bioplastics companies include their EoL processes in the CSR report, aligning with circular economy strategy.	
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of biodegradability	A few studies have shown, depending on the environment condition and its production, PLA's biodegradability varies from 29% to 90%. In comparison to other bioplastics, PLA microplastics are resistant to degrade (S. K. Awasthi <i>et al</i> , 2022).	No. However, further research on biodegradation of bioplastics in boarder condition is necessary.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle GHG emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	PLA conversion releases the most kg of CO ₂ per kg of PLA (E. R. Ghomi <i>et al.</i> , 2021).	No. However, the technology around PLA production, especially its conversion,
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP100; gr eq. CO ₂)	The largest contributor to the GWP of PLA is the feedstock yield and production process. GWP values for PLA vary with the scopes considered. For instance, for the cradle-to-gate: resin, the median GWP value for PLA was 1.63 kg CO ₂ eq./kg. Whereas from cradle-to-grave was 3.91 kg CO ₂ eq./kg (B. Pinlova <i>et al.</i> , 2024).	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Air quality	Amount of volatile organic compounds (VOC) emitted (parts per billion (ppb), parts per million (ppm), or as micrograms per cubic meter (µg/m ³))	PLA processing plays a big role on VOCs formation. According to M. Jang <i>et al.</i> (2022), PLA and PHA emit less VOCs compared to PVC and PET.	No.

6.2.4.2 Economic indicators

Table 40 provides an overview of 3 economic indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2.

Table 40. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the PLA case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Strategy for creating infrastructure and systems necessary for recovering and recycling materials (yes/no)	Yes. The EU's strategies include the Waste Framework Directive (EC, n.d.g), BBCP policy framework (EC, n.d.h) and The Alliance to End Plastic Waste.	Yes. The question of creating an efficient EoL of bioplastics remains. Not only does the diversity of plastic materials hinder the recycling process, the alternatives to mechanical recycling at scale is required.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Value Added of the bioeconomy sectors	Contribution of the product/service/organisation to economic progress (revenue, gain, paid wages, R&D costs in relation to revenue, etc.)	There is a noticeable impact from the bioplastics sector to the bioeconomy growth. According to European Bioplastics, the market has shown a significant increase. However, the concrete number of costs related to economic progress of bioplastics is not yet provided as data.	Yes.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Full time equivalent jobs along the full value chain of a product	In regard to falling oil demand, the bioplastics sector opens new opportunities in every bioplastic value chain.	Yes.

The global bioplastics production has been constantly rising parallel to the increasing demand, and is expected to reach approximately 5.73 Mt of production capacity in 2029 (European Bioplastics and nova-Institute, 2024). This can be attributed to growing employment opportunities along the value chain and contributions to economic progress in bioeconomy. Granting all these, the challenging certification process and high initial cost significantly disadvantage small and medium-sized businesses to enter the market. A reasonable approach to tackle this issue could be to support SMEs during the initial phase in order to ignite a diversification in innovation and grow market competition within the bioplastics sector.

Building on previous environmental/circular indicators, another major uncertainty is the lack of information availability regarding infrastructure that facilitates the recycling of bioplastics. The European Commission has introduced strategies to help the Member States establish a suitable infrastructure for recovering and recycling materials within the bioplastics sector. Owing to the wide range application of PLA, a more widespread disposal system is expected for each Member States to enable a more efficient EoL processing and attract long-term investment.

6.2.4.3 Social indicators

Table 41 provides an overview of 5 social indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. In this analysis, 1 indicator has been removed because of limited data specifically impacting PLA.

Table 41. *Highly relevant social indicators identified for the PLA case study*

S O	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Presence of a formal policy in place concerning health and safety of all workers, including contractors (yes/no)	Yes. The Green Jobs Initiative, the employment package by the EU Commission, the REACH regulation, etc.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness		Presence of a law or norm regarding transparency (yes/no)	Yes. Regulating types of policies such as PPWR and Waste Shipments Regulation provides assurance in transparency.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Full time equivalent jobs along the full value chain of a product	Yes. Because of its exceeding growth, the bioplastics sector opens up employment opportunities in every field along the value chain.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Risk of forced labour used for production of commodity (yes/no)	Yes and no. When it comes to forced labour, it is hard to truly define “forced”. Although, bioplastics sector is highly regulated, and therefore, compared to fossil-based plastics, the bioplastics sector has a lower risk of forced labour. Nevertheless, comprehensive data is needed to prove this topic.	Yes.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Presence of working children under legal age (yes/no)	Yes and no. Although the bioplastics sector is highly regulated and monitored, this exact objective still lacks transparency and not enough to draw a conclusion.	Yes.

The developing bioplastics sector creates job opportunities and increases social awareness in the circular economy. As the demand of bioplastics rises, new employment opportunities emerge along the value chain, from research and production to waste management and recycling. Moreover, the bioplastics sector plays a role in shaping consumer awareness about sustainability to make a better decision supporting bioeconomy. This can be briefly illustrated by one of SUPD rules that set a minimum biomaterial content.

The European Commission enforces strict regulations such as PPWR and REACH Regulation to ensure safer working conditions and material handling. However, the transition toward bioeconomy introduces new challenges. Upskilling workers and preparing the next generation of workers for evolving technologies in bioplastics production and recycling cannot be ruled out to maintain growth and stability of the bioplastics sector.

6.2.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Policy dimension

Challenges

- The stakeholders address the insufficient support from the government for the use of compostable plastics for food and soil applications, which further affect the market and sustainability aspects of PLA.

Recommendations and examples of good practice

- Recommendation from the stakeholders includes more support for the use of compostable plastics for food and soil applications, specifically in updating current legislation of fertilisers and microplastics.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- Stakeholders refer to the current biodegradability certifications, which heavily focus on full degradation of CO₂ formed. In reality, not all incomplete degradation is harmful for the environment.
- The inadequacy of certifications for “readily biodegradable” plastics poses another challenge. Therefore, a wider spectrum of the biodegradability definition is needed.

Market dimension

Challenges

- Stakeholders emphasise on the difficulty in upscaling the production capacity due to the challenging bureaucracy and inadequate land for production sites.
- In addition, the high initial cost, followed by a lengthy process to reach the market hinder the growth of the PLA market.

Recommendations and examples of good practice

- To improve the current market dimension, the stakeholders recommend an aid from the government to increase production capacity by easing the current bureaucracy.
- Additionally, a clearer definition of chemical and physical characteristics of PLA must be addressed, to bring focus research on feasible applications (e. g., PLA is not suitable for the textile sector).

6.2.6 Key learnings of PLA case study

The PLA case study highlights several key takeaways:

- Policymakers emerge as crucial stakeholders for driving the transition towards a sustainable PLA value chain. Their actions and decisions significantly influence the development and adoption of this biobased material.
- A major hurdle is the lack of clear and consistent definitions for bioplastics and polymers. This ambiguity leads to confusion regarding certifications and recycling regulations, hindering the development of a robust and reliable market for PLA products. Furthermore, the availability of consistent and reliable raw materials, suitable production sites, and efficient end-of-life management facilities pose significant challenges to the successful implementation of PLA.
- Customer confusion surrounding general labelling further complicates the market. Consumers often lack clear and accessible information about the environmental impact and end-of-life options for different plastic products, including PLA. This lack of transparency hinders informed consumer choices and can discourage the adoption of more sustainable alternatives.
- While research and data on PLA is quite advanced compared to the other bioplastics, addressing remaining research and data gaps is crucial. Further research is needed to understand the full scope of the environmental and social impacts of PLA throughout its entire lifecycle. This will require the collection and analysis of robust and reliable data on various aspects of the PLA value chain.

6.3 Plastics - Polypropylene from used cooking oil

6.3.1 Introduction to PP from UCO case study

6.3.1.1 General description

Polypropylene (PP) represents one of the most widely used plastics in Europe thanks to its versatility. Motivated by the growing demand for plastics and related concerns about their climate impact, biobased plastics have attracted attention as alternatives for petrochemical plastics. In this sense, biobased PP could be a significant alternative to petrochemical PP. This biopolymer can be synthesised through three routes. Specifically, this case study focuses on the hydrotreatment of used cooking oil (UCO) and the environmental impacts of biobased PP obtained through this route.

Biobased PP is a polymer compound derived from plants and has balanced properties as does standard PP. This polymer is manufactured from materials such as corn, vegetable oils, and sugarcane.

UCO can serve as a feedstock for the production of various kinds of biobased products and has the advantage of being low-budget and renewable at the same time. UCO originates from edible oils derived from vegetable or animal sources, making it initially suitable for human consumption. However, after undergoing frying processes to the extent that it can no longer be safely reused in food preparation, it is classified as UCO.

The present case study takes as an example a joint project from Neste and LyondellBasell to produce biobased PP (and biobased low-density polyethylene) using Neste’s renewable hydrocarbons derived from sustainable biobased raw materials (e.g., waste and residue oils). The project achieved to produce several thousand tonnes of biobased plastics for the production of food packaging, marketed as LyondellBasell circular economy products.

Within the above mentioned project, UCO is converted into high value hydrotreated vegetable oil (HVO). Together with the HVO renewable diesel grade product, a renewable HVO naphtha grade product is obtained from the hydrotreatment process. This study focuses on the cracking of this “bio-naphtha” to obtain propylene via a process equivalent to petrochemical steam cracking.

6.3.1.2 Value chain and the process

The production of UCO-based PP (see Figure 47) starts from the collection of UCO. Then, the oil is pre-treated and deoxygenated under high pressure to transport fuel quality using hydrogen. The triglycerides of UCO are converted to saturated straight and branched-chain hydrocarbons and oxygen. After hydrotreatment, biobased naphtha is transported by train to the steam cracking unit. During steam cracking, biobased naphtha is diluted with steam and cracked into smaller hydrocarbons such as propylene and ethylene. The last process is polymerisation of the propylene to obtain PP. The polymerisation of biobased propylene is identical to that of petrochemical propylene.

Figure 47. Value chain of PP from UCO

6.3.1.3 Value chain and the process

The European Waste Catalogue (EWC) classifies them as Municipal Wastes (household waste and similar commercial, industrial, and institutional wastes) including separately collected fractions, under the code 20 01 25 (edible oils and fats). UCO obtained from wastewater treatment plants

is also considered non-hazardous materials with a different code: 19 08 09 (grease and oil mixture from oil/water separation containing edible oil and fats) (European Biomass Industry Association, n.d.).

It is estimated that currently around 90% of cooking oils and fat used in the EU are produced from vegetable oils. According to EU estimations, the potential UCO to be collected is around 8 L UCO/capita/year. In the EU-28, the total potential UCO available from the gastronomy sector, food processors and households is estimated at around 4 Mt per year. Moreover, China supplies more than a third (34%) of Europe’s UCO imports, while almost a fifth (19%) comes from the major palm oil producers Malaysia and Indonesia combined (Transport & Environment, n.d.; 2020).

Nevertheless, it should be noted that UCO is a very limited feedstock. The European Commission already promotes its use of renewable diesel as a second-generation biofuel. UCO-based PP is developed from biobased naphtha, which is a by-product of this renewable diesel. Within a decade, the volume needed in Europe could double to 6 Mt as EU countries strive to meet renewable transport fuels targets.

According to European Bioplastics, commercialisation of biobased PP started in 2019. Therefore, the market is still at its nascent stage, and it is expected to quadruple by 2025. On the basis of application, the market is segmented into building & construction, automotive, consumer goods, packaging and others (see Figure 48).

Figure 48. Global biobased PP market (Source: Wang et al., 2023)

6.3.2 Stakeholders in the PP from UCO value chain

6.3.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

To begin with, the stakeholders relevant to the PP from UCO value chain were determined by means of an exploratory desk research (e.g., on websites of governmental organisations, PP companies and users of cooking oil). Figure 49 provides a schematic representation of the identified stakeholders, both in the Bioeconomy supply chain (i.e., the light green section) and its Enabling environment (i.e., the light grey section).

Figure 49. Identified stakeholders in PP from UCO value chain

Overview of key stakeholders in the present case study:

Households and restaurants are key stakeholders in the value chain, as they generate UCO, the primary feedstock for the production of PP. Their waste collection practices significantly impact the efficiency and sustainability of the recycling process. Proper **waste management policies** implemented by governments at various levels - national, regional, and local - are essential to ensuring the effective collection and processing of UCO.

A well-structured regulatory framework can facilitate the establishment of collection systems that encourage responsible disposal practices, prevent illegal dumping, and optimise the recycling potential of UCO. However, for these policies to be successful, collaboration between governmental entities and private stakeholders is crucial. Local governments, in particular, play a pivotal role in enforcing collection programs, raising public awareness, and engaging businesses and households in sustainable waste management. Effective coordination among all levels of government will enhance the overall efficiency of UCO collection and contribute to the circular economy by transforming waste into valuable resources.

Entities involved in processing UCO into a usable form for PP plastic are key stakeholders in the value chain. These actors include oil processing facilities and **manufacturers** specialising in the production of biobased plastics. Their role is crucial in converting waste oil into high-value materials, contributing to the development of sustainable alternatives to traditional petroleum-based plastics.

One of the first steps in this transformation process is the efficient collection and refining of UCO, ensuring it meets quality standards for further processing. To achieve this, it is essential to establish well-structured waste management systems that support the seamless transition from waste oil to raw material for bioplastics. A robust **regulatory framework** at the national, regional, and local levels is necessary to facilitate this process. Governments must implement policies that encourage innovation in oil processing technologies, provide incentives for industries to invest in sustainable materials, and establish clear guidelines for waste-to-resource conversion.

Several leading companies are driving innovation in the bioplastics sector. According to Emergen Research (2023), major players like NatureWorks, Novamont, and Biome Bioplastics are at the forefront of producing environmentally-friendly bioplastics. These companies are developing cutting-edge solutions that enhance the biodegradability and performance of sustainable plastics.

Borealis and Neste are actively collaborating to develop sustainable solutions for renewable plastic production. Through this partnership, they have successfully produced renewable polypropylene from used cooking oil (UCO) waste, promoting a circular economy approach in the plastics industry. Neste, a leader in renewable and circular solutions, provides biobased feedstock derived from waste oils and fats, including UCO. Borealis then processes this feedstock into high-quality renewable polypropylene, maintaining the performance and properties of conventional plastic while significantly reducing its carbon footprint.

This collaboration showcases the potential of waste valorisation as an alternative to fossil-based plastics and highlights the importance of innovation and strategic partnerships in driving a more sustainable industry.

Plastic manufacturing companies are key stakeholders in the bioeconomy value chain. They are responsible for producing goods that incorporate sustainable materials, ensuring that biobased plastics meet performance and regulatory standards. These companies collaborate with plastic suppliers, designers, and manufacturers to maintain product quality while committing to more sustainable practices.

To successfully integrate biobased plastics into their production processes, these companies must be willing to purchase and utilise such materials, ensuring they comply with industry standards and legal regulations. Companies like Grupo Mathiesen (n.d.) and Plásticos Reig are examples of plastic manufacturers engaged in producing high-quality plastic products, aligning with sustainability principles.

Companies which use plastic packaging or materials (packaging industry, construction, automotive). Their role is crucial in driving the transition toward sustainable plastic alternatives. They must be willing to use biobased plastics for packaging their products or as vehicle parts, and to do so they must be sure that they meet the same quality standards required of them for fossil fuel products (e.g., vehicles manufacturers, supermarkets)

Finally, **users or consumers** of products made from biobased plastic are integral stakeholders in the value chain. Their purchasing decisions drive demand for sustainable products, influencing the actions of other stakeholders in the supply chain.

For biopolypropylene products to contribute to a sustainable economy, they must be designed to be recyclable. This requires alignment with existing plastic recycling systems, ensuring that the material can be efficiently sorted, processed, and reused. Collaboration between plastic manufacturers, recycling companies, and policymakers is key to establishing clear guidelines and infrastructure that support the effective recycling of biopolypropylene. **Plastic recycling industries** play a crucial role in closing the loop within the biobased plastic value chain. These actors, including recycling facilities and manufacturers specialising in processing and reusing biobased plastics, ensure that materials like biopolypropylene can be efficiently reintegrated into production cycles. Their capacity to handle and process biopolypropylene is essential for achieving true circularity and minimising environmental impact.

6.3.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

Afterwards, the stakeholders identified as relevant were mapped in a power-interest matrix, based on a desk research. The result can be found in Figure 50.

Figure 50. Stakeholders of the PP from UCO value chain mapped in a power-interest matrix

There is significant interest from research centres and universities in transforming UCO into other valuable materials. However, this process requires external funding to advance. Additionally, the plastics industry must be technologically equipped to convert used oil into bioplastics. These bioplastics need to exhibit properties equivalent to or closely resembling those of fossil-based plastics while meeting quality standards appropriate for their life cycle and applications.

European, national, and local policies increasingly emphasise the circular economy and promote the use of waste as a raw material. Policymakers, through targeted policy instruments, have the power to either drive or hinder the implementation of bioplastics derived from used cooking oil. Furthermore, plastics manufacturing industries still rely heavily on fossil fuels for production. Nevertheless, growing pressures for sustainable production are likely to invent greater exploitation of fossil free alternatives, including bioplastics.

6.3.3 Policies of relevance to PP from UCO value chain

In this section, policies were identified that could either propel or impede the implementation of the PP from UCO value chain. There are a range of applicable policy frameworks. Depending on the final use, different types of legislation should be considered (see Table 42).

At European level, the **Circular economy action plan (CEAP)** (EC, 2020) is essential for the biopropylene case study since it pushes industry to adopt more sustainable, closed-loop systems in place of conventional linear production methods (take-make-dispose). Through the promotion of resource efficiency and renewable materials, the CEAP encourages the development and use of bioplastics, such as biopropylene. Because it is biobased and recyclable, biopropylene is a perfect fit for the objectives of lowering carbon emissions, decreasing waste, and reducing reliance on fossil fuels. In line with larger EU sustainability goals and legislative frameworks intended to combat climate change and resource depletion, this strategy is essential to accelerating the industrial adoption of biopropylene. Additionally, it opens doors for companies who adopt circularity, establishing biopropylene as a competitive and ecologically friendly material in a market that is becoming more and more environmentally conscious.

Another relevant initiative is the **EU Waste Framework Directive** (EC, 2008), a comprehensive regulation designed to encourage recycling and lessen waste production in the EU. It requires improved waste management techniques in all member states, raises recycling rates, and establishes legally binding waste reduction targets. In keeping with the tenets of a circular economy, the directive also highlights the necessity of more effective resource usage. The use of sustainable materials, such as biopropylene made from used oil, is encouraged for your case study. It also helps enterprises meet EU waste reduction targets, lessens their impact on the environment, and encourages the circular use of resources.

Moreover, several relevant EU initiatives linked to plastics were identified:

- The **EU Plastic strategy** (EC, 2018) aims to transform the way plastic products are designed, produced, used and recycled in the EU. The plastics strategy is a key element of Europe's transition towards a carbon neutral and circular economy. It will contribute to reaching the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals, the Paris Climate Agreement objectives and the EU's industrial policy objectives. It is part of the EU's circular economy action plan. One key is to include measures on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics.
- The **EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics** (EC, 2022) promotes the switch from fossil fuels to sustainable plastic substitutes made from renewable resources like plant-based materials. With an emphasis on decreasing plastic waste and improving the recyclability and biodegradability of plastic products, this policy aims to solve the environmental issues raised by conventional plastics. It promotes environmentally friendly solutions that decompose organically, lowering pollutants over time.

This policy fits in well with the idea of using used oil to produce biopolymers in this case study. Reducing plastic waste and fostering a circular economy are two benefits of turning waste oil into biodegradable and biobased bioplastics. The policy fosters creativity in the

creation of novel materials that satisfy sustainability standards, which makes the market conditions for this biopolymer project perfect. The use of safe biodegradable plastics is also encouraged, which increases the environmental attractiveness of biopolymers derived from recycled waste, such as spent oil.

It is advantageous because it expands the market for bioplastics, encourages technological development in the industry, and satisfies consumer and regulatory demands for more sustainable, greener materials. It puts your project in a position to take advantage of incentives, comply with environmental laws, and attract businesses and consumers looking for environmentally responsible substitutes for traditional plastics.

At a national level, **Circular España 2030** (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, 2020) seeks to disentangle economic growth from resource use and environmental deterioration as part of Spain's national policy for promoting the shift to a circular economy. Promoting eco-design, expanding recycling infrastructure, enhancing waste management systems, and expanding the use of recycled and renewable materials in industry are some of the main initiatives that this strategy focuses on. The creation of laws and financial incentives to persuade companies to embrace circular practices, which include the usage of sustainable materials like bioplastics, are examples of specific projects. According to your case study, this framework encourages the manufacturing of biopolymers from spent oil and offers chances for funding and cooperation with businesses who want to lower waste and carbon emissions while fostering innovation in bioplastics.

Table 42. Information regarding the policy instrument to the PP from UCO value chain

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/planned/proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
Circular Economy Action Plan	CEAP aims to foster a circular economy in the EU by promoting sustainable production, enhancing product longevity, and reducing waste, particularly for plastics, through the use of recycled materials.	Stimulating instrument	It sets binding targets for plastic recycling, encourages the use of secondary raw materials, and improves the market for recycled plastics by creating standards for quality and safety.	European Union	Current	Strategic framework and regulatory directives	Circular Economy Action Plan
Plastic strategy	The strategy aims to transform the design, production, use, and recycling of plastics to reduce environmental impacts, support sustainable development, and increase the circularity of plastic materials within the EU.	Stimulating instrument	It stimulates the adoption of recycled plastics (e.g., PP) by setting targets for recyclable packaging by 2030, mandating increased use of recycled materials, and reducing single-use plastics.	European Union	Current	Strategic framework and regulatory policy	Plastic strategy
European Green Deal	The European Green Deal aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 through a broad framework of policies, including emission reduction, resource efficiency, and circular economy initiatives.	Stimulating instrument	It provides funding and regulatory support for circular economy initiatives, including promoting recycled materials like recycled PP (rPP), while discouraging the use of virgin plastics through carbon taxation and environmental regulations.	European Union	Current	Policy framework and financial incentives	European Green Deal
EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics	This framework promotes the sustainable production and use of biobased, biodegradable, and compostable plastics while ensuring their compatibility	Stimulating instrument	It encourages the market uptake of alternative plastics while setting guidelines to avoid unintended environmental impacts.	European Union	Current	Policy guidance and standardisation framework	Biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics

SUSTRACK: D3.3 Case study assessment results

	with circular economy principles						
Plan Estatal Marco de Gestión de Residuos (PEMAR) 2016-2022	The plan establishes Spain's national waste management strategies, aiming to reduce waste generation, improve recycling rates, and encourage the recovery of materials.	Stimulating instrument	It sets targets for plastic recycling and waste reduction, promotes the use of recycled materials, and provides funding for waste management technologies.	National, Spain	Old	National waste management framework	PEMAR
Plastics. Recycled polypropylene (PP). Characteristics and typology” UNE 53972:2020	This standard provides guidelines on the characteristics and typologies of rPP, ensuring quality and safety for its use in industrial and commercial applications	Stimulating instrument	It facilitates market adoption of recycling PP by standardising its properties, thus increasing trust and consistency in its application.	National, Spain	Current	Standardisation document	UNE 53972:2020
Circular economy Strategy - España Circular 2030	This strategy aims to transition Spain to a circular economy by reducing waste generation by 15%, increasing material reuse, and promoting recycled materials.	Stimulating instrument	It encourages investment in circular economy initiatives, including better recycling infrastructure, and promotes the use of recycled plastics in products.	National, Spain	Current	Strategic framework	España Circular 2030
EU Directive on Waste Framework	This directive considers the waste hierarchy. Requires that waste should be managed without environmental impact.	Both	It explains when waste ceases to be waste and becomes a secondary raw material, and how to distinguish between waste and by-products. The Directive also introduces the "polluter pays principle" and the "extended producer responsibility".	European Union	Current	Strategic framework and regulatory policy	EU Directive on Waste Framework

6.3.4 Analysis of indicators of the PP from UCO value chain

In T2.3, a preliminary monitoring and assessment framework was developed, containing a list of indicators structured under Bioeconomy Strategy societal objectives (SOs). This section includes indicators which were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (consistency check) in light of the PP from UCO value chain. Subsequently, a selection of indicators was labelled as highly relevant. In the event that no information or data could be found to support the analysis of the indicator, this was reported as a research gap.

6.3.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators

22 indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (see Table 43).

Table 43. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the PP from UCO value chain

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Abiotic depletion (kg SB eq.)	impact of mineral and fossil fuel extraction, taking into account their availability and associated environmental impact.	Yes.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Resource depletion (mineral, fossil)/ product unit (mJ)	The amount of energy measured in mJ used or produced from a resource.	Yes.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	Change in consumption level of fossil fuel resources/ product unit	Raw material decreases fossil fuel input and aligns with EU directives on sustainable resource use (ABC, 2025).	No, information can be obtained at a general level. Use of bioplastics or estimations.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Waste generated	The transformation of UCO into PP minimises waste generation by valorising what is otherwise considered waste.	No, countries usually have information on the waste they generate and collect.

2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Procedures for separating and using recyclable materials from the waste stream (yes/no)	Policies at both the EU and national levels, such as the CEAP, encourage the collection and processing of waste oils for reuse in industrial applications. This framework provides a supportive context for scaling up PP production from UCO.	No, countries have standards or procedures to ensure proper waste separation.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Procedures for recovering materials for other uses, such as incineration for raising process steam or heating, or agricultural use (yes/no)	Techniques and methods used to reuse materials that would otherwise be considered as waste.	Yes.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of product is actively being recovered and recycled	The product (UCO) is being used in industry to generate biofuels, but there is little information on the transformation of used oil into plastic.	Yes.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of by-products or wastes reused by the processing/production facility or transferred to other sectors	Proportion of by-products or waste generated during production are reused instead of being discarded.	Yes.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of biodegradability	Proportion of a material that can decompose naturally.	Yes, there are not enough studies showing the biodegradability of used oil-based biopolypropylene.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Procedures for handling, collecting, separating and disposal of hazardous waste as defined by the	There are different policies and strategies available at national and EU level that consider plant oil collecting.	No.

			relevant local and national regulatory authorities (yes/no)		
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Bioenergy replacing non-renewable energy	% of biofuels produced with co-products, residues and waste	Proportion of biofuels that are made using materials other than crops exclusively dedicated to biofuel production.	Yes.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Bioenergy replacing non-renewable energy	Biofuels	Biofuels produced through oil.	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Bioenergy replacing non-renewable energy	Municipal waste	Waste generated in urban and rural areas.	No, countries usually have information on the waste they generate and collect.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Biomaterial replacing non-renewable resources	Biobased plastics	It is aligned with sustainable production and use of biobased, biodegradable, and compostable plastics.	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Material and (municipal) waste recycling and recovery rates	Aligning municipal waste management systems with biobased production processes is key to maximising efficiency.	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle GHG emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	Reduce emissions compared with the conventional PP.	No, life cycle analysis comparing PP production processes from fossil fuels and renewable products.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Rate of GHG emissions reduction or savings		

4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP100; gr eq. CO ₂)		
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Air quality	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	Measure used to assess the relative impact of various chemicals on ozone depletion.	Yes.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Climate footprint	Climate footprint	Low climate footprint compared with the conventional PP.	No, life cycle analysis comparing PP production processes from fossil fuels and renewable products.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Greenhouse gas emissions		
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Presence of environmentally/friendly technologies (yes/no)	Research and innovation in the use of bio-PP is an example of an innovative environmentally friendly technology.	No.

This table shows that, concerning environmental indicators, four areas are predominantly relevant: sustainable natural resource management, dependence on non-renewable resources, mitigating and adapting to climate change and employment and economic competitiveness. Due to PP's dependence on fossil fuels, its production from waste materials like UCO represents a promising opportunity to reduce fossil consumption and, consequently, lower GHG emissions.

The transformation of UCO into bioplastics is an emerging area of research aimed at providing sustainable solutions to the issues of plastic waste and environmental pollution. Although still a developing field, significant studies have been conducted in this area.

A team of researchers from the University of Chile, led by Dr. Francisca Werlinger, has developed methods to convert discarded cooking oil into biopolyurethane and biopolyester, types of bioplastics with potential applications in various industries (Universidad de Chile, 2023). The process involves the epoxidation of used oil followed by its reaction with CO₂ to generate cyclic carbonates, which serve as precursors in the synthesis of these bioplastics. This approach not only repurposes common household waste but also contributes to CO₂ capture, addressing two environmental issues simultaneously. Its study emphasises that the proper treatment of UCO could significantly reduce ocean pollution and mitigate the associated environmental problems.

Innovation and research in this area are essential to develop and adopt more environmentally friendly technologies within the plastic industry.

Researchers at the University of Santiago de Compostela in Spain have explored the conversion of UCO into bioplastics. Although specific details of the process are not available in the referenced sources, this work represents a significant effort in valorising domestic waste for the production of sustainable materials.

The conversion of UCO into bioplastics offers multiple environmental benefits, including waste reduction and decreased reliance on fossil resources. However, the lack of publicly available studies and accessible data on these processes limits their scalability and industrial adoption. It is crucial to promote research and dissemination of these studies to evaluate the economic feasibility, process efficiency, and environmental impact of these technologies

To achieve this, it is crucial to ensure the proper collection of used oil in municipalities. This requires the establishment and enforcement of regulations that guarantee the correct collection and treatment processes.

Neste (n.d.) and Borealis collaborated to produce polypropylene at industrial level using used cooking oil. They developed an LCA to evaluate the environmental impacts of chemical recycling. This study, carried out in their plant, is crucial for understanding the environmental implications of using recycled materials. Neste’s findings suggest that chemical recycling can significantly reduce the environmental impact of plastic production—by up to 35% when compared to conventional plastic production—by complementing traditional mechanical recycling and supporting a more sustainable, circular economy. The LCA highlights the substantial potential of chemical recycling to transform the polypropylene (PP) industry by reducing reliance on fossil resources and minimising waste.

6.3.4.2 Economic indicators

7 indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2 (see Table 44).

Table 44. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the PP from UCO value chain

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Recycling rate of biobased products	Higher recycling rates reduce dependence on non-renewable resources by reintroducing valuable materials into the production cycle (e.g., Fedrigoni self-adhesives, 2023).	No.

5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving policies	Strategy for creating the infrastructure and systems necessary for recovering and recycling materials (yes/no)	It refers to a planned and coordinated approach to developing facilities, processes that enable the efficient and effective management of waste and recyclable materials (e.g., Borealis and Neste).	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Potential market share of the product	PP represents one of the most used plastics in Europe thanks to its versatility. The market is segmented into building, construction, automotive, consumer goods, packaging and others according to Fortune business insights (2025).	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Number of partnerships in R&D	Number of formal collaborations that an organisation has with other entities, such as universities, research centres, companies, or even governments, to carry out research and development activities.	Yes.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Economic viability	Return on Investment (ROI)	The ROI of biobased products depends on production costs, market demand, and regulatory incentives.	Yes.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Economic viability	Cost of production (CoP)	The production cost of biobased PP is higher than conventional PP due to feedstock sourcing and technological constraints. However, economies of scale, advancements in production technology, and governmental subsidies can reduce costs over time.	Yes.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Economic viability	Cost competitiveness with the conventional, incumbent product	Cost competitiveness is a major determinant for the adoption of biobased PP.	Yes.

Economic indicators identified as highly relevant to PP are bioeconomy driving policies, potential market share of the product, number of partnerships in R&D, return of investment, cost of production and cost competitiveness with conventional products.

As the concept of the circular economy has become more widely accepted as an attractive way forward, companies around the world have been rethinking the way they design, make, and remake their products. That is why a Strategy for creating the infrastructure and systems necessary for recovering and recycling materials is needed.

Some companies, such as Neste, already provide technology and engineering to transform waste into products. However, the PP production process is not possible without the cooperation of Borealis. Neste sells renewable propane produced using its patented NEXBTL™ technology to the Borealis propane dehydrogenation plant in Kallo. There, it is converted into renewable propylene.

6.3.4.3 Social indicators

7 indicators were identified as highly relevant in T3.2, in the further analysis, T3.3 (see Table 45).

Table 45. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the PP from UCO value chain

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment	Stakeholder engagement and capacity building	Number of informal workshops to build local understanding in the community of the processes that may impact them directly to aid meaningful engagement	Number of educational or information sessions related to proper waste treatment.	Yes.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Adoption of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) (yes/no)	Voluntary integration by companies of social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interaction with stakeholders.	Yes.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Involvement in technology transfer program or projects (yes/no)	Bringing technological innovations and breakthroughs from the laboratory to the market or society.	Yes.

5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy driving policies	Country level strategies	There are different policies and strategies available at national and EU level that consider bioplastics.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Employment	Quality of employment	Characteristics and conditions of work that contribute to the well-being and satisfaction of workers.	Yes.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Gender equality	Number of women having equal job opportunities as men	The extent to which women have access to the same opportunities for hiring, and professional development as their male counterparts.	Yes.
7	Just inclusive and resilient economy	Gender equality	Ratio of basic salary of men to women by employee category	Comparison of the average salary of men and women in the same job category or job title.	Yes.

While promising initiatives exist for transforming UCO into bioplastics, the scarcity of public studies and accessible data poses a barrier to their development and large-scale application. Encouraging research and fostering collaboration between academic institutions, industry, and the public sector are essential to advancing sustainable solutions that mitigate plastic pollution and promote a circular economy.

6.3.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Market dimension

Challenges

- The higher costs of biobased plastics compared to their fossil counterparts, due to the lack of monetarisation of environmental costs, represent a major challenge for the sector.
- Market-related bottlenecks, including investments, time to market, availability of well-equipped specialised technology parks and plants accessible to (small) third parties are a further challenge.

- The lack of market pull measures to promote the willingness to use products containing circular materials has been identified.

Examples of good practices

- Incentivise schemes that enhance the use of UCO for materials. Such schemes could include the implementation of minimum biobased plastics content targets for key plastics applications to create the required market pull.
- Moreover, enhancing the quality and quantity of collected organic waste suitable as feedstock for plastics production, as well as implementing a mandatory separate collection of organic household waste in all EU member states are suggested.

Policy dimension

Challenges

- Inefficient collection of UCO from households limits the availability of this valuable resource for recycling and sustainable biobased production, highlighting the need for better waste management policies and public awareness.
- Industries that utilise PP derived from UCO require clear market regulations to ensure product quality, sustainability standards, and fair competition in the biobased plastics sector.
- The absence of favourable policies, such as incentives for using renewable carbon, discourages the development and market penetration of biobased plastics.

Examples of good practices

- Strengthening regulations on oil waste management is essential to ensure proper collection, recycling, and reuse of UCO. Implementing stricter policies can help reduce environmental contamination, promote circular economy practices, and support industries that produce sustainable biobased materials.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- When UCO is improperly disposed of, it can become a significant environmental pollutant, contaminating water sources, harming aquatic life, and clogging drainage systems. Proper collection, recycling, and conversion into biobased products can help mitigate these negative effects and promote sustainable waste management practices.

Examples of good practices

- Increasing and improving the separate collection of organic waste is essential for enhancing recycling efficiency and reducing landfill waste. Proper sorting ensures that organic materials can be effectively composted or converted into bioenergy, contributing to a more sustainable waste management system and lowering environmental impact.

6.3.6 Key learnings PP from used UCO value chain

The European Green Deal, CEAP, and the EU Waste Framework Directive form a solid policy foundation for advancing biobased and circular economy innovation. These policies emphasise reducing reliance on fossil fuels, promoting waste valorisation, and enhancing recycling systems. However, while there is significant policy coverage on plastics, their reuse, and value chain improvements, specific policies addressing the transformation of waste into bioplastics are scarce.

Although Spain has introduced policies that support circular economy strategies and waste management (España Circular 2030), specific regulations addressing the transformation of waste into bioplastics remain limited. The existing policies mainly focus on broader waste reduction and recycling initiatives rather than directly promoting bioplastic production from waste streams. While some measures encourage innovation in biobased materials, there is no comprehensive regulatory framework that explicitly facilitates and incentivises the large-scale conversion of waste into bioplastics. This lack of targeted policies highlights a gap that could hinder the widespread adoption of bioplastics as a sustainable alternative to conventional plastics.

Scaling up Spain's policies to the EU level could be a step forward in addressing this gap. However, the implementation of such policies across different member states would require harmonisation, financial support, and alignment with existing EU directives on circular economy and plastic waste. A dedicated EU-wide framework promoting the transformation of waste into bioplastics could enhance investment in research, improve industrial adoption, and create standardised guidelines for waste valorisation. Without such a framework, progress in this field may remain fragmented, limiting the potential environmental and economic benefits of bioplastics.

Despite supportive policies, the limited research and the limited technological and economic readiness of the plastics industry to transform UCO in plastic remains a barrier. The petrochemical industry's vested interests and the relatively high cost of implementing new technologies further hinder progress.

A significant challenge in analysing this case is the limited availability of research on UCO transformation into PP. Existing studies provide fragmented insights, making it difficult to conduct a comprehensive comparison of results. Key gaps include:

- In depth LCAs to quantify environmental benefits.
- Scalable and cost-efficient technologies for UCO conversion.

- Exploration of market readiness and industrial applications for UCO-derived PP.

While policies on plastics and waste management provide a foundation for advancing the use of UCO in PP production or other polymers, significant barriers remain. These include economic and technological challenges, as well as gaps in data and research. However, the environmental benefits of transforming a pollutant into a valuable material align strongly with circular economy goals. Addressing these gaps through targeted research and policy implementation could accelerate the transition to more sustainable production practices.

6.4 Plastics - Cellulose acetate

6.4.1 Introduction to cellulose acetate case study

6.4.1.1 General description

Cellulose acetate (CA) is a modified natural polymer, or biobased polymer, with a rich history and a high versatility, observable through various applications and sectors (GVR, 2024). In 1865, the reaction between cellulose and acetic anhydride forming cellulose acetate was first observed (Schützenberger, 1865) and further processing of CA was enabled with the discovery of the first soluble forms in 1903 (Kidder Maede, McCormack, Clark, Sclater, & Lamborn, 1905). Since then, CA has been used for producing films for photography, man-made fibres for clothing and filter production, frames for eyeglasses, precursors for coatings and paints, plastic materials, packaging as well as medical applications (Bardy, Dürig, Lee, & Li, 2017; Teixeira, Paiva, Amorim, & Felgueiras, 2020; Teixeira, et al., 2021; Wolfs & Meier, 2021; GVR, 2024).

The properties of CA vary and depend on the way it is processed. For instance, Teixeira et al. (2020) describe CA as a “*derivative of cellulose with excellent biocompatibility, high water adsorption capacities, good mechanical stability, non-toxicity, and can be efficiently processed into membranes, films, and fibres from either solutions or melts*” (Teixeira, Paiva, Amorim, & Felgueiras, 2020, p. 3). In addition to that, and thanks to its biodegradability, the use of CA is also feasible in cosmetics, coatings and other fields that are currently contributing to microplastic pollution. In fact, its properties contribute to several sustainability benefits to using CA compared to other materials. For instance, a recent study published by the American Chemical Society’s journal of Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering contrasts the most used polymers (PS foam, PP, PET, Paper, PLA and CA foam) and analyses their material impacts. The study shows that CA foam degrades much faster than most other materials analysed, including paper, whether in an ocean or soil environment (James, et al., 2024b; James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024b). Given that CA foam production is slightly more expensive, and requires slightly more energy and water, the study concludes that, if environmental persistence is the determining factor, CA foam can be the best choice (James, et al., 2024a).

6.4.1.2 Value chain and the process

In this case study, the CA value chain is presented and described. As presented above, CA is a very versatile material that has the capacity to displace fossil-based materials in a variety of sectors, such as consumer goods, packaging, filtration, fibres, and construction. At its core, the ingredients of CA production are cellulose fibres (usually in form of wood pulp) and acetic anhydride, with acetic acid as solvent and sulfuric acid as catalyst to speed up the reaction (Wolfs & Meier, 2021). This means that the CA value chain connects to the forestry and wood pulp industry as well as the chemicals industry, given that precursors such as methanol are required to produce acetyls. As discussed throughout this document, while precursors such as methanol are often fossil fuel based, there are biobased production processes, and more technology driven approaches, using chemical recycling and/or carbon capture and utilisation, to produce those precursors. In terms of the uses of CA, a lot of different industries can be considered in the value chain, such as packaging, eye wears, textiles, coatings, consumer goods, and tobacco. In the current environment, while the demand for CA may be very large, the current policy environment leads to a certain degree of hesitation, for reasons that will be elaborated in the policy section of this document.

Figure 51. Value chain of the cellulose acetate system

The production process of CA flakes is presented in Figure 52 below. The process steps described below follow the “traditional process” to produce CA, also referred to as the “Acetic Acid Process” (Wolfs & Meier, 2021). The steps involved in this process are activation, acetylation, hydrolysis, precipitation, washing and drying.

- **Activation of cellulose:** The cellulosic raw material (mostly wood pulp) is mixed with acetic acid and a sulfuric acid catalyst under mechanical stress, resulting in homogenous slurry. Thereby, the cellulose fibres are made equally well-accessible for the reaction; and the even distribution of the reagents is facilitated and ensured.

- **Acetylation:** Acetic anhydride is added to the mixture from the activation step and reacts, catalysed by sulfuric acid, with cellulose to form fully acetylated cellulose (cellulose triacetate) and acetic acid. The cellulose fibres are completely dissolved only at the end of the acetylation step; therefore, the reaction cannot be stopped at a certain lower degree of acetylation.
- **Hydrolysis:** For many applications, fully acetylated cellulose does not offer the desired properties (e.g., with respect to solubility). Therefore, water is added to the mixture from the acetylation step to remove almost one fifth of the acetate groups from the cellulose acetate polymer molecules to yield cellulose diacetate as the most common form. Finally, the sulfuric acid neutralises.
- **Precipitation and processing:** The mixture from the hydrolysis stage is concentrated by evaporating part of the acetic acid. Cellulose acetate is precipitated in the form of flakes by the following addition of larger amounts of water. Subsequently, the flakes are washed with water to remove the remaining acid. To form the final product, the flakes are dried. The separated acetic acid is completely recovered.

Figure 52. Production process cellulose acetate flakes (Source: Cerdia, 2022)

6.4.1.3 Baseline and market

An overview of the current biobased polymer capacities and production in 2023 is presented in Figure 53. Capacities and production are projected to increase at a rate of 17% per year between 2023 and 2028. According to this study by the Nova Institute, CA makes up around 24% of global production, with a fossil share of roughly 50% (Skoczinski, et al., 2024). The study argues that the fossil share persists, mainly due to the EU's focus on supporting bioenergy rather than taking a more comprehensive approach to also include renewable carbon, CO₂ and recycling. The fossil share for CA stems mainly from the production of acetyls (e.g., acetic acid, acetic anhydride) as well as energy inputs, depending on the energy mix used for the production process outlined above. The good news is that several feedstock producers are already shifting their production processes to also include carbon capture and utilisation, for example in the production of methanol (which is one of the inputs to the acetyls production process), irrespective of the policymaking of the EU.

Figure 53. Biobased polymer capacities and production 2023 (Source: Skoczinski, et al., 2024)

According to market research publicly available by Grand view Research, the current market size for CA is estimated at USD 5.9 billion in 2023 (GVR, 2024). The distribution of the market revenue is presented in Figure 54, whereby it must be noted that *market size and composition estimates vary strongly depending on the market research that is consulted*. According to the estimate presented, the largest market for CA are the cigarette filter market, textiles and apparels, and LCD & photographic films. Moreover, CA is used for tapes & labels and a variety of other applications. However, based on recent insights concerning the biodegradability of CA (Sebruyns, Van de Perre, & Hölter, 2024; James, et al., 2024a), this picture may shift rather quickly. If degradability and with it the prevention of fossil microplastics is a factor, then CA holds huge potential beyond typical fields of application, for instance for packaging materials (e.g., foods), consumer goods (e.g., cosmetics, textiles, other packaging, etc.), or wastewater treatment (Kramar, Laxbacher, Far, & Gonzáles-Benito, 2023; Elaissaoui, et al., 2024; James, et al., 2024a).

Figure 54. Cellulose acetate market share by major application (Source: GVR, 2024)

Some of the major global producers of CA are listed below (PMR, 2024), whereby most of the companies are located in the US or Asia, with Cerdia International GmbH being the only producer in the EU:

- Celanese Corporation (US)
- Cerdia International GmbH(CH)
- Daicel Corporation (JPN)
- Eastman Chemical Company (US)
- Nantong Zhuhai Kunming Cellulose Fibres (CN)
- Sichuan Push Acetate Co., Ltd. (CN)
- Jinan Acetate Chemical Co., Ltd (CN)
- Hubei Xinyang Special Fibre Co., Ltd. (CN)

The growth potential for CA is partially reflected in the projected trend for the evolution of worldwide production capacities for biobased polymers presented in Figure 55. In the projection obtained from the Nova Institute (Skoczinski, et al., 2024), PLA is the biobased polymer for which production capacities are projected to expand the most until 2028. On the other hand, commercial PLA is also the material with very long biodegradability time spans besides the degradation under industrial composting conditions (Slezak, Krzystek, Puchalski, Krucińska, & Sitarski, 2023; James, et al., 2024a). Consequently, depending on the standards that will be issued for the transition towards a biobased circular economy, the composition of demand (and hence those capacity estimates) may vary, even if the total growth rate remains unchanged. At this point, it should be noted that there are currently no plans to significantly increase CA production capacity within the EU. There are, however, CA plants that will be established in China that will add around 85kt/y of production capacity outside of the EU.

Figure 55. Biobased building blocks and polymers - global capacities, production and trends 2022-2027 (Source: Skoczinski, et al., 2024)

6.4.2 Stakeholders in the cellulose acetate value chain

6.4.2.1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

Several stakeholders influence the CA value chain and CA producers in particular. Broadly speaking, the stakeholders can be classified into four categories: (i) government, (ii) academia, (iii) industry, and (iv) civil society. Each of these four categories has the potential to both act as an enabling factor as well as creating barriers for the expansion of the CA production systems and the use of CA. A high-level overview of stakeholders for CA is presented in Figure 56.

Figure 56. Identified stakeholders in the cellulose acetate value chain

Governments, or rather governance, plays a pivotal role for shaping the business environment for CA. Governance is exhibited by policymakers at EU and national level, through regional partnerships and by supra-national organisations, such as the United Nations or the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Policymakers at EU level, often in collaboration with supranational organisations, are levelling the playing field by setting rules, regulations, and standards, as well as issuing incentives for specific desired regimes. The resulting policies and laws apply at the national or global level, rendering these stakeholders particularly powerful in picking the “winners and losers” among materials, or even within and across markets. The same applies to national policymakers, who transpose the respective regulations into national law and have the power to define their own priorities and preferences concerning implementation. Lastly, regional partnerships are critical for a successful business environment. Strong ties between the producing company and its social and economic environment are paramount to unlocking potential opportunities that are mutually beneficial.

Knowledge institutes and education providers can be found in the quadrant of academia for the CA sector. The role of knowledge institutes such as NOVA is to bring together fact-based information that enables a deeper understanding and to provide this information and advice to the other stakeholders. Education providers, such as the Karlsruhe Institute for Technology (KIT) and the University of Freiburg (UoF) are important components of the business environment, for two reasons. First, because they conduct research that enables CA producers to improve their processes or develop new products. Second, because they educate the employees of tomorrow and thereby shape tomorrow’s workforce. Especially the latter is becoming more critical, given the emerging labour shortage for medium to high-skilled workers in developed countries like Germany.

In the industry quadrant, there are financial institutions, trade and business associations and commercial businesses. Regarding commercial businesses, it makes sense to distribute them into three categories (i) suppliers, (ii) customer, and (iii) business partners. Financial institutions are highly relevant partners, as they provide financial services that are required for daily business as well as future investments. Depending on the type of company (e.g., privately owned vs publicly traded), financial institutions may have more or less leverage on future capital provisioning. Trade and business associations also play an important role, both for advocacy reasons as well as for sharing information and knowledge on important topics. Most of the time, these are interest groups that form on a needs basis and provide a forum for discussing specific items or challenges. Lastly, commercial businesses comprise the ecosystem of companies that is required to do business. Suppliers are required to ensure that operations can continue as planned, ensuring full capacity utilisation. Clients are those companies that purchase and process CA towards the final product. Lastly, business partners can range from research partners, companies providing technical services or consultancy, among others. These companies are required to ensure business continuity and innovation.

Finally, civil society plays an important role for CA companies. There are citizens, who are either directly or indirectly affected by operations. Impacts can be both positive and negative, and it is

generally of mutual interest to have a beneficial relationship with the local population and local interest groups. Non-governmental Organisations (NGOs) are important advocates for specific causes and interests, both for citizens and businesses. It should be noted that the focus of and approach taken by the respective NGOs shape the nature of interactions between them and producers. The NGOs also include organisations for standardisation like ISO or DIN, bringing together stakeholders from industry, government, academia, and civil society to set standards for materials and processes including, for instance, methods to determine the biodegradability of a material. Alliances and coalitions are an important part of the business environment as well, as they can serve as incubators for ideas or platforms for critical reflection and learning.

6.4.2.2 Power-interest mapping of the stakeholders

The influence of the stakeholders listed in Figure 56 varies, depending on their relative interest and power to drive change. Figure 57 presents the different stakeholders mapped by relative interest and power. It should be noted that the power mapping was done through the lens of “power and interest to shape the CA business environment” rather than power and interest to affect the CA producer, acknowledging that citizen and employees, if considered in the latter case, would hold significantly more power than indicated by the matrix.

Legislators, NGOs and supranational organisations are those stakeholders with the highest power and interest level, which places them at the top of the list of stakeholders with significant leverage to affect the CA business environment. Stakeholders with very high interests, but intermediary levels of power are trade and business associations, knowledge institutes and CA producers themselves. The former two have slightly more influence than the individual producer, given that they are, by design, a conglomerate of interested stakeholders that is likely better connected than any company would be. While there is a high interest in the subject matter, all the aforementioned stakeholders usually provide input to the decision-making process that takes place at the national or international level, with often limited ability to affect the outcome.

Stakeholders with very high interest but relatively little power are coalitions and alliances, citizens, commercial businesses, and CA processors. All these stakeholders have an interest in the CA environment to flourish, even if for different reasons. CA processors and commercial businesses think of business opportunities and continuity, while alliances and coalitions and citizens may care more about the use of more sustainable products. In either case, the power to affect the CA business environment is typically fairly low, unless these actors are connected to the policymaking realm.

Lastly, stakeholders with very high power but limited interest are feedstock providers, financial institutions and the processing and chemicals industries. From an aggregate point of view, they are the upstream supply chain without whose inputs (i.e., raw materials and finances) production is not possible. Depending on their interest in sustainability and in the CA supply chain themselves, these players may opt to use their power to accelerate a shift in the way that CA is produced. In light of recent shifts towards more sustainable investments, this is especially true in the case where producers are dependent on outside finance to realise capital acquisitions.

Figure 57. Stakeholders of the cellulose acetate value chain mapped in a power-interest matrix

6.4.3 Policies of relevance to cellulose acetate value chain

Given the versatility of CA, there is a range of different policy frameworks that apply to it. Regulations cut across the value chain, such as REACH, which assesses final products and raw materials that are used for production, or SUPD, which mainly focuses on the end-of-life stage of products in the attempt to reduce littering of plastics into the environment. An overview of policies that are affecting CA is presented in Figure 58, which is representative but not exhaustive. A more comprehensive overview of policies is presented in Table 46 together with a brief description of each measure and whether it is proposed or already enforced.

Figure 58. Overview of main policies affecting the cellulose acetate sector

Despite its long history as material for many purposes, for CA, the current policy environment is quite scattered and hampers the uptake of the material. The current policies hence act rather as barriers than enablers. Heavy emphasis is put on the end-of-life stages of the product, which is likely in part attributable to the fact that CA is, among other things, used to produce cigarette filters. Most of the regulations applicable to CA are either meant to reduce the use of specific products (or ban them) or to ensure that the supply chain diligence and related losses (e.g., pellet losses) are curbed. It should be noticed here already that CA’s treatment under different policy regimes is different, due to the absence of clear definitions and classifications for biopolymers. There is a clearly observable trend towards constraining the use of CA, not targeting the material

itself, but resulting from ambiguous definitions and unclear classifications of materials. The following sections provide a brief description of the main policy frameworks applicable to CA and how they apply.

The proposed revision of the **Waste Framework Directive (WFD)** is anticipated, but can be both a barrier and stimulant for a developing biobased circular economy, depending on the revisions implemented. As is “natural” in developing economic sectors, initial volumes might be low, which renders recycling economically difficult. Furthermore, new biobased materials might require new recycling technologies and collecting and separation schemes, that would need to be developed or existing ones to be refined (Akinsemolu, Idowu, & Onyeaka, 2024). Both factors, market penetration and technological development, will need time and effort. An upcoming revision of the WFD should adequately reflect these issues and foster a developing and promising industry sector, rather than “choking” it. Just very recently the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) called to strengthen the circularity in waste management (EESC, 2024), suggesting a “paradigm shift in the waste industry”. The same ambition underlies a recent paper on the recycling of biobased polymers that highlights the current status quo and several challenges (Akinsemolu, Idowu, & Onyeaka, 2024).

The proposed **Green Claims Directive (GCD)** aims to reduce unfair business practices and sales methods to empower consumers and ensure a transition to greater overall sustainability. From the industry point of view there are two general caveats: The regulation could potentially contribute to an even more diversified “certification landscape”, as more labels and certification schemes will likely contribute to consumer confusion rather than informed decisions. Secondly, article 21(3(c)) lists criteria most relevant to a biobased polymer industry. From an industry perspective, especially the criteria for “biodegradability” need careful examination, as the currently existing biodegradation criteria are unattainable even for many natural, non-man-made materials. A critical review of those criteria, including timelines and performance indicators, could benefit the biopolymer industry and the environment, by formulating more relevant and realistic sustainability performance requirements.

As **adequate and realistic biodegradation criteria and appropriate tests** need to be developed, a collaborated effort between academia, industry and regulators is required to ensure alignment between policy ambition, science and industrial reality. It is very clear that the development of a scientific foundation that does justice to the wide range of materials renders close cooperation between the different stakeholders’ imperative.

The importance of adequate definitions and criteria is exemplified with the **Single Use plastics directive (SUPD)**. Article 3 deliberately summarises all polymer materials that do not occur naturally under the term “plastic”, which is in stark contrast to the ISO definition of plastic. This stance assigns similarity to materials that often have nothing more in common than being polymers. Furthermore, in the context of SUPD, this inclusion stipulated the wrong, but nevertheless widespread, assumption that naturally occurring polymers are somehow “better” in terms of environmental pollution caused by irresponsible littering. While this pollution is certainly more than a nuisance, the SUPD prevents the whole biobased and biodegradable polymer industry

from developing functional solutions that might benefit environment and society. Article 15 of the SUPD requests an evaluation considering “an assessment of the scientific and technical progress concerning criteria or a standard for biodegradability in the marine environment ...”. Since the SUPD itself does not define those criteria, any development towards these goals is “left in the dark” while it increasingly becomes evident, that e.g., paper-based solutions for drinking straws suffer from functional deficits or make use of soon to be restricted chemicals to achieve functionality. It should not be forgotten that, in many cases, man-made polymer materials are used due to essential properties that are not found in materials provided by nature. Since the EU recently started the SUPD evaluation process, this evaluation would be an excellent opportunity to address these issues in the upcoming call for evidence.

In contrast to the SUPD, biodegradability is already applied within the **Microplastic Regulation**. However, also here the same non-technical definition of “plastic” is used. Moreover, the biodegradability criteria listed for exemption from the restriction for certain applications are defined in such a way that they are not easily met even by many organic natural materials. Also, this regulation puts all man-made polymer materials under general suspicion regarding their environmental impact, despite being a heterogeneous group with very different properties. On the one hand, taking account of the importance of biodegradability under different environmental conditions is welcome. On the other hand, the requirements are set in such a way that even CA, which is one of the very few polymers that has been proven to biodegrade under practically all conditions, runs the risk of not passing individual tests at first try. These tests are very costly and time-consuming, and many questions regarding the implementation of the biodegradation tests and their transferability remain unanswered. As with SUPD, the ambiguity about materials that may or may not be exempt poses a challenge to businesses that market a solution to the environmental problem envisaged to be resolved by the policy.

The **Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR)** is another example of “good intention with unintended side effects” - while its ultimate goal is to reduce the deforestation by providing a framework that only allows deforestation free products to be sold in Union markets, it does so by placing a considerable bureaucratic burden on all market participants. This bureaucracy even extends to individual landowners in non-Union countries, whereby the timeframes for implementation were so ambitious that the enactment of the directive needed to be postponed. The postponement of the EUDR by the Commission is a testament that, while the ambitions of policy and legislation may be good, the burden for implementation is typically underestimated. Additionally, the EUDR requirements were not aligned with, or complementary to, already existing certification systems that are widely adopted throughout industry, thereby creating a massive additional burden to companies.

There are initiatives that aim to increase the sustainability of material use in the Union, such as the **Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)**. CEAP focuses on increased uptake of circular practices and the reuse of materials, longer product lifetimes, increased recycling of products and reduced use of single use materials (EC, 2020). As with the other policies, there is an acknowledgement of biobased materials in the policy, referring to the “EU policy framework on biobased,

biodegradable and compostable plastics” (EC, 2022) and other documents. However, the underlying absence of definitions and classifications, as well as the application of quasi unattainable standards, remains. Further, the mere fact that polymers can biodegrade should not prevent the conversation about the need for separate collection as well as recycling processes and infrastructure, which also suffers from policy support due to the ambiguity surrounding biopolymers (Akinsemolu, Idowu, & Onyeaka, 2024).

The above paragraphs outline some of the challenges that CA faces in the current policy landscape, whereby CA is only one of several, if not many, materials that are facing the same challenges. While the ambiguity in the definitions and policy frameworks may be on purpose, given the vast uncertainty regarding drivers of and solutions to the problem, policymakers should be mindful of the fact that uncertainty resulting from this ambiguity is a major barrier for the transition towards more sustainable materials. Biobased industries would benefit from increased clarity and a more lenient framework (and standards) for judging the sustainability of materials, especially when compared to fossil-fuel based materials. The implementation of a more holistic approach that levels the playing field for all contenders, not just the well-researched ones, is required. This approach must start with the evaluation of materials using science-based methodologies that are grounded in latest industry research and end with the implementation of enabling factors, such as for instance levies on fossil-based materials, collection and recycling systems for biopolymers, and more.

Table 46. Information regarding the policy instruments relevant to cellulose acetate

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/ planned/ proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
REACH	“To improve the protection of human health and the environment from the risks that can be posed by chemicals, while enhancing the competitiveness of the EU chemicals industry.” (ECHA, 2024)	Barrier	Market restrictions; Annex XVII Prevents the use of certain materials in the market.	EU	Current	Regulation	(ECHA, 2024)
EUDR	The goal of the Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR) is to reduce the deforestation by providing a framework that only allows deforestation free products to be sold in Union markets.	Barrier	Market barrier, import restriction - places a huge bureaucratic due diligence burden on companies that import commodities under the EUDR.	EU	In force, implementation postponed	Regulation	(EC, 2023a)
SUPD	“To prevent and reduce the impact on the environment of certain plastic products and to promote the transition to a circular economy.” (EUROPEN, 2019)	Barrier	The SUPD is a market restriction that practically bans a number of materials that are largely used for single use. The policy hereby is applied indiscriminately without a proper definition.	EU	Current	Regulation	(EU, 2019; EUROPEN, 2019)
SUPD (revision)	See above; revision of SUPD is planned for 2027	Barrier	See above	EU	Planned	Regulation	

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/ planned/ proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
Microplastic Regulation	“Restricts synthetic polymer microparticles on their own or intentionally added to mixtures with the aim of reducing the emission of microplastics in everyday products in order to protect the environment.” (EC, 2023b)	Barrier	Market restriction - placed within REACH and hence prohibits the use of this materials. As is the case with SUPD, there is insufficient differentiation between plastics themselves as well as with regard to their actual environmental impact	EU	Current	Regulation	(EC, 2023b)
PPWD	“The Packaging and Packaging Waste (PPWD) Directive [...] aims to harmonise national measures concerning the management of packaging and packaging waste to prevent or reduce any impact on the environment.” Updates the EU legislative framework by giving Member States and businesses adequate support to achieve waste reduction targets. This support takes the form of a harmonised regulatory framework that supports investment, reduces waste and promotes high-quality recycling, which will apply equally in all EU Member States	Barrier and stimulating	Steering the transition towards the use of recycled materials needs to be balanced for suitable alternatives, availability of materials and positive incentives for the transition.	EU	Q4 2024	Regulation	(EC, 2023c)
Waste framework directive	“The Waste Framework Directive sets the basic concepts and definitions related to waste management, including definitions of waste, recycling and recovery.” (EC, 2023d)	Barrier		EU	Current	Regulation	(EC, 2008; EC, 2023d, e)

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/ planned/ proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
Unintentional release of Microplastics Regulation	Reducing pellet losses to the environment and preserving ecosystems and biodiversity, decreasing potential health impacts and benefiting local economic activities.	Barrier	This regulation constitutes a bureaucratic hurdle, given that both the loss estimations as well as various analytical documents need to be readily available upon request by authorities.	EU	Proposed		
Circular Economy Action Plan	“This Circular Economy Action Plan provides a future-oriented agenda for achieving a cleaner and more competitive Europe in co-creation with economic actors, consumers, citizens and civil society organisations. [...].The plan presents a set of interrelated initiatives to establish a strong and coherent product policy framework that will make sustainable products, services and business models the norm and transform consumption patterns so that no waste is produced in the first place.”	Barrier	The regulation largely favours the recycling of already existing materials, with little consideration for the need that processes, technology and infrastructure for recycling biobased materials	EU	Current		(EC, 2020)
Green Claim Directive	Reducing unfair business practices and sales methods to empower consumers and ensuring a transition to greater overall sustainability.	Stimulating or barrier	The GCD can be stimulating by creating a trusted basis for informed consumer decisions on biobased products. However, it must coherently reflect the	EU	Proposed	Regulation	(EC, 2024)

Policy instrument - name	Short description of main goal of the policy instrument	Barrier or stimulating instrument?	How is it a barrier or stimulation instrument?	Geographic coverage (EU, national - which country?)	Timeframe (old, current, future/ planned/ proposed)	Type of instrument	Information sources
			potential of a biobased economy.				
Waste Framework Directive	Reduce environmental and climate impacts, increase environment quality, improve public health associated with textiles waste management in line with the waste hierarchy, reduce the environmental and climate impacts of food systems associated with food waste generation.	Barrier or Stimulating	Depends on the definitions and scope. We deem it important to foster new biobased materials having small market penetrations in new sectors.	EU	Revision Proposed	Regulation	(EC, 2023d)

6.4.4 Analysis of indicators of the cellulose acetate case study

In T3.2, a consistency check was conducted to identify the indicators in the Bioeconomy Monitoring and Assessment framework deemed relevant for CA by industry partners. The long list of indicators was used for inspiration purposes of the indicators that may apply, and new indicators were added where applicable. The indicators presented in this section do not just focus on the comparison between CA and the conventional fossil-based system, but also on priorities for CA production as such (i.e., sustainability ambitions of producers and challenges & barriers to potential future business). Given the overlap between several categories of indicators in the long list, the most important ones were chosen, and additional context is provided in the analysis section of the indicator.

The indicators are roughly divided into environmental indicators, economic indicators, and social indicators, acknowledging that various interconnections exist between them. For instance, while sustainable forestry and biomass production are listed as an economic indicator, we are mindful of the fact that sustainable forestry provides both economic (higher value added, increased business volume) and social (employment and income, social cohesion, inclusivity) benefits, in addition to being more environmentally beneficial to conventional wood production (higher carbon stored, no clear cutting, improved land management). These benefits are not elaborated in the analysis of the indicator, to ensure that only the main argument is presented.

Using the insights from the process followed above, the following sections will provide information about the CA production system and relevant indicators regarding environmental, economic, and social indicators. Moreover, in several instances, information will be contrasted with conventional plastic production, and/or the production of other biopolymers, to highlight some of the strengths and weaknesses of CA compared to other materials. A research gap was indicated in two instances: (1) when there was no or insufficient information available for contrasting CA with conventional systems, and (2) when there are policy or practical challenges or knowledge gaps that require attention.

6.4.4.1 Environmental/circular indicators

Table 47 provides an overview of environmental and circular indicators that were identified as highly relevant in T3.2. In total, eight indicators were identified to be highly relevant for CA. Not all the indicators presented can be directly compared to the fossil-fuel based production regime, given for instance the reliance on natural resources.

Table 47. Highly relevant environmental and circular indicators identified for the cellulose acetate case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Primary Biomass Production	Forests	The production of CA requires cellulose as production input, typically in the form of wood pulp (Bardy, Dürig, Lee, & Li, 2017). Consequently, the availability of production forests is essential to produce CA at a large scale. The land footprint of biopolymers is arguable larger than that of fossil polymers (Brizga, Hubacek, & Feng, 2020), however, it should also be considered that land degradation from fossil fuel production often leads to severe environmental degradation (NRDC, 2022).	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Forest quality	Share of forests certified for sustainable management	Being dedicated to zero deforestation or zero clear cutting, most CA producers only use wood pulp from certified sustainable forestry (e.g., FSC, PEFC). Consequently, the availability of forest biomass from sustainably managed forests is essential. There is no equivalent to this in the fossil-fuel based system, other than remediation of polluted areas, which is fundamentally not sustainable.	No.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Sustainable resource use	% of biological content/product	The demand for biobased products is increasing, which makes it important to show that the acetals used are produced sustainably (biobased), in addition to the wood pulp. As highlighted by the Nova Institute (Skoczinski, et al., 2024), the fossil share prevails due to a lack of incentives at EU level to facilitate the production of biobased raw material inputs.	Yes, pathways that incentivise the expansion of biobased raw material production capacities are required.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Energy efficiency	Energy Intensity (product value added / mJ primary energy)	The traditional production process of CA requires inputs in form of electricity and steam/heat, if performed at industrial scale. Energy consumption drives cost and GHG emissions, which makes it paramount to identify ways to reduce energy use, or new concepts that can be applied to existing capacity and are implementable with national ambitions.	Yes, viable energy concepts for chemical production companies are required. A transition to hydrogen is planned, however, feasible technologies to replace existing assets do not exist yet.
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	% of biodegradability	In a world full of microplastics, biodegradability becomes ever more important. As shown, CA degrades faster than many other biobased polymers (Slezak, Krzystek, Puchalski, Krucińska, & Sitariski, 2023; James, et al., 2024a) as well as conventional polymers (Kubiawicz & Booth, 2017; Yu & Flury, 2024). Research into improving biodegradation is ongoing, however, is far away from	Yes, increased research on biodegradability of existing materials which is then condensed into a database that allows for fair comparison.

				a consolidated database that provides input to decision makers on the performance on various materials.	
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Waste generation and management	Social cost of plastic pollution	Studies suggest that CA has the lowest cost of plastic pollution, compared to other materials (James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024b). Together with PHA, CA shows by far the lowest cost of plastic pollution, with below 1 USD/1,000 lids. Other materials range between 3-100+USD/1,000 lids.	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Certified biobased products	Biobased content	Approaches such as the mass balance approach (ISCC, 2023) provide the opportunity for chemical companies to highlight biobased inputs, even in continuous processes. It should be noted, however, that the biobased content does not necessarily affect the sustainability (i.e., biodegradability) of polymers and that fossil polymers can still not be biodegradable, despite having biobased content (Yu & Flury, 2024). However, the availability of biobased raw materials is limited (Skoczinski, et al., 2024), which constrains the ability of chemical companies to increase the input of biobased content in their production processes.	Yes, research on enabling the scale-up of biobased raw material production is required to address the matter of improving sustainability at supply chain level.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Greenhouse gas emissions	Generally speaking, the GHG intensity of producing biobased polymers is similar to that of conventional polymers (Brizga, Hubacek, & Feng, 2020). However, the mean GHG for CA is significantly lower than most of the other materials (James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024b). However, it should be noted that energy sources used for production matter. GHG are not just relevant in economic terms. For instance, under the EU Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS), companies need to purchase allowances if they emit more than their predetermined emissions. At the same time, the consequences of climate change can have significant impact on own operations and the supply chain.	No.
4	Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions	Life cycle GHG emissions (gr eq. CO ₂ /product unit)	Availability of viable GHG emission reduction strategies is required. Many large companies commit to science-based targets (SBTi, 2024), whereby the ambition trickles down into the supply chain. But lifecycle GHG also depend on the processing of the material. While the study of James et al. (James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024b) shows that CA has the lowest GHG footprint, a different study by James et al. (2024b) shows that CA foam is the most energy intensive among the materials used. This shows that, when comparing	Yes, same database on attributes of various biopolymers and their derivatives that is indicated above.

				products, the same type of product should be compared to ensure fair treatment.	
--	--	--	--	---	--

This table shows that, concerning the environmental indicators, there are three main areas that are relevant to the CA value chain: (1) land-related sustainability, specifically forests and their sustainability certifications, (2) the availability and use of sustainable raw materials, which reflects onto product properties and the ability for the CA supply chain to become more sustainable (and/or biobased), (3) GHG as well as efficiency related parameters, with emphasis on energy, and (4) existing environmental regulations, policy frameworks and standards that are applied to biopolymers. The main research gaps identified concern (i) the lack of an integrated knowledge hub for comparing the product properties of biopolymers across all potential materials, (ii) viable pathways for defossilising the chemical industry and hence effectively reduce GHG emissions, (iii) the availability of biobased raw materials as inputs to the production process, and (iv) the harmonisation of policy frameworks with current achievements as well as potential prospects for specific materials, taking account of (i).

Given its dependency of cellulose as one of the main raw materials, both the availability of cellulose, typically in form of wood pulp, as well as the sustainability of its sourcing is relevant to the CA value chain. All large producers are aware of their sustainability implications, as are the final users of CA, making sustainable sourcing imperative. This pressure also translates downwards into the supply chain, whereby wood producers are often leading the charge on becoming more sustainable and attaining sustainability certifications, such as issued by the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC). This is in stark contrast to the conventional polymer production, which relies on fossil fuels as main input material. As highlighted by the Natural Resources Defense Council (NRDC), the exploitation of land for fossil fuels can often have detrimental effects on ecosystems and pollute landscapes for decades to come (NRDC, 2022).

The second aspect is the availability of sustainable raw materials, which, in the case of CA, translates directly into the share of biomass content in the final product. As highlighted by the Nova Institute, roughly 50% of the raw materials used for CA are fossil based (Skoczinski, et al., 2024), which is partially related to the fact that the availability of biobased acetlys is still limited in the global market, at least their procurement in large quantities. While the mass balance approach (ISCC, 2023) allows for highlighting the biobased share in products, if biobased raw materials are used, the availability of biobased acetlys is a bottleneck and hence an enabler that needs to be established. One of the key underlying assumptions is that there is a desire to transition towards biodegradable materials that are fully biobased, and that this transition leads to a more sustainable trajectory. However, as highlighted by Yu and Flury (2024), it should be considered that the use of biobased materials does not translate into the biodegradability of products. This highlights that not only biobased raw materials are important, but also the consideration of environmental persistence of their derivatives, of course acknowledging the challenges that come with degradation of biobased materials.

Indicators related to environmental sustainability, such as GHG and environmental persistence, are where the CA value chain shows a stark contrast to the fossil-fuel based regime. Studies show that GHG related to biopolymer production are similar or slightly lower when compared to fossil-fuel based polymers (Brizga, Hubacek, & Feng, 2020; James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024a). Lifecycle GHG also depend on the type of processing that is performed for production. This becomes evident when comparing the GHG intensity of CA, which is lower compared to

various other materials (James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024b), to that of CA foam, where GHG intensity is highest compared to all other materials (James, et al., 2024b). On the other hand, if CA foam is compared to PS foam, values are similar (James, et al., 2024b). In the assessment of GHG emissions, it should be considered that large portions of the GHG can be addressed through the energy mix used for production. Concerning environmental persistence, biodegradability becomes the hallmark indicator. Studies show that several biobased polymers are performing much better on this indicator (James, et al., 2024a; James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024a; Yu & Flury, 2024), and CA in particular better compared to many other biobased polymers (James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024b). This highlights that CA is among the "best in class" materials to address the accumulation of microplastics in the environment.

6.4.4.2 Economic indicators

An overview of economic indicators that were identified as highly relevant for CA is provided in Table 48. As per the indicators provided by T3.2, three indicators were identified as highly relevant, with three additional indicators being added (indicated in red).

Table 48. Highly relevant economic indicators identified for the cellulose acetate case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
2	Sustainable natural resource management	Primary Biomass Production	Forests	The production of CA requires cellulose as production input, typically in the form of wood pulp (Bardy, Dürig, Lee, & Li, 2017). Consequently, the availability of production forests is essential to produce CA.	No.
3	Dependence on non-renewable resources	Material use efficiency	Material and (municipal) waste recycling and recovery rates	Recycling and reuse are important aspects to reduce waste and maximise material efficiency. For CA, there are various opportunities for recycling and reuse. In the current regime, biopolymer recycling is still in need of development and faces various challenges and barriers (Akinsemolu, Idowu, & Onyeaka, 2024).	Yes, research into how infrastructure required to enable a full "lifecycle" for biopolymers, including recycling, can be incentivised (e.g., policy support).
	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Potential market share of the product	CA is a very versatile biopolymer that can be used for numerous applications, indicating that the potential market share is significant. For the realisation of this market share, it is important to have a levelled policy environment and harmonised legislation, to ensure that investment in production capacities, which are significant, are	Yes, and deep knowledge about the properties of the most used as well as new biopolymers that serves as input to the policymaking process and the strategic direction of

				implemented in anticipation of increased demand.	developing the biobased sector.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Capital costs	The expansion of capacity is related with significant investments, which currently would need to be implemented in an uncertain environment. Clarity on use cases for the material as well as an outlook on regulatory frameworks would provide confidence to invest.	No.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Operating costs	Raw material and energy cost are of significant importance to the viability of CA production. While raw materials can be sourced globally, energy is typically location dependent. This means that countries such as Germany, that have a vast industrial base and high energy prices, are at risk of losing their attractiveness for domestic production.	Yes, a concept for a sustainable energy transition that is supported by and at the same time supports businesses is required. This includes concepts for industrial energy use that are workable (i.e., technologies exist) while at the same time developing the infrastructure required to
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Comparative advantage	Cost of decarbonisation	The cost of decarbonisation is quite significant in the chemicals industry, of which the CA industry is a part of. An estimate of the marginal abatement cost puts the cost per ton of CO ₂ avoided at between 25€ and 500€ (Rekker, Kasina, & Mulder, 2023). The mean cost of biobased solutions to climate change mitigation in this study ranges from 150€ to 325€ per ton. This highlights the significant barrier that exists for their implementation.	Yes, there is a need to provide incentives for the development of those technologies, which can in part be done by providing certainty on the business and policy environment.

Economic indicators identified as highly relevant to CA are (1) forest biomass production for raw materials availability, (2) waste generation and circular use of products, (3) capital and operational expenditure for running operations and increasing capacity, and (4) the cost of decarbonisation. The main research gaps that are related to these four categories are (i) the need for methodologies and infrastructure to enable the recycling of biopolymers, (ii) the cost requirements for setting up biopolymer production capacity as well as producing biobased raw materials, and (iii) the cost of decarbonisation for the chemicals industry in general, but also CA production in particular, given the significant cost per ton of CO₂ eq. mitigated for various interventions (see e.g., MACC presented by Rekker, Kasina & Mulder, 2023)

The first aspect overlaps with the environmental parameters that are presented for CA in the previous section. Given its dependence on cellulose as one of the main raw materials, and wood being the main source of cellulose for CA, the availability of healthy production forests is paramount. If managed correctly and sustainably, forestry can be advantageous to both producers and the environment. Forests become even more important to consider in light of the fact that many biobased products, not just polymers, are using cellulose (from wood) as main raw material, as highlighted, among others, by the laminated timber case study. The higher the market penetration of these products, the higher the demand for wood will be, which again highlights the need for production forests, their output and their sustainability.

The second aspect is related to waste generation, both from the production process as well as end-of-life management of intermediary and final products. At the moment, recycling of biopolymers can be roughly divided into mechanical and chemical recycling processes (Akinsemolu, Idowu, & Onyeaka, 2024), whereby mechanical recycling focuses on grinding biopolymers into smaller pieces in order to re-cycle them in the form of pellets, and chemical recycling can be implemented through various processes, each more or less suitable for specific polymers. However, there are various challenges related to the recycling of biopolymers that may be overlooked, based on the assumption that “technologies exist”. Akinsemolu et al. (2024) provide an overview and classification of challenges for biopolymers and their recycling, classifying them into technical challenges, economic challenges, and regulatory challenges. Technical challenges are aspects related to the chemical properties of biopolymers and how recycling affects their quality (e.g., recycled PHA loses important properties, limiting future use). Economic challenges relate to the costs required for establishing collection and sorting procedures as well as recycling capacity for biopolymers, which is economically questionable due to the low market penetration thus far. A scattered regulatory and policy landscape and a lack of clear and consistent definitions and classifications for biopolymers within regulatory frameworks are highlighted as regulatory and policy challenges. The resulting ambiguity leads to uncertainty, and moreover, the current absence of policy support for biopolymer recycling prevents the sector from growing, constraining circularity where it should be supported.

The additional indicators for CA production concern the cost of capacity, the cost of operations and the cost of decarbonisation. The production of CA is a capital and energy intensive process, and cost estimates for plants are typically not publicly available. Concerning operations costs, both raw materials as well as energy intensity of the production process, requiring both electricity and heat, is important for two reasons. The first reason is that the cost of energy can have a significant impact on the total cost of production. This makes energy efficiency important but also highlights that production capacity may be established in countries where the cost of energy is reliably low. The second reason is the GHG emissions from production, which can lead to additional cost if the producer location falls under an emissions trading scheme. This is where operational expenditure meets the cost of decarbonisation, given that decarbonising production can be economically superior, under given circumstances. Policymakers should, however, consider that the decarbonisation of chemical producers comes with a massive price tag. The median cost per ton of GHG abated in the European chemicals industry is 429 €/t CO₂ (Rekker, Kasina, &

Mulder, 2023), which highlights the need for an integrated approach that drives national decarbonisation. Governments and businesses need to work together to align initiatives for driving decarbonisation. For one, because it will reduce friction and build momentum, and more importantly, it will be aligned with the ability of industrial producers to move towards low carbon. Decarbonisation at industry level may be much more complex than it appears from the outside. Industrial installations are fine-tuned ecosystems that, more often than not, cannot simply replace one component to be more sustainable, but every technical decision must be analysed considering potential systemic consequences.

6.4.4.3 Social indicators

Table 49 provides an overview of social indicators that were identified as highly relevant for CA under T3.2 (i.e., five indicators in total). In addition, three indicators were added to the list as they were not included in the original list with indicators proposed by T3.2. These additional indicators are presented in red font.

Table 49. Highly relevant social indicators identified for the cellulose acetate case study

SO	Societal objectives	Sub-topics	Indicator	Analysis of the indicator	Research gap?
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Regulatory measures	At EU level, there are at current several policies that affect the biopolymer space. In some instances, biobased materials that provide a viable alternative to fossil-based plastics, among which CA, are at threat to fall under regulations that aim to reduce plastic pollution, such as the Single Use Plastics Directive, or SUPD (EU, 2019). While the Commission’s ambition is the right one, SUPD’s design lacks information that allows for a more granular and comprehensive approach.	Yes, a database that allows a fair comparison of biobased materials is required, which can inform a more future-oriented approach to plastics legislation.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Presence of a formal policy in place concerning health and safety of all workers, including contractors	Health and safety are among the top priorities of chemical producers, and the CA industry is no different in this space. The presence of a strong health and safety culture is paramount for maintaining and attracting a strong workforce.	No.

5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Innovation	Corporate social responsibility	Next to business objectives, which play an important role, it is important to note that some CA producers are enablers to the attainment of social objectives. The company Cerdia Produktions GmbH in Germany, for instance, is incorporated into a network with industrial neighbours and the city of Freiburg, consciously contributing to low carbon development and various social initiatives.	Yes, research on how to make industrial residents contributors to society (i.e., converting externalities into benefits)
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Incoherent definitions of biopolymers in EU strategies	A big challenge of biopolymers is a lack of clear and consistent definitions and classifications of biopolymers in policy frameworks that govern their use (Akinsemolu, Idowu, & Onyeaka, 2024). The lack of a coherent definition, and hence treatment, makes navigation of the policy environment difficult and puts some biobased materials at a disadvantage, or disincentivises their use.	Yes, a mechanism that allows for a coherent definition of biobased materials across policy frameworks, considering all scientific evidence, is required.
5	Employment and economic competitiveness	Bioeconomy-driving Policies	Arbitrary combination of existing standards and political ambition - Selective adoption of sustainability requirements misaligned with current industrial achievements	The current definition of biodegradability used in policy does not sufficiently consider the peculiarity of biodegradation of polymeric materials, such as the lag phase that results from the need of the microbial environment to adapt to the material. It is only oriented towards very rapidly degrading polymers because policymakers combine established standards (i.e., methodologies for testing) with timelines so ambitious that many materials cannot hit the mark. At the same time, the biodegradability benefits of CA start to be documented in the literature (Slezak, Krzystek, Puchalski, Krucińska, & Sitarski, 2023; James, et al., 2024a; James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024a). An illustration of the lag-phase in biodegradation for CA according to different testing standards is presented in a recent research article (Sebruyns, Van de Perre, & Hölter, 2024). A more nuanced approach that assesses the	Yes, a revision of standards in light of data on biobased materials is desirable to ensure that non-linear processes (and related time requirements) are accounted for. This requires comparable scientific evidence on biobased materials and polymers.

				hierarchy of biodegradability across materials would be desirable.	
--	--	--	--	--	--

On the social indicators, there is a strong emphasis on both the responsibility of an organisation to contribute to society as well as the regulatory environment.

The first part of social responsibility concerns the generation of employment and the quality of work. The production of CA relies on a skilled workforce familiar with production processes, which is something acquired through training and experience. Moreover, being a chemical production company, there is an inherent health risk to employees working at the plant, which is addressed by the company. The mere presence of health and safety guidelines is insufficient; it is required that all employees are advocates of such measures to ensure not only the safest possible working environment, but also that new employees immediately notice the importance of health and safety.

However, social responsibility goes beyond employees and into the communities of which companies are part of. As indicated in the table, Cerdia Produktions GmbH in Germany is collaborating with the municipality of Freiburg im Breisgau as well as a major utility company. Joint projects cover, for example, the provisioning of carbon free heating to neighbouring companies in the industrial park where Cerdia’s facilities are located, or the provision of heat to enable a carbon-neutral living district in Freiburg. And there are other social projects that affect the community beyond the mere provisioning of utilities. In many instances, chemical companies, such as CA producers and others, are a major factor in cities or regions where they have been established. This makes it even more important to engage with them and to assess whether there are potential benefits that can be realised from collaboration. If those companies leave, or go bankrupt, an important building block of modern society could disappear. Companies, on the other hand, should strive to actively seek out projects that make them relevant and reliable partners in the energy transition and decarbonisation space.

Lastly, and most importantly, CA is affected by existing environmental regulations, policy frameworks and standards that are applied to biopolymers. While the above indicators address the benefits and drawbacks of CA as material, regulations, standards, and policy frameworks frame the business environment and prospects of materials today and in the future. The existing definitions for biodegradation at policy level can (and should) be challenged in terms test conditions of time requirements, given that many biopolymers cannot live up to them. As outlined in the description of the policy environment provided above, CA is in a somewhat uncomfortable position, being caught between various frameworks. This is presumably also due to its use in a product that is often deemed the "epicentre" of microplastic pollutions and irresponsible littering, and the fact that CA is not considered a versatile biobased polymer by several institutions and organisations that provide input to the policy environment. In other words, advocacy for CA has been absent at European level. The lack of advocacy is part of the reason why different definitions apply to CA, depending on the policy framework. Consequently, a knowledge base covering all biobased polymers, as is for instance the case with the forecasts for capacity provided by the

Nova Institute (Skoczinski, et al., 2024) should be built to ensure that all materials and their potential are covered.

6.4.5 Case-specific insights from stakeholder consultations

Market dimension

Challenges

- Competition from outside the EU is increasing, whereby production practices are oftentimes less sustainable due to the use of fossil fuels, such as coal. The ability to buy renewable energy certificates shrouds this fact, creating the appearance of sustainability and of “low-carbon products” are entering the Union market.
- The demand for CA in new markets is in part constrained through its ambiguous position in the current policy environment (see below). This ambiguity leads to hesitation to invest in upscaling production capacity, given the risk of massive sunk costs.
- There is increased demand for biogenic products (i.e., 100% biobased content) to replace fossil-fuel based ones. This is a welcome trend, but leads to two challenges: (1) it is hard to address this demand in the absence of sufficient biobased feedstock for production, and (2) CA is typically produced in a continuous process, and mass balance attribution of biobased content is insufficient to address this requirement; rendering (1) the main bottleneck.

Examples of good practices

- Increase operational efficiency and renewable resource use as much as possible to remain competitive.
- Conduct research with industry partners and participants in potentially new markets to explore the potential for expanding the use of CA.
- Engage with suppliers (existing and new) to assess the feasibility of increasing the production of renewable feedstocks.
- Engage with certification providers to assess applicability of sustainability certification schemes to existing (and potentially new) processes.
- Set up sample production to generate proof of concept and to highlight readiness to engage in new markets.

Policy dimension

Challenges

- Incoherent definitions of biopolymers across various policy frameworks often end up classifying CA together with fossil-based or otherwise unsustainable materials.
- The absence of unified definitions and classifications that include CA as biopolymer rather than common plastic threatens to create a regulatory environment that makes the use of CA prohibitive. The fact that there is huge market potential, but yet so little applications

beyond those presented highlights that there is a policy gap for levelling the field towards all biopolymers.

- The defined requirements for and methodologies to prove sustainability, such as the biodegradability testing that is applied, are sometimes unattainable even for non-manmade organic materials, suggesting that a revision of said requirements might benefit the whole biopolymer industry. While CA is likely to ultimately pass these tests, these tests constitute a barrier for many biopolymer producers, both in terms of threshold for material sustainability and their significant costs. Furthermore, conditions for confirming biodegradability are only designed to prevent false positives and therefore accept the increased risk of false negatives.
- The circularity of biopolymers is not yet established, as policy incentives for the collection and recycling of biopolymers specifically are lacking. This is a problem that concerns all biopolymers (not just CA) and hence requires urgent attention, otherwise those polymers will end up being used for energy generation or composting.
- Several ongoing or planned revisions to EU regulations, such as the Waste Framework Directive and the Single-Use Plastics Directive, threaten to restrict the space for CA even further. The ambition of these policies should be levelled with existing and upcoming research on biopolymers to ensure that materials, whose current use is associated with an undesirable application, are not eradicated from the market.

Examples of good practices

- Monitoring the policy and regulatory environment and facilitating research focusing on complying with sustainability requirements.
- Engagement of policy makers with experts from industry, laboratories, and academia to share knowledge and contribute to the development of feasible requirements.
- Engage in research projects that contribute to generating information for policymakers.
- Conduct research with partners that targets the development of compliant materials for markets that are currently not attainable.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges

- The transition towards a low carbon economy is very complex for chemical companies, with the probability that large investments are required. To make matters worse, in some instances, technologies may not even be available yet at the scale that is required to enable a sustainable transition of the industry.
- The absence of recycling processes (i.e., collection, sorting, etc.) and infrastructure specifically for biopolymers constrains the ‘circularity’ of materials. In the current system, the default options of composting or incineration with energy recovery are the most “sustainable” uses for end-of-life biopolymers, although not circular.
- A concerted effort of policymakers, companies and academia is required to enable the chemical industry to transition towards more sustainable operations. If the system

surrounding the industry changes at a pace that companies cannot keep up with, there is the risk of major disruptions in operations.

Examples of good practices

- Conduct efficiency-related studies (materials, energy, water, etc.) focusing on both existing assets as well as potentially new concepts.
- Conduct research into recycling techniques that can be applied to the materials that are sold (both virgin and intermediary). This is an enabling factor to increase material efficiency through recycling, reuse, or cascading uses.
- Engage with key customers in the endeavour to establish a collection and sorting scheme to bypass the absence of biopolymer recycling infrastructure.
- Assess the possibility to engage with the local municipality in joint sustainability initiatives and to explore options how 'externalities', such as excess heat, can be used to realise local or regional sustainability ambitions.

6.4.6 Key learnings of cellulose acetate case study

In summary, there is a fragmented picture when it comes to CA. The material has been around for more than 100 years and recent studies show its significant potential to contribute to addressing many of today's sustainability challenges. But it seems that, because of certain use cases, cellulose acetate has been cornered and excluded as alternative in many studies and policy papers. This skews the playing field towards less sustainable alternatives, whereby the field should be levelled towards all biopolymers and merits decide about applications.

The interaction of stakeholders in shaping the policy arena is a highly critical factor. EU legislators, their scientific advisors and powerful NGOs have the highest leverage on the potential that various materials can realise. The biggest challenge is the absence of a consistent set of definitions and classifications for biopolymers at EU level, including all biopolymers, not just the ones being advocated by NGOs and others. The strategy for a bio-circular economy can be a major enabler for biopolymers such as CA, however, the design of the strategy and policies used for implementation are the determining factor. Creating an enabling environment for all biopolymers requires a fair and balanced view on the merits and disadvantages of the materials that are serious contenders to be rivalling the fossil-based plastics sector. To establish this, all biopolymers, including CA, should be researched using the same test setups to allow for the comparability of results.

There is no real 'hindrance' when it comes to policy or stakeholders, just policy design that is driven with a specific purpose in mind, that may in some instances fall short on recognising bigger dynamics, and where in some instances ambiguity prevails. This makes it, however, even more important to assess how policies are designed and whether this design is fit for purpose. If there is an absence of a consistent definition and classifications in one framework that serves as reference for others, the same ambiguity will reproduce and compound throughout various policy

frameworks. This creates an environment of uncertainty and levels the field towards a few materials, which may not even be as fit for purpose for the envisaged policy goals as some of the materials that are falling through the cracks. Regulations such as SUPD are well-intentioned and aim to address the problem of littering, especially when it comes to plastic waste. The intention of SUPD is not misguided, but the way in which the directive defines "plastics" disadvantages a whole host of materials that could otherwise be a viable alternative for fossil-based materials. The same applies to the Microplastics directive. Here again, the right ambition is driving the process, however, without consideration of the timeframes of environmental persistence. While microplastics from fossil-based materials will take a very long time in the scale of centuries to degrade, microplastics from biopolymers may degrade within months or years, depending on the material used. Furthermore, a recent study of the Alfred Wegener Institute (Walther, Pasolini, Korez Lupše, & Bergmann, 2024) that examined polymer pollution on beaches using a randomised control trial (i.e., not only included beaches frequented by tourists) suggests that large parts of the polymer emissions found on beaches may not even be covered by SUPD. Around 60% of emissions were constituted by foil, foam, fibres, with an additional 35% of emissions being fragments of uncertain origin. This suggests that the efficacy check of SUPD also requires critically analysing methods for the determination of pollution, as the current setup may be biased through the sampling practices that are applied.

Important feedback to consider on the road ahead

There are several feedback loops affected by the dynamics outlined above. The strongest feedback is that feedback that drives the demand for a specific material. Once there are conditions in place that favour a specific material, this material will most likely be able to gain market share. The gain in market share of that specific material comes at the cost of market share for other (potentially sustainable) materials, which are themselves suffering a policy disadvantage, which disincentivises their production and marketing. Consequently, unless conditions change, it is economically not attractive to produce (or buy) those materials, given the policy regime that is in place. In the long run, this will lead to a few widely used materials, while many other materials remain niche or disappear from the market.

Policy disadvantage also translates into other benefits beyond market share, such as increased research into the specific material and potential applications, as well as potential certifications required for those applications. This in turn increases the uptake of that material relative to its counterparts, given (i) that there is a knowledge base of how the material can be used and what applications are possible, and (ii) that the material has already all the required certifications to be used for specific purposes, such as food or medical applications. This further strengthens the position of that material compared to its peers, consolidating a potential lock in into the new material.

It should be noted that, only because a material may be biobased, the material is not automatically more sustainable or degrades at a faster rate. Depending on the environmental persistence of the material favoured by policy, it is possible that we just replace one material against another one, just with a more sustainable label. Accumulation in the environment can

also occur with biobased materials, which have widely different times for biodegradation. For example, CA biodegrades faster across different environments when compared with alternative compounds, including to PLA (James, et al., 2024a; James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024a), whereby specific biodegradation rates depend on the type of material used. This is especially highlighted by the comparison specific surface degradation rates for different polymers presented by James et al. (James, et al., 2024a). The supplement to the study presents the surface degradation rates for PS foam (5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$), PP (3.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$), PET (16.7 $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$), Paper (176.6 $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$), PLA (1.4 $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$) and CDA foam (1,086 $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$) in a marine environment. These numbers suggest that, if we assume that CA foam is fully degraded after 1 year, the time for the same amounts of paper and PLA to degrade is 6.15 years and 775 years respectively, highlighting the potential for accumulation.

Urgent policy actions and research requirements to level the field for biopolymers

There are several urgent actions recommended to improve the standing of biopolymers, among which CA, in the current policy regime:

- 1) Review and revise current guidelines and standards used to judge the sustainability of biopolymers. Even some natural materials cannot comply with the current standards, rendering these standards and procedures overly ambitious, which creates unnecessary roadblocks for sustainable alternatives in terms of time to market and costs for testing (and research and development).
- 2) Develop a consistent set of definitions and classifications for biopolymers, based on the above. This is paramount, not only for assessing use cases for various materials, but also to enable and support their recycling. The latter is essential for enabling the “circular” part of the bio-circular economy, and both research and policy support are desperately required for this sector.
- 3) Establish a fair and objective database of biopolymers, with consistent definitions and classifications. This database shall inform future policymaking efforts, by providing detailed and comparable information about the different materials (biopolymers) and their derivatives.
- 4) Review and revise the SUPD, using the data established in 1) and the classification systems and definitions in 2), to ensure that the materials covered by SUPD are in fact “unsustainable”. As highlighted above, a methodology using a randomised approach for assessing environmental plastic emissions is required, as other methods (e.g., choosing areas frequented by tourists or humans) are likely biased and have the potential to shroud the real problem.

Research and data gaps

The main research gaps to be addressed to enable the urgent key actions are the following:

- 1) Assess the **interplay between various policy frameworks focusing on biopolymers and plastics** to better understand interrelationships and ensure that all policy frameworks are informed by the same objective facts (i.e., policy being science driven to prevent that science is policy-driven). Moreover, it is important to ensure that policy levels the playing

field towards multiple biobased materials, irrespective of their current usage. A visualisation of the interconnections between frameworks would be an excellent first step for building a more comprehensive understanding of policy interactions.

- 2) Research on **unilaterally agreed upon definitions of and classifications for biopolymers** is required. How should such definitions look like? What classifications make sense? These questions need to be answered under consideration of already existing frameworks and definitions, as well as industry input on testing requirements.
- 3) It is important to address the question about the **enabling factors to produce biobased raw materials**. Biobased raw materials, if produced sustainably, are the enabling factors to increase the sustainability of the whole supply chain. What conditions (and potentially incentives) are required to facilitate the establishment of biobased production clusters?
- 4) Research surrounding the **defossilisation of the chemical industry** is needed. A holistic project must not only account for the ambitions at country level, but also of the needs and abilities at industry level. Especially the transition towards H2 poses challenges, given that it is unclear whether technologies required for providing the same level of (utility) services will be available at the time of the shift.

Moreover, closing the following data gap would be beneficial to inform the transition towards a biobased circular economy:

- 1) Provide a database with objective facts about biopolymers and their properties. In the best case, this database is established using harmonised (and standardised) testing methodologies to ensure comparability of test results, and under consideration of inputs from academia, industry and NGOs. It should further contrast the data about biopolymers with the data for fossil-based materials to allow for an unbiased analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of using each material.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER STEPS IN WP3

This deliverable presents the results from the assessment of the 11 case studies selected in SUSTRACK, belonging to the four sectors that face critical challenges within the current fossil, linear economy: Construction, Textile, Chemical and Plastics. In D3.2, guidance was provided in terms of mapping of stakeholders and policies of relevance for case studies, and collection of information and data from literature and stakeholders. This was used as input in defining the step-wise case study assessment methodology followed in this report. In each assessment, an introductory section provides information on the value chain and the market context of the examined case study. Following that relevant stakeholders are identified and mapped in terms of their power and interest to drive change. This is followed by a mapping of relevant policies and describing in what ways they are stimulating or impeding the development of the examined system. Afterwards, an analysis of indicators is presented. The review of indicators of the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System that was carried out as part of a consistency check in D3.2, forms the foundation of this work. The indicators identified a most relevant were further elaborated on and refined as part of T3.3 case study assessment where the case study owners collected further data and information on their case studies through literature review and stakeholder engagement. Each case study assessment ends with a summary of the key learnings highlighting key challenges, recommended (policy) actions, and research needs. The case studies are shown to offer promising replacements of conventional, fossil-based counterparts, providing important solutions in the transition towards a circular bioeconomy. Yet, realising their full potential requires overcoming certain challenges and gaps as reported in the assessments.

The deliverable also presents sectorial and case-study specific insights collected from stakeholder engagements. This includes sectorial stakeholder workshops carried out as part of DESIGN conference as well as interviews carried out with targeted stakeholders. The findings were reported under three categories: Policy, Sustainability and Market. A common challenge identified in all sectors is insufficient regulatory support for biobased products hindering their market entry and growth. R&D support can foster innovation and accelerate the transition towards more sustainable biobased products. Lack of data on sustainability performance, especially regarding social indicators, was seen as a gap. Consistent assessment of biogenic carbon is important to ensure environmental benefits are accurately reflected. High perceived risk of novel biobased products makes it difficult to secure investment, limiting upscaling. One of the main challenges is the non-level playing field between mature and established fossil-based products and emerging biobased products, making them hard to compete in terms of price. Policy support instruments such as targets, premiums and carbon tax can create an enabling environment for biobased

products. Furthermore, policies supportive of a circular economy are called for to adopt effective recycling strategies and an after-use economy.

The outcomes from these case study assessments serve as input for other WPs, especially for WP4 for the analysis of each sector by means of the Green Economy Model and for WP5 for the identification of policy priorities, the definition of policy actions based on discussions on challenges and opportunities. As a follow up work, in T3.4 the findings from the case study assessments will be generalised to provide conclusions and recommendations for the four sectors. Outcomes from this work will be disseminated during the national DEPLOY conferences.

8 REFERENCES

The references are classified according to the four sectors central to the SUTRACK project, and the case studies belonging to these sectors.

CONSTRUCTION SECTOR

Cross laminated timber case study:

Ahn, N., Doodoo, A., Riggio, M., Muszynski, L., Schimleck, L., & Puettmann, M. (2022). Circular economy in mass timber construction: State-of-the-art, gaps and pressing research needs. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 53, 104562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2022.104562>.

Arto, I., Cazcarro, I., Garmendia, E., Ruiz, I., & Sanz, M. J. (2022). A new accounting framework for assessing forest footprint of nations. *Ecological Economics*, 194, 107337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107337>.

Atnoorkar, S., Ghatpande, O. A., Haile, S. L., Goetsch, H. E., & Harris, C. B. (2024). Carbon intensity of mass timber materials: impacts of sourcing and transportation. *Frontiers in Built Environment*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2023.1321340>.

Benneter, A., Forrester, D. I., Bouriaud, O., Dormann, C. F., & Bauhus, J. (2018). Tree species diversity does not compromise stem quality in major European forest types. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 422, 323-337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2018.04.030>.

Cesprini, E., Greco, R., Causin, V., Urso, T., Cavalli, R., & Zanetti, M. (2021). Quality assessment of pellets and briquettes made from glued wood waste. *European Journal of Wood and Wood Products*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00107-021-01695-1>.

Debitum Investments. (2023, September 29). *Eco-house building project - available - Debitum Investments*. Retrieved from: <https://debitum.investments/blog/eco-house-building-project-available/>.

Debnath, R., Bardhan, R., Shah, D., Koronaki, A., Bukauskas, A., Colman, A., Gatoo, A., Wiegand, E., Gin, Y., Ramage, M., Centre for Natural Material Innovation (CNMI), & Sustainable Design Group (SDG). (2021). Climate repair through built environment: Decarbonising UK's building sector

through energy efficiency and natural materials. In University of Cambridge, *University of Cambridge*. University of Cambridge.

Dupas, N., Hudert, M. M., & Aarhus University. (2024). *Enabling the circular use of Cross-Laminated Timber by upcycling production waste* (Philippe Block, Giulia Boller, Catherine DeWolf, Jacqueline Pauli, & Walter Kaufmann, Eds.). https://app.ias2024.org/files/IAS2024_Paper_198.pdf.

Duran, R. R., Muhr, L., & Barth, D. (2024). Extraction processes of high added value molecules from wood waste: overview and comparison of processes for an eco-friendly recovery from paper industry by-product. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 213, 118403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2024.118403>.

European Union. (2019). *EUR-LEX - 52019DC0640 - EN - EUR-LEX*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2019:640:FIN>.

European Union. (2023a). *Regulation - 2023/1115 - EN - EUR-LEX*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/1115/oj/eng>.

European Union. (2023b). *Directive - 2023/1791 - EN - EUR-LEX*. Retrieved from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AJOL_2023_231_R_0001&qid=1695186598766.

European Union. (2024). *Regulation - EU - 2024/3012 - EN - EUR-LEX*. Retrieved from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202403012.

European Parliament. (n.d.). *Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment | Legislative train schedule*. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-strategy-for-a-sustainable-built-environment>.

Fetting, C. (2020). *“The European Green Deal”*, ESDN Report, December 2020, ESDN Office, Vienna.

Guo, H., Liu, Y., Chang, W., Shao, Y., & Sun, C. (2017). Energy saving and carbon reduction in the operation stage of cross laminated timber residential buildings in China. *Sustainability*, 9, 2, 292. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9020292>.

Haisma, R., Den Boer, E., Rohmer, M., & Schouten, N. (2023). *IMPACT SCAN FOR TIMBER CONSTRUCTION IN EUROPE*.

Harris, C., Goetsch, H., & Atnoorkar, S. (2022). *Cross-Laminated Timber Workshop: Pathways and Priorities for Cross-Laminated Timber Building Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1868051>.

Mantau, U. & INFRO e.K. (2012). Wood flows in Europe (EU 27). In CEPI confederation of european Paper industries & CEI-Bois european confederation of Woodworking industries, *Project Report* (p. 24).

Nepal, P., Johnston, C. M. T., & Ganguly, I. (2021). Effects on global forests and wood product markets of increased demand for mass timber. *Sustainability*, 13(24), 13943. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132413943>.

Pierobon, F., Huang, M., Simonen, K., & Ganguly, I. (2019). Environmental benefits of using hybrid CLT structure in midrise non-residential construction: An LCA based comparative case study in the U.S. Pacific Northwest. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 26, 100862. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2019.100862>.

Sheppard, J. P., Chamberlain, J., Agúndez, D., Bhattacharya, P., Chirwa, P. W., Gontcharov, A., Sagona, W. C. J., Shen, H., Tadesse, W., & Mutke, S. (2020). Sustainable forest management beyond the Timber-Oriented status quo: Transitioning to co-production of timber and non-wood forest products—a global perspective. *Current Forestry Reports*, 6(1), 26-40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40725-019-00107-1>.

Shin, B., Chang, S. J., Wi, S., & Kim, S. (2023). Estimation of energy demand and greenhouse gas emission reduction effect of cross-laminated timber (CLT) hybrid wall using life cycle assessment for urban residential planning. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 185, 113604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113604>.

Tetty, U. Y. A., Dodoo, A., & Gustavsson, L. (2019). Effect of different frame materials on the primary energy use of a multi storey residential building in a life cycle perspective. *Energy and Buildings*, 185, 259-271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.12.017>.

UN Climate Change High-Level Champions, International Energy Agency (IEA), & International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). (2023). *The Breakthrough Agenda Report*. <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/d7e6b848-6e96-4c27-846e-07bd3aef5654/THEBREAKTHROUGHAGENDAREPORT2023.pdf>.

Vamza, I., Valters, K., Luksta, I., Resnais, P., & Blumberga, D. (2021a). Complete circularity in Cross-Laminated timber production. *Environmental and Climate Technologies*, 25, 1, 1101-1113. <https://doi.org/10.2478/rtuect-2021-0083>.

Younis, A., & Dodoo, A. (2022). Cross-laminated timber for building construction: A life-cycle-assessment overview. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 52, 104482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2022.104482>.

Biochar in concrete case study:

Bastos, A.C., Prodana, M., Abrantes, N. et al. (2014). Potential risk of biochar-amended soil to aquatic systems: an evaluation based on aquatic bioassays. *Ecotoxicology*, 23, 1784-1793. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10646-014-1344-1>.

Buss, W., Jansson, S., & Mašek, O. (2019). Unexplored potential of novel biochar-ash composites for use as organo-mineral fertilizers. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 208, 960-967.

CDR.fyi. (2024). *Trending on Track? - CDR.fyi 2023 Year in Review*. Retrieved on February 25, 2025, from <https://www.cdr.fyi/blog/2023-year-in-review>.

European Biochar Industry. (2024). *Market Report 2023/2024*. Retrieved from <https://www.biochar-industry.com/market-overview/>.

EC. (n.d.a). *Construction Products Regulation (CPR)*. Retrieved from https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/construction/construction-products-regulation-cpr_en.

EC. (n.d.b). *Land use sector*. Retrieved from https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/land-use-sector_en.

EC. (n.d.c). *Bioeconomy strategy*. Retrieved from https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/bioeconomy/bioeconomy-strategy_en.

EC. (n.d.d). *Energy Performance of Buildings Directive*. Retrieved from https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en.

EC. (n.d.e). *Industrial carbon management*. Retrieved from https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/carbon-management-and-fossil-fuels/industrial-carbon-management_en.

EC. (March 22, 2023). *Proposal for a Directive on Green Claims Details*. Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-directive-green-claims_en.

European Union. (2024). *Regulation - EU - 2024/3012 - EN - EUR-LEX*. Retrieved from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202403012.

International Energy Agency. (2018). *Technology Roadmap: Low-Carbon Transition in the Cement Industry*. Retrieved from <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/cbaa3da1-fd61-4c2a-8719-31538f59b54f/TechnologyRoadmapLowCarbonTransitionintheCementIndustry.pdf>.

Schmidt H-P, Hagemann N, Draper K, Kammann C. (2019). The use of biochar in animal feeding. *PeerJ*, 7, e7373. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.7373>.

Weber K., Quicker P. 2018. Properties of biochar. *Fuel*, 217, 240-261. ISSN 0016-2361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2017.12.054>.

Hemp insulation case study:

- Blandinières, H., & Amaducci, S. (2022). Adapting the cultivation of industrial hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) to marginal lands: A review. *GCB Bioenergy*, 14, 9, 1004-1022. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12979>
- Bócsa, I., & Karus, M. (1998). *The cultivation of hemp: Botany, Varieties, Cultivation and Harvesting*.
- BOU CHERIFI, F., TRANNOY, L., Nomadéis, DUTREIX, N., BAECHER, C., PIANU, B., MARX, I., & HABASQUE, M. (2017). Etude sur le secteur et les filières de production des matériaux et produits biosourcés utilisés dans la construction. *Nomadéis*, 2-97. Retrieved from https://www.pays-de-la-loire.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/0723_dgaln_-_etude_economique_biosources_vf.pdf.
- Boutin, M.-P., FLAMIN, C., QUINTON, S., GOSSE, G., & INRA, Lille. (2006). *ETUDE DES CARACTERISTIQUES ENVIRONNEMENTALES DU CHANVRE PAR L'ANALYSE DE SON CYCLE DE VIE*. Retrieved from https://www.interchanvre.org/documents/5.actu_presse/documents_de_reference/2006_ACV%20chanvre.pdf.
- Cardellini, G., & Mijndendonckx, J. (2022). *Synergies, energy efficiency and circularity in the renovation wave*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6530825>.
- Crini, G., Lichtfouse, E., Chanet, G., & Morin-Crini, N. (2020). Applications of hemp in textiles, paper industry, insulation and building materials, horticulture, animal nutrition, food and beverages, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and hygiene, medicine, agrochemistry, energy production and environment: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 18, 5, 1451-1476. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-020-01029-2>.
- Davis, K. (n.d.). *Life cycle assessment of a hemp-based thermal insulation panel*. Western CEDAR. Retrieved from <https://cedar.wvu.edu/wwuet/1295>.
- EC. (2024). *Hemp*. Agriculture and Rural Development. Retrieved on December 2, 2024, from [https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/crop-productions-and-plant-based-products/hemp_en#:~:text=Hemp%20production%20in%20the%20EU,-Hemp%20is%20a&text=In%20the%20same%20period%2C%20the,and%20The%20Netherlands%20\(5%25\)](https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/crop-productions-and-plant-based-products/hemp_en#:~:text=Hemp%20production%20in%20the%20EU,-Hemp%20is%20a&text=In%20the%20same%20period%2C%20the,and%20The%20Netherlands%20(5%25)).
- EEA. (2007). Estimating the environmentally compatible bioenergy potential from agriculture. *EEA Technical Report*. <https://doi.org/10.2800/13734>.
- EERE. (2023, April 19). *EERE Success Story—HEMP for home Insulation by hempitecture*. Energy.gov. Retrieved from <https://www.energy.gov/eere/articles/eere-success-story-hemp-home-insulation-hempitecture>.

Eurostat. (2025). *Crop production in EU standard humidity* [Dataset]. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/APRO_CPSH1_custom_5830898/default/table?lang=en.

Guo, Y., Wen, L., Zhao, X., Xing, C., & Huang, R. (2024). Industrial hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) can utilize and remediate soil strongly contaminated with Cu, As, Cd, and Pb by phytoattenuation. *Chemosphere*, 358, 142199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2024.142199>.

Gutierrez-Moscardo, O., Canet, M., Gomez-Caturla, J., Lascano, D., Fages, E., & Sanchez-Nacher, L. (2021). Sustainable materials with high insulation capacity obtained from wastes from hemp industry processed by wet-laid. *Textile Research Journal*, 92, 7-8, 1098-1112. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00405175211046058>.

Hult, M., & Karlsmo, S. (2022). Life Cycle Environmental and Cost Analysis of Building Insulated with Hemp Fibre Compared to Alternative Conventional Insulations - a Swedish Case Study. *Journal of Sustainable Architecture and Civil Engineering*, 30, 1, 106-120. <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.sace.30.1.30357>.

Ingrao, C., Lo Giudice, A., Bacenetti, J., Tricase, C., Dotelli, G., Fiala, M., Siracusa, V., Mbohwa, C., Department of Economics, University of Foggia, Department of Quality and Operations Management, Faculty of Engineering and the Built Environment, University of Johannesburg, Department of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences, Production, Landscape, Agroenergy, University of Milan, Department of Chemistry, Materials and Chemical Engineering "G.Natta", Politecnico di Milano, INSTM RU-POLIMI, & Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Catania. (2015). Energy and environmental assessment of industrial hemp for building applications: A review. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 51, 29-42. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.06.002>.

Ip, K., & Miller, A. (2012). Life cycle greenhouse gas emissions of hemp-lime wall constructions in the UK. *Resources Conservation and Recycling*, 69, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2012.09.001>.

Kallakas, H., Närep, M., Närep, A., Poltimäe, T., & Kers, J. (2018). Mechanical and physical properties of industrial hemp-based insulation materials. *Proceedings of the Estonian Academy of Sciences*, 67, 2, 183. <https://doi.org/10.3176/proc.2018.2.10>.

KOBE-cz s.r.o. (2020). *Environmental Product Declaration for KOBE-CZ HEMP FIBRE INSULATION*.

Liu, C. H. J., Pomponi, F., & D'Amico, B. (2023). The extent to which hemp insulation materials can be used in Canadian residential buildings. *Sustainability*, 15, 19, 14471. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151914471>.

Lu, Z., Hauschild, M., Ottosen, L. M., Ambaye, T. G., DTU Sustain, Department of Environmental and Resource Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs Lyngby, Denmark, Zerbino, P., Aloini, D., & Department of Energy, Systems, Territory and Construction Engineering, University

of Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56122, Pisa, Italy. (2024). Climate mitigation potential of biobased insulation materials: A comprehensive review and categorization. In *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 470, 143356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.143356>.

Muhit, I. B., Omairey, E. L., & Pashakolaie, V. G. (2024). A holistic sustainability overview of hemp as building and highway construction materials. *Building and Environment*, 256, 111470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111470>.

Pavel, C., & Blagoeva, D. (2018). Competitive landscape of the EU's insulation materials industry for energy-efficient buildings. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://doi.org/10.2760/750646>.

Piotrowski, S., Zukunftsagentur Rheinisches Revier GmbH, Carus, M., & nova-Institut. (2011). Ecological benefits of hemp and flax cultivation and products. *nova-Institute*, 1-4. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267766816>.

Rabbat, C., Awad, S., Villot, A., Rollet, D., & Andrès, Y. (2021). Sustainability of biomass-based insulation materials in buildings: Current status in France, end-of-life projections and energy recovery potentials. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 156, 111962. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111962>.

Rehman, M., Fahad, S., Du, G., Cheng, X., Yang, Y., Tang, K., Liu, L., Liu, F., & Deng, G. (2021). Evaluation of hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) as an industrial crop: a review. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(38), 52832-52843. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-16264-5>.

Scrucca, F., Ingrao, C., Maalouf, C., Moussa, T., Polidori, G., Messineo, A., Arcidiacono, C., & Asdrubali, F. (2020). Energy and carbon footprint assessment of production of hemp hurds for application in buildings. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 84, 106417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2020.106417>.

Sieracka, D., Frankowski, J., Wacławek, S., & Czekąła, W. (2023). Hemp biomass as a raw material for sustainable development. *Applied Sciences*, 13, 17, 9733. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13179733>.

Statica. (2023, September 28). *Hemp cultivation: surface area by country in Europe 2020* | Statista. Statista. Retrieved from [https://www.statista.com/statistics/1204146/area-for-hemp-cultivation-by-country-europe/#:~:text=With%2020%2C000%20hectares%20\(approximately%2049%2C421.08,step%20of%20the%20European%20podium](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1204146/area-for-hemp-cultivation-by-country-europe/#:~:text=With%2020%2C000%20hectares%20(approximately%2049%2C421.08,step%20of%20the%20European%20podium).

Vrins, M., NEN, TUB, WFBR, & nova. (2018). Report on implementation for creation of new or revised standards. In *Standards and Regulations for the Bio-based Industry*.

Zampori, L., Dotelli, G., & Vernelli, V. (2013). Life cycle assessment of hemp cultivation and use of Hemp-Based thermal Insulator materials in buildings. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 47, 13, 7413-7420. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es401326a>.

TEXTILE SECTOR

Recycled carded wool Prato case study:

Bamonti, S., Spinelli, R., & Bonoli, A. (2016). Environmental footprint in the production of recycled wool. *Environmental Engineering & Management Journal (EEMJ)*, 15, 9.

BioMonitor. (2019). *Data and data gaps for bioeconomy drivers and indicators and their implications* BioMonitor Project. Retrieved from: https://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/BioMonitor_D2.1_-proofread.pdf.

Borsacchi, L., Barberis, V., & Pinelli, P. (2018). *Circular economy and industrial symbiosis: The role of the municipality of Prato within the EU Urban Agenda partnership*. In *Proceedings of the 24th International Sustainable Development Research Society Conference (ISDRS 2018)*, Messina, Italy, 13-15.

Bussolo, G.H., Bressanelli, G., Visintin, F., Sacconi, N. (2025). Italy. In: Wynn, M., Wiegand, T. (eds) *Sustainability, the Circular Economy and Digitalisation in the European Textile and Clothing Industry*. *SDGs and Textiles*. Springer, Singapore.

Camilleri, M. A. (2018). Closing the loop for resource efficiency, sustainable consumption and production: A critical review of the circular economy. *International Journal of Sustainable Development*, 21, 1-4, 1-17.

Circular Economy EU. (2021). *Circular City Governance: Prato as a Model for the Circular Economy*. Report. Retrieved from <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu>.

Confindustria Toscana Nord. (2024). *Annual Report on the Prato Textile Industry*. Retrieved from https://www.confindustriatoscananord.it/media/UFFICIO_STUDI/2024_N_51_PAPER_CS_CTN_CO_NGIUNTURA_II_2024_def.pdf.

Consorzio Detox. (2021). *Il sistema di riciclaggio delle acque reflue nel Distretto tessile di Prato*. Retrieved from <https://consorziodetox.it/index.php/2021/01/19/il-sistema-di-riciclaggio-delle-acque-reflue-nel-distretto-tessile-di-prato/>.

Corertex. (2023). *Gestione dei rifiuti tessili e economia circolare a Prato*. Retrieved from <https://corertex.it/>.

ERIM. (2006). *The Recent Transformation of the Prato Industrial District: Policies for Local Development*. Report. Retrieved from <https://www.erim.eur.nl>.

- Fladrich, A. (2012). Chinese SMEs in Prato, Italy. *Chinese international investments*, 234-256. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations. (FAO). (2018). *ASSESSING THE CONTRIBUTION OF BIOECONOMY TO COUNTRIES' ECONOMY* FAO. Retrieved from <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/31f2ed11-64ea-4d16-a8f8-a1323e1f31dd/content>.
- Hall, C. (2018). MIXING IT UP IN PRATO: identifying innovation hotspots within mechanical textile recycling. *What's Going On*, 1-19.
- Harsanto, B., Primiana, I., Sarasi, V., & Satyakti, Y. (2023). Sustainability Innovation in the Textile Industry: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 15, 2, 1549.
- Jiang, Z., Yu, C., Yang, J., Han, G., & Xing, M. (2019). Estimation of yarn strength based on critical slipping length and fiber length distribution. *Textile Research Journal*, 89, 2, 182-194.
- Kalyazina, S., Borremans, A., & Dubgorn, A. (2018). Participation of citizens in sustainable development of big cities. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 193, 01029. EDP Sciences.
- Köhler A., Watson D., Trzepacz S., Löw C., Liu R., Danneck J., Konstantas A., Donatello S. & Faraca G., 2021. Circular Economy Perspectives in the EU Textile sector, EUR 30734 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2021, ISBN 978- 92-76-38646-9, doi:10.2760/858144, JRC125110.
- Lewis, T. L., Park, H., Netravali, A. N., & Trejo, H. X. (2017). Closing the loop: A scalable zero-waste model for apparel reuse and recycling. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education*, 10, 3, 353-362.
- Next Generation Prato. (2023). *Project Proposal for the Textile Hub*. Retrieved from <https://www.pratocircularcity.it/it/next-generation-prato/documento-strategico/pagina1942.html>.
- Ottati, G. D. (1996). Economic changes in the district of Prato in the 1980s: Towards a more conscious and organized industrial district. *European Planning Studies*, 4, 1, 35-52.
- Ottati, G. D. (2009). An industrial district facing the challenges of globalization: Prato today. *European Planning Studies*, 17, 12, 1817-1835.
- Patten, L. A. (2019). Insight into Emerging Opportunities for Sustainable-Led Strategies in Textiles. *Journal of Textile Science & Fashion Technology*, 4, 1. JTSFT.MS.ID.000576.
- Piscitello, L., & Sgobbi, F. (2004). Globalisation, e-business and SMEs: evidence from the Italian district of Prato. *Small Business Economics*, 22, 333-347.

Russell S., Swan P., Trebowicz M., Ireland A. (2016) Review of Wool Recycling and Reuse. In: Fangueiro R., Rana S. (eds) *Natural Fibres: Advances in Science and Technology Towards Industrial Applications*. RILEM Bookseries, vol 12. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-7515-1_33.

Salvioni, D. M., & Almici, A. (2020). Transitioning toward a circular economy: The impact of stakeholder engagement on sustainability culture. *Sustainability*, 12, 20, 8641.

Saxena, S., Raja, A. S. M., & Arputharaj, A. (2017). *Challenges in sustainable wet processing of textiles. Textiles and clothing sustainability: sustainable textile chemical processes*, 43-79.

Shabbir & Mohammad (2017). 7 - Sustainable production of regenerated cellulosic fibres. *Sustainable Fibres and Textiles. The Textile Institute Book Series 2017*, 171-189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102041-8.00007-X>.

Schiros, T., Lu, H H., Zhu, Y., Bina, T., Gomez, V., Lee, C L., Lu, H H., & Obermeyer, A C. (2021, November 1). Bioengineering textiles across scales for a sustainable circular economy. *Elsevier BV*, 7, 11, 2913-2926.

Shishoo, R. (2012). Introduction: trends in the global textile industry. *The global textile and clothing industry*, 1-7. Woodhead Publishing.

Testa, F., Nucci, B., Iraldo, F., Appolloni, A., & Daddi, T. (2017). Removing obstacles to the implementation of LCA among SMEs: A collective strategy for exploiting recycled wool. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 156, 923-931.

Tuci, F., Allocca, M., Fibbi, D., Daddi, D., & Gori, R. (2025). Membrane treatment to improve water recycling in an Italian Textile District. *Water*, 17, 1, 123-139. Retrieved from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11767956/>.

Vagnoni, E., Carrino, C., Dibenedetto, N., Pieragostini, E., & Consenti, B. (2016). The enhancement of native sheep's wool: Three case studies from some Italian regions. *Small ruminant research*, 135, 85-89.

Venkatesan, H., & Periyasamy, A. P. (2019). Eco-fibers in the textile industry. *Handbook of ecomaterials*, 3, 1413-1433.

Man-made cellulosic fibres case study:

Allied Market Research. (2022). *Lyocell Fibers Market Size, Share, Competitive Landscape and Trend Analysis Report, by Type, by Application: Global Opportunity Analysis and Industry Forecast, 2022-2031*. Report code A31029. Retrieved from [Lyocell Fibers Market Trend, Share and Industry Forecast 2031](#).

- Canopy. (2024). *Hot Button report*. Retrieved from [1735923692-hot-button-full-grid-2024.pdf](#).
- EC. (1994). *COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 94/33/EC of 22 June 1994 on the protection of young people at work*. Retrieved from [eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31994L0033](#).
- EC. (2018). *A sustainable Bioeconomy for Europe Strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment Updated Bioeconomy Strategy*. ISBN 978-92-79-94145-0 doi: 10.2777/478385.
- EC. (2021). *Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a stronger Single Market for Europe's recovery*. (SDW(2021) 351 final) (SDW(2021) 352 final) (SDW(2021) 353 final).
- EC. (2022). *EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles*. Brussels, 30.3.2022 COM(2022) 141 final. Retrieved from [74126c90-5cbf-46d0-ab6b-60878644b395_en \(europa.eu\)](#).
- EC. (2022). *Sustainable and circular Textiles 2030*. 30 March 2022 #EUGreenddeal. Retrieved from [Textiles Factsheet.pdf](#).
- EC-JRC. (2025). *Bio-based textiles in a sustainable and circular bioeconomy*. Joint Research Centre (JRC) prepared for the European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy. JRC140676.
- EEA. (2022). *Textiles and the environment: the role of design in Europe's circular economy*. EEA briefing. Retrieved from [Textiles and the environment: the role of design in Europe's circular economy – European Environment Agency](#).
- Felgueiras, C., Azoia, N. G., Gonçalves, C., Gama, M., & Dourado, F. (2021). Trends on the cellulose-based textiles: raw materials and technologies. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 9, 608826.
- Harmsen, P., Post, W., & Bos, H. (2022). *Textiles for circular fashion*. Part 2, From renewable carbon to fibres. Wageningen Food & Biobased Research. Materials Market Report 2023 - Textile Exchange.
- Hugill, R., Ley, K., & Rademan, K. (2020). Coming full circle: innovating towards sustainable man-made cellulosic fibres. *Fash Good*, 1-33.
- Shabbir & Mohammad. (2017). 7 - Sustainable production of regenerated cellulosic fibres. *Sustainable Fibres and Textiles. The Textile Institute Book Series 2017*, 171-189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102041-8.00007-X>.
- Shen, L., Worrell, E., & Patel, M. K. (2010). Environmental impact assessment of man-made cellulose fibres. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 55, 2, 260-274.
- Textile Exchange. (2024). *Materials Market Report 2024*. Retrieved from [Materials-Market-Report-2024.pdf](#).

Venkatesan, H., & Periyasamy, A. P. (2019). Eco-fibers in the textile industry. *Handbook of ecomaterials*, 3, 1413-1433.

ZDHC. (2023). ZDHC Man-made Cellulosic Fibre (MMCF) Guidelines. Version 2.2. August 2023. Retrieved from [mmcf-guidelines](#).

Website links:

CO2 Everything: [Cotton Carbon Footprint | 8.3kg CO2e](#)

Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water work - Consulted November 2024 - [Overheid.nl | Consultatie Concept beleidsprogramma circulair textiel 2025-2030 \(internetconsultatie.nl\)](#)

[Lyocell Fiber Market Share, Growth Analysis & Forecast | SkyQuest Technology](#)
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chempr.2021.10.012>

<https://www.lenzing.com/sustainability/production/resources/water>

Lenzing: [Evaluations](#) (visited November 2024)

Lenzing - Climate partner ID:

[lenzing.com/?type=88245&tx_filedownloads_file%5BfileName%5D=fileadmin/content/PDF/01_Medien/Presseausendungen/EN/PA_2025_01_14_EN_LENZING_TM_Lyocell_Fill_expands_portfolio.pdf](https://www.lenzing.com/?type=88245&tx_filedownloads_file%5BfileName%5D=fileadmin/content/PDF/01_Medien/Presseausendungen/EN/PA_2025_01_14_EN_LENZING_TM_Lyocell_Fill_expands_portfolio.pdf)

[Our fiber - TreeToTextile. Tree to textiles and Lenzing join forces for next generation cellulose fibres. October 2024](#)

Spinnova: [Spinnova. Cleanest process. Disruptive circularity. | Spinnova](#)

Tencel: [Sustainability | TENCEL™ Responsible Fiber Production](#)

Yarnsandfibres.com - [Where is lyocell produced in the world? - YnFx](#)

[74126c90-5cbf-46d0-ab6b-60878644b395_en \(europa.eu\)](#)

Laxta sheep wool case study:

EC. (2022). *Textiles strategy*. Retrieved from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/textiles-strategy_en.

EC. (2024). *Ecodesign for sustainable products regulation*. Retrieved from: https://commission.europa.eu/energy-climate-change-environment/standards-tools-and-labels/products-labelling-rules-and-requirements/ecodesign-sustainable-products-regulation_en.

European Union. (September 27, 2011). *Regulation (EU) No 1007/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 September 2011 on textile fibre names and related labelling and marking of the fibre composition of textile products and repealing Council Directive 73/44/EEC and Directives 96/73/EC and 2008/121/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council Text with EEA relevance*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2011/1007/oj/eng>.

European Union. (November 27, 2020). *European Commission Decision (EU) 2020/1805 of 27 November 2020 amending Decisions 2014/350/EU and (EU) 2016/1349 extending the period of validity of the ecological criteria for the award of the EU Ecolabel to textile products and footwear and of the related assessment and verification requirements (notified under document C(2020))*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/2020/1805/oj/eng>.

Gobierno vasco. (2021). *Plan de economía y bioeconomía*. Retrieved from: [Economía-Circular-y-Bioeconomia-WEB.pdf \(euskadi.eus\)](#).

Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico (MITECO). (2020). *España Circular 2030*. Retrieved from: [espanacircular2030_def1_tcm30-509532_mod_tcm30-509532.pdf](#).

ORIENTING project. (n.d.). *Home*. Retrieved from: [Provisional - Orienting](#).

UN Environmental Programme (UNEP). (2019). *Textile Initiative*. Retrieved from: [The One UNEP Textile Initiative | UNEP - UN Environment Programme](#).

CHEMICAL SECTOR:

Waste-to-methanol case study:

Abis, M., Bruno, M., Kuchta, K., Simon, F. G., Grönholm, R., Hoppe, M., & Fiore, S. (2020). Assessment of the synergy between recycling and thermal treatments in municipal solid waste management in Europe. *Energies*, 13, 23, 6412.

Adlhoch, W., Sato, H., Wolff, J., & Radtke, K. (2000, October). High-temperature Winkler gasification of municipal solid waste. *In Gasification Technologies Conference*, 8, 11.

Afzal, S., Singh, A., Nicholson, S. R., Uekert, T., DesVeaux, J. S., Tan, E. C., & Beckham, G. T. (2023). Techno-economic analysis and life cycle assessment of mixed plastic waste gasification for production of methanol and hydrogen. *Green Chemistry*, 25, 13, 5068-5085.

De Leeuw, M., & Koelemeijer, R. (2022, July). Decarbonisation options for the Dutch waste incineration industry. Retrieved from [Decarbonisation options for the Dutch waste incineration industry \(pbl.nl\)](#).

Dianda, P., & Munawar, E. (2018, March). Production and characterization refuse derived fuel (RDF) from high organic and moisture contents of municipal solid waste (MSW). *In IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 334, 1, 012035. IOP Publishing.

DOPS RT. (n.d.). The Technology. Retrieved on January 7, 2025, from [The Technology - DOPS](#).

Dutch Enterprise Agency. (December 8, 2023). *DEI+: Vergassing van reststromen*. Retrieved on January, 2024, from [DEI+: Vergassing van reststromen \(rvo.nl\)](#).

Dutch Government. (n.d.). *Omslag naar de circulaire economie versnellen*. Retrieved on January 30, 2024, from [Omslag naar circulaire economie versnellen | Circulaire economie | Rijksoverheid.nl](#).

EC. (1999). *Landfill Directive. Council Directive 1999/31/EC of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste*. Retrieved from <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/1999/31/oj>.

EC. (2008). *Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives*. Retrieved from <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2008/98/2018-07-05>.

EC. (2020). *Circular Economy Action Plan. COM/2020/98 final. Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions. A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe*. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>.

EC. (2020). *Chemicals Strategy. COM/2020/667 final. Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions. Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A667%3AFIN>.

EC. (2021). *Zero Pollution Action Plan COM/2021/400 final. Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions. Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil'*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0400&qid=1623311742827>.

EC. (2023). *Renewable Energy Directive - RED III, EU/2023/2413. Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32023L2413&qid=1699364355105>.

Enerkem. (2014). *Enerkem proud to be part of Canada's \$11 billion clean technology industry, 2014 Canadian Clean Technology Report*. Retrieved on January 7, 2025, from <https://enerkem.com/newsroom/enerkem-proud-to-be-part-of-canadas-11-billion-clean-technology-industry>

EU Monitor. (November 15, 2023). *Waste management in the EU: infographic with facts and figures*. Retrieved on January 7, 2025, from [Waste management in the EU: infographic with facts and figures - EU monitor](#).

European Council. (December 13, 2023). *Fit for 55*. Retrieved on January 29, 2024, from [Fit for 55 - The EU's plan for a green transition - Consilium \(europa.eu\)](#).

Expert Market Research. (2023). *Europe Methanol Market Size, Share, Report and Forecast 2023-2028*. Retrieved on July 13, 2023, from [Europe Methanol Market Size, Growth, Share, Report 2024-2032 \(expertmarketresearch.com\)](#).

GIDARA Energy. (n.d.). *HTW® Gasification*. Retrieved on January 7, 2025, from [HTW® Gasification - GIDARA Energy](#).

Hakandai, C., Pramono, H. S., & Aziz, M. (2022). Conversion of municipal solid waste to hydrogen and its storage to methanol. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 51, 101968.

Iaquaniello, G., Centi, G., Salladini, A., Palo, E., Perathoner, S., & Spadaccini, L. (2017). Waste-to-methanol: Process and economics assessment. *Bioresource technology*, 243, 611-619.

IRENA & METHANOL INSTITUTE. (2021). *Innovation Outlook: Renewable Methanol*, International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi. Retrieved from [Innovation Outlook: Renewable Methanol](#).

ISCC. (2023, September 1). *ISCC PLUS. Version 3.4*. Retrieved from [ISCC PLUS \(iscc-system.org\)](#).

ISCC. (2016, August 24). *Press release from Enerkem on the world's first ISCC certification of their plant in Edmonton (Canada) to convert municipal solid waste into biomethanol*. Retrieved on January 29, 2024, from [Press release from Enerkem on the world's first ISCC certification of their plant in Edmonton \(Canada\) to convert municipal solid waste into biomethanol - ISCC System \(iscc-system.org\)](#).

Lee, R. P., Seidl, L. G., Huang, Q. L., & Meyer, B. (2021). An analysis of waste gasification and its contribution to China's transition towards carbon neutrality and zero waste cities. *Journal of Fuel Chemistry and Technology*, 49, 8, 1057-1076.

METHANOL INSTITUTE. (2022). *Carbon footprint of methanol*. Retrieved from [CARBON-FOOTPRINT-OF-METHANOL-PAPER_1-31-22.pdf](#).

Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management. (January 24, 2017). *Grondstoffenakkoord. Intentieovereenkomst om te komen tot transitieagenda's voor de Circulaire Economie*. Retrieved from [pdf \(overheid.nl\)](#).

Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management. (October 16th, 2020). *Duurzaamheidskader biograndstoffen*. Retrieved from [pdf \(overheid.nl\)](#).

Offshore Energy. (May 9, 2024). *Gidara Energy gets green light for methanol plant in port of Amsterdam*. Retrieved on September 12, 2024, from <https://www.offshore-energy.biz/gidara-energy-gets-green-light-for-methanol-plant-in-port-of-amsterdam/>.

REPSOL. (n.d.). *Ecoplanta: A project for non-recyclable municipal waste recovery*. Retrieved on January 7, 2025, from [Ecoplanta, Spain's first circular methanol facility](#).

Research Dive. (2021, November 22nd). *Global Methanol Market Envisioned to Generate a Revenue of \$24,000.0 Million and Grow at a CAGR of 6.4% During the Forecast Period from 2021-2028*. Retrieved on July 13th, 2023, from [Global Methanol Market Envisioned to Generate a Revenue of \(globenewswire.com\)](#).

Road2Bio, Vom Berg C. (2018). *Deliverable 2.1: Roadmap for the Chemical Industry in Europe towards a Bioeconomy*.

Sarp, S., Hernandez, S. G., Chen, C., & Sheehan, S. W. (2021). Alcohol production from carbon dioxide: methanol as a fuel and chemical feedstock. *Joule*, 5, 1, 59-76.

Silvarrey, L. D., & Phan, A. N. (2016). Kinetic study of municipal plastic waste. *International journal of hydrogen energy*, 41, 37, 16352-16364.

Statista. (January 2023). *Distribution of municipal waste treatment in the European Union (EU-27) in 2021, by method*. Retrieved on July 20, 2023, from [EU-27: waste treatment shares by method | Statista](#).

Stylianou, E., Pateraki, C., Ladakis, D., Cruz-Fernández, M., Latorre-Sánchez, M., Coll, C., & Koutinas, A. (2020). Evaluation of organic fractions of municipal solid waste as renewable feedstock for succinic acid production. *Biotechnology for biofuels*, 13, 1-16.

Bio-MEG case study:

Avantium. (n.d. a). *About Ray Technology - A Bright Step to the Future, Amsterdam*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://avantium.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/20191107-Press-kit-Avantium-celebrates-the-opening-of-MEG-demonstration-plant-final.pdf>.

Avantium. (n.d. b). *PlantMEG & PlantMPG*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://avantium.com/products-technologies/plantmeg-plantmpg/>.

Awaja, F., & Pavel, D. (2005). Recycling of PET. *European polymer journal*, 41, 7, 1453-1477.

Bioenergy International. (n.d.). *About us*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://bioenergyinternational.com/about-us/>.

BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE. (n.d.). *Sustainable solutions for bio-based plastics on land and sea*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://bioplasticseurope.eu/>.

Braskem. (2023). *Braskem and SCG Chemicals join forces to advance in the bio-based Ethylene project in Thailand*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.braskem.com.br/usa/news-detail/braskem-and-scg-chemicals-join-forces-to-advance-in-the-bio-based-ethylene-project-in-thailand>.

Bronsema, V., Lewandowski, I., Thrän, D. & Wolperdinger, M. (2022). *Hintergrundpapier Industrielle Bioraffinieren, BioÖkonomieRat*. Retrieved from <https://www.biooekonomierat.de/media/pdf/hintergrundpapiere/boer-hintergrundpapier-industrielle-bioraffinerien.pdf?m=1693295807&>.

Bundesministerium der Justiz. (n.d.). *Gesetz über die Durchführung von Maßnahmen des Arbeitsschutzes zur Verbesserung der Sicherheit und des Gesundheitsschutzes der Beschäftigten bei der Arbeit*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/arbschg/>.

CEFIC. (n.d.). *Restoring sustainable carbon cycles: the chemical industry as a solution provider*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://cefic.org/policy-matters/restoring-sustainable-carbon-cycles-the-chemical-industry-as-a-solution-provider/>.

Coca-Cola Europe. (2024). *Coca-Cola collaborates with partners to create bottle prototype made from 100% plant-based sources*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.coca-cola.com/eu/en/media-center/bottle-prototype-made-from-plant-based-sources>.

COWI A/S & Utrecht University. (2018). *Environmental impact assessment of innovative bio-based product Task 1 of “Study on Support to R&I Policy in the Area of Bio-based Products and Services”*.

De Jong, E., Stichnothe, H., Bell, G. & Jørgensen, H. (2020). *Bio-Based Chemicals A 2020 Update, IEA Bioenergy*.

Elvers, B. (1991). *Ullmann's encyclopedia of industrial chemistry* (Vol. 17, pp. 363-376). Hoboken, NJ: Verlag Chemie.

European Bioplastics. (2024a). *Bioplastics Market Development Update 2024*, Berlin.

European Bioplastics. (2024b). *End-of-life options for bioplastic products*, Berlin.

European Bioplastics. (n.d.). *European Bioplastics represents the interests of the bioplastics industry and is committed to building and strengthening a supportive policy environment in the EU for biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics to thrive*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/>.

European Chemicals Agency. (n.d.). *Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://echa.europa.eu/hot-topics/chemicals-strategy-for-sustainability>.

EC. (2018). *A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy*, Brussels.

EC. (2020). *A new Circular Economy Action Plan*, Brussels.

EC. (2021). *Annual Single Market Report 2021*, Brussels.

EC. (2022). *EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics*, Brussels.

EC. (n.d.a). *Ecodesign for Sustainable Products and Regulation*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from https://commission.europa.eu/energy-climate-change-environment/standards-tools-and-labels/products-labelling-rules-and-requirements/ecodesign-sustainable-products-regulation_en.

EC. (n.d.b). *Horizon Europe*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en.

EC. (n.d.c). *Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive (IED 2.0)*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/industrial-emissions-and-safety/industrial-and-livestock-rearing-emissions-directive-ied-20_en.

EC. (n.d.d). *Waste Framework Directive*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/waste-framework-directive_en.

EC. (n.d.e). *Implementation of the Transparency Regulation*. Retrieved on February 24, 2025, from https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/general-food-law/implementation-transparency-regulation_en.

European Council (n.d.). *Fit for 55*. Retrieved on February 5, 2025, from <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/fit-for-55/>.

Fabbri, S., Owsianiak, M., & Hauschild, M. Z. (2022). Evaluation of sugar feedstocks for bio-based chemicals: A consequential, regionalized life cycle assessment. *Global Change Biology Bioenergy*, 14, 5, 540-555. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.13009>.

FKUR (n.d.). *Eastlon*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://fkur.com/en/bioplastics/eastlon/>.

Francois, J.M., Alkim, C. & Morin, N (2020). Engineering microbial pathways for production of bio-based chemicals from lignocellulosic sugars: current status and perspectives. *Biotechnol Biofuels*, 13, 118. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13068-020-01744-6>.

Fraunhofer UMSICHT. (n.d.). *Circular Economy*. Retrieved on January 22, 2025, from <https://www.umsicht.fraunhofer.de/de/circulareconomy.html>.

Global Chemical Transparency. (n.d.). *Global Chemical Transparency Initiative*. Retrieved on February 24, 2025, from <https://www.globalchemicaltransparency.org/>.

Gursel, I. V., Moretti, C., Hamelin, L., Jakobsen, L. G., Steingrimsdottir, M. M., Junginger, M., ... & Shen, L. (2021). Comparative cradle-to-grave life cycle assessment of bio-based and petrochemical PET bottles. *Science of The Total Environment*, 793, 148642.

Hwang, K. R., Jeon, W., Lee, S. Y., Kim, M. S., & Park, Y. K. (2020). Sustainable bioplastics: Recent progress in the production of bio-building blocks for the bio-based next-generation polymer PEF. *Chemical engineering journal*, 390, 124636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.124636>.

ISCC (n.d.). *ISCC PLUS Certification*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.iscc-system.org/certification/iscc-certification-schemes/iscc-plus/>.

Islam, M., Hadadi, N., Ataman, M., Hatzimanikatis, V., & Stephanopoulos, G. (2017). Exploring biochemical pathways for mono-ethylene glycol (MEG) synthesis from synthesis gas. *Metabolic engineering*, 41, 173-181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymben.2017.04.005>.

Kawabe, K. (2010). Development of Highly Selective Process for Mono-Ethylene Glycol Production from Ethylene Oxide via Ethylene Carbonate Using Phosphonium Salt Catalyst. *Catalysis Surveys from Asia*, 14, 111-115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10563-010-9094-4>.

Lindorfer, J., Fazeni, K., & Steinmüller, H. (2014). Life cycle analysis and soil organic carbon balance as methods for assessing the ecological sustainability of 2nd generation biofuel feedstock. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 5, 95-105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SETA.2013.12.003>.

Luo, N., Ji, Y., Mao, Y., & Zhang, B. (2012). Syn-gas-based mono ethylene glycol synthesis in Pujing Chemical. *Applied Petrochemical Research*, 2, 23-26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13203-012-0012-8>.

Market Data Forecast. (2024, June). *Monoethylene Glycol (MEG) Market Size, Share & Trends, 2032*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.marketdataforecast.com/market-reports/monoethylene-glycol-market>.

Mendieta, C. M., González, G., Vallejos, M. E., & Area, M. C. (2022). Bio-polyethylene furanoate (Bio-PEF) from lignocellulosic biomass adapted to the circular bioeconomy. *BioResources*, 17, 4, 7313-7337.

Motagamwala, A. H., Won, W., Maravelias, C. T., & Dumesic, J. A. (2016). An engineered solvent system for sugar production from lignocellulosic biomass using biomass derived γ -valerolactone. *Green Chemistry*, 18, 21, 5756-5763.

NIB. (2020). NIB finances UPM's next-generation biorefinery in Germany. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.nib.int/releases/nib-finances-upms-next-generation-biorefinery-in-germany>.

Nova-Institut. (2024). *Plastics Production From 1950 to 2022 (PNG)*. Retrieved through: <https://renewable-carbon.eu/publications/product/plastics-production-from-1950-to-2022-png/>.

Núñez, M., Antón, A., Muñoz, P., & Rieradevall, J. (2013). Inclusion of soil erosion impacts in life cycle assessment on a global scale: Application to energy crops in Spain. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 18, 755-767. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-012-0525-5>.

Putri, R. E. (2018). *The water and land footprint of bioplastics* (Master's thesis, University of Twente).

Radici Group. (n.d.). *Biofeel*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.radicigroup.com/en/products/fibres-and-nw/bio-yarn>.

Rueter, C., Reif, D., Menzies, W., & Evans, J. (1996). Measurement and Enhanced Monitoring of BTEX and VOC Emissions from Glycol Dehydrators. *SPE Advanced Technology Series*, 4, 13-22. <https://doi.org/10.2118/29698-PA>.

Raj, T., Chandrasekhar, K., Kumar, A. N. & Kim, S.-H. (2022). Lignocellulosic biomass as renewable feedstock for biodegradable and recyclable plastics production: A sustainable approach. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 158.

Ren, H., Qiao, F., Shi, Y., Knutzen, M. W., Wang, Z., Du, H., & Zhang, H. (2015). Plantbottle™ packaging program is continuing its journey to pursue bio-mono-ethylene glycol using agricultural waste. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, 7, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4929336>.

SCS Global Services. (2022). *INEOS Oxide*. Retrieved on January 29, 2025, from https://rsb.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/RSB_CRT_GBL_INEOS-OXIDE_090222-1.pdf.

Selenis (2023). *UPM Biochemicals and selenis form strategic alliance to develop sustainable PETG*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.selenis.com/news/upm-biochemicals-and-selenis>.

Semba, T., Sakai, Y., Sakanishi, T., & Inaba, A. (2018). Greenhouse gas emissions of 100% bio-derived polyethylene terephthalate on its life cycle compared with petroleum-derived polyethylene terephthalate. *Journal of cleaner production*, 195, 932-938.

Shehata, W. M., Nady, T. G., Gad, F. K., Shoaib, A. M., & Bhran, A. A. (2024). A comparative study of mono ethylene glycol economic production via different techniques. *Scientific Reports*, 14, 1, 28375.

S&P Global. (2019). *Surging monoethylene glycol supply shifts global trade flows*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.spglobal.com/commodityinsights/es/market-insights/latest-news/chemicals/112519-commodities-2020-surging-monoethylene-glycol-supply-shifts-global-trade-flows>.

TOPSOE. (n.d.). *MOSAİK*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from https://engage.topsoe.com/y1141001434_lp.

UPM Biochemicals. (2023). *UPM selects Brenntag as sole European distributor of its new bio-based MEG*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.upm.com/about-us/for-media/releases/2023/09/upm-selects-brenntag-as-sole-european-distributor-of-its-new-bio-based-meg/>.

UPM Biochemicals. (2024). *UPM, Selenis and Bormioli Pharma introduce the world's first pharmaceutical bottle partially made with wood-based plastics*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.upmbiochemicals.com/about-upm-biochemicals/news-and-stories/2024/10/upm-selenis-and-bormioli-pharma-introduce-the-worlds-first-pharmaceutical-bottle-partially-made-with-wood-based-plastics/>.

UPM Biochemicals. (n.d. a). *UPM BioPura™ BioMEG Clean. Sustainable. Premium*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.upmbiochemicals.com/glycols/meg/>.

UPM Biochemicals (n.d. b). *Building a state-of-the-art biorefinery in Leuna*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.upmbiochemicals.com/about-upm-biochemicals/biorefinery-leuna/>.

Uranukul, B., Woolston, B., Fink, G., & Stephanopoulos, G. (2019). Biosynthesis of monoethylene glycol in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* utilizing native glycolytic enzymes. *Metabolic engineering*, 51, 20-31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymben.2018.09.012>.

VAUDE. (2023). *UPM and VAUDE showcase the future of fabrics at ISPO Munich 2023 with first ever fleece jacket made from wood-based polyester*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from https://www.vaude.com/nl/en/blog/post/worlds-first-fleece-jacket-made-from-wood-based-polyester.html?srsId=AfmBOooxgM1s2BTZD0FAM_JtSehUJs1P-AiTRKBQrFq5DYxbeW7CVHKA.

VEHICLE. (n.d.). *VEHICLE project*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.vehicle-project.com/>.

Wójcik, A. (2020). *Braskem and Haldor Topsoe achieve first production of bio-based MEG from sugar*. Retrieved on January 28, 2025, from <https://www.topsoe.com/press-releases/braskem-and-topsoe-achieve-first-production-of-bio-based-meg-from-sugar>.

Wong, M. K., Lock, S. S. M., Chan, Y. H., Yeoh, S. J. & Tan, I. S. (2023). Towards sustainable production of bio-based ethylene glycol: Progress, perspective and challenges in catalytic conversion and purification. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.143699>.

Zhao, Z., Jiang, J., Zheng, M., & Wang, F. (2021). Advancing development of biochemicals through the comprehensive evaluation of bio-ethylene glycol. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 411, 128516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEJ.2021.128516>.

Žmak, I. & Hartmann, C. (2017). Current state of the plastic waste recycling system in the European Union and in Germany.

PLASTICS SECTOR

PLA case study:

Ali, S. S., Abdelkarim, E. A., Elsamahy, T., Al-Tohamy, R., Li, F., Kornaros, M., ... & Sun, J. (2023). Bioplastic production in terms of life cycle assessment: A state-of-the-art review. *Environmental science and ecotechnology*, 15, 100254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ese.2023.100254>.

Alliance To End Plastic Waste. (n.d.). *Alliance To End Plastic Waste Homepage*. Retrieved from <https://www.endplasticwaste.org/>.

Awasthi, S. K., Kumar, M., Kumar, V., Sarsaiya, S., Anerao, P., Ghosh, P., ... & Awasthi, M. K. (2022). A comprehensive review on recent advancements in biodegradation and sustainable management of biopolymers. *Environmental Pollution*, 307, 119600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119600>.

BASF. (n.d.). *About BASF: Our Values and Global Standards*. Retrieved from <https://www.basf.com/global/de>.

BEWI. (n.d.). *BEWI company overview and history*. Retrieved from <https://bewi.com/>.

Benavides, P. T., Lee, U., & Zarè-Mehrjerdi, O. (2020). Life cycle greenhouse gas emissions and energy use of polylactic acid, bio-derived polyethylene, and fossil-derived polyethylene. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 277, 124010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124010>.

Brizga, J., Hubacek, K., & Feng, K. (2020). The unintended side effects of bioplastics: carbon, land, and water footprints. *One Earth*, 3, 1, 45-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.06.016>.

Bundesministerium der Justiz. (2023). *Gesetz über das Inverkehrbringen, die Rücknahme und die hochwertige Verwertung von Verpackungen (Verpackungsgesetz - VerpackG)*. Retrieved from https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/verpackg/inhalts_bersicht.html.

CARBIOS. (2024). *CARBIOS Sustainability Report 2023*. Retrieved from <https://www.carbios.com/newsroom/carbios-publishes-first-sustainability-report-and-underscores-commitment-to-circularity-and-environmental-responsibilities/>.

Dutch Government. (2025). *Wet milieubeheer*. Retrieved from <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0003245/2025-01-01>.

EC. (n.d.a). *The European Green Deal*. Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en.

EC. (n.d.b). *Circular Economy*. Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy_en.

EC. (n.d.c). *Single-use plastics*. Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics/single-use-plastics_en.

EC. (n.d.d). *Bioeconomy strategy*. Retrieved from https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/bioeconomy/bioeconomy-strategy_en.

EC. (n.d.e). *Packaging waste*. Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/packaging-waste_en.

EC. (n.d.f). *REACH Regulation*. Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/chemicals/reach-regulation_en.

EC. (n.d.g). *Waste Framework Directive*. Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/waste-framework-directive_en.

EC. (n.d.h). *Biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics*. Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics/biobased-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics_en.

International Labour Organisation. (n.d.). *The Green Jobs Initiative*. Retrieved from <https://www.ilo.org/projects-and-partnerships/projects/green-jobs-initiative>.

European Bioplastics, nova-Institute and FAO. (2023). *Land use estimation for bioplastics 2023 and 2028*. Retrieved from <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/bioplastics/feedstock/>.

Escobar, N., Haddad, S., Börner, J., & Britz, W. (2018). Land use mediated GHG emissions and spillovers from increased consumption of bioplastics. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13, 12, 125005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aaeafb>.

Futero. (n.d.). *The company: Futero, leads the way to a better, sustainable future*. Retrieved from <https://www.futero.com/>.

Green European Foundation. (2017). *A strategy for biobased economy*. Retrieved from https://gef.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/A_strategy_for_a_biobased_economy.pdf.

Jang, M., Yang, H., Park, S. A., Sung, H. K., Koo, J. M., Hwang, S. Y., ... & Park, J. (2022). Analysis of volatile organic compounds produced during incineration of non-degradable and biodegradable plastics. *Chemosphere*, 303, 134946. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.134946>.

Lambert, S., & Wagner, M. (2016). Formation of microscopic particles during the degradation of different polymers. *Chemosphere*, 161, 510-517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.07.042>.

Masutani, K., and Kimura, Y. (2014). Poly(lactic acid) Science and Technology: Processing, Properties, Additives and Applications. *The Royal Society of Chemistry*, 1, 1-36. <https://doi.org/10.1039/9781782624806>.

Matbase. (2012). Polylactic Acid (PLA) Properties. *Web Archive*. Retrieved on May 2024 from [Material Properties of Polylactic Acid \(PLA\), Agro Based Polymers | Polymers Data Sheets](#).

Ministry of Environment and Water. (2012). *Waste Management Act*. Retrieved from [WASTE MANAGEMENT ACT](#).

Morão, A., & De Bie, F. (2019). Life cycle impact assessment of polylactic acid (PLA) produced from sugarcane in Thailand. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 27, 11, 2523-2539.. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-019-01525-9>.

NatureWorks. (n.d.). *NatureWorks homepage*. Retrieved from <https://www.natureworkslc.com/>.

Pinlova, B., Sudheshwar, A., Vogel, K., Malinverno, N., Hischier, R., & Som, C. (2024). What can we learn about the climate change impacts of polylactic acid from a review and meta-analysis of lifecycle assessment studies?. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 48. 396-406. ISSN 2352-5509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.05.021>.

PLA Solutions. (2024). *PLA Family of Companies ESG Report 2023*. Retrieved from <https://www.plasolutions.com/hubfs/PLA%20ESG%20Report%202023.pdf>.

Rezvani Ghomi, E., Khosravi, F., Saedi Ardahaei, A., Dai, Y., Neisiany, R. E., Foroughi, F., ... & Ramakrishna, S. (2021). The life cycle assessment for polylactic acid (PLA) to make it a low-carbon material. *Polymers*, 13, 11, 1854. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13111854>.

Skoczinski, P., Carus, M., Tweddle, G., Ruiz, P., de Guzman, D., Ravenstijn, J., Káb, H., Hark, N., Dammer, and Raschka, A. (February, 2023). *Bio-based polymers - Evolution of worldwide production capacities from 2018 to 2027 (PNG)*. <https://doi.org/10.52548/CMZD8323>.

Stellantis. (2024). *Stellantis Corporate Social Responsibility Report 2023*. Retrieved from <https://www.stellantis.com/content/dam/stellantis-corporate/sustainability/csr-disclosure/stellantis/2023/Stellantis-2023-CSR-Report.pdf>.

Sulzer. (n.d.). *About Sulzer: Company*. Retrieved from <https://www.sulzer.com/>.

Taib, N. A. A. B., Rahman, M. R., Huda, D., Kuok, K. K., Hamdan, S., Bakri, M. K. B., ... & Khan, A. (2023). A review on poly lactic acid (PLA) as a biodegradable polymer. *Polymer Bulletin*, 80(2), 1179-1213. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00289-022-04160-y>.

TotalEnergies Corbion. (n.d.). *About TotalEnergies Corbion*. Retrieved from <https://www.totalenergies-corbion.com/>.

Polypropylene from used cooking oil case study:

ABC. (January 13, 2025). *El problema con solución: Segunda vida para el aceite de cocina usado*. Retrieved in January 2025, from <https://www.abc.es/economia/problema-solucion-segunda-vida-aceite-cocina-usado-20250113182600-nt.html>.

Asociación Española de Normalización. (UNE, 2020). *UNE 53972:2020*. Retrieved in January 2025, from <https://www.une.org/encuentra-tu-norma/busca-tu-norma/norma?c=N0063582>.

EC. (2008). *Waste Framework Directive*. Retrieved on January 2025 from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02008L0098-20180705>.

EC. (2018). *EU Plastic strategy*. Retrieved in January 2024, from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/plastics-strategy_en.

EC. (2019). *European Green Deal*. Retrieved in January 2024, from <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/es/policies/green-deal/>.

EC. (2020). *New circular economy action plan*. Retrieved in January 2024, from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>.

EC. (2022). *Biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics*. Retrieved in January 2024, from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/communication-eu-policy-framework-biobased-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics_en.

Emergen Research. (2023, April 18). *Las 8 mejores empresas de bioplásticos que transforman el mundo de una manera ecológica*. Emergen Research. Retrieved in January 2025 from <https://www.emergenresearch.com/es/blog/las-8-mejores-empresas-de-biopl%C3%A1sticos-que-transforman-el-mundo-de-una-manera-ecol%C3%B3gica>.

European Biomass Industry Association. (n.d.). *Challenges related to biomass. Used Cooking Oil*. Retrieved in January 2024, from <https://www.eubia.org/cms/wiki-biomass/biomass-resources/challenges-related-to-biomass/used-cooking-oil-recycling/>.

Fedrigoni Self-Adhesives. (2023). *Descubre nuestros films Biobased de base biológica*. Fedrigoni Self-Adhesives. Retrieved in February 2025 from <https://selfadhesives.fedrigoni.com/es/noticias/descubre-nuestros-films-biobased-de-base-biologica/>.

Fortune Business Insights (2025). *Tamaño del mercado de polipropileno de base biológica, participación y análisis de la industria, por aplicación (edificación y construcción, automoción, bienes de consumo, embalaje y otros) y pronóstico regional, 2024-2032*. Retrieved in February 2025 from <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/es/biobased-polypropylene-market-102758>.

Grupo Mathiesen. (n.d.). *Polipropileno*. Grupo Mathiesen. Retrieved in February 2024 from <https://www.grupomathiesen.com/productos-industrias/polipropileno/>.

Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico. (2016). *Plan Estatal marco de gestión de residuos (PEMAR)*. Retrieved in February 2024, from https://www.miteco.gob.es/content/dam/mitesco/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/planes-y-estrategias/pemaraprobado6noviembrecondae_tcm30-170428.pdf.

Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico. (2020). *España Circular 2030*. Retrieved in January 2025, from https://www.miteco.gob.es/content/dam/mitesco/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/temas/economia-circular/espanacircular2030_def1_tcm30-509532_mod_tcm30-509532.pdf.

Neste. (n.d.). *Chemical recycling Neste*. Retrieved in February 2025 from <https://www.neste.com/products-and-innovation/plastics/chemical-recycling>.

Plásticos Reig. (n.d.). *Plásticos Reig*. Retrieved in February 2024 from <https://www.plasticosreig.com/>.

Transport & Environment. (n.d.). *Europe's imports of dubious used cooking oil set to rise, fuelling deforestation*. Retrieved in January 2025, from <https://www.transportenvironment.org/discover/europes-imports-dubious-used-cooking-oil-set-rise-fuelling-deforestation/>.

Transport & Environment. (2020, July 2). *More palm oil and rapeseed oil in our tanks than on our plates*. Transport & Environment. Retrieved in January 2025 from <https://www.transportenvironment.org/articles/more-palm-oil-and-rapeseed-oil-our-tanks-our-plates>.

Universidad de Chile. (2023). *Investigadora postdoctoral genera bioplásticos utilizando aceite de desecho*. Retrieved in January 2025, from <https://quimica.uchile.cl/noticias/213516/investigadora-posdoctoral-genera-bioplasticos-utilizando-aceite-de-des>.

Wang, S., Muiruri, J. K., Soo, X. Y. D., Liu, S., Thitsartarn, W., Tan, B. H., ... & Loh, X. J. (2023). Bio-Polypropylene and Polypropylene-based Biocomposites: Solutions for a Sustainable Future. *Chemistry-An Asian Journal*, 18, 2, e202200972.

Cellulose acetate case study:

Akinsemolu, A. A., Idowu, A. M., & Onyeaka, H. N. (2024). Recycling Technologies for Biopolymers: Current Challenges and Future Directions. *Polymers*, 16, 19, 2770. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16192770>.

Bardy, J., Dürig, T., Lee, P., & Li, J.-X. (2017). Chapter 7 - Polymer Properties and Characterization. In Y. Qui, Y. Chen, G. Zhang, L. Yu, & R. Mantri, *Developing Solid Oral Dosage Forms (Second Edition)* (p. 181-223). Elsevier Inc.

Brizga, J., Hubacek, K., & Feng, K. (2020). The Unintended Side Effects of Bioplastics: Carbon, Land, and Water Footprints. *PLOS One Earth*, 45-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.06.016>.

Cerdia. (2022). *Production of Cerdia Filter Tow - Technical information*. Freiburg im Breisgau: Cerdia Production GmbH. Retrieved from <https://www.cerdia.com/>.

Cerdia. (2024). *Cellulose Acetate - Versatile & Sustainable*. Retrieved from Cerdia GmbH: <https://www.cerdia.com/cellulose-acetate>.

EC. (2008). *Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (Text with EEA relevance)*. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32008L0098>.

EC. (2020, March 11). *COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS. A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe.* Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A98%3AFIN>.

EC. (2022, November 30). *EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics.* Retrieved from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics/biobased-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics_en.

EC. (2023a). *Regulation on Deforestation-free Products.* Retrieved from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/forests/deforestation/regulation-deforestation-free-products_en.

EC. (2023b). *Restriction of microplastics in the EU from 17 October 2023.* Retrieved from: [Restriction of microplastics in the EU from 17 October 2023 | Access2Markets](https://access2markets.eu/restriction-of-microplastics-in-the-eu-from-17-october-2023).

EC. (2023c). *Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWD) - Directive (EU) 2018/852.* Retrieved from: <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/support-materials/eu-regulations-legislation/packaging-and-packaging-waste-directive-ppwd-directive>.

EC. (2023d). *Proposal for a targeted revision of the Waste Framework Directive.* Retrieved from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-targeted-revision-waste-framework-directive_en.

EC. (2023e). *Waste Framework Directive.* Retrieved from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/waste-framework-directive_en.

EC. (2024). *Green claims - New criteria to stop companies from making misleading claims about environmental merits of their products and services.* Retrieved from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/green-claims_en.

ECHA. (2024). *Understanding REACH.* Retrieved from: <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/understanding-reach>.

EESC. (2024, October 29). *From waste to resource: the EU must strengthen circularity in waste management.* Retrieved from European Economic and Social Committee: <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/news-media/news/waste-resource-eu-must-strengthen-circularity-waste-management#:~:text=Recycling%20and%20the%20recovery%20of%20strategic%20raw%20materials,its%20dependence%20on%20third%20countries%20for%20raw%20materials>.

Elaissaoui, I., Sayeb, S., Ounif, I., Ferhi, M., Karima, H. N., & Ennigrou, D. J. (2024). Preparation and characterization of acetate cellulose electrospun nanofibers membrane: Potential application on wastewater treatment. *Heliyon*, 10, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e32552>.

EU. (2019). *Directive (EU) 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment (Text with EEA relevance)*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/904/oj>.

EUROPEN. (2019). *Single Use Plastics Directive*. Retrieved from <https://www.europen-packaging.eu/policy-area/single-use-plastics-directive/>.

GVR. (2024). *Cellulose Acetate Market Size, Share & Growth Report, 2030*. Retrieved from: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/cellulose-acetate-market-report#>.

ISCC. (2023). *ISCC PLUS - Version 3.4*. Retrieved from: https://www.iscc-system.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/ISCC-PLUS-System-Document_V3.4.pdf.

James, B., Sun, Y., Pate, K., Shankar, R., Izallalen, M., Mazumder, S., . . . Ward, C. (2024a). Foaming Enables Material-Efficient Bioplastic Products with Minimal Persistence. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 16030-16040. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.4c05822>.

James, B., Sun, Y., Pate, K., Shankar, R., Izallalen, M., Mazumder, S., . . . Ward, C. (2024b). Foaming Enables Material-Efficient Bioplastic Products with Minimal Persistence - Supplement S2. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 16030-16040. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.4c05822>.

James, B., Ward, C., Hahn, M., Thrope, S., & Reddy, C. (2024a). Minimizing the Environmental Impacts of Plastic Pollution through Ecodesign of Products with Low Environmental Persistence. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry Engineering*, 1185-1194. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.3c05534>.

James, B., Ward, C., Hahn, M., Thrope, S., & Reddy, C. (2024b). Supplementary Information for: Minimizing the Environmental Impacts of Plastic Pollution through Ecodesign of Products with Low Environmental Persistence. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry Engineering*. Retrieved from https://pubs.acs.org/doi/suppl/10.1021/acssuschemeng.3c05534/suppl_file/sc3c05534_si_001.pdf.

Kidder Maede, R., McCormack, H., Clark, L., Sclater, A., & Lamborn, L. (1905). *A Monthly Journal of Practical, Applied and Analytical Chemistry, Band 3*. Chemical Engineer. McCready Publishing.

Kramar, A., Luxbacher, T., Moshfeghi Far, N., & González-Benito, J. (2023). Active cellulose acetate/chitosan composite films prepared using solution blow spinning: structure and electrokinetic properties. *Polymers*, 15, 15, 3276. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15153276>.

Kubiwicz, S., & Booth, A. (2017). Biodegradability of Plastics: Challenges and Misconceptions. *Environmental Science & Technology - Scientific Opinion*, 12058-12060. <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4702-2210>.

NRDC. (2022, June 1). *Fossil Fuels: The Dirty Facts*. Retrieved from: <https://www.nrdc.org/stories/fossil-fuels-dirty-facts#sec-disadvantages>.

OECD. (1992). *OECD GUIDELINE FOR TESTING OF CHEMICALS - Ready Biodegradability*. Retrieved from: https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/1992/07/test-no-301-ready-biodegradability_g1gh2913/9789264070349-en.pdf.

PMR. (2024). *Cellulose Acetate Market Share, Size, Trends, Industry Analysis Report, By Type (Fibre, Plastics); By Application; By Region; Segment Forecast, 2024- 2032*. Retrieved from: <https://www.polarismarketresearch.com/industry-analysis/cellulose-acetate-market>.

Rekker, L., Kesina, M., & Mulder, M. (2023). Carbon abatement in the European chemical industry: assessing the feasibility of abatement technologies by estimating firm-level marginal abatement costs. *Energy Economics*, 126, 106889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2023.106889>.

SBTi. (2024). *Science Based Targets Initiative*. Retrieved from <https://sciencebasedtargets.org/>.

Schützenberger, P. (1865). Action de l'acide acétique anhydre sur la cellulose, l'amidon, les sucres, la mannite et ses congénères, les glucosides et certaines matières colorantes végétales. *Comptes rendus hebdomadaires des séances de l'Académie des sciences*.

Sebruyns, L., Van de Perre, D., & Hölter, D. (2024). Biodegradability of Cellulose Diacetate in Aqueous Environments. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 1326-1341.

Skoczisnki, P., Carus, M., Tweddle, G., Ruiz, P., Hark, N., Zhang, A., . . . Raschka, A. (2024). *Biobased Building Blocks and Polymers - Global Capacities, Production and Trends 2023-2028*. Hürth, Germany: nova-Institut GmbH. <https://doi.org/10.52548/VXTH2416>.

Slezak, R., Krzystek, L., Puchalski, M., Krucińska, I., & Sitarski, A. (2023). Degradation of bio-based film plastics in soil under natural conditions. *Science of The Total Environment*, 866, 161401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.161401>.

Teixeira, M. A., Paiva, M. C., Amorim, M. T. P., & Felgueiras, H. P. (2020). Electrospun nanocomposites containing cellulose and its derivatives modified with specialized biomolecules for an enhanced wound healing. *Nanomaterials*, 10, 3, 557. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10030557>.

Teixeira, S. C., Silva, R. R. A., de Oliveira, T. V., Stringheta, P. C., Pinto, M. R. M. R., & Soares, N. D. F. F. (2021). Glycerol and triethyl citrate plasticizer effects on molecular, thermal, mechanical, and barrier properties of cellulose acetate films. *Food Bioscience*, 42, 101202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2021.101202>.

Walther, B. A., Pasolini, F., Korez Lupše, Š., & Bergmann, M. (2024). Microplastic detectives: a citizen-science project reveals large variation in meso-and microplastic pollution along German

coastlines. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 12, 1458565.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2024.1458565>.

Wolfs, J., & Meier, M. A. (2021). A more sustainable synthesis approach for cellulose acetate using the DBU/CO₂ switchable solvent system. *Green Chemistry*, 23, 12, 4410-4420.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/D1GC01508G>.

Yu, Y., & Flury, M. (2024). Unlocking the potentials of biodegradable plastics with proper management and evaluation at environmentally relevant concentrations. *npj Materials Sustainability*, 2, 1, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44296-024-00012-0>.

Project Consortium

